

Overview & Welcome

Hello, welcome to this document which explores [Education](#) and [Knowledge Engineering](#) from a variety of perspectives, starting from about September 2022 and continuing through this day (2024).

Explore the sidebar to the left and unfold pages to find out more.

To get acquainted with some of the major areas of collaboration, check out:

- [2024 Projects](#) for a top-level view at ongoing projects, and [2024 Phase 2 \(2024.2\)](#) for ongoing work.
- [ISSS June 2024 Workshop](#) for the materials that were explored during the [ISSS conference](#) in June 2024 in Washington DC.
- [Education](#) and the dozens of [Live Education meetings](#), where we explored [Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions](#), [Systems Science](#), did a [Systems Census](#), and much more.
- [Knowledge Engineering](#) and dozens of [Live Knowledge Engineering Meetings](#), where we explored [KM as a project](#), archiving with the [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#), development of the [Systems Language / sysXML](#), used synthetic intelligence with [LLM & ISSS](#)/[LLM tools](#), and much more.

With Questions/Comments, please contact [Daniel Friedman](#).

2024 Phase 2 (2024.2)

From **R. Don Peel, PGeo**

Thank you Daniel for leading this crusade on education. I found the many fractals captured in Coda were beyond my comprehension, which is no surprise as my primary schooling was in the public education system. In this environment, along with all my peers, i lost my divergent thinking capacity. To me "Indigenizing education" is an easy solution. There are a number of books that are much more informative than the roll out of publications listed by the National Academies, such as [Braiding Sweetgrass](#) (Kimmerer 2013), [Groundswell: Indigenous Knowledge and a Call to Action for Climate Change](#) (Joe Neidhardt & Nicole Neidhardt 2019) and [Medicine Wheel for the Planet](#) (Grenz 2024). Understanding the background development of education is key to strategizing a paradigm shift in education towards systems thinking. This background is conveyed in [Weapons of Mass Instruction](#) (Gatto 2008).

My recommendation is to have everyone on your Education people list, read these publications to simplify the process of developing an epistemology that nurtures divergent thinking. It was an unfortunate "side quest" that the proposed Panel for the 2023 Conference did not manifest. I still think k-12 education is a significant lever to regain our thinking capacity, but changing such a vast ingrained system, with so many "stakeholders" will take a massive collaborative effort. You gave it a shot, but i find it difficult to measure any gains exploring the Coda.

2024.2 meetings

See [🌐 2024.2 meetings](#) in the subpages here/above.

6-21-2024

2024 Projects

- James R., Rob Y., Peter T., Daniel F., Dave D.
- JR — several people over the years listening to what he has to share.
 - Len and JR — Interest rate & speed of money flowing through economy.
 - Talking around the wrong subject.
 - X number of differences. Len's integration/differentiation.
 - In looking for simplicity and sharing, unified simple thing about system that founders thought it might be useful to get at? What is useful in serving
 - Continuing to exist (FEP).
- We can:
 - Get all the primary materials, documented at bibliographic level & full text if possible.
 - Also collaborate in conversation and annotation to connect dots with the materials, and provide historical context.
- How do we want these sessions going forward?
- Dave sharing from Archiving Archiving.
 - There are multiple people ready/working on different aspects of the Archiving and Indexes.
 - Working on interfaces & content. Representations of semantic spaces.
 - There is more acute awareness of the need for maintenance of archiving. There are several schemes for referencing this, including the [Active Inference meta-analysis schema](#).
- Thingness. Making it a foundation for other applications and field.
- Consider how this could be a general work project, for grant/funding/support — funded people with interests.
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2024 Projects

6-28-2024

6-28-2024

- David D, Peter T, Tom M, Rob Y, Daniel F, Lynn R, Randall, James R.
- ASC videos —
 - Everything that Peter streamed, is recorded. <http://asc.networkvideo.org/>
 - <https://vimeo.com/coexploration>
 - <https://asc.networkliteracy.org>
 - <https://asc.networkliteracy.org/>
 - A. Leonard — Biological Computer as Retronym (e.g. “analog wristwatch”). She and other humans.
 - Patricia Clough and Paul Pangaro <https://youtu.be/ze2iEjyrjgo?si=BA-utN4Sb1bcU556>
- [Len Troncale Archive](#)
 - Rob & Luke have catalogged.
 - Luke focusing on AI Wilson. Rob on the Systems. Daniel has “ISSS archives”.
 - There are tapes heading to Peter for digitization.
 - Len’s work is vast & there is time while we are still able to work it out together.
 - Lynn with many years of digital
- [Bucky Fuller](#) archives
 - <https://exhibits.stanford.edu/bucky>
- Archives
 - Contrasts above with Len & Bucky.
 - Bertalanffy archives
 - Biological Computing lab
 - ASC // Archiving Archiving
 - Oral History archive with rich markup; accepting donations: <https://libguides.uky.edu/oralhistory>
 - Introduction to Archives https://youtu.be/cAXA-_hJ9Hw?si=2ldg8EpTOkcBI02n
 - It is one thing to secure the bibliographic details and even full text. It is another level/mode to make it useful and accessible.
 - What is the value/meaning of what was done? What was and wasn’t done? What is the value of a (technical) archive?
 - To show the history of how a science emerges is an amazing thing. Cobbling together a science from the mass of materials (e.g. see [◀ Len Troncale](#) ISGE education program).
 - In Sonomna, Bar-Yam & Geoffry West, Lynn. It is here, just not well-organized.
- Rob
 - ISSS conference recordings
- This group?
 - In many cases seeing the same problems. Moving forward in different ways separately and together (community, infrastructure).
 - One opportunity is to support the living use of Systems and Cybernetics archiving. Weaving together a way to introduce people into the field.

- Name, inviting
- Checklists for stages of the archiving
- ISSS and meta-.
- ISSS and history/founders.
- More
 - “(T)he philosopher is a perpetual beginner. This means that he accepts nothing as established from what men or scientists believe they know. This also means that philosophy itself is an ever-renewed experiment of its own beginning , that it consists entirely in describing this beginning, and finally, that radical reflection is conscious of its own dependence on an unreflected life that is its initial, constant, and final situation.”
— Maurice Merleau-Ponty, Phenomenology of Perception
 - General Semantics functions (among other things) as a higher-order cybernetic, focusing on cognitive and affective prophylaxis - Self-consciously cleaning out bad thinking.
<https://www.generalsemantics.org/>
- .

7-5-2024

- Present: Rob Y, James R, Daniel F.
- Projects & directions for this specifically.
 - Weekly Organizing 📅 [2024 Phase 2 \(2024.2\)](#)
 - Reporting back on activities that support the broader infrastructure, skills, networks, research.
 - Writing summary paragraph
 - Agenda?
 - at :10 — 1-5 minutes sharing.
 - What happened? What are the main learnings, frictions, asynchronous opportunities?
 - Use development of archival checklist for discovery + making open source products
 - Closing down an office?
 - Calendar event
 - Coda name.
 - Form / process for invitation.
- What is the simplest System?
 - Tetrahedral // Four-fold
 - Interaction, communication, interface
 - Edgar Morin https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Edgar_Morin . (Structure, Interaction, Organization) — Multiplex
 - Relationship with upper ontology?
 - Structural // Mereotopological. And in an interactive/dynamic way.
 - Abstraction → Event as space-time in (agent-specific) world line. Nothing happening with it till it intersects/interact with another thing.
 - Physical interactions // Forces. Systems abstracts from materials models.
 - Buoyancy — is this a system? Instance and general aspects of Buoyancy, that is the gap to be respected/jumped.
- General 📄 [Systems Language / sysXML](#) .
- [@James Rose](#) — on the post-Shannon information theory. Usable aspects of Noise
- [Information flow in context-dependent hierarchical Bayesian inference](#) . <https://youtu.be/ldg2An-tEIE>
<https://youtu.be/zF-EUnA-di4> and .0 <https://youtu.be/o7sJ-5vFJGk> . Chris Fields course
<https://coda.io/@active-inference-institute/fields-physics-2023> . Essentials of communication.
 - Agent construction of spacetime with Quantum Reference Frame.
 - Communication // Holography across the relational Interface as fundamental
 - Dual Fungible // Non-fungible nature of info-thermo exchange (can develop special cases as well as “pure” flows).
- Starting with ordering // disordering? Neg/Entropy, Temperature, Energy. (E.g. early post-Big Bang too much heat/energy/entropy).
- Instance-General (unbridgable?)
 - Generalizations. Authentic universality (versus “counterfeit”, removing differences), Goethe's morphology, thing at the higher level/whole with the primacy & the subsequent instances
 - Generalization. Undecidable as 3 option of un/verifiable.

- Consciousness & ability to bridge/jump arbitrarily. Artist has said “this is art”, and so in the mind ~anything can be imagined.
- How much Cybernetics can we handle?
 - So much involvement, simultaneity, polycomputation, etc... — can we understand them all together?
 - Utility only in Cybernetics?
 - [Equation 2.6](#), EFE = Epistemic + Pragmatic.
- Subjective & Objective together.
 - Rose 96, Objectivity is not an Object (don't be fooled by root form). Objectively how/can 2 or more people come together with interpretations of system? Towards truest form of a situation, where would we find a non-subjectively existential situation? Incorruptability in “not a thing” because of the +/- . “Look down and hone in”. Regardless of the tests we do. So net thing is not an object, the intangibility is the relationship. Only getting there via the personal-subjective.
 - Have the ability to communicate (topological) and ability for semantic transfer.
 - Alice & Bob — Driving the car on the bridge, jumping, teleporting, ferrying, etc...
 - Coupling of communication can be made/broken (topologically). Information/Alignment retention and decay.
 - Electron wave/particle.
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7-12-2024

- Agenda

- at __:05 — 1-3 minutes sharing each.
 - What happened? What are the main learnings, frictions, asynchronous opportunities?
 - Present: George M, James R, Rob Y, Steve S, Tom M, Daniel F
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- Peter ~ Primer “Premiere” — information trying to put together. How for getting it to be user friendly?
 - 🌐 ISSS site, and/or where for the Systems basics?
 - 2000's, Primer was a big ISSS project, on the old website. Peter et al. saved this in movement to the new website
 - <https://www.issss.org/primer-1/> && <https://web3.issss.org/primer/primer.htm>
 - <https://www.issss.org/blog/?view=blog&id=16&ssrch=Primer#sr>
 - What are the basics? Communities sense/agreement
 - [Gene Bellinger](#), teaching SS. On website. Showing, not telling/convincing. Relationships Expert. *Systems Thinking World*, journal.

📎 stwj.systemswiki.org-Overcoming_Barriers_to_Understanding_Systems_Thinking.pdf

- What would scientific//spiritual//? mind, why would existence exist at all along with sentience? Why is this part of what existence involves? Why are there architectures of systems at all? What is purpose, function, of self-reflecting and existence? Value of to even exist?
 - Answers do connect with spirituality, religion, theological question. Research questions and on correlation/connection with Science and Religion.
 - How do the Real and Ideal fit together? New thought is old && new. What is pragmatic of this, in participating in the process, being productive in the world in what they are working on. This is a great potential of Systems. People will/do come to this from their stance/perspective; they will interpret which things how they want.
 - In the body/organs/tissues, each with own competency and levels/type of representation.
 - <https://www.mdpi.com/1099-4300/24/6/819> “Competency in Navigating Arbitrary Spaces as an Invariant for Analyzing Cognition in Diverse Embodiments”.
 - Waves, concepts, ideas,?....., is there a grand schemata for these variables? Epistemological limits?
 - Where do we come from? Where are we going?
 - Which areas and authors of the Systems community, are active and addressing this?
 - John Kinneman
 - Mechanistic sides & interests. Pragmatists and others who have embarked on the dialectical turn.
 - Theory/Practice.
 - Targeting the single and big questions AND the informational side.
 - Internal consistency in theory. External consistency with lateral and discussion.
 - 90 degrees to each other, precession. And comedy!
- 📧 2024 Projects & weekly Organizing 📅 2024 Phase 2 (2024.2)
 - Reporting back on activities that support the broader infrastructure, skills, networks, research.

- We are an informal group, meeting since 2022, that uses a [shared document](#) and weekly 1-hour meeting (currently at 16 UTC on Fridays) to share, connect, and collaborate on projects related to: Systems Science theory and, archiving, ethnography (eggnography, gardening), education, and much more.
- Our key shared initiative right now is the development of open source [archiving guides/checklists](#), in collaboration with the [Systems Community Alliance](#) project. Briefly, this project will continuously develop, publish, and deploy methods related to physical and digital archives (whether for a young person beginning their journey, or an elder closing their academic office or moving).
- To signal interest in joining our weekly meetings or receiving email updates, [complete this form](#).
- Use development of archival [Archives & Checklists](#) for discovery + making open source products
- Calendar event
- Coda name.
- Form / process for invitation.
- Scenius <https://www.scenius.space/> , Trimtab....
- 🌸 [Jamie Rose](#)
 - I read “How Much Cybernetics Can You Handle? 2002/2021”. Can this material be uploaded here for reference, and/or are there other links?
 - *““Least action” is a “dimensional state”, not a thermodynamic condition, nor a Planck limit. “Least action” is found as internally present in the topological architecture of dimensions, even if a minimal “one (geometric) point” off-axis from 1D of Euclidean ‘perfect straight line’... even fractal exponent values produce “non-zero stressors of an “exponent greater than unit-one topos”.”*
 - This may have closest connections with Free Energy Principle (which enables/describes these paths of least action in arbitrary spaces (e.g. [Fields & Levin](#)).
 - Curious about Topos usage here, if it is related to category theory specification for multi-agent systems as in <https://www.mdpi.com/1099-4300/26/4/303>
 - Also read: Re: 7-5-2024 Notes JAMIE .. after thoughts to today's 3 way ZOOM ---- on archiving Gen Sys historicals
 - *“ .. if you'd only pay attention.”* — You are seeing (the artifacts of) my attention. I have nothing else to “pay” any person or thing. I am open and open to specific kinds of tasks, feedback, research, evaluation, archiving, etc., on a case-by-case. If you think some other regime of attention/action should be engaged in, feel free to write/suggest it. Otherwise, this/my attention is not a counterfactual.
- MathArtStream 4 ~ 7/12/2024 at 17 UTC
Kirby Urner
“Dimension” in Synergetics
<https://www.youtube.com/live/i9oij02oje0>

7-19-2024

- Updates and Roundup:
 - GST SIG in Summer Recess
 - [Shingai blogs @Shingai Thornton](#)
 - Specialism — narrowing scope of effort. Vs. competent in generalization.
 - Long-term: Be More Tactical (lol).
 - See though: Cybernetics, Systems Dynamics, Complexity, etc. — can/do only discuss in the context of a System.
 - These as semi-independent fields as doing good work with applications, techniques, etc. to [Systems Science](#). Now there is clearly line of sight from the systems modeling methods here, towards the more general [GST-24](#) General Systems, What is System, Systemsness.
 - Need to find some way to re-integrate these. People can be out there working on Complexity, Cybernetics, etc. — and seeing embedding within bigger picture of How systems work. Generalized.
 - Complexity: Melanie Mitchell, Simon, Signals & Boundaries. What is the Complexity's System concept? Do they talk about system as system? Trying to set up the context for what they are talking about // modeling. e.g. in ALife Artificial Life, how do complex systems/outcomes arise from simple rules? Prigogine / Self-organizing / Chemical, and Mandelbrot / Fractal / Math. Self-organizing (1958-1961 → Auto-poiesis, ecological, etc).
 - How for unifying system?
 - Complexity came with organization/management/legacy/math. Cybernetics with the practical advantages. And resistances within/among universities. Challenges and fundamental with mapping terms, ontologies.
 - Axiomatic approach to building system (Thing, Low/High Road). Into [GST-24](#) universe. Long-term Pragmatic value with inter/operable models.
 - Tradeoffs in coarse-graining, abstracting. E.g. Clare and Rosen, set/graph/category theory. And Input/Output. Smut's Holism. Macro-Micro. Observer. Coins and Sides.
 - In terms of Systemsness — the set of attributes (to __?) that make up what a system is. Taking all this simultaneously in complex systems design — accounts/addresses for the concept of wholeness. Not just feedback loops, aspects 123, taking all into account and this enables decomposition (breakdown reductionist analysis) and synthesis-analysis. Keeping all the connections documented in the analysis process. If you consider that every system has THIS SET of attributes (communication, holarchy, etc). — when then analyzing, need to look at all simultaneously. Are these "just traits"? Taking into account the inner (neural) and external (ecosystem). Smut's holism 1930 encyclopedia, primacy to whole over parts. Causality. Framing. There is a kidney functioning.
 - [George Mobus](#)
 - [GST-24](#) Bertalanffy's Open System.
 - [Trimtab Book Group](#) — Tomorrow 9am PT, Buckminster Fuller discussion, archives discussion & Systems.
 - [Math4Wisdom](#) & Trimtab
 - <https://blogs.oregonstate.edu/scarc/2021/03/06/the-trevor-blake-collection-on-r-buckminster-fuller/>
 - [Meeting with Kirby 7-17-24](#) — Knowledge Engineering
- [Archives & Checklists](#)
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7-26-2024

- Rob Y, Shingai T, George M, Daniel F.
- Updates and Roundup:
 - [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#) — Rob working on website
 - <https://cursor.sh/> — schema & API fusions
https://github.com/ActiveInferenceInstitute/ActiveInferAnts/tree/main/9_OTHER
 - Shingai, working on the systems analysis methods, Bitcoin.
 - <https://www.barnesandnoble.com/w/the-science-of-synthesis-debora-hammond/1117350650> The Science of Synthesis: Exploring the Social Implications of General Systems Theory by Debora Hammond
 - Debora Hammond's The Science of Synthesis explores the development of general systems theory and the individuals who gathered together around that idea to form the Society for General Systems Research. In examining the life and work of the SGSR's five founding members — Ludwig von Bertalanffy, Kenneth Boulding, Ralph Gerard, James Grier Miller, and Anatol Rapoport — Hammond traces the emergence of systems ideas across a broad range of disciplines in the mid-twentieth century.
 - Is Atom a system
 - Proof-based bottom up
 - Definitional/Plural/Archival ([Tom Marzolf](#))
 - First-principles
 - DIKW — Data Information Knowledge Wisdom —
 - Definitional, at the Data level. Talking at different levels about same things, are we dealing with e.g. operational, logical, conceptual, realities, domains, etc. — it is discourse around the same thing, hence necessity of sharing models
 - ???
 - ??? — many Unknowns. We can Know the Unknowns — by choosing the frame there can be constructive conversation with the thing.
- [Archives & Checklists](#)
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mario_Bunge
-

???

https://coda.io/d/_d7R4wffe3Bu

8-2-2024

- Updates
- Peter T, Rob Y, George M, Daniel F, Shingai T, Tom M.
- Music
 - Cybernetics & Music, Engineerings, Memory.
- Archives & Checklists
- Active InferAnts // <https://www.cursor.com/>
 - CodeStreams
 - CodeStream #002.2 ~ Pre-Pro-Grants Unleashed: Generating 1000's of GrAnt Catechisms with LLMs
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=i04yvNf75IU>
 - Open Source code & outputs:
https://github.com/ActiveInferenceInstitute/ActiveInferAnts/tree/main/1_PREPARE/Methods/Research/Research_Methods
 - "Who's On First"-style README:
https://github.com/ActiveInferenceInstitute/ActiveInferAnts/blob/main/1_PREPARE/Methods/Research/Research_Methods/WhosOnFirst_README.md
- ▼ From [@Dave Douglass](#), on Cybernetics, ASC, Archiving Archiving
 - ▷ Dear conference attendees,
 - ▷ We have planned two special journal issues and *An Experimental Glossary* related to the ASC 60th anniversary theme of **living cybernetics | playing language** with its three sub-strands as outlined on the ASC60 website:
 - ▷ **linguaging in/for action**
 - ▷ The question of how to conceive linguaging in/for action is at the heart of the 60th anniversary meeting. How to describe what goes beyond description? How to explain cybernetics? What words do we need to speak cybernetics, and how do they need to be spoken? Proposals focusing on 'linguaging in/for action' may take a word for a walk and, in the process, create a Cybernetics 101 or a grammar of cybernetics.
 - ▷ **archiving archiving**
 - ▷ The 60th anniversary provides an opportunity to reflect on the history of cybernetics and the ASC's past. However, 'archiving archiving' alludes to a second-order reflexive turn. Rather than simply storing the voices of the past, we would want to revive them so that their wisdom becomes a productive contribution to creating desirable futures. Proposals within the 'archiving archiving' strand may suggest new structures and methods that link pasts, presents, and futures; they may also reflect on the risks related to attempts of revival.
 - ▷ **reimagining technicity**
 - ▷ The term technicity suggests that creating things and techniques to assist with the processes of living is an essential and inherent part of being human. How design, agency, and action are conceptualized in relation to technology in the widest sense holds significance for how we understand both time and space and, with it, community, environment, and interaction. Proposals within the 'reimagining technicity' strand may reflect on processes and tools that support human agency, diversity, and the creation of sustainable, more-than-human worlds.
 - ▷ **An Experimental Glossary**
 - ▷ *The Experimental Glossary* will be flexible regarding contribution formats, and we have not yet decided on a deadline. In the meantime, you are encouraged to add your related ideas and thoughts to the [NewMacy Little Books Zine](#) project as

we plan to take the Zine as a basis for the *Experimental Glossary*. There are instructions on the website for how you can contribute to the Zine. Send an email to submissions@asc-cybernetics.org if you need more clarification.

▷ **Two special journal issues**

▷ The ASC 60 special journal issues will be with *Constructivist Foundations* and *Cybernetics & Human Knowing* and will be published in the spring of 2025.

▷ We are happy to announce that we have negotiated a new deadline for both issues. The deadline for both special issues will be **31 July 2024**. Please note that we need the submissions by this deadline.

▷ If you plan to submit an article to one of the special journal issues, please familiarize yourself with the scope of the two journals. A good way to get a feel for the different scopes of the two journals is by looking into the two special Humberto Maturana issues edited / co-edited by Pille Bunnell, one for *Constructivist Foundations* and one for *Cybernetics & Human Knowing*. Please see below for more details. **Detailed instructions for the two journals:**

▷ Cybernetics & Human Knowing

▷ Please follow the guidelines on the journal homepage to submit your article for the ASC60 special issue.

▷ <https://chkjournal.com/node/116>

▷ Carlos Vidales will edit the issues with assistance from Claudia Jacques.

▷ When you send your article to the editor, please indicate that your submission is for the ASC60 special issue

▷ Constructivist Foundations

▷ If you do not know this journal's format of publishing research in target articles and related open peer-reviewed articles, please take a closer look and then follow the guidelines on the journal homepage to submit your article for the ASC60 special issue.

▷ <https://constructivist.info/guidelines/>

▷ This special issue will be edited by Claudia Westermann (that's me) and Alexander Riegler.

▷ When submitting your article, please indicate in your email to the editors that your submission is for the ASC60 special issue.

▷ We are looking forward to receiving your contributions. Please let me know if you have any questions.

▷ With best regards,

▷ **Claudia Westermann**

▷ **Vice President**

▷ American Society for Cybernetics (ASC)

▷ <http://asc-cybernetics.org> | claudia.westermann@asc-cybernetics.org

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8-16-2024

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- George, Rob, Tom, Daniel
- Jitsi <https://meet.jit.si/SystemsEducationKnowledgeEngineering>
 - First person needs to use the google login.
- Archiving
 - <https://archivaria.ca/index.php/archivaria/article/view/12648> **Theoretical Principles and Practical Problems of *Respect des fonds* in Archival Science (1983)**
📎 12648-Article Text-14644-1-10-20061208.pdf
 - Since the second half of the nineteenth century, respect des fonds has traditionally been considered as the basic principle of archival science. By its practice the archivist is most clearly distinguished from the librarian on the one hand and from the professional researcher or documentalist on the other. Like many principles, however, it is easier to state than to define and easier to define than to put into practice. Although its origins are relatively easy to establish, difficulties arise as soon as an attempt is made to study its theoretical aspects thoroughly and to show its practical applications. Generations of archivists and archival technicians have examined these problems without resolving them
 - Consequently, to appreciate a document, it is essential to know exactly where it was created, in the framework of what process, to what end, for whom, when and how it was received by the addressee, and how it came into our hands.
- [Archives & Checklists](#)
 - Personal, Shared archives/fonds. That is a turn and difference.
 -
- Re:
What are the five most important things each participant thinks to consider, to advance the value of ISSS learning among its members or separately among the public at large?
 - Joe Velikovsky added a comment: "Some ideas, at:
<https://on-writering.blogspot.com/2024/08/on-systems-education.html>"
- <https://systemscommunityalliance.net/> (soft launch of...) Systems Community Alliance website
 [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)
- GEN-24
 - https://coda.io/d/Active-Blockference_dlvNESFmyj6/GEN-24_su2DYdSx#_lufakeld
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Active Blockference

https://coda.io/d/_dlvNESFmyj6

8-23-2024

Shingai, Jamie, George, Daniel, Randall, Rob, Chris.

- Rare autographs? From ISSS.
- Shingai presenting:
 - Using Protoge <https://webprotege.stanford.edu/> tool for Ontology development along lines of Systems Language / sysXML, formalizing the ontology of George's book.
 - User interface (there is Web and Local).

- Top level — making it explicit.
 - Boundary, Component, Environment, System
- This enables comparison of assertions about systems.
- Where does Recursion go?
 - George: System has Sub-System and can continue. There can be a tree structure for this. That is a computational / analytic process, with the recursive travel on that. Mandelbrot. Taking the output and repurposing. Recursion and similarities/differences from Recurrency (e.g. Recurrent Neural Network).
- Shingai can go with, anyone in ISSS feeling like they have (near) complete ontology, then can be achieving sets of ontologies, where out of a set of those there is mutually satisfying.
- What about Instructions? George says, these are “Work Processes”.
- In Ontological framework, George did not include in Diagram — “Existence of Matter-Energy-Information-Knowledge”. Shingai began with Thing. How can these 4 (*not* Elementals haha), as being base for the 1 thing. “Daughters of Matter-Energy-Information-Knowledge”
- What about Scaffold? — in the book, Placeholders and Relations. Scaffold, Skeleton structure that is then used to build new.
 - Ontology does this, Structurally and Conceptually.

- It is a tool for Deep Systems Analysis, Shingai sees using this for systems, Blockchains, Governments, Organizations, Biological systems.
- Upper Ontologies — George says, this is the Matter-Energy-Information-Knowledge. From that all emerges (Emanations).
- Where for Next?

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BTC analysis — Decompose? Simulation

- Chris S is analyzing, situation with Insurance, how would start thinking about “How are you involving climate change in the policies?”
- <https://www.llnl.gov/article/48711/physics-based-cryptocurrency-transmits-energy-not-just-information-through-blockchain>
- George’s first paper, Biophysical Economics meeting. Relationship with Money and Energy.
- <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Emergy> — Odom. George argues for Emergy.
- GEN-24
 - https://coda.io/d/Active-Blockference_dlvNESFmyj6/GEN-24_su2DYdSx#_luyn6wKX
- RxInfer.jl
 - https://coda.io/d/RxInfer-2024-Active-Inference-Institute_ddtS-XZ4BJb/Home_suGOGSZH#_lu6FLujP
- All examples of Systems, each domain/system nucleating a local Ontology. Then as maturing, reaching out their roots, coming back to (Systems) Theory side of things.
 - *Two Roads Diverged*, can go the narrower domain-focus, and/or can go systemic. GST showing, value and implications of taking Systems view on life, also there is still value along the local path.
 - What are the seeds, anchor points?
- Transdisciplinary projects. Getting together people.
 - https://github.com/ActiveInferenceInstitute/ActiveInferAnts/tree/main/1_PREPARE/Methods/Research/FieldSHIFT-2/Inputs_and_Outputs
 - Find researchers across disciplinary.
- .
-

8-30-2024

- Rob, Chris, Daniel
- [Ontology](#)
 - <https://philpapers.org/archive/MUNAOA-2.pdf> Katherine Munn, Barry Smith (Eds.) “Applied Ontology An Introduction”
 - Knowledge display, retrieval, etc. — aimed at researchers and archivist as well as Ontologists. Knowledge from multiple viewpoints.
 - 📎 MUNAOA-2.1.pdf
 - I love a good ontology. I judge them as how useful a tool are they to help you think through a complex problem. But it is that complex practical problem solving which is most important to me.
 - Mereotopological questions (part, whole, connection, etc) and the General Systems questions too.
 - <https://www.ontologyportal.org/>
 - Ontology applied to BTC, ETH, etc.
 - Addressing risks/outcomes of quantum cryptographic developments?
 - [LLM tools](#) and Ontology? Semantic search, and limitations for Syntax search.
- [Education ISSS VP https://vimeo.com/990975692](https://vimeo.com/990975692) **Clifford Whitcomb July 27 2024**
- Community of practice
 - With Bruce M, creating shared artifacts. 👍
 - Reviewing the e.g. [Systems Futures]. Tired of email threads, Wheels Within/Without Wheels.
 - Getting to know offline & their work.
 - Back in the “Phase 1” days — good to have some collaborative projects and finding the deliverables there.
 - YouTube videos could go from unlisted to public. (we did this)
 - [Notes and pages — published to Zenodo?](#)
 - Longer term aims for group.
 - Bridging SIGs that are close? SIGIG?
 - Scouts looking for a old person crossing a road? Finding a need and helping there?
 - Also to [ISSS](#) and elsewhere? ISO, IEEE, INCOSE.
 - Like the web standards, Spatial/Semantic web <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/2874/10375/>
 - Are we trying to integrate the Systems approach into business, domains, life, etc.
 - Global, universal, interoperable. Practically, opportunities to formalize ontologies ([ActInf](#)).
 - As a services
 - Archiving [Archives & Checklists](#)
 - Ontology fusion
 - Education & Knowledge Engineering.
- .

9-6-2024

- We shared the YouTube's unlisted, as public. Chris S, asked about communicating the passions/motivations. There is an audience in [ISSS](#) and also, how can this build bridges to other communities? And then, why would we/they WANT to?
 - Solve problems with Systems.
 - Pro bono works ~ even then, people have to want to be helped.
- <https://vimeo.com/990975692> Clifford Whitcomb July 27 2024
 - [ISSS](#) VP of Education. Developing shared core for [Systems Science](#)
 - Fields/Sectors, SYSBOK, INCOSE, initial stages for researching.
- Engineering & Systems theoretical frameworks (GST et al.)
 - For using engineering tools, the theoretical frameworks have to be effective, clear, est.
 - MBSE — Model-Based Systems Engineering — all rides and functions on the “model”. Mobus 3rd — Which model? 4th — How to use in design?
- Systems Engineers came to ISSS looking for foundational help.
 - Jen, Gary, et al, IFSR Austria; What is Systems SCIENCE? [Systems Science](#) — Based upon scientific framework. To justify/evaluate what they should be doing.
 - Attitude of, Not Invented Here. Systems Science Working Group there. That is a motivational schism.
 - Systems Scientists should do the systems science and Show, Take, Tell. George and laying out how the science element can contribute with the engineering processing.
- Has anyone, dealt with issue, used method, to retrieve solution?
- Can you describe one?
 - This was problem. Rationale. Solutions.
 - Jamie - solving 'systems issues' does not always require labeling the technique “systems thinking”. A sister organization to ISSS, the Forum on Democracy, gave an ISSS weekend presentation in December 2023 and then an ISSS 2024 post-conference event the next day, also in DC and as segue to the ASC annual conference. The Forum on Democracy, is treating the USA and other countries stressed democratic systems as needing modern revue and analysis dealing with “What is happening in democracies?”. Their approach is to foster organized groups around respective tables to discuss and understand the issues, and then decide on solutions built on new/different communal consensus. Jamie, from the sideline as an invited ISSS Systems Scientist to join the Forum group — decided he might have an advantage as being a skilled Systems Analyst - compared to these well meaning folk - and should be able to come up with identifying what's wrong and suggest possible solutions. The methodology starts with understanding the ideals proposed by people wanting a new governance instead of enthroned royalty claiming divine privilege. Then - appreciate that if polity practices do not match the intentions - either good organisation is not well connected internally, or something is missing — either of these being likely sources of dysfunction compared with aspirations. The starting point here is, read and understand the stated goals in the Declaration of Independence and the USA Constitution — What's in the documents as best social ideals? What deliberative and practical authority bodies are designed? and are there rules of operation which provide for meeting the Ideals and social precepts? What relationships and ideals? Are all the notions of a democracy, explicitly stated in the documentation? Are there specified practices designed to achieve specific goals, like Equality, Liberty, Fraternity? .. pursuit of Happiness? Are there practices~laws to guarantee mutual respect as superior to disputes and disagreements between citizens .. committed to allegiance to the Ideals - versus a person or religion? **** Jamie examined the documents, interpreted the aspirations~intentions and then spotted that significantly critically important ideas have been left NOT ENUNCIATED, and certain social mechanisms to assure those goals could be achieved, were ... ARE ... glaringly missing. ****
-

- We can assume that through human history, social groups originally formed simply around mutually experienced needs of co-support, simply by the agency of events - a hundred thousand years ago - instincts - on the primal inkling edges of new awarenesses. Then oral traditions ... clarifications ... to lessen mis-understandings .. or prevent problem misinterpretations. And then written specifications. Symbols etched in stone, inscribed on papyrus, rice paper, parchment, vellum. Hand scribed as if the writing itself was a commitment to the ideas being written. Then on pulp paper using perfectly replicated printing press practices. [then to now — electronic re-representations].
-
- But the obligation taken on by written~printed visual presentations was to not mince words, to strive for exactness and prevent disputes, to avoid missed nuances lost in omissions.
-
- The Constitution is a legal document. Binding laws expressing expectations striven for, with repercussions for failure to enact expected behaviors. Enunciated ideals, not left for inference, only being educed through examples of actions described.
-
- America's founding documents, as wondrous as they are, fail on both those points. (!) But that does not mean throw them out and try other ideas, other writings. The founding writers established a nation they believed could thrive and mature, and improve itself. Not on whims of local fads and fashion, but ever important improvements on having clarity and transparency of ideas and ideals ... readable by all, comprehensible to all.
-
- American office holders, at all levels of government, make a pledge to the entire community, that they will take on the responsibilities of specific authority granted to the office holder, for a short period of time only, the authority of decision maker and enforcer of society's agreed rules and practices. And Oath of Office is sworn to. And at the national level, an Oath to Protect and Defend the Constitution of the United States "so help me God". But not on, "or suffer the penalties of oath breaking or swearing false allegiance."
-
- The First glaring hole in our founding documents. There are penalties for treason to the nation. But there is no penalty for disregarding Constitution precepts and expectations. There is no penalty .. not even swift and immediate removal from office .. when there are indisputable unfaithful derelictions to upholding Social Ideals. Like unlawfully putting an average citizens rights away, or being obviously unfaithful to the ideas of the Constitution. NO ONE is above the law, not even a President, under ANY CIRCUMSTANCES .. even feigned 'national security' claims. Primal Accountability is missing from the Constitution.
-
- The other glaring hole is for a democratic ideal also Implied in a described political action, but not published in explicit undeniable words and made punishable for non-compliance. The act is the "peaceful transfer of power" after open and fully equitable honest elections. Refusing to relinquish office holding is frowned upon, but is not required, as things stand. Not only does refusal have no mandate requirement nor accountability for refusal - endangering social political order at its most fundamental, there is no explicit founding theory written on which peaceful transfer stands.
-
- The foundation of Peaceful Transfer is community wide commitment to the protection and respect for all member citizens. It implies that differences of opinions and life practices and choices will be different from person to person, from concept groups to others, on what life practices are preferred and what life values are important. But even though there is recognition of differing practices and values, as long as those practices do not impinge or prevent or deny or harm individual rights and liberties of other people, there is TRUST that people holding different views and beliefs will PROTECT the rights of other people to live as they choose, practice rituals or life choices they may have. We give standing legal authorities to people who do not practice or even have to like or agree with, alternative life choices. Protection of ALL, stands above choices by any FEW — even if each is uncomfortable with the others' choices and practices. That is the Life Principle underpinning "peaceful transfer of power". Any legal authority is temporarily

granted, and is periodically made available to other citizens with different personal beliefs holding personal choices of actions and life style. Each and every person granted legal authority over others carries MANDATED RESPONSIBILITY for Stewardship care and protection of even that which they do not like or prefer personally. This mutually of care and protections is THE bedrock basis for transfer of power and trust in companions franchise practices and honesty as well. Government in the Sunshine, and full accounted for unblocked voting participation for all citizens, with trusted oversight timely and dependable, is key also. Again - acting in good faith and trust with no abuses tried - must be agreed by compact.

-
- Fix these two current loopholes in American social political legal documents, social ideals documents, and the main bulwark of Republican Democracy will be strengthened for all Americans advocates wishing to participate in American democracy. *****

MathArtStream 8 ~ 9/6/2024 at 17 UTC

Shanna Dobson, Daniel Friedman

William Blake, Kierkegaard, Gothic

<https://www.youtube.com/live/yIS0OW2o18s>

9-13-2024

- Chris S, actuarial, major change in the legal and systems context. How to think from systems, and start with non-linearities.
- <https://openai.com/o1/> — reasoning
 - Legal Reasoning and inference
 - Teaching it language to use. Goal: Structured way desiring to use language for ontology, risk types. With structured outputs like this
 - Auditability
- Blake, Goth, Kierkegaard
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yIS0OW2o18s> MathArtStream 8 ~ William Blake, Kierkegaard, Gothic
 - <https://zenodo.org/records/13711302> — slides from the above.
- .
 - Archiving (Archiving).
 - Systems
 - AI, LLM
- .
- .

9-27-2024

- Central definitions of Systems.
 - Entropy. Work.
 - Entropy low at beginning, then work.
 - Any new action, taking place in setting of — too much energy in beginning, before other forces come into play (tightly negentropic location), other kind of entropy, e.g. too much energy/entropy to do work. Before some inflation, so much was so tightly together, that is a situation where there is a lot of plausible future conventional work, yet situation cannot do work at that time. Too much or too little energy? Analogy with information overload? Entropy always moving towards MaxEnt (no work can be done in the final stage, is not false, it is incomplete though).
 - Big Bang as birth of energy and matter, creation of laws enabling the discussion of complexity and etc. We do not know before then, different laws might apply. Is this specific to the period of the birth of matter — what came before that? (Jamie not concerned).
 - If there is another sense of — what accomplishes causality. Then a way to talk about alternative ways of causality.
 - Isn't there an Ontological causal chain being sought to be identified? Epistemological humility.
 - Metaphorically, flying out into the space & delusion epistemologies perish. Before this in the <https://philpapers.org/rec/CONTFE-3> The free energy principle: it's not about what it takes, it's about what took you there.
 - Rosen's model, we are only recognizing/sentience the realness of that situation. Starting as baby and from there. Individual, Group, Personal, Social, Absolute laws, truths outside of humans.
 - [Systems Science](#) and the pursuit of truth, systems.
 - Request:
 - Work — Standard physics, (What I do when not at play).
 - activity involving mental or physical effort done in order to achieve a purpose or result.
 - Which should general systems be concerned with? [Systems Science](#) concerned with the laws/patterns of the physical world.... Continuing loss of the possibility to do work (Entropy).
 - Allowing that too much at the beginning of universe, would that make it true/applicable for any system?
 - (Goldilocks and the) 3 Bears — Too Hot, Just Right, Too Cold. What is too hot/cold for something might be for
 - What unique predictions or experiments? (For different entropies.
- Were the Romantics/ William Blake – Systems Thinkers?
 - Enough! or Too much!
 - One law for the lion and ox is oppression
 - Milton & Blake — Denis Saurat.
 - Goethe.
 - [Wikipedia: Romanticism: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Romanticism](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Romanticism)
 - [Goethe. Milton; Blake; Shelling](#)
 - [Mythic World Builders. World Systems. Ontologies.](#)
 - "Romanticism (also known as the Romantic movement or Romantic era) was an artistic and intellectual movement that originated in Europe towards the end of the 18th century. The purpose of the movement was to advocate for the importance of subjectivity, imagination, and appreciation of nature in society and culture in response to the Age of Enlightenment and the Industrial Revolution."
 - Systems & Imagination

- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/The_Perennial_Philosophy
- <https://www.amazon.com/Romance-Reality-Organizes-Consciousness-Complexity/dp/1637740441>
- System, meta-framework for hanging all insights. Cognitive ground floor.
- Jamie's/any ones opinion on Tyler Volk's talk
- Next GST SIG meeting on Thursday Oct 17th. 11:00 AM Pacific Time (US and Canada); 19:00 UK Time.
- .

[Read this message in Coda here](#)

Hello all, some updates from this corner of the Systems world ~

1. Overall we are continuing on, sharing and learning about projects and topics, connecting Systems projects and people, and more. Whether you are joining the regular 🌐 [2024.2 meetings](#), reading the documents on your own time, or participating in your own way, thank you for the attention. Always feel free to take a step away from this fractal aspect of the fun/work, and if you want to step up in a moment (present at upcoming meeting? facilitate your own session at a different time? steward some aspect of the Coda? something else?), just reply here.
2. Our next meeting will be 🗓️ [9-27-2024](#) at 16 UTC [at this link](#). This Jitsi link can be begun by anyone (if you are the first person to join, log in with Google account and it will open the room).
3. Next week 🌐 [10-4-2024](#) I will not be there (travelling for a wedding). Again, please feel free to join regardless & note anything on the page if you want. I'll be back on 🔥 [10-11-2024](#).

Let me know if you have any questions, otherwise feel free to directly update our shared document.

Peace,

Daniel

10-4-2024

Entanglement?

10-11-2024

Entanglement?

- <https://famos.org/> , FarmWorks <https://zenodo.org/records/13754586>
 - Systems and Farming.
 - Resources modeling
 - https://coda.io/d/RxInfer-2024-Active-Inference-Institute_ddtS-XZ4BJb/FarmWorks_su194Ep3#_luYkqvV
 - Permaculture & Regenerative methods.
- In George's [Systems Science](#) book —
 - Earth is a system
 - Human population is sub-system of Earth. This seems purposeless / self-serving, which is creating and causing issues we are facing, the problematique. What is the purpose of the human species as sub-system? Humans could take on roles, not in Extracting, in finding/entertaining balances.
 - Asteroid and tactical relationship of earth.
 - Mobus SRBS [Gaia needs a mind and humanity needs a purpose](#). He discussed here and in book, with small permaculture communities in terms of sustaining human beings so that can embody that purpose. Food, water, shelter, and other needs for thriving. Hierarchy from largest possible
 - How does Purpose relate with Science?
 - What need purpose mean?
 - <https://www.amazon.com/Plan-Purpose-Nature-George-Williams/dp/0297819313> **Plan and Purpose in Nature, 1996**

by [George C. Williams](#)

- https://ackoffcenter.blogs.com/ackoff_center_weblog/files/ackoffsystemofsystems.pdf Ackoff
- Complex Adaptive System in seeking to produce that teleos so it is supplied by Super-System with needs.
- Onto-Epistemological combination. Plan and Purpose for mankind is critical question for GST.
- <https://www.e-c-o.net/wiki/Econet/Welcome>
 - https://coda.io/d/Math4Wisdom_d0Svdl3KSto/econet_sukjaJUF#_luOf0pnt
- .
- .
- .

10-25-2024

Jamie, George, Daniel, Rob, Shingai, Luke.

- 📅 2024 Phase 2 (2024.2) since June 2024, after ISSS June.
 - We will 📅 11-1-2024 and 📅 11-8-2024.
 - 📁 Len Troncale Archive. Luke is processing/storing.
 - ISGE integrated systems general education, Len's course
 - Peter and Digitizing.
 - ✅ Archives & Checklists
 - Dr John B. Cobb, Jr <https://cobb.institute/learning-lab/probing-process-and-reality/> Alfred Whitehead
 - How to make the nuggets in the discourse/emails? And higher order / worldviews.
 - Knowledge management for this?
 - Extracting definitions as quoted from a person.
 - The Cornell Systems Summit, November 3–5, 2024 <https://www.systemseng.cornell.edu/schedule>
 - Shingai continuing to work with Ontology development in Protoge, Bruce's UML scheme, George's, 🌐 GST-24 boundary work.
 - <https://symposium.activeinference.institute/> Nov 13-15
 - Subject: Mini Symposia Reminder - How can we engage positive dynamics of differentiation and integration in developing systems / cybernetics / complexity?
 - How can we engage positive dynamics of differentiation and integration in developing systems / cybernetics / complexity?
 - Benjamin will introduce the four organisational dynamics (and their systems | cybernetics | complexity roots), their pathologies, diagnosis, and associated prescriptions:
 - • Segment – separating out into teams and specialisms
 - • Blend – coming together to work effectively as one unit
 - • Empower – each person to use their specific skills and talents
 - • Harmonise – bringing everyone together to focus on a common goal
 - He will then discuss how we might apply these to our own extended field, and invite discussion on whether and how we can use these concepts to positively influence more effective organisation.
 - Benjamin Taylor, is a dedicated amateur in the systems | cybernetics | complexity space. He is on the board of SCiO (systems and complexity in organisation), the systems practice professional body, teaches on the level 7 systems thinking practice apprenticeship, and at times has been the noodle in every soup in the field... he runs a network consultancy in the UK, RedQuadrant, and a social enterprise, the Public Service Transformation Academy. He regularly blogs and writes in the space – all links at antlerboy.com
 - President
 - International Society for the Systems Sciences
-
- Bit. Different, discontinuity, reduction of uncertainty. Recognizing information.
 - Syntactic and Semantic information contents. Meaningful and not.
 - How deep to go back with defining

- Building and working with Ontologies that can be compared, using LLM and synthetic intelligence methods, comparable methods. Learning and Applying Systems, for [Systems Science](#) and Research.
 - LLMs as tool, semantic and syntactic search.
 - Comparing perspectives and corpus.
 - Infrastructure for the shared meaningmaking.
 - Connect back with the GST for unifying the conversations, paradigmatic for coherence within
 - Communities of practices, within and among.
- Theory translator
- https://www.theorytranslator.com/index.php?structure=three_minds
- https://coda.io/d/Math4Wisdom_d0Svdl3KSto/Theory-Translator_suuuulmK
- 🌐 GST-24 and list. Criteria for this. What is truth? What is reality?
- Active Inference for Absolute Truth
https://coda.io/d/Math4Wisdom_d0Svdl3KSto/Templeton-2024-Grant_sulOwv--#_luYDYE18 Grant proposal not accepted.
-

Robert,

All well and good, but Bateson NEVER gave a crisp scientific definition, he provide a pun in the English language "the difference which makes a difference". That is a Meaning Referent which requires pre-knowledge of two distinct interpretations of a singular same word .. in the mind (or AI dictionary) of the message receiver.

I provided to this group MY proposed scientific/mathematics based Fundamental Theorem of Signal Recognition .. identifying that Calculus partitioning ... (Leibniz; Newton) .. sets a non-subjective Objective math relation of

"any existential measure criteria number (information bit) .. COMPARED against the transcendental numberline .. will, for any circumstance or device or organism neural capability or system having 'signal sensitivities' involved in its ongoing functioning (EM fields interacting; spacetime curvature responses to masses and vice versa), will always be a situational constraint and/or allowed capability. Always conditional on the actual architecture and qualia arrangements of ANY SYSTEM local and specifically."

By this relationship theorem, a "bit" [minimal useful unit for any~all given "systems" having communication activities and performances having a local capability] is any differential signal qualia poised against all possible communication forms, scales,sizes, intensities .. et cetera. from and into the environment co-present and co-engaging with the system. [inferring "states changes" from specific external sources or generally present in the EM spectrum environment at large].

THIS is an "information bit " GENERAL DEFINITION .. universally relevant and applicable to any system imaginable, actual or potential. It is based in Objective mathematics relations. Where it is now recognized that "objective" now has an improved 'definition as well. It is no longer the old conventional interpretation of "least variant status within the spectrum of all Subjective measures, testing results, states ranges identified" That is. it is NO LONGER a comparative asymptotic value or state .. the "best subjective target value derived from subjective encounters/measures/identifiers.

"Objective" as a state or identification .. was sought for to meet a status of "unquestionable" - INVARIANT - no matter who or what system or agents are identifying the information qualia~quantia.

And the ONLY "things"which are never variable .. are not physical - material - energetic "things" at all. They are NOT and

cannot be an "object". {ergo the confusion because of the word root property of "tangible thingness").

The only phenomena which are uncorruptable, invariant, never affected to change are ... INTANGIBLE RELATIONS. **Relations** are OBJECTIVE. They 'exist' instantiated and observable only through SUBJECTIVE EXISTENTIAL EXAMPLE PRESENCES. But the RULES and RELATIONS are not the subjective sample instantiations, but the behaviors and performance relations they function as following .. regardless of extraneous states changes, noise in the existential environment et al. which WILL generate subtle differences at all times in any measurement or assessment or encounter arrangement.

Existence involves constant energetics and informational variances at all times. At all times. Existence is Subjectivity superlified. But all existences perform function and enact as physical material energetic embodiments of the

intrinsic "Rules of Behaviors --- Relations Performable". In some fields of study -- eg Physics -- they have been labeled in the past: "Laws of Nature". General Systems improves on that label. They are the "Rules (not 'laws') of behaviors and performances". Why not "laws"? .. because the word "law" implies .. must never be broken under any circumstance. But there are infinite situations where the operant criteria is challenged or even reversed or nullified. SO, to allow for conditional variants, "Rule" conveys ... to open possibilities where deep compounded factors will generate events which on their face SEEM to CONTRADICT the dictum. That is permissible.

Any such intangible dictum must still hold in all situations .. but -may- be masked within unusual existential presentations.

GENERAL SYSTEMS THEORY fundamentals a priori's ... eventually giving sentient evaluators insights into where those relations and qualia show up in systems and phenomena of interest for ... *practical purposes*.

But they are universal and are primitively innate Paradigm Attributes and Properties in all systems, entities, ensembles ---- first and foundational.

{(transferred recognitions connecting the theory ideas with real world instantiations .. is where human intellectual~conceptual Systems Literacy capability shines in human **understanding**. .. associating the qualia and relations rules -- which multitudes of co-engaging **influences** .. are happening "real time".)}

General Systems Literacy involves knowing (theory) and then knowing where they are found in the physical dynamic world we contend with and survive and advance within.

Jamie

Dear Jamie,

You are free to define your terms any way you want. So long as you understand that your definitions have no relationship to the definitions that are used in the telecommunications and computer industries. The term "bit" was coined by the engineers at Bell Labs and it is short for "binary digit." It refers to the method of coding a set of logical choices.

Peace and love,

Robert

11-1-2024

- Rob, Alfred Whitehead, process theology. Laws of form.
 - <https://footnotes2plato.com/category/alfred-north-whitehead/>
 - With Russel and *Principia Mathematica*
 - John Cobb, of later Cosmological work of Whitehead. Universe's creation and place of humans, *Process & Reality*.
 - Previous discussions on upper [📖 Ontology](#)
- Evolution, Competition, Cooperation. Corning. 2019 ISSS.
 - Peter T finished putting up content from 2000 World Systems Congress. Systems 2K.
 - https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLffuelQHqR9Sa56yyp_Lt5SafmXVeJvz
- Chris S, Peter Cook, Systems self-organizing.
- 📅 11-8-2024 next meeting, last for the interval.
- ; Innovation talk, how could that help our group?
 - As we've participated in some same sessions, it gives language for talking and relating. Can we connect our work and interests to give presentation, then connects with some new person joining in.
 - Seeing the value/relevance of other's projects.
 - Intermediate link. Surveyability. Is this among
- 🗣️ GST-24 — picking a specific topic/questions, then assessing people's views of that.
 - Boundary. Starting point. Can be compiled into Glossary definitions
 - Charles Francious — Int. Dic. Syst. Cybernetics.
 - What of the value, of a glossary, that majority of people ISSS & Beyond.
 - Fractal languaging (English and More).
 - Ontology translations (e.g. [Active Inference](#) translations).
 - Who is in room/discussion?
- Mapping frameworks.
 - Epistemic infrastructural element [📁 Archives & Checklists](#) [📖 Ontology](#) [📁 Systems Science](#)
 - Rhetorical / Perspectival element [📁 Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions](#)
 -
- .
-

11-8-2024

Rob, George, Chris, Daniel, Shingai

- Began with [Knowledge Engineering](#) [Education](#) and making [Systems Science](#) more accessible. Different layers for each of us. Coming back for getting [something](#). In helping others it enables different views. Everything can/does connect with systems and fractals.
- Education is an activity that needs to go along with, sometimes preceded by, knowledge engineering. Our journey has had different divergences, untied ends. Not all so simply aligned with education. Who for education? What can be done? Should be done?
- <https://systemexplorers.substack.com/p/thoughts-on-the-us-political-system>
- Demand for systems approach to understanding complex (social, ecological, ...) systems.
- More discussion
- Download PDF + upload to Zenodo

2024.2 ~ People

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Form for 2024.2

Form for 2024.2 ~ Table form

Name Email Do you want email updates? Do you want to be added to the calendar events? Any other cor

There are no rows in this table

View of Form for 2024.2 ~ Table form

What is your name?

What is your email?

Do you want email updates?

Do you want to be added to the calendar events?

What is your interest in our group and activities?

What projects are you interested/active in? Please feel free to describe your interests and share links to work.

Any other comments or questions?

Sign in to have your response emailed to you.

What is your name?

What is your email?

Do you want email updates?

Do you want to be added to the calendar events?

What is your interest in our group

What projects are you

2024 Projects

Research & Development

- George Mobus: Research towards a general systems theory (GST)
 [GST-24](#)
- Shingai [System Modeling SIG](#),
 [Active Blockference](#),
 [Systems Language / sysXML](#)

Education

- Working with Clifford in [ISSS](#)
- Working on documentation for own projects.

Archiving & Capabilities

- [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)
 - Growing in capabilities of the systems community. Starting with archiving, then including e.g. taxonomy, curated.
- Active Inference Institute & Journal
- People
 - Robert Rosen's archive (Jude Rosen)
 - Tom's model [Thomas Marzolf's Model](#)
 - [Len Troncale Archive](#)
- More.....
 - Global, Russian, Eastern traditions
- .

 2024 Phase 2 (2024.2) is where we are continuing.....

More notes below

Intra- & Inter-Organizational

- ▼ [Crossover for EDU from KE](#)
 - ▷ This meeting Fridays at 17 UTC — alternating
- ▼ Systems Community Alliance — Archival
 - ▷ [Crossover for EDU from KE](#)
- ▼ Planning

- ▷ Business Motivation Model — Object Management Group. Building the model of a plan.
- ▷ Diagram starting with a vision or ideal. Strategy, Tactics, etc. considered holistically as changes happen through time.
- ▷ Tom took the spec from OMG and did a class model — plans as defined classes.

📄 Systems Science

ISSS

- ▷ George 🌐 GST-24
 - ▷ Shingai 📄 System Modeling SIG
-
- ▷ Tom's model 📄 Thomas Marzolf's Model
-
- ▷ Shingai 📄 Systems Language / sysXML
 - ▷ Shingai, Daniel 🌐 Active Blockference — Optimism grant

To do:

- Calendar / ISSS email with new timing + scopes.

The geometrical calculus of Isaac Barrow, ca 1670. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1111.6145>

Calculus during the life of "Thrice-Greatest Hermes." <https://personal.math.ubc.ca/~cass/courses/m446-03/exhaustion.pdf>

GST-24

Research towards a general systems theory (GST)

- They are working on a process for evaluating different fragments of general systems theory — now they are realizing that understanding the core concepts of how to evaluate/compare the basis/grounds.

-
- What is a GST?
 - How do we know it when we see it?
 - How do we develop it to be useful?
 - 3-8-24
 - Coming notification for GST
 - Challenges/Test of GST.
 - Looking at the major emergences/arising (major transitions), e.g. life, noosphere.
 - Should be providing guidance to those in the research
 - George studying the systems perspective on emergence of life. From *Science*, chirality in amino acids.
 - Smith & Morowitz — origin of life on earth, even explicitly mentioning several systems principles.
 - The Emergence of Everything how the world became complex Harold J. Morowitz
<http://sackett.net/EmergenceOfEverything.pdf>
 - [Len Troncale](#), Lynn, Tyler (Combo), George (Onto). These recordings may be on YouTube,.
 - Pask said, Systems & Cybernetics, are interested in the same things. As System is more interested in WHAT, and cybernetics on HOW and WHY. — Cannot separate these out. Every cybernetic/complexity paper “In This System.....”
 - It has to be tied back to that which provides the context, the systems.
 - Wolfram etc. could — give overall framework for evaluating the respective contributions of DATA and THEORY.
 - Known that one can illuminate, feed the other. The meta-question though, how is that articulation actually manifest — could have over-riding principles.
 - What sort of challenges to ask for, from observers? Which theoreticians to send results to?
 - Strength and a curse (for [Systems Science](#)) — other areas, can do great reductionist work. Whereas System necessitates the dual Holistic-Reductionist approach. “Zoom in, Zoom out, when in doubt” for Systems.
 - How will we create a culture of publication that allows people to always embed their work in a larger pictures?
 - Ackoff: Data, Information, Knowledge, Wisdom.
 - Goethe in his Morphology — shaping, as Kant Hegel Heidigger.
 - Multiple framing.
 - .
 - ./
 - .
 - 2-23
 - Meetings and administrative details proceeding.
 - George writing blurb for Newsletter. Working with Lynn R on the description.

- March — [Rousseau et al. 2016](#) is the focal discussion topic — read it, make notes, get ready for commentary. Meeting to discuss. Paper for orientation of initial/prospective members of the SIG in terms of what they are looking to do. Not following R et al's format, rather as a peer/process in to open up for the SIG. Then to invite people who actively engaged in the material & provide comments.
- Following with some of the GST and development, ideas from the first meeting for what is G,S,T, criteria.
- SIG sessions at the conference. And through past that.
- 2-16-2024
 - George et al with meeting earlier in the week.
 - March for 1st open meeting of the SIG. 2+ more before the conference.
 - Format:
 - Send out target paper/chapter to those who want to read it (+ add notes, think, etc).
 - Open meeting is a discussion — raising questions if they've read/thought about this. Keeping it on the target paper.
 - Bruce developed on Rob's list + categorizing + improving. Using pivot tables for views.
 - <https://sysml.org/>
- 1-26-24 —
 - George sent out emails & there was a BoD meeting earlier in the week.
 - Previously there were also many emails — threads and also with George. So it could/should be an active SIG.
 - This is about the handover to SIG co-chairs George & Tyler. They also need e.g. email list, webpage.
- Plan to start with "Searching for general systems theory" [Rousseau et al. 2016](#) for target paper — make it clear for those who want to participate with voice, that they have READ IT and THOUGHT ABOUT IT and have something to say.
 - Following, John Kinneman also wrote about some candidates.
- Rob has a list for candidates.
- Send paper. Read & think it. Ready to discuss. From there, people can e.g. prepare papers.
- Rob Bruce Shingai Lynn — Steering committee for the SIG. So that George/Tyler.
- Recording and Archiving
 - ISSS zoom or? <https://meet.jit.si/ISSSSS>
 - Some [KM as a project](#) work can annotate and enjoy the recordings/transcripts. This could be a general available SIG service.
 - Rob has experience from Holism SIG regarding the appropriate infrastructure for the SIG. These questions have come up.
 - ISSS providing collaboration to SIG. That's a big/integrated thing.
 - Private emails flying around. Mailing list?
 - Presentation, did we have permission, Red/Amber/Green system
 - SIG review presentations (e.g. monthly/quarterly rhythms).
- About [Thomas Marzolf's Model](#)
 - .xmi — there is more to it than XML. It is a standard output. Tom sent the XML.
 -

Systems Language / sysXML

2-2-24 — Shingai working on this, and with Joseph & development

<https://systemlanguage.notion.site/System-Language-84bf57e4fd6541269733bb8893ee84a4>

- Systems Language / Systems Modeling —
 - Designed explicitly to accompany the deep analysis technique.
- George started with the ontology of Systems.
 - From here a syntax of how objects come together / between them / causal relation.
 - Started from this isomorphism of interaction of systems we can think of and started from that.
 - Describes structural & functional relational aspects.
 - Hence it is comprehensive.
 - XML model — embed software.
 - Possible consider serialization methods <https://serde.rs/>
- Another aspect of this — brained creatures:
 - Inherent in the way the brain works, there is unspoken mental language.
 - “Systemese” — Evolved language of system (evolutionarily implicit).
 - In this framing the explicit formalization by George (and implementation) is like Alphabet “invention” from unwritten language.
 - In Educational setting — [OpCloud](#) “*OPCloud is a real-time collaborative Web-based environment for Model-Based System Engineering using OPM ISO 19450*” — and repositories of information.
 - Which modeling approach is applicable for my situation/system?
 - Active Inference over methods/contexts.
 - Evolution produced a modeling system/machine, brain — children learning in the world. Structure learning && Learning structure.
 - Hence for emulating the best kind of modeling approach for building constructing and using models, internally/cognitively and externally/software; this is something to pay attention to.
 - Brain is capable of encoding objects and relations.
 - And archival work on systems, cybernetics, control.
 - 0th level systems learning...?
- [System Modeling SIG](#) and with Education...
 - Developing systems model of the [ISSS](#).
 - Modeling tools, processes, practices, collection.
 - Model-based collaboration
 - Building a model with/from subject-matter experts in feedback.
 - Get input → improve model → feedback → →
 - Model-based systems engineering (MBSE)
 - Ackoff and asymptotical/incremental procedural maintenance and improvement

- We started with....
 - Website.... Education.... Education/KnowledgeEngineering... Education..... Website.....
 - Peter made parallel iss.org architecture from the Drupal, using it for membership management, then SIG pages. More development, some organizational rerouting of the websites. Then Peter's site became/is the iss.org. Roelin as president in conversation with Daniel et al. with the [www Education](http://www.education.org) on the [www Website](http://www.website.org). Hence then many of our works with e.g. ISSS archives, SCA, and beyond.
- Rob & different models/resources.
 - [Scott Page — Coursera MOOC](#) on model thinking.
 - Systems Thinking / Model Thinking / Multi-frame Perspectival model
 - Perfectibility — conjure up the model, find out what it means, perfect it as we look at different aspects of that. In model thinking, education for modeling and metaphors, images too. groups of concepts, not only the particular approaches.
 - Then Peter's systems literacy etc. — the epistemological endeavor of mankind and various big subjects, arguably systems are now very modified/engineered/synthetic/cyberphysical and even new understandings of natural systems, intuitions, — then theories, methods, frameworks.
 - Inquiry & Action. Abductive. Models.
 - Robert Frost — Two Roads Diverged....

— Natural and Technical — multiscale bifurcating into safety and civilization. Developing tech layer that builds roads on shifting sands. Tech branches unlocked by e.g. Shannon information. Choices to go down a given path have consequences. Bifurcations. The orthogonal aspects will come back to bite us unless.... ????????. Why do (cities, empires, etc) rise and fall, and the processes in life phases, cyclic, keeping it together and “the fork cannot hold” and the models that we choose. Can move away from the identity and complexity that holds it together in the first place.

- Where does Knowledge come from? Perceptions and Realities. ... talks about how technology is interpreted via Hermeneutics & immersal in the language of the technology. Creating sub-ontologies & games on the fly.
 - There is tension between the mediated perceptual space, and nature as it is (with or without theory of it). Hidden states and dynamics beyond comprehension.
 - Earlier in the discussion of Expressing the ideas quickly and effectively. Cecilia Hayes, Cognitive Gadgets, imitation & language.
 - Norms gonna norm.
 - Connection with Education and Learning.
- For Shingai's work in the [Systems Language / sysXML](#) —
 - The approach for easily modeling different systems as easily as possible (BTC, neuron, city) — most successful way for coherent model of system of interest.
 - The scope/approach/draft of George is a/the best current starting place for us now. And there are other approaches.
- S.C. Pepper — World hypotheses; a study in evidence 1961.
 - This tension between common sense and expert knowledge, between **cognitive security** without responsibility and cognitive responsibility without full security, is the interior dynamics of the knowledge situation.

This tension between common sense and expert knowledge, between cognitive security without responsibility and cognitive responsibility without full security, is the intrinsic dynamics of the knowledge situation. The indefi-

✚ Re: sysXML

See [George Mobus](#) for more information.

- Read Chapters 6, 7
- Re-familiarize myself with cadCAD (in progress)

I think the key issues are:

1. representation of both structure and function in a human-readable form,
2. translation into multiple modes of human perceptual representations (e.g., visual), and
3. generation of machine code to implement simulation models for empirical research.

We do bits and pieces of these now in different platforms. But we need a fully integrated platform that supports frontend analysis, knowledge encoding, and backend simulation. Could be a great PhD thesis!

sysXML ~ Milestones

Area	Name	Memo	Notes	Images
▼ Systemese 5	GM Chapter 3	Ontology		
	GM Chapter 4	System Language		
	GM Chapter 5	Deep Systems Analysis		
	GM Chapter 8	Knowledge base		
	Synthetic specification	— What moves forwards		

▶ cadCAD	3
▶ Application	2
▶ Use	4

📄 Systems Science Book.pdf

Exploring a Systems Language (presentation)

- Shingai making many developments for 📄 [Systems Language / sysXML](#) and distilling our work + including more participants.
 - 📄 [GM Chapter 5](#)
 - Different kinds of Holons applied to 📄 [Systems Science](#) — Reflect, Observe, Plan, Reflect (*O Active Inference, where art thy sting?*)
 - Committee can:
 - Utilize 📄 [GM Chapter 5](#) diagram and deep systems analysis as a committed single source of truth. Follow the procedure and de-compose the sub-systems. You will then find the processes that make up the thing.
 - What is the tracing of systems principles to this diagram? That's the book :)

- The book outlines a draft specification of attributes of systems, and many truth drops in terms of process. Following the 📄 [GM Chapter 5](#) chapters (understood as only a linearized pointer sequence of their own experiences). This is not a complete descriptor. This is A CORE (not "the" or "whole thing") and George's work points towards 📄 [Systems Language / sysXML](#)
- Scaffold and plan to use 📄 [Systems Language / sysXML](#) as open source project — including "triple play" of natural languages, production of visualizations, and executable systems simulations.
- Human as natural processes.

cadCAD in sysXML

I've had a chance to look over the cadCAD website and see what the platform can do. In terms of figure 5.1 in the SS book, it looks like subsystems 3 & 4 would readily be accommodated within the cadCAD framework. A few questions: How would it work with subsystem 1, Analysis? One idea that I'm working on would be to have the archetype models (CAES) of Part 3 already in the knowledgebase, subsystem 2, and used by a generative AI as part of subsystem 1 to prompt or suggest to the analyst the process of analysis steps to refine or elaborate the model as per the process outlined in chapter 6. The archetype models would be "seed" models and act as prompts to the AI that would, in turn, prompt the human analyst about what to do or look for next.

What sorts of interoperability interfaces would be needed to couple the cadCAD core with the knowledgebase and the presumptive analysis modules? Since it is written in python and is opensource I shouldn't think this would be difficult to work out. I looked briefly at NeoJ4's Nodes database system which might be a good candidate for the knowledgebase implementation. It appears to be a closed architecture but I would expect its import/export interfaces would be flexible.

Re: sysXML

I got to thinking I ought to emphasize that my conception of sysxml is not meant to suggest that it would be the "best" way to approach a user-friendly representation of code for the systems framework. It was meant primarily as an example of how the coding might look. And XML is a highly transportable language. In case either of you wanted to explore alternatives I have no objections.

-George

This makes sense, thanks for the clarification George.

I see it like

HTML : Webpage :: sysHTML : Systems-Oriented Programming

And the analogical transformation from the left to the right side, is left to the reader.

-Daniel

sysXML notes

- Systems-Based Engineering
 - We have different models of kinds of systems, which engineers can refer to, regarding engineering a system.
 - Last part of George's book. Then the models can guide the implementation
 - <https://www.omgwiki.org/MBSE/doku.php>
 - sysML — went beyond UML. However still they struggle to get something general. sysML is oriented towards engineering. However George's emphasis in [Systems Language / sysXML](#) is more general in application scope.

•

Java and C++ were complex, developed to support software engineering, however you had to know the concepts deeply. Python was not initially Object-Oriented as such, and thus was flexible enough to accept the OO paradigm in implementation. Language of choice.

- [Systems Language / sysXML](#) and Systems-Oriented Programming.
- Try to marry up, in a systems framework, the Descriptive and the Functional aspects. Functional programming.
- The idea, was to make this accessible like a Markup language.
- So many people were able to learn HTML. Describing what a page would look like. Then embedding scripting languages within HTML and so on. However the page description, and the scripting environments, were not built from an integrated system perspective.,
- Start with Systemsness, staying in both lanes (Object and Process).
- I attended a webinar with Sophia Prater a couple of years ago, Object-Oriented UX:
<https://www.ooux.com/people/sophiavprater>
- Once you Described an object, then you had to go back to Process orientation. The hardest thing for George to teach the students was this shift.
- Teaching Object-Oriented programming in C (not C++), to show how C++ implemented things. Because the C++ compiler was a pre-processor for C programs, which could be compiled and executed.
- This issue is resolved with the systems orientation.
- Systems Dynamic (STELLA) tried to merge object and process in an (incomplete) systems framework. Did not have the fullness of Systems-ness in it. People did not look at SD as a programming language (they were not looking to it when engineering the Denver airport baggage handling system).

George building some more realistic models regarding Energy Production. Not just proximate solar energy production, but how much energy/inputs were needed. The other languages at the time did not have the expressiveness that was needed.

So he considered these Systems icons (Stocks, Flows, Controls and MORE), all the things that are required for Systemness.

- You are constructing a System, not just an Object/Program.
- <https://www.ibm.com/docs/en/rational-soft-arch/9.5?topic=migration-rational-rose-model>
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IBM_Rational_Rose_XDE
- UML — [Unified Modeling Language](#) it described the structure, and captured relationships, it was a good thinking tool for the time. Then there was a disconnect when trying to implement.
 - sysML is a little better because Function is included within the model.
 - People would make elaborate UML diagrams without [@Front end](#) guidance. Since then, many model-based design approaches have arisen.

Is it useful to think about [Systems Language / sysXML](#) as....

- Program (written in another language).
- Package specification (could be written in another language).
 - Analytic representation.
- Language
- Paradigm — Systemness

If the programs work well, people will want to adopt the paradigm (Bucky Fuller and whatnot).

Writing the [@Front end](#) as a Guide, so the underlying Syntax would constrain/enable different kinds of Operations. You have to follow the rules, balanced system, etc. — Force the issue of Systemness. Then the [@Back end](#) is implementing this system.

System Modeling SIG

- ▷ Wednesday 10am PT (18 UTC) — Shingai plans for
 - ▼ [Systems Language / sysXML](#)
 - ▷ Shingai sharing:<https://systemlanguage.notion.site/System-Language-84bf57e4fd6541269733bb8893ee84a4>
 - ▼ Systems Modeling SIG
 - ▷ <https://www.isss.org/systems-modelling-and-systems-engineering/> — will change from “S Modeling and S Engineering” to just the Modeling — applies in [Systems Science](#) and Systems Engineering.
 - ▷ It was not very formal process for taking over a dormant SIG. Starting one, does have minimum thresholds.

Active Blockference

▷ 16 UTC on Mondays (8am PT) in the [All Discord](#).

https://coda.io/d/Active-Blockference_dlvNESFmyj6/Active-Blockference_suGC9#_luzK-

June 2024

Here is the standalone [June 2024](#) document to share:

https://coda.io/d/ISSS-June-2024-Workshop_d0Vgv8w8Z06/ISSS-June-2024-Workshop_suF2T#_Ju5kS

Dates

- June 9-13 — ISSS conference in Washington DC.
 - Some topics/events we are tracking
 - George's plenary lecture
 - [ISSS June 2024 Workshop](#)
 - GST SIG [GST-24](#) and papers here
 - Karl H — The Roots and Future of human-centered artificial intelligence, user experience, and accessibility — Englebart, NIC, ABC.
 - [@Shingai Thornton](#) do you have any plans to join any events? [Systems Language / sysXML](#)
 - Robert Johannsen et al.
- .

To do before then.

- Register personally for the conference.
 - Plan travel & stay
- Write email to send to 🇺🇸 Education People 🇺🇸 Knowledge Engineering People , about updates & plans & offer for coauthorship on our conference paper.

Hello all,

This is a short update from our work in Education & Knowledge Engineering at ISSS ([see this email in our Coda](#)).

In June, multiple of us will be heading to Washington DC (in person &/or remotely) for the [ISSS conference](#). We will be submitting a paper as a group, reflecting on our work over the last 18 months.

Depending on who wants to contribute what to this collaborative paper, we are excited to be covering variety topics in this paper related to Systems (drawing upon previous meetings & contributions to [Education](#) and [Knowledge Engineering](#)).

So:

1. If you have participated in our activities and would like to join as a co-author on this conference paper — **please respond to this email before April 12**. We will write the draft Abstract during our April 12 meeting at 16 UTC, submit that in the following days (Abstract deadline is May 1), and then write the paper during May.
2. When this paper is complete in June, we will send it out to you, and again ask to see who has interest/capacity to participate in the next (post-June) phase of our work.

Thank you,

Daniel

- Writing Abstract for the submission
 - Can write that on 4/12/2024**
 - George, Rob, Peter, Karl H, Shingai, Dave, Tom Daniel,
- .
- View on which
 - KE=E
 - E=KE
 - E-KE
- Engineering & Learning?
 - In project-based pedagogy
 - As in some of George's papers, and 🗨️ [ISSS June 2024 Workshop](#) like: Chalk talk → Application.
 - Knowledge Transfer? Some are not thriving from the lecture/note-taking, and Yes in the application setting.
 - How related to Design?
 - Designing, still requires the Engineering to be implemented.
- Information // Knowledge
 - Terrance Deacon — levels of informative patterns.
 - Shannon information.
 - The communication channel Sender/Receiver context is taken as *a priori* from the Entropic calculation. Meaning/Media of the message is in the receipt.
- .
- ...
 - Build the awareness/preference/desire for ____

- Provide tools, approaches, learnings, connections, for ____
- Revitalizing people's interest and
- GST as the fundamental piece here.
- .
- Formal and minable interdisciplinary analogical structures? Often invisible due to disciplinary boundaries/etc. E.g. if Mathematics had suppressed analogical relations — Weyl would not have lived long enough to prove Fermat's. Math has been accelerated thusly. Nothing is blocking a much-expanded exploitation of these existing analogies and metaphors.
- .
- Intersection & Integration
 - 🗣️ Language Models
- .
- .
- .
- Total numbers, e.g. 70-200. Not sure for 2024 who will be in person, who will be online.
- Learn by doing, project-based teams
- IBM & learning exercise.
 - Starting with a chaotic process.
 - Materials in // ??? // Products out.
 - Then enable splitting up to reorganize/resolve these.
- Why isn't Systems Science/Literacy, more widely taught?
 - And why not used in Knowledge/Systems?
- .
- Persona matrix.
- Systems as infra-/pre-disciplinary. It must come fractally-first, earlier in education (not in College for first time) and earlier in the course (e.g. lead in with the nested/interacting systems rather than implicit/explicit framing as like a capstone after disciplinary ladder).
- What else to do
 - Download & Zenodo publish

Abstract

Deadline for Abstract Submission: May 1, 2024.

- 4/19 - 4/26 — Email all the authors, get anyone comments on abstract, confirmation on authorship/ORCID, and [ISSS June 2024 Workshop](#) ideas.
- 4/26 — submit the [ISSS June 2024 Workshop](#) abstract. People can register for the conference.
- May — prepare [June 2024](#) travels.

Title

"To see a World in a Grain of Sand, And a Heaven in a Wild Flower, Hold Infinity in the palm of your hand, And Eternity in an hour of Systems Science Education and Knowledge Engineering."

"...And Eternity in an hour of Systems Science Education and Knowledge Engineering."

Abstract

Here we report on our works in Education & Knowledge Engineering, drawing upon the authors' activities at the International Society for Systems Science (ISSS).

In 2022, efforts to enhance the ISSS website and documentation revealed opportunities to systematize educational resources. Along with participatory dialogs, a Systems Education Survey was conducted to assess the current landscape and future possibilities of educational aspects and initiatives. Active community participation highlighted the importance of knowledge engineering as enabling infrastructure for curating and disseminating systems knowledge, leading to collaborations with the Systems Community Alliance (SCA), a platform for preserving and sharing systems science knowledge assets. Development efforts centered around Systems Language (sysXML), an example of using knowledge representation to structure systems concepts.

We argue that advances in systems science education and practice can arise at the **intersection** of many approaches. The **integration** of knowledge engineering and educational initiatives will support the realization of systems science as a more influential academic discipline and responsible societal force. By harnessing the power of knowledge engineering, even with tools already available freely today, systems science researchers can more effectively capture, organize, and disseminate the transdisciplinary knowledge that characterizes this field. This, in turn, will enable the development of more comprehensive and accessible educational programs, fostering the growth of a knowledgeable and engaged community of systems thinkers and practitioners.

June 2024 Abstract submission

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Hello all,

You have expressed interest in being a co-author in our upcoming workshop submission to the ISSS conference (whether you will be joining the conference in person, remotely, or not at all).

Please go to [this page](#) and add your affiliation + ORCID information, and then click the checkbox for "Authorship confirmed".

Next week, 4/26, we will submit the workshop abstract with the authors who have confirmed authorship directly in Coda or via email.

Reply here privately if you have any questions.

Thank you,

Daniel

Deadline for Abstract Submission: May 1, 2024.

<https://www.isss.org/2025-washington-dc/>

https://www.isss.org/editor_upload/File/ISSS%20Washington%202024%20Call%20for%20Papers.pdf

Preparing Abstracts

- Download the [ISSS instructions and template for abstracts as word doc](#)
- Open the abstract template using a word processing program that will let you save your abstract as a Microsoft Word .doc file.
- Complete the fields in the template, including:
 - Title
 - Author
 - Address
 - Body text
- Abstracts SHOULD NOT exceed 500 words and SHOULD NOT include:
 - Underscores
 - Figures and tables in the abstract
 - References
 - Footnotes
 - Font size changes.

<https://www.isss.org/submitting-abstracts/>

FOR THE 2024 Conference:

Paper/Presentation categories

Category 1: Complete papers and presentations regarding completed work. SIG Chairs will identify which manuscripts are suitable for this category and the paper will undergo a double-blind peer review. The SIG Chair will identify two reviewers to conduct a blind review. A selection of authors from this category will be invited to submit an extended/reworked or updated version of the presented paper for review to the Systems Research and Behavioral Science (SRBS, <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/10991743a>) special issue known as the ISSS Yearbook. Manuscripts that SIG Chairs determine are not suitable for Category 1, will become Category 2 submissions.

Category 2: Reports and presentations on work-in-progress, preliminary results and directions of future work. Full reports suitable for the proceedings of the conference. Authors may wish to incorporate feedback from the conference into future revisions of the work.

- Internal headings
- Color.

5. Save the document as a .doc file under a name that includes the surname of the lead author, e.g. 2016ISSSAuthor1.doc We cannot use PDF files.

Category 3: Presentations of proposed concepts, position papers/essays, or speculative thoughts.

All three categories require extended abstracts (up to 500 words) with submission, abstracts to be published in the conference proceedings.

Category 1 requires full paper submissions for peer review. Categories 2 and 3 may be proposals for presentations only (except in the case of position papers or essays). All abstracts will be reviewed by SIG chairs.

1. "To see a World in a Grain of Sand, And a Heaven in a Wild Flower, Hold Infinity in the palm of your hand, And Eternity in an hour of Systems Science Education and Knowledge Engineering."
2. "In the universe, there are things that are known, and things that are unknown, and in between, there are doors to the Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository."
3. "The road of excess leads to the palace of Knowledge Engineering."
4. "If the doors of perception were cleansed, everything would appear to man as it is, Infinite in Systems Language (sysXML)."
5. "I must create an ontology or be enslaved by another man's; I will not reason and compare: my business is to create knowledge graphs."
6. "The man who never alters his opinion is like standing water, and breeds reptiles of the mind in digital repositories."
7. "The Systems Education Survey that can be told is not the eternal Systems Education Survey."
8. "He who binds to himself a joy, Does the winged life destroy; But he who kisses the joy as it flies, Lives in eternity's sunrise of Educational Aspects & Initiatives."
9. "Improvement makes strait roads, but the crooked roads without Improvement, are roads of Genius in the ISSS website and documentation."
10. "What is now proved was once only imagined in the integration of knowledge engineering and educational initiatives."
11. "The bird a nest, the spider a web, man friendship through systems science as an academic discipline and responsible societal force."
12. "The hours of folly are measured by the clock; but of wisdom, no clock can measure in the realm of leveraging knowledge engineering approaches."

te

Here's a reimagining of William Blake's "Proverbs of Hell" to align with the themes of the Abstract:

Proverbs of Systems Science

In seed time learn, in harvest teach, in winter enjoy the fruits of knowledge engineering.

Drive your cart and your plow over the bones of the dead theories, for the path of systems science is paved with innovation.

The road of excess leads to the palace of wisdom in the realms of complexity.

Prudence is a rich ugly old maid courted by Incapacity, while Boldness is the key to unlocking the potential of systems thinking.

He who desires but acts not, breeds pestilence in the stagnant waters of outdated paradigms.

The cut worm forgives the plow that tills the soil of interdisciplinary research.

Dip him in the river who loves water, but immerse him in the depths of systems science who loves knowledge.

A fool sees not the same tree that a wise man sees, for the branches of systems thinking are many and varied.

He whose face gives no light, shall never become a star in the constellation of systems science pioneers.

Eternity is in love with the productions of time, and the Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository is a testament to this enduring relationship.

The busy bee has no time for sorrow, but the diligent systems scientist makes time for reflection and growth.

The hours of folly are measured by the clock, but of wisdom there is no clock that can measure the insights gained through systems science education.

All wholesome food is caught without a net or a trap, and the feast of knowledge is open to all who seek it.

Bring out number weight & measure in a year of dearth, for the tools of knowledge engineering are ever-ready to serve.

No bird soars too high, if he soars with his own wings of systems thinking.

A dead body revenges not injuries inflicted upon the stagnant pools of outdated thinking.

The most sublime act is to set another before you, and the Systems Education Survey does just that by assessing the needs of the community.

If the fool would persist in his folly he would become wise, and the persistent pursuit of systems science leads to enlightenment.

Folly is the cloak of knavery, but the cloak of wisdom is woven from the threads of knowledge engineering and educational initiatives.

Shame is Pride's cloak, but the proud pursuit of systems science casts off shame and embraces growth.

Prisons are built with stones of Law, Brothels with bricks of Religion, but the edifice of systems science is built upon the foundation of knowledge and understanding.

The pride of the peacock is the glory of God, and the glory of systems science is in its ability to bridge the gap between the known and the unknown.

The lust of the goat is the bounty of God, and the bounty of systems science is in its ability to inspire and transform.

The wrath of the lion is the wisdom of God, and the wisdom of systems science is in its ability to illuminate the complex web of interconnectedness that underlies all things.

The nakedness of woman is the work of God, and the work of systems science is to lay bare the truth of the world in all its complexity and beauty.

Excess of sorrow laughs. Excess of joy weeps, and the pursuit of systems science brings both joy and sorrow in the quest for understanding.

The roaring of lions, the howling of wolves, the raging of the stormy sea, and the destructive sword are portions of eternity too great for the eye of man, but the eye of the systems scientist sees the eternal in the temporal.

The fox condemns the trap, not himself, and the unenlightened condemn the complexity of the world, not their own limited understanding.

Joys impregnate. Sorrows bring forth the seeds of new understanding in the fertile soil of systems science.

Let man wear the fell of the lion, woman the fleece of the sheep, and let the systems scientist wear the cloak of knowledge and wisdom.

The bird a nest, the spider a web, man friendship through the shared pursuit of systems science and the common goal of understanding.

The selfish smiling fool, & the sullen frowning fool shall be both thought wise, that they may be a rod for the backs of those who seek wisdom through systems science.

What is now proved was once only imagined, and what is now imagined in the realm of systems science will one day be proved.

The rat, the mouse, the fox, the rabbit watch the roots; the lion, the tyger, the horse, the elephant watch the fruits of knowledge that grow from the tree of systems science.

The cistern contains: the fountain overflows with the waters of wisdom that spring from the well of systems science.

One thought fills immensity, and that thought is the transformative power of systems thinking.

Always be ready to speak your mind, and a base man will avoid you, but the wise will seek out your counsel.

Everything possible to be believed is an image of truth, and the truth of systems science is that everything is interconnected.

The eagle never lost so much time, as when he submitted to learn of the crow the ways of systems thinking.

The fox provides for himself, but God provides for the lion the prey of knowledge that is systems science.

Think in the morning. Act in the noon. Eat in the evening. Sleep in the night, but let the light of systems science guide your path always.

He who has suffered you to impose on him knows you, and the impositions of ignorance are no match for the clarity of systems thinking.

As the plow follows words, so God rewards prayers with the bounty of understanding that comes from the pursuit of systems

science.

The tigers of wrath are wiser than the horses of instruction, for the wrath of the systems scientist is tempered by wisdom and understanding.

Expect poison from the standing water of stagnant thinking, but expect the elixir of wisdom from the flowing stream of systems science.

You never know what is enough unless you know what is more than enough, and the pursuit of systems science is a journey of discovery that knows no bounds.

Listen to the fool's reproach! It is a kingly title! For the fool's reproach is a spur to the wise, urging them ever onward in the pursuit of systems science.

The eyes of fire, the nostrils of air, the mouth of water, the beard of earth are the elements of systems science, each playing its part in the grand tapestry of understanding.

The weak in courage is strong in cunning, but the strong in courage and wisdom is the systems scientist.

The apple tree never asks the beech how he shall grow, nor the lion the horse how he shall take his prey, for the systems scientist knows that each must find its own path to understanding.

The thankful receiver bears a plentiful harvest in the fields of systems science, for gratitude is the key to unlocking the bounty of knowledge.

If others had not been foolish, we should be so, but the foolishness of others is a reminder to the systems scientist to seek wisdom always.

The soul of sweet delight can never be defiled by the pursuit of systems science, for it is a noble and enlightening endeavor.

When thou seest an Eagle, thou seest a portion of Genius. Lift up thy head! And when thou seest a systems scientist, thou seest a portion of wisdom. Lift up thy heart!

As the caterpillar chooses the fairest leaves to lay her eggs on, so the priest lays his curse on the fairest joys, but the systems scientist finds joy in the pursuit of truth and understanding.

To create a little flower is the labour of ages, and to create a new paradigm in systems science is the labour of lifetimes.

Damn braces. Bless relaxes, and blessed is the systems scientist who can find relaxation in the pursuit of knowledge.

The best wine is the oldest, the best water the newest, and the best ideas are those that have stood the test of time in the annals of systems science.

Prayers plow not! Praises reap not! Joys laugh not! Sorrows weep not! But the prayers, praises, joys, and sorrows of the systems scientist are the seeds that bring forth the harvest of understanding.

The head Sublime, the heart Pathos, the genitals Beauty, the hands & feet Proportion, and the systems scientist embodies all of these in the pursuit of knowledge.

As the air to a bird or the sea to a fish, so is contempt to the contemptible, but the systems scientist rises above contempt and seeks only truth.

The crow wished everything was black, the owl that everything was white, but the systems scientist knows that the world is a tapestry of many colors and shades.

Exuberance is Beauty, and the beauty of systems science is in its exuberance for discovery and understanding.

If the lion was advised by the fox, he would be cunning, and if the systems scientist was advised by the narrow-minded, he would be lost.

Improvement makes strait roads, but the crooked roads without Improvement are roads of Genius, and the genius of the systems scientist lies in the ability to navigate the crooked roads of complexity.

Sooner murder an infant in its cradle than nurse unacted desires, and the desires of the systems scientist are for knowledge and understanding above all else.

Where man is not, nature is barren, and where systems science is not, knowledge is barren.

Truth can never be told so as to be understood and not be believed, and the truth of systems science is that it has the power to transform our understanding of the world.

Abstract:

- In our works, we continue to explore the critical role of knowledge engineering as an enabler for effective systems science education. Specifically we draw upon the our activities at the International Society for Systems Science (ISSS).
- Our projects discussed here began in 2022 with efforts to enhance the ISSS website and documentation, revealing opportunities to systematize educational resources
 - Initially we assessed and implemented a Systems Education Survey, exploring different Educational Aspects & Initiatives, to understand the current landscape and future possibilities.
 - Active community participation highlighted the importance of knowledge engineering as enabling infrastructure for curating and disseminating systems knowledge — leading to collaborations with the Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository as a platform for preserving and sharing systems science knowledge assets
 - Development efforts centered around Systems Language (sysXML), as an example of using knowledge representation to structure systems concepts.
- We argue that advances in systems science education may be linked to leveraging knowledge engineering approaches such as ontologies, knowledge graphs, and digital repositories. The integration of knowledge engineering and educational initiatives will support the realization of systems science as a more influential academic discipline and responsible societal force.

ISSS June 2024 Workshop

Workshop overview:

- ▼ Abstract in [the agenda](#) (unfold).
 - ▷ Here we report on our works in Education & Knowledge Engineering, drawing upon the authors' activities at the International Society for Systems Science (ISSS).
 - ▷ In 2022, efforts to enhance the ISSS website and documentation revealed opportunities to systematize educational resources. Along with participatory dialogs, a Systems Education Survey was conducted to assess the current landscape and future possibilities of educational aspects and initiatives. Active community participation highlighted the importance of knowledge engineering as enabling infrastructure for curating and disseminating systems knowledge, leading to collaborations with the Systems Community Alliance (SCA), a platform for preserving and sharing systems science knowledge assets. Development efforts centered around Systems Language (sysXML), an example of using knowledge representation to structure systems concepts.
 - ▷ We argue that advances in systems science education and practice can arise at the intersection of many approaches. The integration of knowledge engineering and educational initiatives will support the realization of systems science as a more influential academic discipline and responsible societal force. By harnessing the power of knowledge engineering, even with tools already available freely today, systems science researchers can more effectively capture, organize, and disseminate the transdisciplinary knowledge that characterizes this field. This, in turn, will enable the development of more comprehensive and accessible educational programs, fostering the growth of a knowledgeable and engaged community of systems thinkers and practitioners.
- To accommodate & synergize the contributions/affordances of in-person and remote participation, in this 90 minute session, we will center the session around an editable shared document.
 - This document will have some prefigured structural elements and concepts/links from the broader [document when our ISSS Knowledge Engineering & Education](#) efforts have been documented since 2022.
 - We can publish the snapshot of the document the end of the session using [Publishing & Dissemination](#). This will serve as a milestone & reflect the collaborative spirit of this project and session. Additionally the open science publishing methodology will enact transferable skills & catalyze discussions related to dissemination, accessibility, and beyond.

Agenda:

Workshop agenda

Name	Time	Page
Opening & About this session	10	👤 Overview & 👤 Participation
Driving questions	10	🗨️ Driving questions
Education	20	📖 Education Workshop
Knowledge Engineering	20	🔧 Knowledge Engineering Workshop
Publication	15	📄 Publishing & Dissemination
Future, Onwards, and To Be Done	15	🚀 Onwards...
	Sum	90

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Overview

One trunk....

- Weekly Live Knowledge Engineering Meetings, first on Thursdays then later on Fridays.
 - Playlist of Education meetings
 - Playlist of Knowledge Engineering meetings

With two (sub-)trees....

- Education
- Knowledge Engineering

Thanks to all the co-authors on this session & those who came through during the last few years~

On the title of the session:

**To see a World in a Grain of
Sand
And a Heaven in a Wild
Flower
Hold Infinity in the palm of
your hand
And Eternity in an hour**

To see a World in a Grain of Sand / And a Heaven in a Wild Flower / Hold Infini

[Auguries of Innocence, William Blake](#)

Participation

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Coda is like our digital niche, where we can bring/add/move pebbles (like text, images, links) and mark with pheromones (e.g. ↕, **formatting**, color, and other interesting elements).

This extended niche helps us integrate Participation and diverse perspectives/contributions from our online and in-person participants.

For a given page, Coda is like a text document. Like a wiki, several linked/nested pages together make up a Document.

Some commands and functions can be explored by selecting text, and:

using `/` (the backslash) will reveal many templates & ways to use Coda.

using `@` can call any object, page, or row in the document.

Some modes of Participation

- Listening to what is happening live,
- Reading and scanning through what has been posted here
- Adding questions, comments, edits, resources; restructuring, etc.
- Writing in the online chat (and/or copying what others have written
- If you want to be contacted and/or part of [🔗 Publishing & Dissemination](#), add your information to [📋 Workshop Participants](#)
-
- add.....
- ...
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Driving questions

Driving questions

.....feel free to read, comment, and add questions/thoughts below:

What (does **Education?**

- Given that we don't have "the GST" — consider the discussion of "a theory of Systemsness" as opposed to "general systems theory" per George's talk.
- To be knowledge, structure must be indexible and accessible, to relate concepts to various other concepts.
 - The question of education is then how these structures are transferred. And on this we can look to the work of neurolinguistics.
- Weltaunshaaung — World view in body of knowledge, cognitive structures and shared bodies of knowledge, dialog, epistemological structures.
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How is Education best facilitated, in terms of how Knowledge is organized?

- The coordination between a knowledge engineering process to organize knowledge for purposes of teaching/learning is not new.
- Textbooks and syllabi's are examples of the organization of knowledge in a format accessible for education
- The effort to provide effective education has always been knowledge engineering, long before that term was created. That is, the organizing of knowledge into categories and "chunks" in a structure that allows efficient access and that reflects the actual epistemological structure itself. Writing and reading was the first knowledge engineering.
- Teacher preparation itself relies on properly engineered knowledge.
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How can modern approaches to corpus analysis (formal, analogical, metaphorical, and statistical/ **Language Models**) catalyze this work & what are hurdles/frictions along this road?

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What are the Education & Knowledge Engineering gaps/frictions/limitations that people are actually having? In past years of the ISSS?

What is the gap between e.g. widespread and continual recognition of "Systemic issues", and the application of science to these issues?

How can we work effectively today to preserve physical and digital legacies?

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What might be functions or roles of the ISSS in Education in general?

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George's Notes (May 2024)

Systems Education — to save the education system. In order for this, treating *Knowledge as a System* meaning organizing/interacting with it as such.

Historically, just doing stuff. Libraries then were methods for systemically organizing knowledge. Guidance for Library classification and Dewey Decimal System, is essentially completely prone to Disciplinary boundaries and norms. That is Systematic, though not Systemic.

Natural Science bodies of knowledge, through science, do take on / reflect elements of systemsness.

How do Semantic technologies come into play here?

- Why do we need to categorize?
 - It does not need to be in single or fixed categories. E.g. a given book can be tagged with different categories/descriptions per person.
- How with working across languages and contexts?
- Ray Jackendoff — production and understanding of language.
 - <https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.07987> The Platonic Representation Hypothesis
 - Patterns emerging in languages. Linguistic-based sorting.
 - Taxonomy as Systematic. Living systems as Systemic.
 - Species names in e.g. English, German, Latin. Species concept.
 - In Tom's modeling, key useful element to decouple the Definition and Presentation.
 - Underlying definition/completeness in the database. Then use the Views and zooming in/out from there to control detail.
 - Within single defined model, can check and establish coherence, guaranteeing multiple views can be generated.
 - Structural-Function decomposition methodology in George's book. Breadth/Depth search, either way combining in to the knowledgebase. Then from viewing perspectives, can view into sub-systems down to components.
 - Adaptability and feedback in use. Updating names.
<https://www.digitalocean.com/community/tutorials/gangs-of-four-gof-design-patterns>
 - Semantic Reaction Function — Expression function mapping (generative) and interpretative (recognition).
 - Geometry of Meaning — Peter Gärdenfors <https://mitpress.mit.edu/9780262533751/the-geometry-of-meaning/> & combining with Topological, Discrete, Category Theory.
 - — What is meant, and in transferring, with Systems.
The diagram is a triangle with a circle around it. The top vertex is labeled 'representamen', the bottom-left is 'object', and the bottom-right is 'interpretant'. Arrows connect them in a cycle: representamen to object, object to interpretant, and interpretant to representamen. The circle is labeled 'semiosis'.
 - Modeling, adaptability, infinite semiosis.
- Make an image of birds flying in a V.
 - Tip of the V is Systems Science.
One wing is Education and pedagogy.
Other wing is Archival and Curation.
- <https://networkliteracy.org/> — Peter T

Knowledge Engineering for Education

The objective of an **education system is to transfer veridical knowledge from the current curating (and discovering) generation to the next.** By "veridical knowledge" we mean mental beliefs about the world that correspond with the actual nature of the world we live in. If the proposition that the world is a system is correct, then this means that the most effective veridical knowledge is systems knowledge.

The responsibility of the current generation is to organize knowledge in a systemic fashion so that it is:

- Categorized appropriately (hierarchically structured)
- Indexable
- Accessible
- Comprehensible (age appropriate)

Over the course of the history of education, these requirements have been met by evolutionary development, that is, by hit-and-miss, experimental try-and-see methods. Nobody set out to design a grand architecture of knowledge. Constructs of knowledge have been developed by discovery and recording in a haphazard way. This is not necessarily bad or wrong; after all, humans started from a state of ignorance and gradually developed their sense of knowing (what, how, when, etc.) following the evolution of language. Their organization simply followed a natural bottom-up structuring.

Most of the organization of knowledge has been the result of ad hoc subject development within the various subject silos. Natural science and math subjects have been reasonably successful in constructing reasonable knowledge structures by virtue of being highly rational processes of knowledge discovery and recording. It is less clear that the social sciences and humanities subjects have been as organized. However, in the latter case, it is uncertain as to what it even means to have "veridical" knowledge. More research on the epistemology of these subjects is warranted. Even so, we might conjecture that a systemic organization of knowledge in these domains would benefit students. Indeed, we might argue it would benefit all human kind. Given the complexities of the modern world, and the apparent existential threats to our continuing as a species, getting a handle on the nature of, and organization of, veridical knowledge would seem to be a front-and-center necessity.

Systems science offers an approach to designing a systemic structure of knowledge. Knowledge engineering further provides a potential methodology for organizing knowledge to obtain the above listed requirements.

We seek to accomplish two objectives. First we want to develop an architecture for systems knowledge that is based on systems principles (e.g., recognizes the nature of hierarchies and networks for the organization of knowledge). Second we want to develop a methodology for exposing learning minds to this knowledge in a way that maximizes inculcation and, especially, an individual's access to their own knowledge for effective interactions with their own world.

This working group has engaged in discussions aimed at exploring how these objectives might be met.

Original notes from George to Daniel 5-22-2024 below.

Knowledge Engineering for Education

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Education Workshop

- 🏠 Education
 - What could be done? 📄 [Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions](#)
 - What is out there?
 - 📄 [Systems Census of](#) 🏢 [Systems Organizations, Universities, Programs](#) (frontend link)
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Knowledge Engineering Workshop

- [Knowledge Engineering](#)
 - What can be learned and done with new computational methods? [Language Models](#) & [LLM & ISSS](#) & [LLM tools](#)
 - How can we support local and broader archival and curatorial work? [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#) & [ISSS Collections](#) from [ISSS @ SCA](#).
 - How can we develop tools from [George Mobus](#) textbook for applying Systems Science
[Systems Language / sysXML](#)
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Workshop Participants

Participation

Name	Email	ORCID	Affiliation	Include in publication?	Looking to interact about...
				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
				<input type="checkbox"/>	
				<input type="checkbox"/>	

Publishing & Dissemination

Zenodo is an Open Science publishing platform. It enables any files/dataset/repository, to get a digital object identifier (DOI) and hosting.

[10.5281/zenodo.10034511](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10034511).

<https://zenodo.org/records/10034512>

1. Finalize Workshop Participants information
2. Any last changes to pages.
3. Download PDFs of pages.
 - a. Driving questions
 - b. Education Workshop
 - c. Knowledge Engineering Workshop
4. Concatenate pages ([link](#)).
5. Upload PDF to [Zenodo](#) & enter metadata.
6. Published link:

Onwards...

Communications

Coda documents:

Education: [LINK](#)

Knowledge Engineering: https://coda.io/d/ISSS-Knowledge-Engineering_dPEy1CASvFL/Knowledge-Engineering_suNUS

Video playlists:

Education: https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL36GDzgkIWrmJvnc_xwIZiJFcgK0FQbx7

Knowledge Engineering: https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL36GDzgkIWrlMofRzb0h2qqwi_pjabb8t

- Thank you for the response & suggestions, much appreciated.
- To find a time to discuss Education live, here are some availabilities:
 - <https://calendly.com/docxology/education-meeting>
 - Or let me know your preference.
- I am currently integrating the Education-related input from many ISSS members into some coherent initiatives. I will keep you posted on these ISSS Education developments, and provide more information on progress. Let me know if you have any other ideas/questions, and feel free to reach out any time.
- Thank you for the message and contributions here, very much appreciated.
- Definitely resonate the perspective on Systems education here. Agreed it should be a central aspect of lifelong education and training (youth on up). Also agreed that it is best to take a multiperspectival/transdisciplinary approach towards Systems conceptually/pedagogically, and an action/service/ethics/embodied approach towards Systems applications.
- I see my ISSS role as coordinating global Systems education (Section 4.6.3.8 in the By-Laws: <https://www.iss.org/by-laws/>). From what I have seen so far, the ISSS and many individuals are wanting to constellate more/better in some way. So all your suggestions and inputs are noted & very relevant.
- I found “xxxxxxxxxxxxxxxx” YouTube channel and will watch the videos when I have a chance.
- Also I am interested to learn more about this training
- Am happy to continue the discussion here, or via email, and/or finding time to talk.

Aug 19 2022 ~ ISSS Education update to Board

to: Roelien Goede <roelien.goede@nwu.ac.za>, George Mobus <gmobus@uw.edu>, Michele Friend <michele@gwu.edu>, Jennifer M <makarjennifer@gmail.com>, Gary Smith <gary.r.smith@airbus.com>, Pamela Buckle <buckle@adelphi.edu>, Haider Al-Shareefy <haider.alshareefy@soton.ac.uk>, "Calvo-Amodio, Javier" <Javier.Calvo@oregonstate.edu>, David Rousseau <david.rousseau@systemsphilosophy.org>, Peter D Tuddenham <peterdtuddenham@gmail.com>

cc: "Daniel Friedman (VP of Education at ISSS)" <education@issss.org>

Hello all,

This email is an update from my role as VP of Education at ISSS. It is addressed to the current Board; those who I believe may want to read my update & have insights to add at this point. Feel free to loop anyone else in who may assist at this stage, before any specific Educational initiatives are designed or communicated to the membership.

Overall update:

- The attached "ISSS_Education.png" image provides a graphical abstract for how I understand the ISSS By-laws are addressing Education, in terms of overall Objectives as well as Role/Committees structure.
- Following the email sent to active ISSS members on August 17th, direct email responses were obtained from about 30 members (so far). These emails ranged from short "keep me posted" messages, to much longer comments with addressable suggestions and provisions of capacity.
- To structure and synthesize the member input, I am using Coda for documentation. The attached screenshot "ISSS_Education_Coda.png" shows the current top-level directory of the Coda (the links are to pages/tables with more information). Anyone who would like access to this documentation for their consideration & optional contributions, just let me know.
- Over the coming several weeks I will be condensing the diverse inputs provided into several domains, reflecting plausible Education initiatives. At that point I will communicate again with the Board for their feedback, and incorporate it, before sending another round of batched communications to the membership broadly and interested individuals specifically.

Other than anyone's additional thoughts on the 3 questions sent to the membership (reproduced post-script) -- I have two specific areas of uncertainty where I would appreciate your thoughts:

1.

In the [ISSS By-laws 4.8.5](#), there is the specification of an "Educational Programs and Materials Committee". I am unsure about the existence, membership, or status of this EPMC, however by the letter of the (by-)law I am the Co-Chairperson. So I am seeking to understand the situation regarding the EPMC, then assess how it relates to SIGs and other structures that might scaffold Educational programs.

2.

Regarding the [SIG "Designing Educational Systems"](#) — I am not sure about the status of this SIG. It appears to be inactive since around 2017. Several members have suggested to me that we make use of a SIG for Education — I am seeking to assess whether it makes sense to revive this "Designing Educational Systems" SIG or start a new one.

- 8/25/2022 — This SIG is still active.
 - Perhaps
-

Let me know where I can provide more details, otherwise I expect to provide another Education update in several weeks.

Thank you & Peace,

Daniel

Questions asked to ISSS members in the email of August 17, 2022:

1. In terms of **Member education**, what could ISSS do, be, and provide?
2. In terms of **public and non-Member education**, what could ISSS do, be, and provide?
3. Between now and the end of 2022, do you have any skills/capacity/interest for contributing here?

Sept. 6, 2022

Dear Daniel

We are planning to start a meeting every two weeks for the next few months to get started with knowledge engineering our ISSS resources.

Daniel Friedman will send an invite and zoom link. He has created a CODA and will say more about this on Thursday,

I created a webpage <https://www.iss.org/knowledge-engineering/> and on there are some outline ideas and links to some existing resources on ISSS displayed on a mind map.

We will take notes/minutes of the meeting if you cannot attend. I know its short notice but we want to get started.

Peter

Forwarding the above message bcc' and adding:

Hello,

Thank you for your interest in Knowledge Engineering at ISSS.

I have added you with edit access (with the email address this message is sent to) to a [Coda document, which will be our central working document](#). Right now it is pretty sparse, we will use it to document and develop resources, approaches, etc.

We will start 1 hour live meetings on every other Thursday, at 18 UTC (11am PT). The first meeting will be on September 8th (in less than 48 hours), and you have also been added to a calendar (also you can add [ingCal format](#) and [iCal format](#)). We plan for these meetings to be recorded and have live/stored transcript.

[Here is a page in the Coda to add any notes/comments you have before our first meeting](#)

Looking forward to working on this,

Daniel

Sept 10, 2022 ~ To all Interested People

ISSS Education update #1 ~ Optional Meetings and Draft List of Initiatives ~ Sept 10, 2022

Hello,

This email is a first update regarding Education at the ISSS.

This update covers

1. The open bi-weekly meeting/working schedule we will begin on Sept. 15
2. Progress & Process in determining the draft list of 20 Educational initiatives

I expect that this kind of broad update email, to all those who have expressed any interest in Systems Education, will be infrequent (probably not more than once every 2 months). Let me know by reply if you do not want to continue on this Educational updates list.

1.

Starting on September 15th at 18 UTC and continuing on an every-two-weeks basis, there will be optional 1-hour long ISSS Education meetings at [this Zoom link](#). All are welcome at these meetings, they will also be recorded starting a few minutes into the hour. Reply to this email if you would like to be added to a calendar event.

As no meetings have happened yet, there is a lot of openness in terms of structure, and many opportunities for individuals who want to be actively involved and/or take stewardship over some Educational aspects or initiatives.

2.

From the insights and responses provided by dozens of ISSS members and others, currently I have arrived at 20 single-word directions/suggestions for education initiatives. The 20 words are included post-script, and are intended to be interpreted broadly. The list is an initial draft for developing from; hopefully it is subject to much more addition, lumping/splitting, and rearranging.

If anyone would like to see the fuller view of the list and provide any feedback, let me know. Also if anyone is interested to develop any initiatives over the coming 2 months (this could look like however you see fit), it would be highly meaningful and encouraged/supported. We could explore this possibility via email or at a live meeting.

Before the end of 2022 I plan to reach out again (via an update email like this) with the status of the Educational initiatives at that time.

Thank you,

Daniel

International Society for the Systems Sciences (ISSS)
[VP for Communication and Systems Education](#)

Current alphabetical draft list of 20 single-word Educational initiatives

1. Adventures
2. Applications
3. Bridges
4. Consulting
5. Crises
6. Games
7. Health
8. Mentorship
9. Participation
10. Platforms
11. Projects
12. Readings
13. Research
14. [SIG](#)(Special Integration Groups)
15. Symposia
16. Trainings
17. Videos
18. Visualization
19. Web
20. Youth

October 6, 2022 ~ ISSS Knowledge Engineering update with video

Hello,

Here is an 8 minute overview video of the current state of the Knowledge Engineering project:

<https://youtu.be/nLgJHAHjz0Q>

If you have any updates or questions about participation in the project after seeing the video, please reply to this email and/or make the additions directly on the Coda, for example at the page for our [upcoming meeting on October 20](#).

Thank you,

Daniel

- [@Daniel Ari Friedman](#) Thanks for this. Just learning the platform. At the next meeting on 20 October - did you want to give people a tour and maybe some guidelines? I will also upload into a document area the list of digital assets that ISSS has, produced in 2017/2018. I also have a variety of documents when ISSSDigital was operational - a collective intelligence application of managing the ISSS digital offerings. It's great to see that it is progressing in this direction. Thanks again. De. [@Delia Pembrey MacNamara](#)

October 18, 2022

ISSS Education update #2 ~ 10 minute video overview ~ October 18, 2022

Hello,

This email is update #2 about Education at the ISSS.

1.

Here is a 10 minute video update to watch with updates and information on getting involved:

https://youtu.be/V4Mk-MCD_-s

2.

The upcoming 1-hour meetings are on Oct 27 at 18 UTC, and 28 at 17 UTC (Zoom link [here](#)). The agenda structure for these meetings is described in the video overview above.

All are welcome at these meetings (recipients of this email, or anyone else who you think would want to contribute), they will also be recorded starting a few minutes into the hour.

Reply to this email if you have any ideas/questions, or would like to be added to a calendar event.

Thank you,

Daniel

International Society for the Systems Sciences (ISSS)

[VP for Communication and Systems Education](#)

3. 📦 Crossover for EDU from KE

- Upcoming Jan 26 agenda & structure
- 2023 directions

Hello, happy 2023.

This email is sent to you because you have previously expressed interest in the Education and/or Knowledge Engineering projects at [ISSS](#).

Here is a 10-minute summary video that covers the status/directions of both projects in 2023, and describes ways to contribute:

<https://youtu.be/yDUayFVuFyo>

If you want to learn more or get involved:

- Watch the summary video above.
- Respond to this email or education@iss.org with any questions or interest.
- Watch the most recent meeting recordings at the [Education playlist](#) or [Knowledge Engineering playlist](#).
- Join the weekly meetings (19 UTC on Thursdays, alternating focus between the two projects) — request to be added to calendar events for either/both project if you are not already.

Thank you for the attention & service to Systems!

Daniel

January 2023 communication

March 23, 2023

Hello all,

On April 20th 2023 at 18 UTC at [this Zoom link](#), the Knowledge Engineering project at ISSS will host an hour-long “positive entanglement” around the topic of *Systems Science and Large Language Models*, with attention to how these models can be applied to the ISSS Archives in service of accessibility, rigor, and applicability.

For more information on the Knowledge Engineering project, see the [playlist with all recordings of our meetings](#), and our work with the Systems Community Alliance on developing the [ISSS Archives](#).

Reply to this email (or contact education@iss.org) with any comments or questions. We hope you join!

Also, as a primer/prompt for next month’s discussion, postscript we’ve included a generative summary (from GPT3.5) that wrote a short essay based upon some notes from today’s meeting.

Thank you & Peace,

Daniel

Material recommendation is a matter of matching the level of insights of the audience with the suitability of the chosen material. It follows then, that different materials will be more suitable for different people.

The International Systems Science Society (ISSS) provides an opportunity to navigate the spectrum of options for different participant levels. ISSS offers both education streams and research streams, so this allows for the development of specific resources for the promotion of the different use cases.

Furthermore, it is important to be able to recognize false positives and false negatives when navigating the training material and other resources. False positives mean that materials are not suitable for the intended target audience whereas false negatives indicate mismatches with the capabilities of the person dealing with the material. This can lead to individuals spending valuable time on topics outside their expertise.

Organizational learning curves are also a key part of the development of the ISSS program. As people progress through the materials, the community can gain valuable insight into the best ways to support initiatives within the systems thinking realm. Building the capabilities and maturities of members is paramount in this development process.

In conclusion, material recommendations depend fully on matching the knowledge of the audience with the suitability of the chosen material. It is important to consider false positives and false negatives in the recommendation process and is essential to build organizational learning curves as the ISSS program develops. This will ensure that everyone is able to get the most out of their experience with the ISSS program.

June 1, 2023

Knowledge Engineering at ISSS: Unleashing the ISSS Archives with LLM

Dear ISSS Members,

We welcome you to contribute and co-create an innovative project that will revolutionize the way we interact with the vast knowledge stored in the [ISSS Archives](#). This project aims to harness the power of [Coda.io](#), a cutting-edge data representation system, and LLM (Large Language Models) to create an engaging conversation with the past, unlocking the full potential of our Systems Science corpus for Education, Research, and Application.

As a proof of concept, we have developed a Coda representation of the ISSS Archives (e.g. [see the Yearbooks](#)) that will not only pique the interest of other archivists but also enable us to use LLM and ISSS resources in unique ways. This is building on the work of the [Knowledge Engineering team's previous session and curation of LLM tools and topics](#). Imagine having a conversation with the voices of the past, delving into the depths of Systems Science, and uncovering new insights that will shape the future of our field.

To achieve this ambitious goal, we need your invaluable input, expertise, and engagement. We invite you to ask questions that you would like to explore within the Systems Science corpus. Your questions will be used to create a preliminary set of available documents that will help us develop educational materials and plan coursework for using ChatGPT as a powerful learning tool.

We are also seeking generative work in the spirit of Systems Science that will not only enhance our understanding of the field but also contribute to the development of innovative learning techniques. Your involvement in this project will play a crucial role in shaping the future of ISSS and the broader Systems Science community.

To participate, please share with us:

1. Questions you want to ask of the Systems Science corpus.
2. Ideas for generative work that embodies the spirit of Systems Science and enhances learning.
3. Your excitements about direct contributions to the project (e.g. via synchronous meetings on Thursdays at 18 UTC, or kinds of asynchronous contributions you'd like to make).
4. Any other suggestions or insights on how to utilize the ISSS Archives and LLM effectively.

Your contributions will be instrumental in driving this project forward and ensuring its success. We look forward to your participation and the exciting journey that lies ahead.

Warm regards,

Knowledge Engineering project at ISSS

June 2024 ~ Concluding this chapter of Education & Knowledge Engineering at ISSS, and starting the next one

Hello all,

This chapter-ending email is sent to you, as you have previously interacted/communicated with me in some way over the last 2 years, related to Education and Knowledge Engineering at the [ISSS](#).

This past week in Washington DC was the ISSS conference. That milestone concludes my two-year term as VP of Education at ISSS. I have greatly appreciated this highly-collaborative experience and would like to acknowledge the contributions made by many individuals during meetings and between. Best of luck to the ISSS & all going forward in their works.

Here is an [overview of the work we did over the last 2 years](#), centering around weekly meetings which spawned, reviewed, and iterated on our long tail of fractal projects. Not that the infinite can be quantified, however I found it interesting that the document has almost 100,000 words, and almost 700 viewing sessions. Incrementally (not necessarily continually) we have co-created a space of learning, utility, comedy, camaraderie, and insight.

Importantly going forward — myself and multiple others are also motivated and available to continue the work along various fronts related to systems, education, archiving, language, design, tools, and more.

So: If you would like to continue collaborating with us as we embark on the next phase of this journey (or would like to stay updated going forward), please respond to this email. This is an open project, so also feel free to forward this invite/opening along to a colleague. Otherwise, this email will be the last one sent to you on this topic.

Initially at least, we will continue weekly meetings on Fridays at 16 UTC . From there we will catch up from the DC conferences, see who is around for what, and continue from there.

Thank you for your attention and involvement with Systems, Education, and/or Knowledge Engineering — an Eternal Golden Braid (to quote GEB).

Daniel

p.s.

What if the side-quests were the real quests after all?

Archives & Checklists

Big pictures (collapse this to see the Archives & Checklists list)

Here we can create templates and connect/draw from Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository formats/scheme

Connections with e.g. Business process modeling language.

Terminology. Coordination on the GST-24.

High-level

- COLLECTIONS are from Entity (Organizations/People/Family).
 - These are official series, usually from organization (yearbooks, conference, etc).
- FOND (someone's organically-growing collections of materials). *"In archival science, a fonds (plural also fonds) is a group of documents that share the same origin and that have occurred naturally as an outgrowth of the daily workings of an agency, individual, or organization"*
 - Articles written
 - Draft/Unpublished work
 - Personal correspondences
 - Marginalia/Annotation
 - Digitally:
 - Files
 - Websites (self-hosted, other platforms, collaboration websites).

- .
- .
-

 [Overview & Welcome](#)

- Archiving
 - <https://archivaria.ca/index.php/archivaria/article/view/12648>
Theoretical Principles and Practical Problems of *Respect des fonds* in Archival Science (1983)
 12648-Article Text-14644-1-10-2006... pdf
 - Since the second half of the nineteenth century, respect des fonds has traditionally been considered as the basic principle of archival science. By its practice the archivist is most clearly distinguished from the librarian on the one hand and from the professional researcher or documentalist on the other. Like many principles, however, it is easier to state than to define and easier to define than to put into practice. Although its origins are relatively easy to establish, difficulties arise as soon as an attempt is made to study its theoretical aspects thoroughly and to show its practical applications. Generations of archivists and archival technicians have examined these problems without resolving them
 - Consequently, to appreciate a document, it is essential to know exactly where it was created, in the framework of what process, to what end, for whom, when and how it was received by the addressee, and how it came into our hands.

 [Archives & Checklists](#)

General Questions to Consider

1. Who is the **entity**?
2. What is the **overall context** for this project?
3. What are the **materials** (physical and digital will be broken out later)?
4. Have you identified all **locations** where your materials are stored?
 - a. Physical:
 - b. Digital:
5. Do you have a **system for prioritizing** which materials to keep?
6. Have you documented the **context and significance** of your collections?
7. Are there any general, legal, or ethical **considerations** regarding the retention or disposal of certain materials?
8. Have you considered **donating** materials to an institutional archive or library?
9. Have you identified **collaborators** who might help and/or need access to your archives?
10. Is there a **budget allocated** for long-term storage and preservation?
11. Have you created a guide or **documentation** for future users of your archive?
12. Do you have a plan for regular **review and update** of your overall archival system?
13. How will the archival work plug in with the professional, semantic, narrative, and conceptual **communities** which might want to benefit from the work?

Physical Archiving Checklist

1. Create a detailed inventory of all physical items, including location.
2. If needed/possible, reorganize the physical materials into new containers.
 - a. Organize items by type, date, or significance
 - b. Categorize and index items for easy retrieval.
 - c. Use acid-free folders and boxes for storage.
 - d. Label all boxes and folders clearly.
 - e. Store items in a cool, dry place with controlled temperature and humidity
 - f. **Which boxes to get, any other random physical tips.**
3. Develop a retention/revisiting schedule for documents (checking and/or adding documents).
4. Create an emergency plan for natural disasters or theft
5. Consider external storage options for less frequently accessed item
6. Identify and prioritize items of historical or research value
7. Develop a plan to digitize important physical documents
 - a. Where are the primary physical materials stored? (Info-Physical Supply chain before and after scan).
 - b. Where/How will which works be digitized?
 - c. How will the high-resolution primary digital scans, be down-scaled?
8. Create finding aids or catalogs for larger collections
9. Implement pest control measures
10. Ensure proper handling procedures for delicate materials
11. Establish access protocols for sensitive information

12. How searchable are the materials to whom? E.g. connecting with Dewey Decimal system, what kinds of repositories are being built up with and connecting with.

Digital Archiving Checklist

1. Identify and select **important digital resources** to preserve
 - a. Files
 - b. Emails
 - c. Websites (e.g. see <https://www.httrack.com/> for scraping).
2. Organize digital files with clear metadata (e.g., author, date, subject)
3. Follow the 3-2-1 rule: 3 copies of data, 2 different storage media, 1 off-site or cloud location
4. Use open, non-proprietary file formats when possible
5. Encrypt sensitive files and control access rigorously
6. Backup data regularly and create a data management plan
7. Monitor and maintain backups periodically
8. Establish a records management program following the lifecycle: creation, use, retention, disposition
9. Implement virus protection and data redundancy measures
10. Create descriptive file names and folder structures
11. Document software and hardware requirements for accessing files
12. Migrate data to new formats or storage media as technology evolves
13. Verify data integrity through checksums or other methods
14. Do you have a plan for transferring digital assets and accounts?
15. Develop a strategy for long-term preservation of email and other correspondence
16. Archive relevant web content and social media posts

Education

- Starting to make Systems video?
 - [@Videos](#)
- systemigrams (Boardman & Sauser) — Hugh D. Lester on LinkedIn
- **Systems Thinking has some great concepts and I've endeavoured, over the years, to integrate this thinking into my work on organisational (mainly process) improvement. I have found this difficult as there does not seem to be a methodology and toolset for any practical application. I've used Inisght Maker (free online stock and flow and agent-based modelling) to capture causal loop models, but I feel that Systems Thinking needs to have a Lean six sigma style methodology and Minitab style tool. I appreciate the difference between deterministic and probabilistic modelling and I know ST and LSS are quite different but, at the moment ST feels a bit like a 'smoke and mirrors' conjuring trick where practitioners can twist and turn anyway they like to claim they are wise after the event. Some standard approach, modelling standard and useful toolset needs to emerge to make it relevant. Maybe such things exist and I am not aware of them - please let me know if this is the case.**
- .
 - We can not really use analysis because if we break up a system with out giving up front priority to interrelationships when we later go to add in the relationships the result is going to be a complex mess
 - We can not use synthesis by itself because in order to "lump" the parts together we need to first have a break up into parts.
 - So how do we hands-on, specifically, concretely DO a logical, natural break up of the system?

Live Education meetings

Video playlists and Meetings.

 [Live Education meetings](#)

https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL36GDzgkIWrmJvnc_xwIZiJFcgK0FQbx7

 [Live Knowledge Engineering Meetings](#)

https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL36GDzgkIWrlMofRzb0h2qqwi_pjabb8t

2022

#1 - 9/15/2022

Meeting transcript & recording

- https://youtu.be/_CBArjXDuJw

Notes

- What is the role of ISSS?
- Working in health — complex system where an analytical rather than systemic approach, public health intelligence. How to build capacity around Systems Thinking?
 - Academic and Industry Systems — Analysts in this space (here Health), so Continuing Personal/Professional Development can be hard to fit it in, bandwidth wise.
 - Need to work on their problems via Facilitation — People need to see their interest and needs met, connecting Pragmatic and Epistemic value. Could we have playbooks here?
 - Russel Ackoff — Best way to learn is to teach (also helps with inclusion and scaling Systems)
- There is a knowledge management working group at INCOSE that I have a good relationship with (@Gary Smith)
- **Domains**
 - Watershed management
 - Health systems
 - Systems Engineering
 - Oceans Literacy
- ISSS with a legacy and potential to make a contribution
 - We are organization in the hundreds, of volunteers. What can we actually do with the resources that we have?
- @George Mobus — Expertise in curriculum development and pedagogy. Many initiatives could be a firm footing, with what they are going to use as the basis of teaching.
 - What materials can be provided to teachers in different situations?
 - Alignment with teacher training course?
- @Gary Smith — What is (and is not) Systems Science? What is it for? How do we integrate and communicate all that we have?
 - With INCOSE (main partners in SEBoK) — [Systems Engineering Foundations \(Wiki-based\)](#) — using this as an integration point for diverse knowledge, short articles that lead out. This is used by Educators. Could be potential for engagement there.
 - Wanting diverse systems organizations to be connecting — Operations research, Systems Dynamics, many other organizations — Then Systems Change, Systems Transformations, Systems Innovation, Complexity (Santa Fe, Complexity Weekend, New England CSI, ...)
 - Can leverage the relationships and situation of ISSS
- 🌐 ISSS is largely a USA membership. [US Next Generation Science Standards](#) — Science and Engineering, Disciplinary Core Ideas, interwoven with project-based @Projects learning — Cross-cutting concepts. — Aligning with this process and content makes sense within the USA context.
 - The project-based learning focus, highlighted and enacted by multiple people here today.
 - Quickly be able to access the most appropriate Systems Ideas, Materials, Methods, Trainings, etc.
- **AUDIENCES**

-

Agenda

- Welcome & Introductions (anything people want before we begin recording and transcription)
- Daniel — Status of Education efforts at 🌐 ISSS as of Late 2022
 - 🌐 ISSS Bylaws & Mission
 - Bylaws: 4.8.5 Educational Programs and Materials Committee.
 - [SIG: Designing Educational Systems](#)
 - Many diverse works and smaller initiatives by ISSS members and network
 - Ranging from e.g.
 - [Knowledge Engineering at ISSS](#) (active since September 2022)
 - How to curate and make decades of ISSS materials available on the 🌐 [Website](#)
 - Mind Map — conference, courses, mini symposia, events, SIG, other Publications, etc...
 - This 📖 [Education](#) initiative — WHY and WHAT?
 - WHY & ? [Questions](#)
 - Process and structure — 🏢 [Education People](#) and 📚 [Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions](#)
- Next steps & different modules/contributions for Education
 - Synchronous & Asynchronous participation modes
 - Which areas are important to pursue and why/how?
 - ...
 -

To-Do

-

#2 - 9/28/2022

Meeting transcript & recording

<https://youtu.be/7K4bwFdqZcA>

Notes

- @Peter D Tuddenham @George Mobus @Janos Korn @Daniel Ari Friedman —
-

Agenda

- Welcome & Introductions (anything people want before we begin recording and transcription)
- Live meeting 🗳️ [Live Education meetings](#)
 - Starting October 14th, also biweekly at 17 UTC
- @Len Troncale videos
 - Updates to Len.
 - @Peter D Tuddenham worked with Len previously when President, Len provided Keynotes/Lectures. Also yesterday had conversation with Peter — Systems Engineers Course. He wants to record this course, as he would have given it, in relation with the College of Exploration.
 - Number of Len Troncale, Systems Process Theory on Vimeo/YouTube.
- Relationship with 🗳️ [Crossover for EDU from KE](#) —
 - ISSS and Systems more generally — lots of awesome resources that are not always accessible, indexable, useful, and [Website](#) accessible.
 - James Greer Miller — Lecture series on Living Systems Theory, educational setting.
- Schema and Organization
 - Chapter 4 — George Mobus book
 - <https://www.ontologyportal.org/>
- 🗳️ Education
 - WHY & ? [Questions](#)
 - 🗳️ [Education People](#) and 🗳️ [Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions](#)
 - General points from @Janos Korn —
 - Who do we want to teach?
 - What to teach? What materials, methods, models?
 - What is the result?
 - ISSS issue — There is no symbolic structure that is capable of being taught — All the diagrams are nice, but there is no symbolic structure, as in some Sciences. This is what we are looking for. Well-established how to develop a symbolic structure for Systems Science.
 - Thinks — Systems teaching should be developed (by whom?) to be taught to all ages. Starting with young, like Math.

- @George Mobus — We will have to be training teachers, in systems. So a program for Schools of Education could be an important starting point. In the process of doing this, can experiment with what is age-appropriate.
- Shae has worked on this.
- Distinction between **Systems Science**, and **Systems Practice**.
- In **Systems Practice**, people are using Systems Thinking, and doing e.g. Consulting.
- In Systems Science, that is the work of e.g. Janos, George.
 - Systems + _____ (Thinking, Practice, Theory, etc....)
- Engineering as an Example — most of the Engineering domains are related to each other — All Engineers take some common science classes like physics.
- George Mobus, Jamie Rose, etc — Formal, internally consistent — If someone wants to be “Systems Management Consultant”, they better be grounded in Systems Theory.
 - Theoretical Physics (Synergetics)
 - Applied Physics
 - Engineering domains (Tensegrity)
- Science demands a theoretical approach that must fulfill several features like Explain, Predict, Design, Influence/Control, etc.
- We need the right kind of Symbolic structure — Only two options: Mathematics, Language. Math has now been taken over by conventional sciences, too restrictive. Whereas Natural Language is not rigorous enough, it can be done this way with Discourse Analysis.
 - Linguistic modeling + Systems principles
 - Conventional disciplines like Physics/Chemistry, primary objective is to create models that will help understand the world around us. They have taken hundreds of years to develop.
 - Whereas Modern Disciplines, like Operations, Systems, Control systems, — they are not trying to understand the world, they are focused on Problem Solving. Some of them are also rigorous, like Control.
 - More than one way to impart the Systems Knowledge — Of course there are hundreds of ways and means. However we are communicating here in a special way, trying to create a systems science.
 - 4 conditions that must be satisfied by a Symbolic structure.
 - Is Systems Science a Science of problem solving?
 - Equilibrium? Instances and generality.

George's book

📎 978-3-030-93482-8.pdf

@Janos Korn paper

📎 PAPER 1 ISSS NEW JUN 2022.pdf

- Next steps & different modules/contributions for Education
 - Synchronous & Asynchronous participation modes
 - Which areas are important to pursue and why/how?
 - ...
 -

To-Do

-

#3 - 10/13/2022

Meeting transcript & recording

- YouTube link here

Notes

-
-

Agenda

- Welcome & Introductions (anything people want before we begin recording and transcription)
- 🌐 Live Education meetings
 - Identity & Meaning-making
 - Attribution, Emergent teams
 - (Some) Co-operatives, Credit unions, Economics, Community exchange, De-risking.
 - Post-capitalism / Knowledge economics
- @Len Troncale videos — have watched:
 - Information from @Peter D Tuddenham @Lynn Rasmussen
 - — Natures enduring patterns. @Peter D Tuddenham annual conference, presentations aside from Saturday sessions. Gave graduate course for systems engineers, at university. All videos were records (on a hard drive). Offering the course online? & pamphlets. 2018 — help us with field guide for isomorphies. Related to Lynn work, literacy. Many powerpoints. Previous co-teaching with Lynn, early 2000's on phone. Many efforts to support his work. Many videos already on ISSS 🌐 Website. What's missing? Heart of his thinking and work. Editing & Linearity. Domains... Fundamentals of Systems (key terms, processes, ideas, relationships, etc)
 - 📚 Systems Tools, Courses, Resources, Organizations — start with e.g. a topic, around a topic/term, connecting to particulars in people's work.
 - @Roelien Goede , 🌐 Website efforts, 📂 Crossover for EDU from KE , Education
 - Created a funded ecosystems for systems information.
 - 7 big ideas, 44 concepts of Systems Literacy draft, and funded.
 - Literacy, multiscale resilience, ISSS.
 - What types of conversations can ISSS engage in? Some 📄 Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions with patterns for engagement.
- <https://www.iss.org/mini-symposiums-2022-2023-recordings/> October 12, 2022 have watched:
- Review @George Mobus and @Janos Korn contributions to Systems Science, attachments from previous 📄 #2 - 9/28/2022 .
- Relationship with 📂 Crossover for EDU from KE —
 - Schema and Organization
- 📄 Education
 - WHY & ? Questions, of what?

- Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions
- Next steps & different modules/contributions for Education
 - Summarization for short video update (e.g. as per recent [ISSS Knowledge Engineering update](#))
 - Synchronous & Asynchronous participation modes
 - Which areas are important to pursue and why/how?
 - ...
 - Bottom line: There are tasks to be done. The tasks are simple.
 - We can have reading lists and feedbacks. Discussion & annotations, with the Wiki.
- Next meetings
 - [#4 - 10/27-28/2022](#) — 27th at 18 UTC, and 28th at 17 UTC.

To-Do

Ongoing To-Do

Name	Person	Next steps	Notes
Adding contacts for			
Writing			
FedWiki — how does it fit in with			
For ISSS mini-symposium or any other ISSS effort, determine what tasks we can do in Education group	@Daniel F	Watch videos	
Knowledge and Materials Transfer for			

Assess current ISSS knowledge resources in light of educational paths (further work in Crossover for EDU from KE)	@Daniel F @Rob Young @Peter D Tuddenham	Review map, add materials.	
Send and respond to initial round of University and Educational contacts			
Pub talking points (everyday Systems memes and themes)			
Prepare summary for EDUCATION-23 to be communicated as ask and video update January 2023 communication	@Daniel F	Write communication Prepare and record video	
Exploring Standards in Systems Education			
Curriculum for Systems literacy			
Transformative Education letter from @R. Don Peel <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Daniel contact the DES SIG chairs with Don's request and letter. 	@Don Peel		
Draft of the Survey Questions Questions.	@Daniel F		
Post ISSS blog	@Daniel F		
From Crossover for EDU from KE — How to utilize the Interface (in development) for Education and engagement?			
Building the form and interactive interface	@Daniel F		
Staying updated with the Systems Census			
Make Coda preparation and education materials			

10/21/2022 discussion

- Daniel, Kerry, Marc
- How to go about sensemaking and prioritizing different 🗨️ [Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions](#)
- Based upon what we are trying to achieve with 📄 [Education](#) at 🌐 [ISSS](#) ?
 - But what is this? What does this look like for success?
- Job of creating something.....what tools to use? How to engage in feedback and inclusive participation?
 - Hand people the 1st, 2nd, 3rd step — etc. — How to hand people tasks? Brilliance and challenges.
 - People with things to offer however there are challenges to coordinate.
 - Figuring out how to interact with all relevant/subsets.
 - Attractors, Boundaries, Pruning — Snowden.
 - Give attractors that bring people to something.
 - VP Education holds the seat and is responsible for how things develop.
- Collaboration attractors
 - FedWiki
 - <https://github.com/fedwiki>
 - <http://fed.wiki.org/view/federated-wiki>
 - <https://relocalizecreativity.net/view/welcome-visitors>
 - Pattern languages (paths, recipes)
 - Relationships with Neo4j.
 - Synchronizable, among and within, Fedwiki
 - Using a query language inside the Fedwiki
- Target audience and purpose for 🌐 [ISSS](#) wiki?
 - General agreed-upon resource?
 - Creativity and exploration beyond the consensus statement?
 - No place for a consensus wiki? Because there is already a Wikipedia and we could make these resources there.
 - Whereas the Federated Wiki has better modalities and isn't "reinventing the wheel" here.
 - Teaching ISSS people how to edit Wikipedia pages — this is a skill and art.

FedWiki notes

- As it moves further from the initial programmers, things get easier.
- It is a platform — it is not an application. You can do anything that is possible in Javascript.
- People are expected an “app” — however it has the flexibility as a platform to provide functionality.
- Expectation — whatever is done today, is active.

#4 - 10/27-28/2022

Pre-meeting video

https://youtu.be/V4Mk-MCD_-s

- This video is to catch people up on ISSS in mid-October 2022, and provide clear synchronous and asynchronous affordances for contributing.
- It will cover the agenda for #4 - 10/27-28/2022 Oct 27 at 18 UTC, and 28 at 17 UTC (Zoom link [here](#))
 - If you can join either of these times, please feel free to do so (reply if you are not already added to calendar events).
 - If you have any relevant inputs, post here in the Coda or reply via email.
 - If you no longer want to be updated about Education, reply & I will remove you.
- The next recorded Education update will probably be around the end of 2022.
 - The next ~6 weeks before the holidays are a great window for anyone to get involved if they want to help to structure 2023 plans for ISSS and/or Beyond.

Meeting recording & transcript

- https://youtu.be/qlQzmNT_bMc

Notes

-
- Add any notes here.....
-
- <https://zenodo.org/record/7259007> Transcript of: Mark Solms, "Consciousness as Precision Optimization: Some Physiological and Philosophical Considerations", ActInf GuestStream #016
- Meetings can be transcribed. Speakers are published as co-authors. Contributors can be also named (e.g. people involved in editing, translating, developing the technology).
- <https://zenodo.org/> — Getting free DOIs.
 - SRBS not open.
- ISSS resources and recordings are available. Some materials are Member-only, other resources are open/public.
- Advancing the state of systems science — e.g. [@George Mobus](#) books.
- Geophysical presentation by [@Peter D Tuddenham](#), Open Science, different groups with criteria.
- Good to have discussion about Open Science at the level of Board of Directors meeting.
 - <https://www.cos.io/>
 - Board members can talk at those meetings. Non-directors can request floor Privledge.
- New function-based Role — Video management.
 - [@Peter D Tuddenham](#) can do walkthrough, Daniel will document.
 - Website to support members → Now it is “the” website.
 - College of Exploration gets a small stipend.

- The video piece is one of the main features of the website.
- It is taking a lot of time with Video management — Synchronous (Zoom) and Asynchronous (Vimeo).
- How to manage the Video situation at ISSS, in terms of log in.
- Education — Learning from other people.
- Webinar — George.
 - 12-13 weekly session. Transfer the content of the books, into this format.
 - Rights to the Content → Semester-long course based upon the book.
- General points on Systems education
 - Learning through showing, applications illustrated —
 - Intuitive ability/understanding for systems science.
- Research/Science, and Practical/Bridging areas
- Professional education and upskilling — Systems methods, **helping educate the systems nature of what people do already, then augmenting this.**
 - Actuarial — Mathematics, Business, Legal, Accounting. All around, trying to solve immediate problems that involve financial risks. Play roles in e.g. insurance premiums, strategies.
 - BOLTS — Business Operational Legal Technical Social
 - Geoscience — People also implicitly working with systems / in systems. However also there resistance to systems.
- Intergenerational aspects
 - Conversations with elders and youths, bidirectional learning.
 - Children in school — contact patterns change, community-building is enabled within the space of projects.
- Curious Forecasters.
 - Experts are / can be entrenched, the ability to change mind with relevant changing information.
 - Frozen ideas and structures around Education.
 - Limits and Abilities of AI — systems thinking
- Group research — working together to advance knowledge.
 - Actively involved in bringing education into various areas.
- Systems Thinking general notes:
 - Understand that multiple frames/perspectives are required, pluralism, SystemS
 - Innovate and hone heuristics
 - In the applied setting (including Organizational design/operation), understand what is already happening, and augmented.
 - Thinking patterns / Meta-cognition
 - Balancing people and teams, of Technical and Non-Technical (and every other perspective difference).
 - Different views & perspectives.
 - Other systems groupings/analyses could always be important. Always experimenting, having people with different views — this is important.
- Systems Pathology
 - Fundamental structures, relationships within systems — defining the features/structure of the system, science-based, Structural/Functional/Effective connectivity.
 - Could start with educating on general systems understanding. When you have the insight, you will want more, and you will want that from more advanced heuristics/statistics/models/frameworks.

- Templates, patterns, priors, feedback between the science side and the practice.
- Members and participation in groups
 - Diverging, and Converging aspects.
 - Even few attractors/milestones can be positive for structuring the long-term development.
- DeSchool Coda <https://kernel.community/>
- Conformity/Diversity in education.
-

Agenda

1. Welcome & Introductions (anything to add before we begin recording)
2. Review of [📖 To-Do for #4](#) (anything to add, update, remove)
3. [📖 Education](#) at [🌐 ISSS](#)
 - a. General discussion
4. Active [📖 Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions](#)
 - a. [📖 Crossover for EDU from KE](#)
 - b. [📖 Systems Science](#)
5. Review affordances for people to contribute.
 - a. Get familiar with the Coda and add resources/details anywhere (request edit access if needed)
 - b. Explore and reflect on the [? Questions](#)
 - c. Review the [📖 Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions](#) and see if you want to join any ongoing projects, or activate some other area.
 - d. ????? — If you have some other interest or excitement about Education at the end of 2022 or ideas for 2023, then please get in contact and let's work to structure the collaboration.

To-Do

To-Do for #4

Name	Person	Notes	Next steps
Adding contacts for 📖 Systems Organizations, Universities, Programs	@George Mobus @Peter D Tuddenham @Daniel F @Shingai Thornton	📖	@Shingai Thornton , compiling
Writing 📖 Survey Outreach Copy for Universities, Institutes, and other organizations	@Daniel F	📖	
FedWiki — how does it fit in with 📖 Education ?	Kerry, @Marc Pierson , @Peter D Tuddenham	📖	
For ISSS mini-symposium or any other ISSS effort, determine what tasks we can do in Education group	@Daniel F	📖	Watch videos

Knowledge and Materials Transfer for George Mobus , Educational Work	@George Mobus @Shingai Thornton @Karl Hebenstreit — once content is solid, make interactive		@Shingai Thornton working some more on the material (3 presentations shown today 1/19/23). Then meeting with @George Mobus @Daniel F in coming weeks. With final content version of slides, @Karl Hebenstreit and slides.
Assess current ISSS knowledge resources in light of educational paths (further work in Crossover for EDU from KE)	@Daniel F @Rob Young @Peter D Tuddenham		Review map, add materials.
Send and respond to initial round of University and Educational contacts			
Pub talking points (everyday Systems memes and themes)			
Prepare summary for EDUCATION-23 to be communicated as ask and video update 📢 January 2023 communication	@Daniel F		Write communication Prepare and record video
Exploring 🌟 Standards in Systems Education			
Curriculum for Systems literacy			
Transformative Education letter from @R. Don Peel <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Daniel contact the DES SIG chairs with Don's request and letter. 	@Don Peel		
Draft of the 📄 Survey Questions Questions.	@Daniel F		
Post ISSS blog	@Daniel F		
From Crossover for EDU from KE — How to utilize the Interface (in development) for Education and engagement?			
Building the form and interactive interface	@Daniel F		
Staying updated with the Systems Census			
Make Coda preparation and education materials			

#5 - 11/10/2022

Pre-meeting video

- The next recorded Education update will probably be around the end of 2022.
 - The next ~6 weeks before the holidays are a great window for anyone to get involved if they want to help to structure 2023 plans for 📖 Education at 🌐 ISSS and/or Beyond.

Meeting recording & transcript

- https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ytj5zayp_Mg&list=PL36GDzgLWrmJvnc_xwIZiJFcgK0FQbx7&index=5

Notes

- @Rob Young and @Karl Hebenstreit joining for first time. Also @Kerry Turner @Marc Pierson @Peter D Tuddenham @George Mobus @Daniel F .
- Marc and Kerry — Formal models of Information management, based on Patterns languages, within/upon FedWiki.
- Next generation science standards — Crosscutting concepts.
- @Peter D Tuddenham — Science and Systems Literacy.
- Engaging on the periphery.
- In 🗨️ Crossover for EDU from KE — What's the scope, etc. The Brain, is one of the ways that such networks can be coordinated. — Could be a demonstration of the Brain.
- Potentially generative relationships between curated/centralized information environments, and federated information protocols.
- I would like for us to indicate who any piece of knowledge or particular learning structure is intended for. Leaving that out is deeply confusing.
- *The Accidental Taxonomist* is the most comprehensive guide available to the art and science of building information taxonomies <https://www.goodreads.com/book/show/8468792-the-accidental-taxonomist>
- Systems Engineering: <https://www.incose.org/>
-

Agenda

1. Welcome & Introductions (anything to add before we begin recording)
2. Review of 📖 To-Do for #5 (anything to add, update, remove)
3. 📖 Education at 🌐 ISSS
 - a. General discussion
4. Active 🗨️ Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions
 - a. 🗨️ Crossover for EDU from KE
 - b. 🗨️ Systems Science
 - i. @Len Troncale — 🗨️
 - ii. 🗨️ George Mobus
 - iii. 🗨️ Jessie Henshaw

- iv. [@Shingai Thornton](#) new article on Gitcoin
 - v. [@Gary Smith](#)
 - vi. [@Janos Korn](#)
5. Review affordances for people to contribute.
- a. Get familiar with the Coda and add resources/details anywhere (request edit access if needed)
 - b. Explore and reflect on the [? Questions](#)
 - c. Review the [👉 Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions](#) and see if you want to join any ongoing projects, or activate some other area.
 - d. ????? — If you have some other interest or excitement about Education at the end of 2022 or ideas for 2023, then please get in contact and let's work to structure the collaboration.

To-Do

To-Do for #5

Discussed?	Name	Person	Notes	Next steps
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Adding contacts for 📁 Systems Organizations, Universities, Programs	@George Mobus @Peter D Tuddenham @Daniel F @Shingai Thornton		@Shingai Thornton , compili
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Writing 📄 Survey Outreach Copy for Universities, Institutes, and other organizations	@Daniel F		
<input type="checkbox"/>	FedWiki — how does it fit in with 📄 Education?	Kerry, @Marc Pierson , @Peter D Tuddenham		
<input type="checkbox"/>	For ISSS mini-symposium or any other ISSS effort, determine what tasks we can do in Education group	@Daniel F		Watch videos
<input type="checkbox"/>	Knowledge and Materials Transfer for 👤 George Mobus , Educational Work	@George Mobus @Shingai Thornton @Karl Hebenstreit — once content is solid, make interactive		@Shingai Thornton working more on the material (3 presentations shown today Then meeting with @Georg @Daniel F in coming weeks. With final content version of @Karl Hebenstreit and slide
<input type="checkbox"/>	Assess current ISSS knowledge resources in light of educational paths (further work in 👉 Crossover for EDU from KE)	@Daniel F @Rob Young @Peter D Tuddenham		Review map, add materials.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Send and respond to initial round of University and Educational contacts			
<input type="checkbox"/>	Pub talking points (everyday Systems memes and themes)			
<input type="checkbox"/>	Prepare summary for EDUCATION-23 to be communicated as ask and video update 👉 January 2023 communication	@Daniel F		Write communication Prepare and record video
<input type="checkbox"/>	Exploring 👉 Standards in Systems Education			
<input type="checkbox"/>	📄 Curriculum for Systems literacy			

<input type="checkbox"/>	<p>🗨️ Transformative Education letter from @R. Don Peel</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Daniel contact the DES SIG chairs with Don's request and letter. 	@Don Peel	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Draft of the 📄 Survey Questions Questions.	@Daniel F	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Post ISSS blog	@Daniel F	
<input type="checkbox"/>	From 📄 Crossover for EDU from KE — How to utilize the Interface (in development) for Education and engagement?		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Building the form and interactive interface	@Daniel F	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Staying updated with the 📄 Systems Census		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Make Coda preparation and education materials		

#6 - 12/8/2022

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/nS-NNLv8Q74>

Notes

- @Peter D Tuddenham and conversations Lazlo's — Quantum Leadership — Creation of a course?
 - Educating the teachers?
 - Challenge — Scale. Going beyond the ~20 person size.
 - When talking about scale — Ecologists not always taking in the Human (e.g. not including Person in Picture [PIP]). This requires an experience (sensing, feeling), not only thinking.
- Systems Literacy — cross cutting concepts, next generation science standards — target for teachers.
- International Standards Organizations (ISO) — — 52788? e.g. [9001 Quality Standards](#). NIST, General Services Administration.
 - @Peter D Tuddenham talking with people in the Maritime, and other standards, ad hoc group with Standards
- Meeting with @Don Peel 12-9-2022
 - New allowances in Canada, providing flexibility in teach methods.
 - Michael Fullan “Deep Learning Philosophy”, Moonshot incubator. Aligned with e.g. Montessori, Waldorf — finding out what the child's passion, interest, skills are. Taking ownership of curriculum democratically. Engaging in meaningful learning: Local Issues, being part of community-building, project-based learning.
 - Sir Ken Robinson
 - Can ISSS take some initiative, to bring the message to Teachers, and how to change the mainstream teaching model (meaning radical change in learning).
 - [Open Letter to ISSS members and beyond](#)
- .
- .
- .

For 2023

1. Crossover for EDU from KE (enabling system for Education)
 - i. Index for events (like [All Livestream](#)), Archiving and publishing, indexing, digitization.
 - ii. Secondary MediaWiki
2. Education
 - a. ISSS
 - i. ISSS Services — How can Education help SIG and ISSS members
 - b. External / Collaborative
 - i. Standards setting?
 - ii. Curriculum for Systems literacy — On the order of 12 credit hours.

iii. Partnerships with 🗺️ Systems Organizations, Universities, Programs? PMP?

Agenda

1. Welcome & Introductions (anything to add before we begin recording)
2. Review of 📅 To-Do for #6 (anything to add, update, remove)
3. 🏠 Education at 🌐 ISSS
 - a. General discussion
 - b. 🌐 Website
 - i. @Peter D Tuddenham started two education pages on ISSS.
 - ii. <https://www.isss.org/education/>
 - iii. <https://www.isss.org/education-members/>
 - iv. Please put links to the CODA page on the members page. and a record of you video updates as well.
4. Active 🗺️ Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions
 - a. 🗺️ Crossover for EDU from KE
 - b. 🗺️ Systems Science
 - i. 🗺️ Len Troncale — 🗺️ Len videos and “Education in the Systems Sciences”
 - ii. 🗺️ George Mobus
 - iii. 🗺️ Jessie Henshaw
 - iv. 🗺️ Gary Smith
 - v. @Janos Korn
 - vi. @Shingai Thornton new article on Gitcoin
5. Review affordances for people to contribute.
 - a. Get familiar with the Coda and add resources/details anywhere (request edit access if needed)
 - b. Explore and reflect on the ? Questions
 - c. Review the 🗺️ Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions and see if you want to join any ongoing projects, or activate some other area.
 - d. ????? — If you have some other interest or excitement about Education at the end of 2022 or ideas for 2023, then please get in contact and let's work to structure the collaboration.

To-Do

To-Do for #6

Discussed?	Name	Person	Notes	Next steps
✓	Adding contacts for 🗺️ Systems Organizations, Universities, Programs	@George Mobus @Peter D Tuddenham @Daniel F @Shingai Thornton	☰	@Shingai Thornton, compili
✓	Writing 🗺️ Survey Outreach Copy for Universities, Institutes, and other organizations	@Daniel F	☰	

<input type="checkbox"/>	FedWiki — how does it fit in with 📖 Education?	Kerry, @Marc Pierson , @Peter D Tuddenham	☰	
<input type="checkbox"/>	For ISSS mini-symposium or any other ISSS effort, determine what tasks we can do in Education group	@Daniel F	☰	Watch videos
<input type="checkbox"/>	Knowledge and Materials Transfer for 🛡️ George Mobus, Educational Work	@George Mobus @Shingai Thornton @Karl Hebenstreit — once content is solid, make interactive	☰	@Shingai Thornton working more on the material (3 presentations shown today Then meeting with @George @Daniel F in coming weeks. With final content version of @Karl Hebenstreit and slide
<input type="checkbox"/>	Assess current ISSS knowledge resources in light of educational paths (further work in 🏠 Crossover for EDU from KE)	@Daniel F@Rob Young @Peter D Tuddenham	☰	Review map, add materials.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Send and respond to initial round of University and Educational contacts		☰	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Pub talking points (everyday Systems memes and themes)		☰	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Prepare summary for EDUCATION-23 to be communicated as ask and video update 🗨️ January 2023 communication	@Daniel F	☰	Write communication Prepare and record video
<input type="checkbox"/>	Exploring 🧡 Standards in Systems Education		☰	
<input type="checkbox"/>	📖 Curriculum for Systems literacy		☰	
<input type="checkbox"/>	📄 Transformative Education letter from @R. Don Peel <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Daniel contact the DES SIG chairs with Don's request and letter. 	@Don Peel	☰	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Draft of the 🗨️ Survey Questions Questions.	@Daniel F	☰	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Post ISSS blog	@Daniel F	☰	
<input type="checkbox"/>	From 🏠 Crossover for EDU from KE — How to utilize the Interface (in development) for Education and engagement?		☰	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Building the form and interactive interface	@Daniel F	☰	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Staying updated with the 📊 Systems Census		☰	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Make Coda preparation and education materials		☰	

2023

#7 ~ 1/5/2023

ISSS Education meeting #7 on January 5th, 2023.

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/pPw8graPMao>

Notes

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Agenda

1. Welcome & Introductions (anything to add before we begin recording)
2. For 2023 — Overview and Agenda setting.
 - a. Crossover for EDU from KE (enabling system for Education)
3. 2023 agenda for Education
 - a. Internal - ISSS
 1. Education help SIG and ISSS members?
 - b. External / Collaborative
 - i. Systems Organizations, Universities, Programs, Partnerships, Survey
 - ii. Standards — Standards setting — **waiting for response to survey.**
 - iii. Curriculum for Systems literacy — On the order of 12 credit hours — **waiting for response to survey.**
 1. For next week, Peter will be bringing up some past curricula.
4. Review and Update of Education To-Do for #7 (anything to add, update, remove)
 - a. 1985 Systems Education — Addressed.
 - b. @Prepare summary for EDUCATION-23 to be communicated as ask and video update /_suSE3
 - c. Open Letter to ISSS members and beyond
 - i. Is it possible to have the Open letter sent out to all ISSS members as a news bulletin for consideration and funnel all comments to the SIG on Designing Educational Systems as an agenda item for the AGM?
 - ii. ISSS likely has the ability to influence parents and educational institutions through school administrators, curriculum specialists, school councils, teachers associations, etc. The letter can act as a trigger to forge a path for the SIG and ISSS on education reform.
5. General overviews of ISSS
 - a. Participating in ISSS Education
 - b. Website
6. Active Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions
 - a. Crossover for EDU from KE

b. 🇺🇸 Systems Science

- i. 🗣️ Len Troncale — 📺 Len videos and “Education in the Systems Sciences”
- ii. 🇩🇪 George Mobus
- iii. 🇺🇸 Jessie Henshaw
- iv. 🇺🇸 Gary Smith
- v. @Janos Korn

Education To-Do for #7

Area		Discussed?	Task Status	Name	Pe
▼ 🇺🇸 ISSS Education Services	3	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	For ISSS mini-symposium or any other ISSS effort, determine what tasks we can do in Education group	@l
		<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	Pub talking points (everyday Systems memes and themes)	
		<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	From 🇺🇸 Crossover for EDU from KE — How to utilize the Interface (in development) for Education and engagement?	
▼ 🇺🇸 Standards	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	Exploring 🇺🇸 Standards in Systems Education	
▼ 🇺🇸 Systems Science	2	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	🇺🇸 Curriculum for Systems literacy	
		<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Knowledge and Materials Transfer for 🇩🇪 George Mobus , Educational Work	@l @l co int
▼ 🇺🇸 Systems Census	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Staying updated with the 🇺🇸 Systems Census	
▼ 🇺🇸 Coda Education	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Make Coda preparation and education materials	

To-Do

- Pub talking points (everyday Systems memes and themes)
- Sustainable/Regenerative Business model for ISSS members and public

#8 ~ 1/19/2023

ISSS Education meeting #8 on January 19th, 2023.

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/kYEr-Z6LLL4>

Notes

- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/David_Easton
- Classical Educational Problem/Tradeoff — Impact and Engagement
 - Motivational, in time.
 - Broader invitation. Reminders. — One dimension to automate some email reminders (e.g. few hours before). Might increase influx of new
 - Video
 - Live
 - Recorded
 - Live across platforms
 - Every X weeks, automated email to ISSS — link to watch/comment with lower
- Educational materials
 - People wanting to share more about their ideas, platform for talking about Educational content.
 - @Shingai Thornton working on George Mobus research
 - More compelling content on systems education.
 - What sort of traction do other SIG and working groups have?
 - SIG and Groups with high levels of participation?
 - Conference working group is active.
 - Saturday sessions
 - Newsletter
 - SIG
 - Holism SIG — meeting every 2 weeks
 - Systems Innovation and Engagement SIG — .
 - Crossover for EDU from KE can be considered active.
 - .
 - .
-

Agenda

1. Welcome & Introductions (anything to add before we begin recording?)

2. Short video
3. Overview of Education at ISSS
 - a. Participating in ISSS Education
 - b. Crossover for EDU from KE (enabling system for Education)
4. 2023 agenda for Education
 - a. Internal - ISSS
 - i. ISSS Education Services — How can Education help SIG and ISSS members?
 - b. External / Collaborative
 - i. Systems Organizations, Universities, Programs, Partnerships, Survey
 - ii. Standards — Standards setting — **pending response to survey.**
 - iii. Curriculum for Systems literacy — On the order of 12 credit hours — **pending response to survey.**
5. Review and Update Education To-Do for #8 (anything to add, update, remove)
6. Active Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions
 - a. Crossover for EDU from KE
 - b. Systems Science
 - i. Len Troncale, George Mobus, Jessie Henshaw, Gary Smith, ...

Education To-Do for #8

Area	Discussed?	Task Status	Name	Pe
ISSS Education Services 3	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	For ISSS mini-symposium or any other ISSS effort, determine what tasks we can do in Education group	@l
	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	Pub talking points (everyday Systems memes and themes)	
	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	From Crossover for EDU from KE — How to utilize the Interface (in development) for Education and engagement?	
Standards 1				
Systems Science 2				
Systems Census 1	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Staying updated with the Systems Census	
Coda Education 1	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Make Coda preparation and education materials	

To add

- Pub talking points (everyday Systems memes and themes)
- Sustainable/Regenerative Business model for ISSS members and public.
- .
- .

#9 ~ 2/2/2023

ISSS Education meeting #9 on Feb 2, 2023.

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/ZJVjaPkN8-U>

Notes

- Email of today.
 - Roelien, Please pass this on to our Education Chairperson
 - https://uia.org/sites/uia.org/files/journals/International_Associations_1970_1.pdf 1970
 - James Rose
- Integrations of Systems Science, with rigor, in different educational programs.
 - Falling between/among cracks/gaps of disciplines.
 - George — People from other fields, learning/applying Systems Science approach. These people have familiarity with some deeper history/understanding to different degrees. Feedback loops, emergent properties.
- Dis/Agreements on what the Systems Science field is
 - Focusing on subsets of cybernetics, complexity, etc.
 - Practitioners — use it as-is
- Action Research — hypothesis is formed, if I apply this method to this problem we will solve it — collect data and write it is, if it does not “solve” anything, it is still production of knowledge.
- It is all in George’s book — Also we want to know via the 🗑️ [Survey Questions](#) what activity/energy is out there, possible for teaching around 🛡️ [George Mobus](#) book.
- Systems Education, Education 📄 [Standards](#) .
 - Presentation from [Wayne Wakeland](#), Portland State, describing the Systems program, Challenges and Opportunities.
 - .
 - .
- .
- .
- Before the Berlin conference — <https://www.issss.org/blog/?view=blog&id=40>
- CRM, not down this route.

Agenda

1. Welcome & Introductions (anything to add before we begin recording?)
2. 📄 Education at 🌐 ISSS ([🔗 Participating in ISSS Education](#), 🗨️ [Crossover for EDU from KE](#))
3. Review and Update 📄 [Education To-Do for #9](#) (anything to add, update, remove)

Education To-Do for #9

Area		Discussed?	Task Status	Name	Pe
▼ 🏠 ISSS Education Services	3	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	For ISSS mini-symposium or any other ISSS effort, determine what tasks we can do in Education group	@l
		<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	Pub talking points (everyday Systems memes and themes)	
		<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	From 🏠 Crossover for EDU from KE — How to utilize the Interface (in development) for Education and engagement?	
▼ 📌 Standards	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	Exploring 📌 Standards in Systems Education	
▶ 📖 Systems Science	2				
▼ 📊 Systems Census	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Staying updated with the 📊 Systems Census	
▼ 📄 Coda Education	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Make Coda preparation and education materials	

To add

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#10 ~ 2/16/2023

ISSS Education meeting #10 on Feb 16, 2023.

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/g6rBv5NTVpM>

Notes

- Advances in Systems Science and Practice — Special issue submission.
 - George describing perspective/status from editors and reviewers perspective.
 - Advancement beyond the seminal ideas.... Latching on to core (seminal) ideas (some from ISSS elders), however little progress in deepening the fundamentals.
 - This is in the background of what we do in Education — within the ISSS and beyond.
 - What motivates and hinders diligence in Systems?
 - Availability (in people, and attention allocation) of transdisciplinary colleagues.
 - Looking at “Big Science” (e.g. Genome project, etc) — these projects and endeavors are transdisciplinary, polymath individuals. The founders of this discipline/non-discipline, looked at everything.....
 - On the practitioner side — finding Methodology that seems/actually works (best practices) → Tend to latch onto a methodology ([Golden Hammer](#))
 - Theme coming from Hull University — Theoretical, Methodological Pluralism:
 - <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/scientific-pluralism/>
 - <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Plurality>
 - <https://www.plurality.institute/>
- Possible Token Engineering collaborations and series.
- Coming back to Systemese — applications (see recording of today in the final minutes)

Agenda

1. Welcome & Introductions (anything to add before we begin recording?)
 - a. Begin recording
2. Any news, updates, or questions about ISSS (e.g. [Participating in ISSS Education](#))
 - a. Add Notes and links above.
3. Review and work on To-Do && To Discuss for #10 (add, update, remove)
 - a. Add Herospace

To-Do && To Discuss for #10

Area	Discussed?	Task Status	Name
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▼ ISSS Education Services			3
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		<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	For ISSS mini-symposium or any other ISSS effort, determine what tasks we can do in Education group
		<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	Pub talking points (everyday Systems memes and themes)
		<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	From Crossover for EDU from KE — How to utilize the Interface (in development) for Education and engagement?
▼ Standards	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	Exploring Standards in Systems Education
▼ Systems Science	2	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	Curriculum for Systems literacy
		<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Knowledge and Materials Transfer for George Mobus , Educational Work
▼ Systems Census	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Staying updated with the Systems Census
▼ Coda Education	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Make Coda preparation and education materials

To add

.

#11 ~ 3/2/2023

ISSS Education meeting #11 on March 2, 2023.

Meeting recording

- https://youtu.be/zG2lkX-U_Jk

Notes

- Seminal concepts of [Systems Science](#) —
 - Valuable ideas that scaffolded thinking in the following decades.
 - Using (subset of) the concepts as-is, not pursuing integration
 - Cybernetics is frame on Systems, however not different from Systems.
 - Stafford Beer, working on the integration of Cybernetics/Systems, though with prior works on Neuro.
- .
- .

Agenda

1. Welcome & Introductions (anything to add before we begin recording?)
 - a. Begin recording
2. Any news, updates, or questions about [Participating in ISSS Education](#))
 - a. Add Notes and links above.
3. Review and work on [To-Do && To Discuss for #11](#) (add, update, remove)

To-Do && To Discuss for #11

Area	Discussed?	Task Status	Name
<i>No results from filter</i>			

To add

-

#12 ~ 3/16/2023

ISSS Education meeting #12 on March 16, 2023.

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/GopFdq9AEYs>

Notes

- Seminal concepts of [Systems Science](#) —
 - Valuable ideas that scaffolded thinking in the following decades.
 - Using (subset of) the concepts as-is, not pursuing integration
 - Cybernetics is frame on Systems, however not different from Systems.
 - Stafford Beer, working on the integration of Cybernetics/Systems, though with prior works on Neuro.
- .
- From Alexander Lazlo: <https://www.transformationscommunity.org/systems-education-catalog>
- Parsing the materials into relevant materials
- How much to focus/develop the [Systems Census](#)
 - “[Systems Education](#)” has Systems Transformation angle, perhaps ended in 2021 (? , can contact the leads) — No
- (Some) Areas that can benefit from [Education](#) — within Systems Science.
- [Systems Science](#) from [@George Mobus](#)
 - Systems Change
 - Wanting/Having/Selling their perspective/approach to be grounded in [Systems Science](#)
 - Perspective of the [Systems Education Directory](#)
 - Systems Engineers
 - Rediscovering [Systems Science](#)
 - Members of INCOSE — not as engaged with Science, yes with applied understandings from George’s book/communications.
 - Systems Science beginnings has already taken place, Engineers can help AND don’t have to reinvent the Science.
 - ISSS with many practitioners..... George on the Science/Thinking ISSS swap.
 - Focusing on real achievable things to do
 - To pursue this holistically as education arm of the ISSS — How can we get sub-committees in [Education](#)
 - Young & Old (e.g. K-12 // Adult)
 - [George Mobus](#) and [@Shingai Thornton](#)
 - Lynn — Literacy with younger learners
 - Systems Practitioners
 - Consultants et al.
 - Systems Sensibility/Awareness/Literacy
 - Common/Commons perspective on [Systems Science](#) — sensitive to why/how actions have consequences and so forth.

- What is missing —
 - Material and pedagogy for bringing generalized [Systems Science](#) [Systems Tools, Courses, Resources, Organizations](#) for children —
 - Lynn's work
 - [Systems Science](#) at the upper/graduate education scale.
 - https://works.bepress.com/wayne_wakeland/
 - .
 -

Agenda

1. Welcome & Introductions (anything to add before we begin recording?)
 - a. Begin recording
2. Any news, updates, or questions about [Education](#) at [ISSS](#) (e.g. [Participating in ISSS Education](#))
 - a. Add Notes and links above.
3. Review and work on [To-Do && To Discuss for #12](#) (add, update, remove)

To-Do && To Discuss for #12

Area	Discussed?	Task Status	Name
<i>No results from filter</i>			

To add

-

#13 ~ 3/30/2023

ISSS Education meeting #13 on March 30, 2023.

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/6640lcH4I5w>

Notes

- Seminal concepts of [Systems Science](#) —
 - Valuable ideas that scaffolded thinking in the following decades.
 - Using (subset of) the concepts as-is, not pursuing integration
 - Cybernetics is frame on Systems, however not different from Systems.
 - Stafford Beer, working on the integration of Cybernetics/Systems, though with prior works on Neuro.
- Effort with some similarities to [Survey Questions](#) : <https://www.transformationscommunity.org/systems-education-catalog>
- (Some) Areas that can benefit from [Education](#) — within Systems Science.
-
- Material and pedagogy for bringing generalized [Systems Tools, Courses, Resources, Organizations](#) for children —
 - Lynn's work
 - [Systems Science](#) at the upper/graduate education scale.
- Jan Borda sharing Capra course information
 - 12 weeks, format details and supplemental readings <https://www.capracourse.net/> , variety of topics/areas. Referring back to multiscale systems, spokes relating back to the center metaphor, referring to the basis of cognition, social, ecological.
 - Lecture summaries are available. After the course ends, you are an Alumni, and lectures back and connections back with other graduates.
 - Fees in \$200-\$1000 range —
 - Systems View Lab. Geared more towards Organizations.
 - 3 Modules in the SVL — from the Capra course.
 - Leadership in Organizations (9), ST and state of the world (11), Systemic solutions (12).
 - Capra thinking on a macro level
 - Silo'd/Niched/Disciplinary work, in complement/contrast with Systems view.
 - How can ISSS collaborate, make informations available, with the [Education](#) group or otherwise.
 - Jan with contact for the Capra Course operator, previously spoken with them about organizations.
 - Might be helpful/interesting for some ISSS membership, for expanding their horizons beyond comfort zone.
 - Interest in presenting the Capra Course to ISSS
 - What can ISSS/Capra do in engagements?
 - Communications from ISSS — Blog post on front page, ...
 - ISSS → Course and Course → ISSS Members

- Organizing joint events
- Lot to learn in relationship with Shingai/George course development.
- Increased depth, rigor, [Systems Science](#)
- Also interesting to how course thing is put together — Courses are not often cheap.
- Role of ISSS and Education
 - Supporting groups who want to make new courses (directly & via connections)
 - Offering recommendations for other courses to take
 - → Developing courses & educational processes of Systems Education?
 - ISSS developments of education courses/experiences, leading up to conferences.
- ISSS resources — do we have analytics on how much different resources are used?
 - Measurements of how much attention/filtering to different educational aspects?
 - Perhaps google analytics installed, but not in direct use. Someone could investigate this more.
 - Possibly, Peter T with the Miller tapes & course developments around that.
 - Socialized learning & Individual learning (e.g. video watching & resources, time-bounded pieces)
- Shingai; Lynn has discussion in book on some of the specifics like history and differences among [Systems Science](#) areas
 -

Agenda

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 - a. Begin recording
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 - a. Add Notes and links above.
3. Review and work on [To-Do && To Discuss for #13](#) (add, update, remove)

To-Do && To Discuss for #13

Area	Discussed?	Task Status	Name
No results from filter			

To add

-

#14 ~ 4/13/2023

ISSS Education meeting #14 on April 13, 2023.

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/kUqaR83YJ5o>

Notes

- Review 📄 #13 ~ 3/30/2023
- Education public Interface (with 📄 Systems Census)
- Knowledge Engineering public Interface (with ISSS archival work).
- Upcoming “Language Models + ISSS” next week
-
- @Knowledge and Materials Transfer for /_sulo0, Educational Work —
 - Shingai presented on the overview for his efforts — Systems Explorers, Curriculum, Team, Funding, etc.
 - Beyond just having slides — What is the conveyance method?
 - [cadcad Education](#) — good online educational platform.
 - Educational videos — George interested to see some of the diagrams (circles and arrows) animated and enlivened.
 - e.g. Input flows, things moving through broader arrow.
 - Karl willing to improve some slides once ready.
 - George — see if Springer may be interested to support/partner with a course site or approach.
- TheBrain for ISSS
 - Systems-related organizations — to start thinking in terms of integrated whole (e.g. systems dynamics, cybernetics, networks, etc). Systems dynamics, network of processes (connecting those areas). This is what the actual brain does, associate concepts. Having a map to explore this would be useful.
- Janos — Significant problem with systems thinking. Current approaches are mostly speculative. More concrete methods have been in existence for decades. Innovative thinking is required. To introduce innovation, we have to admit/recognize, that the Systems approach is an empirical exercise (we can observe structural properties of entities). The empirical approach is required. Systems Theory that explores this, in 📄 [Janos Korn](#)'s work. Problem is: No one is interested in this approach, or subjected to peer review.
 - In context of Language Model — see the Linguistic Modeling approach in 📄 [Janos Korn](#) , and also the Ontological/Linguistic work of 📄 [George Mobus](#).
 - Can send Daniel the links.
 - Also note hearing — email is preferred.
-

Agenda

1. Welcome & Introductions (anything to add before we begin recording?)

- a. Begin recording
2. Any news, updates, or questions about [Education](#) at [ISSS](#) ([Participating in ISSS Education](#))
 - a. Add Notes and links above.
3. Review and work on [To-Do && To Discuss for #14](#) (add, update, remove)

To-Do && To Discuss for #14

Area		Discussed?	Task Status	Name
▼ ISSS Education Services	3	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	For ISSS mini-symposium or any other ISSS effort, determine what tasks we can do in Education group
		<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	Pub talking points (everyday Systems memes and themes)
		<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	From Crossover for EDU from KE — How to utilize the Interface (in development) for Education and engagement?
▼ Standards	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	Exploring Standards in Systems Education
▼ Systems Science	2	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	Curriculum for Systems literacy
		<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Knowledge and Materials Transfer for George Mobus , Educational Work
▼ Systems Census	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Staying updated with the Systems Census
▼ Coda Education	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Make Coda preparation and education materials

To add

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#15 ~ 4/27/2023

ISSS Education meeting #15 on April 27, 2023.

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/itCEzgbnMHI>

Notes

- Review 📅 #13 ~ 3/30/2023
- Education public Interface (with 📄 Systems Census)
- Knowledge Engineering public Interface (with ISSS archival work).
- Upcoming “Language Models + ISSS” next week
-
- 🌐 ISSS
 - ISSS should own the Coda document.
 - Subdomain on e.g. census.iss.org & archive.iss.org (KM)
- Coda and.....
 - Gantt chart
 - Accessibility
 - Augmentation & Time
 - 2 minutes
 - 25 minutes
 - Day — 90 minutes.
 - Month
- Coda 101
 - Introduction to Coda — How to use it.
 - Pricing & Use
 - Features
 - Functionality
 - Within a page
 - Roles of Outlining
 - Within a document
 - ..
 - Across documents
 - ..
 - Augmentations and Integrations.
 - OpenAI
 - Websites (standalone, and embed/subdomain).

- Educational use cases
 - Courses —
 - Book → Curriculum Syllabus → Production of presentations and problem-project pedagogy
 - [George Mobus](#) working on the Master's Level course curriculum (his books, and complementary/extending materials).
 - Institute
 - Santa Fe Institute
 - Ontology
 - Transcription
 - Curation
 - Summarization
 - Publishing
 - .
- Shingai's newsletter
 - <https://systemsexplorers.substack.com/>
 - .
 - .

Agenda

1. Welcome & Introductions (anything to add before we begin recording?)
 - a. Begin recording
2. Any news, updates, or questions about [Participating in ISSS Education](#))
 - a. Add Notes and links above.
3. Review and work on [To-Do && To Discuss for #15](#) (add, update, remove)

To-Do && To Discuss for #15

Area	Discussed?	Task Status	Name
ISSS Education Services 3	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	For ISSS mini-symposium or any other ISSS effort, determine what tasks we can do in Education group
	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	Pub talking points (everyday Systems memes and themes)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	From Crossover for EDU from KE — How to utilize the Interface (in development) for Education and engagement?
Standards in Systems Education			
Curriculum for Systems literacy			

In progress

Knowledge and Materials Transfer for [George Mobus](#), Educational Work

▼ Systems Census

1

In progress

Staying updated with the Systems Census

▼ Coda Education

1

In progress

Make Coda preparation and education materials

To add

-

#16 ~ 5/11/2023

ISSS Education meeting #16 on May 11, 2023.

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/5JcKZHEHnZA>

Notes

- Review #15 ~ 4/27/2023
- Education public Interface (with Systems Census)
- Knowledge Engineering public Interface (with ISSS archival work).
- ISSS
 - ISSS should own the Coda document.
 - Can have subdomain on e.g. census.isss.org & archive.isss.org (KM)
- Shingai's newsletter <https://systemexplorers.substack.com/>
- <https://arxiv.org/abs/2006.04182> **Predictive Coding Approximates Backprop along Arbitrary Computation Graphs**
- <https://www.thirteen.org/programs/amanpour-co/godfather-of-ai-warns-of-the-existential-threat-of-ai-lj1i1c/> a link sent to me by Tyler Volk re: a talk by Geoff Hinton re his leaving Google. I haven't listened to it yet.
- An Institute that produces educational programs based upon Systems Science.

Agenda

1. Welcome & Introductions (anything to add before we begin recording?)
 - a. Begin recording
2. Update and fine-tune Coda Education
3. Any news, updates, or questions about Participating in ISSS Education)
 - a. Add Notes and links above.
4. Review and work on To-Do && To Discuss for #16 (add, update, remove)

To-Do && To Discuss for #16

Area	Discussed?	Task Status	Name
▼ ISSS Education Services 3	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	For ISSS mini-symposium or any other ISSS effort, determine what tasks we can do in Education group
	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	Pub talking points (everyday Systems memes and themes)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	From Crossover for EDU from KE — How to utilize the Interface (in development) for Education and engagement?
▼ Standards in Systems Education			

▼ Curriculum for Systems literacy				
		<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Knowledge and Materials Transfer for George Mobus, Educational Work
▼ Systems Census				
▼ Coda Education	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Make Coda preparation and education materials

To add

-

#17 ~ 5/25/2023

ISSS Education meeting #17 on May 25, 2023.

Meeting recording

- https://youtu.be/mIDIP_1Rb8M

Notes

- Review [#16 ~ 5/11/2023](#)
- Education public Interface (with [Systems Census](#))
- Knowledge Engineering public Interface (with ISSS archival work).
- [ISSS](#)
 - ISSS should own the Coda document.
 - Can have subdomain on e.g. census.isss.org & archive.isss.org (KM)
- Shingai's newsletter <https://systemsexplorers.substack.com/>
- Principles, by [George Mobus](#), needing to find new contacts at Springer. Who is the new person that has taken over that job, and re-establish link.
 - See [#16 ~ 5/11/2023](#), enabling supplementary information to be linked.
- [Shingai's recent blog](#)
 - Systems Knowledge Base. Was framed as relational, modern databases may have alternative approaches.
 - Systems Engineering approach towards structuring/utilizing knowledge structured through analysis.
 - Complex and Evolvable systems archetypes, at end of the book.
 - Perhaps how brain encodes/decodes as well.
 - Graphical interface for systems building blocks.
 - Could utilize cadCAD? <https://github.com/cadCAD-org/cadcad-ri>
 - Modules involved
 - Graphical frontend with Icons, Menu, Drag/Drop.
 - Show a system in block diagram style, with simulation running in background.
- [Motivating a Systems Theory of AI March 2020, Insight 23\(1\):37-40 DOI:10.1002/inst.12283](#)

Mesarovician general systems model

- Robert Rosen, Ecology, Anticipatory Systems, Category Theory.
 - [George Mobus](#)
 - Active Inference
 - cadCAD — Generalized Dynamical Systems
- It would be grand if ISSS and members can tackle this approach — [ISSS](#), SCA, et al.

- What does it mean to have a systems theory?
- If we can approach this with an open mind, and a conviction that all of this can be integrated and synthesized into a theory.
- George believes, as long as a minute pheromone trail leads back to 🟢 [George Mobus](#) , this will be good and successful.
- Go back to the sources, but take it on as our own project. Go to the body of work, not the personalities.
- This is along the lines of the synthesis work that [@George Mobus](#) worked on, that bringing the pieces together does not always enable “X was due to Y”. We can list the sources and citations, however specific people/works cannot always be tracked back.
- The two textbooks by George are like skeletons or initial prototypes. Not representing a complete view. They try to bring all the ideas of Systems-ness, and bring into a package. Pointing towards some solutions. Like a starting hypothesis.
- The role of the ISSS is to educate the world about systems.
- Thus to role of the Education committee is to implement this.
- Proceeding along the lines of synthesis as a basis for future standardization is in line with reason for being.
- Karl's work
 - Discovering connection points in Network Improvement Communities.
 - How can we connect this work with doctoral research work.
 - Systems and Complexity groups are extremely rare across universities. So working with ISSS could connect with mentoring, external thesis committee member, broader impacts.
 - <https://www.profsandpints.com/washingtondc>
-

Agenda

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3. Any news, updates, or questions about 📄 [Education](#) at 🏠 [ISSS](#) ([👤 Participating in ISSS Education](#))
 - a. Add Notes and links above.
4. Review and work on 📄 [To-Do && To Discuss for #17](#) (add, update, remove)

To-Do && To Discuss for #17

Area	Discussed?	Task Status	Name
▼ 📄 ISSS Education Services 3	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	For ISSS mini-symposium or any other ISSS effort, determine what tasks we can do in Education group
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▼ 📄 Standards 1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	Exploring 📄 Standards in Systems Education

▼ Curriculum for Systems literacy				
		<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Knowledge and Materials Transfer for George Mobus, Educational Work
▼ Systems Census				
▼ Coda Education	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Make Coda preparation and education materials

To add

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#18 ~ 6/8/2023

ISSS Education meeting #18

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/zLYLfb9I1eI>

Notes

- Review 📅 #17 ~ 5/25/2023
- Education public Interface (with 📄 Systems Census)
- Knowledge Engineering public Interface (with ISSS archival work).
- 🌐 ISSS
- Ongoing:
 - Shingai's newsletter <https://systemexplorers.substack.com/>
 - Principles, by 🛡️ George Mobus, needing to find new contacts at Springer. Who is the new person that has taken over that job, and re-establish link.
 -
- Upcoming
 - <https://www.iss.org/2023-kruger-national-park/> — questions?
- .
- Shingai's recent blog
 - Slides from 6/8/2023
 - Re: cadCAD playing a role — If embedded functions exist within C components, this can be system dynamics model
 - Possible PhD direction? With 🛡️ George Mobus as emeritus advisor.
 - Robotics has a high budgetary requirement.
 - Whereas this Systems research project does not have high research costs.
 - For someone who....
 - Wants to get a PhD in Computer Science.
 - [U Washington, Tacoma https://www.tacoma.uw.edu/set/programs/graduate/phdcss](https://www.tacoma.uw.edu/set/programs/graduate/phdcss)
 - George will get link to PhD description, add some other screeds.
 - .
 - Systems Knowledge Base. Was framed as relational, modern databases may have alternative approaches.
 - Systems Engineering approach towards structuring/utilizing knowledge structured through analysis.
 - Complex and Evolvable systems archetypes, at end of the book.
 - Perhaps how brain encodes/decodes as well.
 - Graphical interface for systems building blocks.
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- Graphical frontend with Icons, Menu, Drag/Drop.
 - Show a system in block diagram style, with simulation running in background.
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 - Go back to the sources, but take it on as our own project. Go to the body of work, not the personalities.
 - This is along the lines of the synthesis work that [@George Mobus](#) worked on, that bringing the pieces together does not always enable “X was due to Y”. We can list the sources and citations, however specific people/works cannot always be tracked back.
 - The two textbooks by George are like skeletons or initial prototypes. Not representing a complete view. They try to bring all the ideas of Systems-ness, and bring into a package. Pointing towards some solutions. Like a starting hypothesis.
 - The role of the ISSS is to educate the world about systems.
 - Thus to role of the Education committee is to implement this.
 - Proceeding along the lines of synthesis as a basis for future standardization is in line with reason for being.
- Karl's work
- Discovering connection points in Network Improvement Communities.
 - How can we connect this work with doctoral research work.
 - Systems and Complexity groups are extremely rare across universities. So working with ISSS could connect with mentoring, external thesis committee member, broader impacts.
 - <https://www.profsandpints.com/washingtondc>

Agenda

1. Welcome & Introductions (anything to add before we begin recording?)
 - a. Begin recording

2. Update and fine-tune [Coda Education](#)
3. Any news, updates, or questions about [Education](#) at [ISSS](#) ([Participating in ISSS Education](#))
 - a. Add Notes and links above.
4. Review and work on [To-Do & To Discuss for #17 2](#) (add, update, remove)

To-Do & To Discuss for #17 2

Area	Discussed?	Task Status	Name
▼ ISSS Education Services 3	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	For ISSS mini-symposium or any other ISSS effort, determine what tasks we can do in Education group
	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	Pub talking points (everyday Systems memes and themes)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	From Crossover for EDU from KE — How to utilize the Interface (in development) for Education and engagement?
▼ Standards 1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	Exploring Standards in Systems Education
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	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Knowledge and Materials Transfer for George Mobus , Educational Work
▼ Systems Census 1	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Staying updated with the Systems Census
▼ Coda Education 1	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Make Coda preparation and education materials

To add

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#19 ~ 6/22/2023

ISSS Education meeting #18

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/icywp8U2TgY>

Notes

- Review 📅 #18 ~ 6/8/2023
- Education public Interface (with 📊 Systems Census)
- Knowledge Engineering public Interface (with ISSS archival work).
- 🌐 ISSS
- Ongoing:
 - Shingai's newsletter <https://systemexplorers.substack.com/>
 - Principles, by 🛡️ George Mobus, needing to find new contacts at Springer. Who is the new person that has taken over that job, and re-establish link.
- Upcoming
 - <https://www.iss.org/2023-kruger-national-park/> — questions?
- Systemism as Ideology
 - Nadia's idea machine

- Communities guided by belief in an ideology. Science sometimes seen as “counter” to ideology (is it really though?).
 - Systemism: the alternative to individualism and holism (Bunge, 2000)
- System-ism “systemism is a worldview grounded in the belief that everything is a system and all problems should be solved in a systematic fashion.” — the belief is related to: everything is a system. Understanding the systemness will help you understand it. As opposed to believing that the answer will be found in Cybernetics, Complexity
- Santa Fe Institute, Complexity explains everything, they have been successful in spreading that (e.g. new PLoS journal).
- Games.
 - SimCity, Systems simulators
- Experience → Questions → Give a framework → Re-engage in holistic fashion
- Results from, I need tools to explore the world I want to understand.

- Where is Curiosity? One has to already be curious about things. Most/many people, especially in younger years, are curious.
- [Shingai's recent blog](#)
 - [Slides from 6/8/2023](#)
 - Re: cadCAD playing a role — If embedded functions exist within C components, this can be system dynamics model
 - Possible PhD direction? With [George Mobus](#) as emeritus advisor.
 - Robotics has a high budgetary requirement.
 - Whereas this Systems research project does not have high research costs.
 - For someone who....
 - Wants to get a PhD in Computer Science.
 - [U Washington, Tacoma](https://www.tacoma.uw.edu/set/programs/graduate/phdcss) <https://www.tacoma.uw.edu/set/programs/graduate/phdcss>
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 - Systems Knowledge Base. Was framed as relational, modern databases may have alternative approaches.
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 - Modules involved
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 - Show a system in block diagram style, with simulation running in background.
- [Motivating a Systems Theory of AI March 2020, Insight 23\(1\):37-40 DOI:10.1002/inst.12283](#)

Mesarovician general systems model

- Robert Rosen, Ecology, Anticipatory Systems, Category Theory.
- [George Mobus](#)
- Active Inference
- cadCAD — Generalized Dynamical Systems
- It would be grand if ISSS and members can tackle this approach — [ISSS](#), SCA, et al.
 - What does it mean to have a systems theory?
 - If we can approach this with an open mind, and a conviction that all of this can be integrated and synthesized into a theory.
 - George believes, as long as a minute pheromone trail leads back to [George Mobus](#), this will be good and successful.
 - Go back to the sources, but take it on as our own project. Go to the body of work, not the personalities.

- This is along the lines of the synthesis work that [@George Mobus](#) worked on, that bringing the pieces together does not always enable “X was due to Y”. We can list the sources and citations, however specific people/works cannot always be tracked back.
- The two textbooks by George are like skeletons or initial prototypes. Not representing a complete view. They try to bring all the ideas of Systems-ness, and bring into a package. Pointing towards some solutions. Like a starting hypothesis.
- The role of the ISSS is to educate the world about systems.
- Thus to role of the Education committee is to implement this.
- Proceeding along the lines of synthesis as a basis for future standardization is in line with reason for being.
- Karl's work
 - Discovering connection points in Network Improvement Communities.
 - How can we connect this work with doctoral research work.
 - Systems and Complexity groups are extremely rare across universities. So working with ISSS could connect with mentoring, external thesis committee member, broader impacts.
 - <https://www.profsandpints.com/washingtondc>
-

Agenda

1. Welcome & Introductions (anything to add before we begin recording?)
 - a. Begin recording
2. Update and fine-tune [Coda Education](#)
3. Any news, updates, or questions about [Participating in ISSS Education](#))
 - a. Add Notes and links above.
4. Review and work on [To-Do & To Discuss for #17 3](#) (add, update, remove)

To-Do & To Discuss for #17 3

Area	Discussed?	Task Status	Name
▼ ISSS Education Services 3	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	For ISSS mini-symposium or any other ISSS effort, determine what tasks we can do in Education group
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	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	From Crossover for EDU from KE — How to utilize the Interface (in development) for Education and engagement?
▼ Standards in Systems Education			
▼ Curriculum for Systems literacy			

In progress

Knowledge and Materials Transfer for [George Mobus](#), Educational Work

▼ Systems Census

1

In progress

Staying updated with the Systems Census

▼ Coda Education

1

In progress

Make Coda preparation and education materials

To add

-

#20 ~ 7/6/2023

ISSS Education meeting #20

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/DXU3YOOi9Vs>

Notes

- Review 📅 #18 ~ 6/8/2023
- Education public Interface (with 📊 Systems Census)
- Knowledge Engineering public Interface (with ISSS archival work).
- 🌐 ISSS
- Ongoing:
 - Shingai's newsletter <https://systemexplorers.substack.com/>
 - Principles, by 🛡️ George Mobus, needing to find new contacts at Springer. Who is the new person that has taken over that job, and re-establish link.
- Upcoming
 - <https://www.iss.org/2023-kruger-national-park/> — questions?
- Systemism as Ideology
 - Nadia's idea machine

- Communities guided by belief in an ideology. Science sometimes seen as “counter” to ideology (is it really though?).
 - Systemism: the alternative to individualism and holism (Bunge, 2000)
- System-ism “systemism is a worldview grounded in the belief that everything is a system and all problems should be solved in a systematic fashion.” — the belief is related to: everything is a system. Understanding the systemness will help you understand it. As opposed to believing that the answer will be found in Cybernetics, Complexity
- Santa Fe Institute, Complexity explains everything, they have been successful in spreading that (e.g. new PLoS journal).
- Games.
 - SimCity, Systems simulators
- Experience → Questions → Give a framework → Re-engage in holistic fashion
- Results from, I need tools to explore the world I want to understand.

- Where is Curiosity? One has to already be curious about things. Most/many people, especially in younger years, are curious.
 - [Shingai's recent blog](#)
 - [Slides from 6/8/2023](#)
 - Re: cadCAD playing a role — If embedded functions exist within C components, this can be system dynamics model
 - Possible PhD direction? With [George Mobus](#) as emeritus advisor.
 - Robotics has a high budgetary requirement.
 - Whereas this Systems research project does not have high research costs.
 - For someone who....
 - Wants to get a PhD in Computer Science.
 - [U Washington, Tacoma](https://www.tacoma.uw.edu/set/programs/graduate/phdcss) <https://www.tacoma.uw.edu/set/programs/graduate/phdcss>
 - George will get link to PhD description, add some other screeds.
 - Systems Knowledge Base. Was framed as relational, modern databases may have alternative approaches.
 - Systems Engineering approach towards structuring/utilizing knowledge structured through analysis.
 - Complex and Evolvable systems archetypes, at end of the book.
 - Perhaps how brain encodes/decodes as well.
 - Graphical interface for systems building blocks.
 - Could utilize cadCAD? <https://github.com/cadCAD-org/cadcad-ri>
 - Modules involved
 - Graphical frontend with Icons, Menu, Drag/Drop.
 - Show a system in block diagram style, with simulation running in background.
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- Systems

Tweet

- This is why there need to be more departments and work in 🇺🇸 [Systems Science](#) . It is an interdisciplinary setting that everyone can have lifelong learning within.
- There is obvious need to make it exciting and accessible for thinking and acting systemically, 🇺🇸 [Systems Science](#) programs would be a great way for this to happen.
- George taught computer science and engineering, during the transformative periods. From assembling the code, to object-oriented programming. The honest systems thinking that was happening in order for this program to be pushed forward.
- Air traffic control in 1980's.... using Ada language. Rational built a machine that was dedicated to the Ada environment. — Karl's father. Then Karl's integrated acquisition environment, bringing the 14 systems together, [SAM.gov](#)
- Java and C++ were complex, developed to support software engineering, however you had to know the concepts deeply. Python was not initially Object-Oriented as such, and thus was flexible enough to accept the OO paradigm in implementation. Language of choice.
 - 🇺🇸 [Systems Language / sysXML](#) and Systems-Oriented Programming.
 - Try to marry up, in a systems framework, the Descriptive and the Functional aspects. Functional programming.
 - The idea, was to make this accessible like a Markup language.
 - So many people were able to learn HTML. Describing what a page would look like. Then embedding scripting languages within HTML and so on. However the page description, and the scripting environments, were not built from an integrated system perspective.,
 - Start with Systemsness, staying in both lanes (Object and Process).
 - I attended a webinar with Sophia Prater a couple of years ago, Object-Oriented UX: <https://www.ooux.com/people/sophiavprater>

- Once you Described an object, then you had to go back to Process orientation. The hardest thing for George to teach the students was this shift.
- Teaching Object-Oriented programming in C (not C++), to show how C++ implemented things. Because the C++ compiler was a pre-processor for C programs, which could be compiled and executed.
- This issue is resolved with the systems orientation.
- Systems Dynamic (STELLA) tried to merge object and process in an (incomplete) systems framework. Did not have the fullness of Systems-ness in it. People did not look at SD as a programming language (they were not looking to it when engineering the Denver airport baggage handling system).
- George building some more realistic models regarding Energy Production. Not just proximate solar energy production, but how much energy/inputs were needed. The other languages at the time did not have the expressiveness that was needed.
- So he considered these Systems icons (Stocks, Flows, Controls and MORE), all the things that are required for Systemness.
 - You are constructing a System, not just an Object/Program.
 - <https://www.ibm.com/docs/en/rational-soft-arch/9.5?topic=migration-rational-rose-model>
 - https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IBM_Rational_Rose_XDE
 - UML — Unified Modeling Language it described the structure, and captured relationships, it was a good thinking tool for the time. Then there was a disconnect when trying to implement.
 - sysML is a little better because Function is included within the model.
 - People would make elaborate UML diagrams without @Front end guidance. Since then, many model-based design approaches have arisen.
- Is it useful to think about Systems Language / sysXML as....
 - Program (written in another language).
 - Package specification (could be written in another language).
 - Analytic representation.
 - Language
 - Paradigm — Systemness
- If the programs work well, people will want to adopt the paradigm (Bucky Fuller and whatnot).
- Writing the @Front end as a Guide, so the underlying Syntax would constrain/enable different kinds of Operations. You have to follow the rules, balanced system, etc. — Force the issue of Systemness. Then the @Back end is implementing this system.
- Analytic Auto-Ethnography (A-E)
 - Collaborative A-E.
 - Supplying the Anthropology techniques to the analysis of one in their own culture.
 - Evocative A-E, which connects to Phenomenology
 - Also there is an Analytic dimension or possibility.
 - Connections to cognitive science and cognitive security.
 - discovered this through Goel's A Cognitive Reformation,
 - The provocative article: Núñez, R., Allen, M., Gao, R., Miller Rigoli, C., Relaford-Doyle, J., & Semenuks, A. (2019). [What happened to cognitive science?](#). Nature human behaviour, 3(8), 782-791.

Friston (not!) be cited!

- Special issue:
 - Topics in Cognitive Science, 11(4)
 - https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=5%2C47&sciodt=0%2C47&cites=4203912265217488311&scipsc=&as_ylo=2019&as_yhi=2019
 - Participatory Narrative Inquiry, Cynthia Kurtz. Project-orientation.
 - <https://www.cfkurtz.com/>
 - Candidate systems.
 - Tyler ___ and @Lynn Rasmussen and George are meeting on zoom to discuss Combogenesis, Onto-genesis of George, engaging in the ontology mapping.
- 🛡️ George Mobus wrote several pieces on 📄 Systems Science shared with Daniel and Shingai. Systems Science is the new liberal arts, it gives you the broadest possible set of thinking tools. Instead of thinking of going into a profession, think about being a problem-solver with these skills.
 - <https://faculty.washington.edu/gmobus/Admin/SystemsScience/explainingSystemsScience.html>
- .
- .

Agenda

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 - a. Add Notes and links above.
4. Review and work on 📄 To-Do && To Discuss for #17 4 (add, update, remove)

To-Do && To Discuss for #17 4

Area	Discussed?	Task Status	Name
▼ 📄 ISSS Education Services 3	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	For ISSS mini-symposium or any other ISSS effort, determine what tasks we can do in Education group
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▼ Standards	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	Exploring Standards in Systems Education
▼ Systems Science	2	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	Curriculum for Systems literacy
		<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Knowledge and Materials Transfer for George Mobus , Educational Work
▼ Systems Census	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Staying updated with the Systems Census
▼ Coda Education	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Make Coda preparation and education materials

To add

-

#21 ~ 7/20/2023

ISSS Education meeting #21

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/reonjhU-gfE>

Notes

- Review 📅 #20 ~ 7/6/2023
- Education public Interface (with 📄 Systems Census)
- Knowledge Engineering public Interface (with ISSS archival work).
- 🌐 ISSS
- Ongoing:
 - Shingai's newsletter <https://systemsexplorers.substack.com/>
 - Principles, by 🛡️ George Mobus, needing to find new contacts at Springer. Who is the new person that has taken over that job, and re-establish link.
- <https://zenodo.org/record/8164667> Generative Research Teams: Active Inference Compositions For Research and Meta-Science
- 📄 Systems Language / sysXML
- 🛡️ George Mobus wrote several 📄 Articles for Systems Science on 📄 Systems Science shared with Daniel and Shingai. Systems Science is the new liberal arts, it gives you the broadest possible set of thinking tools. Instead of thinking of going into a profession, think about being a problem-solver with these skills.
 - <https://faculty.washington.edu/gmobus/Admin/SystemsScience/explainingSystemsScience.html>
 - Why universities in general, and UW Tacoma in specific, should have 📄 Systems Science programs.
 - If you could get a degree, motivated by the idea that you can use this to get good jobs — then, eventually it moves into the Masters/PhD as well as earlier into lifelong learning.
 - Microcredentials (work for technical skills, how might it work in systems science/literacy?).
 - <https://www.instituteforapprenticeships.org/apprenticeship-standards/systems-thinking-practitioner-v1-1>
- .

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To-Do & To Discuss for #17 5

Area		Discussed?	Task Status	Name
▼ 🏢 ISSS Education Services	3	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	For ISSS mini-symposium or any other ISSS effort, determine what tasks we can do in Education group
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▼ 📖 Systems Science	2	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	📖 Curriculum for Systems literacy
		<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Knowledge and Materials Transfer for 📖 George Mobus , Educational Work
▼ 📊 Systems Census	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Staying updated with the 📊 Systems Census
▼ 📄 Coda Education	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Make Coda preparation and education materials

To add

-

#22 ~ 7/31/2023

- Cryptoeconomics
 - George was doing work on the nature of money and its relationship to energy
 - Money has become increasingly divorced from its original social role
 - Currencies are not tied to the real value of work. This gets them further away from the true purpose of money
 - People are only looking at it from the perspective of how can i get rich
 - Within the crypto arena you have blockchain technology that is interesting, distributed decision making and responsibility has a role to play in designing a governance structure
 - Last part of the second textbook
 - Jessie
 - Agrees with george.
 - Currency got its value from representing actual physical needs of people. Not speculative
 - Speculation can be dangerous
 - All of our wonderfully education professionals are unaware that they are profiting from dismantling the assets that our economy relies
 - It does matter that our currencies are connected to legitimate value
 - Money isn't created by fiat, it's created by qualified future earnings. Banks create money when borrowers prove they can repay it
 - Karl
 - MMT
 - Can the government go bankrupt?
 - Government will need to step up and fund things
 - To do
 - Look at chapters on the economy. Look at relationship between money and energy and the economy, how does that relate to crypto?
 - sysML
 - Origin and Nature of Life on Earth, metabolism represents the economy.
 - Archetype model of the economy establishes this approach
 - Bring crypto back to larger economic model
 - Is crypto acting as positive feedback look contributing to depletion of resources. Model how crypto plays
 - Alternative energy sources are not sustainable
 - As enzymes evolved, energy required for doing biosynthesis decreased. Reducing usage of free energy is the goal.
 - Government
 - Jessie. Instead of models using words, create models based on observed patterns of behavior.
 - Without an understanding of overall system goal, it's not very useful to look at all of the details. Use model of governance to explore
 - We are trying to capture as much description as possible, because we use models. The trick is, what language will that be?

- The model needs to have built in innate capacity for asking questions.
- Models need to have steering
- Sustainability
 - People working on this need to understand what they are trying to do
 - This is getting away from the norm
 - If open-source, still would need to be managed. Gatekeepers need to ensure what's being done is aligned with the purpose.
 - A foundation with private money, paying people to learn and then do
 - Core of interested individuals just starting to build something/codebase

#23 ~ 8/17/2023

ISSS Education meeting #23

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/mF1KEzEsTyo>

Notes

- Review 📅 #22 ~ 7/31/2023
- Education public Interface (with 📄 Systems Census)
- Knowledge Engineering public Interface (with ISSS archival work).
- 🌐 ISSS
- Ongoing:
 - Shingai's newsletter <https://systemexplorers.substack.com/>
 - Principles, by 🛡️ George Mobus, needing to find new contacts at Springer. Who is the new person that has taken over that job, and re-establish link.
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 - Why universities in general, and UW Tacoma in specific, should have 📄 Systems Science programs.
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 - Microcredentials (work for technical skills, how might it work in systems science/literacy?).
 - <https://www.instituteforapprenticeships.org/apprenticeship-standards/systems-thinking-practitioner-v1-1>
- Applying 📄 Systems Science to the origin of life problem. Something that George continues to work on. Diagramming of core metabolism as coupled work processes.
 - Electron bifurcation — coupling the Exo- and Endergonic reaction (up and down the Free Energy // Information-Heat variables). Key system property with not wasting energy, energy optimization, path of least action.
 - Origin of life is phase transition of Universe. Some are researching Metabolism as it is today, taking it apart, finding the essential parts, the core core set of reactions. That's the auto-catalytic/autopoietic aspect of self-/re-construction/composition.
 - It can be graduate school type problem to begin to scope/address this 📄 Systems Science question/problem. Multi-disciplinary effort already and with significance (bio-geo-chemistry and other Subject Matter work), this project is trying to put it in the framework of System/Systemness. The do use the term System and features/aspects like composition/nesting, however the discussion often stays within the biochemistry/reductionist paradigm.
 - Then the Systems Science can produce informed accounts and experimental suggestions for the field of Origin of Life. This is / can be empirical and explicit. This gives utility for those in the lab work to connect with broader Systems area.
 - ▼ Charles Darwin closed the last paragraph of the first edition, (publication date 24 November 1859), of his *On the Origin of Species* with this sentence:-

- *There is grandeur in this view of life, with its several powers, having been originally breathed into a few forms or into one; and that, whilst this planet has gone cycling on according to the fixed law of gravity, from so simple a beginning endless forms most beautiful and most wonderful have been, and are being, evolved.*
- [Systems Language / sysXML](#) providing the design suite / enabling system for productive/effective progress
- Abductive reasoning, coming to the front of process in deep analysis. Looking/Mapping phenomena — What would explain how this got to be this way (inputs, causes, etc). As per George's deep analysis: starting backwards and coming to inputs, enforces/supports multiple pathways of different backwards/causal understanding. In terms of sub-systems too (nested generative models and blanket).
- Deduction/Induction + Abduction
 - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WKjqw3My_xM
<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12304-021-09432-0> 2021 Active Inference and Abduction, Ahti-Veikko Pietarinen & Majid D. Beni.
 - Robert Rosen: Recursion, recursion? Abduction? — One of the few who worked with the formal systems tools.
- Gary Smith did the panel: Scientific Foundations of Systems Engineering. After the talk there was interest and he saw the educators with booths as well. What are their current thinkings around integrating [Education](#)?
 - Common Core — for returning and reusing, and diverging (open source?)
 - August 29th — Some dozens of Systems/Education-interested people will try to get to:
 - Work together or 3 or 4 common slides
 - Supporting text
 - Key references.
 - Then this will be commonly referred-to materials
 - This also starts the Education Materials committee
 - [ISSS](#) facilitates these committees
 - Relevant VP as co-chair.
 - Then the main influx of participation is the educational bodies.
 - What changes our ways of working here in [Education](#)?
 - Education SIG activity?
 - Education open house/space (some monthly open space for presentations and updates).
 - Education committee:
 - Educational materials
 - To draw materials together of/from.... Curriculum around....?
 -
 - Professionalization
 - Synthesis work about Systems Science frameworks (SIG or Research network?)
 - Theory-Practice interface.
- SySTEAM (STEM and Arts) — Katelyn Singham (?) a Maryland graduate student. This work already has complementary focus and different backgrounds. [ISSS](#) highlights Systems Science and this can be a positive synergy in the ecosystem.
- Shingai making many developments for [Systems Language / sysXML](#) and distilling our work + including more participants.
-

- [GM Chapter 5](#)
 - Different kinds of Holons applied to [Systems Science](#) — Reflect, Observe, Plan, Reflect (O Active Inference, where art thy sting?)
 -
 - Committee can:
 - Utilize [GM Chapter 5](#) diagram and deep systems analysis as a committed single source of truth. Follow the procedure and de-compose the sub-systems. You will then find the processes that make up the thing.

What is the tracing of systems principles to this diagram? That's the book :)

- The book outlines a draft specification of attributes of systems, and many truth drops in terms of process. Following the [GM Chapter 5](#) chapters (understood as only a linearized pointer sequence of their own experiences). This is not a complete descriptor. This is A CORE (not “the” or “whole thing”) and George’s work points towards [Systems Language / sysXML](#)
- Scaffold and plan to use [Systems Language / sysXML](#) as open source project — including “triple play” of natural languages, production of visualizations, and executable systems simulations.
- Human as natural processes.
- [Systems Science](#) entails a lot of learning, practicing, doing, trying. We do [Education](#) for many reasons, and there is multi-lateral and emergent relation among e.g. Science, Education, Research, Application, Thinking.
 - Working through the problems in reality. The graphics do not (cannot) simply pop out of a slide. There is a method. Keeping multiple aspects in mind. No single English term captures the phenomena and simultaneous multiscale dynamics.
 - Read George’s book.

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▼ 📖 Systems Science 2	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	📖 Curriculum for Systems literacy
	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Knowledge and Materials Transfer for 🟢 George Mobus, Educational Work
▼ 📊 Systems Census 1	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Staying updated with the 📊 Systems Census
▼ 📄 Coda Education 1	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Make Coda preparation and education materials

To add

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#24 ~ 8/31/2023

ISSS Education meeting #24

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/UHBTnUgoREw>

Notes

- Review 📅 #23 ~ 8/17/2023
- Ongoing 📁 Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions
 - 📖 Systems Language / sysXML (🛡️ George Mobus textbook and beyond).
 - 🌐 ISSS
 - Education public Interface (with 📊 Systems Census)
 - Knowledge Engineering public Interface (with ISSS archival work).
 - Shingai's newsletter
 - 🏠 Towards a Common Core
 - 🧠 Systems Literacy
- .
- .

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To-Do && To Discuss for #24

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▼ Systems Census				
▼ Coda Education	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	Make Coda preparation and education materials

To add

-

#25 ~ 9/14/2023

ISSS Education meeting #25

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/UJ7xN2-cork>

Notes

- Review 📅 #24 ~ 8/31/2023
- Ongoing 📁 Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions
 - 📖 Systems Language / sysXML (🛡️ George Mobus textbook and beyond).
 - 🌐 ISSS
 - Education public Interface (with 📊 Systems Census)
 - Knowledge Engineering public Interface (with ISSS archival work).
 - 🚀 Towards a Common Core — INCOSE, sySTEAM, et al.
 - Shingai's newsletter
 - 📖 Systems Literacy
- Accessibility: PDF ingress, Virtual Worlds XR, ____?
- Systems, and Education meetings
 - <https://event.fourwaves.com/n2conference/pages>
 - <https://events.educause.edu/annual-conference>
 - <https://www.aera.net/Events-Meetings/2023-Annual-Meeting>
 - INCOSE — Continued working groups for times between workshops.
 - 🌐 ISSS has the SIG.
- “Systems”
 - Any time we have more than 1 thing, it is easy to say System.
 - In 📖 Systems Science we are looking for what is true and rigorous, about Systems.
 - Search for classes “Systems” (e.g. at UDC)
 - Operating System — Functional composition of what you want it to do. Few people are looking as e.g. OS as Hierarchy, Network. Thus there are analyses that do not get done.
 - George's approach: Bringing the principles into play, understand the properties/systemness of the OS — then it can be linked to experiences in people's lives.
 - Hence, any area of study where they are working on a System (e.g. Food system, Nursing system). — Then what aspects of Systemness are being considered.
 - 📖 Systems Science as a discipline (as a meta-discipline). Then people can apply more broadly to what is called ____ Systems.
 - A Systems Scientist — as consultants called in to other areas, as part of team/business environment. Then can go into other Sciences, other areas — “we think we have a system” here, if something
 - <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41562-019-0626-2> What happened to cognitive science?
 - Volk <https://www.amazon.com/Metapatterns-Across-Space-Time-Mind-ebook/dp/B0753M84Z2>

- Pattern Language for Cognitive Science/Security <https://coda.io/@aien/cogsec-atlas/patterns-26>
- <https://oecd.ai/en/classification>
- <https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/MathML>
- LLM and 🦋 Crossover for EDU from KE
 - <https://twitter.com/DrJimFan/status/1702322181928259586>
 - This is the way to unlock the next trillion high-quality tokens, currently frozen in textbook pixels that are not LLM-ready.
 - Nougat: an open-source OCR model that accurately scans books with heavy math/scientific notations. It's ages ahead of other open OCR options. Meta is doing extraordinary open-source AI, sometimes without as much fanfare as Llama.
 - Website: <https://facebookresearch.github.io/nougat/>
 - Open-source code: <https://github.com/facebookresearch/nougat>
 - Paper "Nougat: Neural Optical Understanding for Academic Documents": <https://arxiv.org/abs/2308.13418>
- .
- .
- .
- .

Agenda

1. Welcome & Introductions (anything to add before we begin recording?)
 - a. Begin recording
2. Update and fine-tune 🇷🇺 Coda Education
3. Any news, updates, or questions about 🇷🇺 Education at 🌐 ISSS ([🔗 Participating in ISSS Education](#))
 - a. Add Notes and links above.
4. Review and work on 🗂️ To-Do && To Discuss for #24 2 (add, update, remove)

To-Do && To Discuss for #24 2

Area	Discussed?	Task Status	Name
▼ 🇷🇺 ISSS Education Services 3	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	For ISSS mini-symposium or any other ISSS effort, determine what tasks we can do in Education group
	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	Pub talking points (everyday Systems memes and themes)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	In progress	From 🦋 Crossover for EDU from KE — How to utilize the Interface (in development) for Education and engagement?
▼ 🇺🇸 Standards 1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	Exploring 🇺🇸 Standards in Systems Education
▼ 🇺🇸 Systems Science 2	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	🇺🇸 Curriculum for Systems literacy

In progress

Knowledge and Materials Transfer for [George Mobus](#), Educational Work

▼ Systems Census

1

In progress

Staying updated with the Systems Census

▼ Coda Education

1

In progress

Make Coda preparation and education materials

To add

-

#26 ~ 9/28/2023

ISSS Education meeting #26

Meeting recording

- https://youtu.be/-RkfeM_onHo

Notes

- Review 📖 #25 ~ 9/14/2023
- Ongoing 📚 Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions
 - 📖 Systems Language / sysXML (🛡️ George Mobus textbook and beyond).
 - 🌐 ISSS
 - Education public Interface (with 📖 Systems Census)
 - Knowledge Engineering public Interface (with ISSS archival work).
 - 🏡 Towards a Common Core — INCOSE, sySTEAM, et al.
 - Shingai's newsletter
 - 📖 Systems Literacy
- Problem solving:
 - → Entailing building a model. Can this always be described as a graph? Any computable problem amenable to algorithmic analysis can be represented with graph
 - Not to be found (yet) in George's PhD educational materials. Seeking, rational for the brain as able to encode models graphically.
 - Mental time travel. Suttendorf. Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN)
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MzYmdBaJIYc> ActInf MorphStream 001.1 ~ David Kappel and Sarah Hamburg
 - <https://arxiv.org/abs/2202.07132> Memory via Temporal Delays in weightless Spiking Neural Network (2022) — tie-back to spike trains in George's PhD and patent (expired).
 - [A Factor Graph Description of Deep Temporal Active Inference](#) (2017)
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Sz7ZP2N6DuE> ActInf GuestStream 058.1 ~ Working with Gerald Edelman
- Cognitive systems
 - Competitive pressure within (neural Darwinism) and across (agent-niche Ecological, population Evolutionary).
 - Through improved temporal Prediction/Control, bounds of e.g. natural systems can be exceeded.
 - [Designing Ecosystems of Intelligence from First Principles](#) (Dec. 2022).
 - Hierarchical control in systems — lowest level regulator is in realtime and often continuous/analog. Then passing up to coordinator levels, at slower/deeper/larger timescales (tactical, logistical). On up through the strategic regulator looking outside and inside the systems, looking at things across multiple timescales, and making system-level decisions.
 - We are evolvable in that we can leverage existing (and slowly-changing) neural circuitry to implement more transient structural dynamical models.
 - Synthetic systems/time. In the Darwinian context, niche
 - Self-modeling, self-construction, self-domestication.
 - <https://press.princeton.edu/books/paperback/9780691232157/the-ecology-of-collective-behavior>

- Emergence (Chris Fields perspective).
- Natural, Artificial, Synthetic systems — “built from bottom up” — non-linear and multiscale systems. Many discontinuities, loops, etc.
- Through the lens of mental time travel.
 - And systems within systems, with different time concepts.
- Bobby Azarian "The Romance of Reality" covers a universal evolution principle
- <https://allpoetry.com/poem/14608180-The-Mental-Traveller-by-William-Blake> The Mental Traveller, William Blake. 'I must create a system, or be enslaved by another man's. I will not reason and compare: my business is to create.'
- <http://www.zakstein.org/publications.html>
- Cognitive [Patterns](#)
- Mapping dependencies for human/cultural systems. —
- Recognition of Beauty.
 - Embodied, Artistic, Technical, Analytic aspects of [Systems Science](#)
 - This has been highlighted in systems conferences!
-

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To-Do && To Discuss for #24 3

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In progress

Knowledge and Materials Transfer for [George Mobus](#), Educational Work

▼ Systems Census

1

In progress

Staying updated with the Systems Census

▼ Coda Education

1

In progress

Make Coda preparation and education materials

To add

-

#27 ~ 10/26/2023

ISSS Education meeting #27

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/uY0TSSVGfYA>

Notes

- Review 📅 #26 ~ 9/28/2023
- Ongoing 📁 Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions
 - 📖 Systems Language / sysXML (🛡️ George Mobus textbook and beyond).
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 - 📖 Systems Literacy
- ▼ Problem solving:
 - ▷ → Entailing building a model. Can this always be described as a graph? Any computable problem amenable to algorithmic analysis can be represented with graph
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 - ▷ <http://www.zakstein.org/publications.html>
 - ▷ Cognitive [Patterns](#)
- ▷ Mapping dependencies for human/cultural systems. —
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 - ▷ Embodied, Artistic, Technical, Analytic aspects of [Systems Science](#)
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To-Do && To Discuss for #24 4

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▼ Systems Science 2	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not started	Curriculum for Systems literacy

In progress

Knowledge and Materials Transfer for [George Mobus](#), Educational Work

▼ Systems Census

1

In progress

Staying updated with the Systems Census

▼ Coda Education

1

In progress

Make Coda preparation and education materials

To add

-

Gantt Chart view

Timeline of Ongoing To-Do

Timeline 2 of Ongoing To-Do

November 2024

Sunday	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday
27	28	29	30	31	01	02
03	04	05	06	07	08	09
10	11	12	13	14	15	16
17	18	19	20	21	22	23
24	25	26	27	28	29	30

More Notes

Getting things done view

Chapter	Section	Column 3	Notes	Page	Status
▼ 1 9	▼ 1 1	1 wwegweg	☰	📖 Curriculum	Not started
	▼ 2 3	1 wwegweg	☰	📖 GM Chapter 3	In progress
		2 fsdgdfgdf	☰	📖 GM Chapter 4	
		3 dfgdfgdf	☰		
	▼ 3 sdfsd	1		☰	
	▼ 4 dfgdfgdfg	1		☰	
	▼ 3	1 sdgsdg		☰	
		2 sfdgfgs		☰	
		3 sfdgdfgdf		☰	
	▼ 2 4	▼ 2		☰	
			☰		
▼ 1 dfbdfbd		1		☰	
▼ 2 sdgvsdfgsd		1		☰	

Table of Contents View

Chapter	Section	Column 3
▼ 1 9	▼ 1 1	1 wwegweg
	▼ 2 3	1 wwegweg
		2 fsdgdfgdf
		3 dfgdfgdf
	▼ 3 sdfsd	1
	▼ 4 dfgdfgdfg	1
	▼ 3	1 sdgsdg
		2 sfdgfgs

		3 sdfgdfgdf
▼	2 4	▼ 2
		▼ 1 dfbdfbd 1
		▼ 2 sgvdfgdsd 1

View of Getting things done view

▼	1 9	▼	2 4
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1

1 wweweg

Curriculum

Not started

1/5/2023

1/5/2023

Math

2

1 wweweg

GM Chapter 3

In progress

1/5/2023

Art Math ISSS

2

2 fsdgdfgdf

GM Chapter 4

1/5/2023

2

3 dfghdfgdf

3 sdfsdf

4 dfgdfgdfg

1 sdgsdg

2 sfdgfgs

3 sdfgdfgdf

1 dfbdfbd

2 sgvdfgdsd

Math View 2 of Getting things done view

Chapter	Section	Column 3	Notes	Page	Status

▼	1 2	▼ 1 ...	1	1 wwegweg	☰	📖 Curriculum	Not started
		▼ 2 ...	1	1 wwegweg	☰	📖 GM Chapter 3	In progress

2024

#28 ~ 1/19/2024

ISSS Education meeting #28

Meeting recording

- https://youtu.be/XkYbfs_9CA0

Notes

- Review 📅 2023
- ▼ Early 2023 discussions & emails ~
 - ▷ Organizational at 🌐 ISSS
 - ▷ 📖 [Systems Science](#), General Systems Theory (GST), and more.
- ▼ [Active Blockference](#)
 - ▷ 16 UTC on Mondays (8am PT).
 - ▷ Wednesday 10am PT (18 UTC) — Shingai plans for Systems Modeling SIG.
 - ▷ This meeting Fridays at 17 UTC — alternating
- ▼ 📖 [Systems Language / sysXML](#)
 - ▷ Shingai sharing:
 - ▷ <https://systemlanguage.notion.site/System-Language-84bf57e4fd6541269733bb8893ee84a4>
- ▼ Systems Modeling SIG
 - ▷ <https://www.issss.org/systems-modelling-and-systems-engineering/> — will change from “S Modeling and S Engineering” to just the Modeling — applies in 📖 [Systems Science](#) and Systems Engineering.
 - ▷ It was not very formal process for taking over a dormant SIG. Starting one, does have minimum thresholds.
- ▼ Tom's model
 - ▷ database can be converted into different form.
 - ▷ Enabling model-based collaboration.
 - ▷ <https://web3.issss.org/marzolf-aug2023/index.html>
 - ▷ more important longer term is to move forward in a “perfectable” idealistic design setting. Coherence.
 - ▷ Information put in, understanding in a context. Improve it in loop with feedback. Needing to catch & register the kinds of (primary, annotation, etc) data.
 - ▷ From capturing the information needed to develop a second model — the Systems Common model was constructed of notes.
- ▼ Systems Community Alliance — Archival
 - ▷ Being addressed in 🏠 [Crossover for EDU from KE](#)
- ▼ Planning
 - ▷ Business Motivation Model — Object Management Group. Building the model of a plan.
 - ▷ Diagram starting with a vision or ideal. Strategy, Tactics, etc. considered holistically as changes happen through time.
 - ▷ Tom took the spec from OMG and did a class model — plans as defined classes.
- ▷ Carlos Gershenson

- ▷ Modern Complexity
- ▷ Bacteria to Bach and Back — Dennett.
- ▷ <https://www.binghamton.edu/ssie/graduate/systems-science.html>
- ▷ <https://complexityexplained.github.io/>
- ▷

Agenda

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 - a. Add Notes and links above.
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To add

-

#29 ~ 2/2/2024

ISSS Education meeting #29

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/wsJCTQHK6TA>

Notes

- Begin recording
- @📧 2024 Projects

Agenda

1. Welcome & Introductions (anything to add before we begin recording?)
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To add

-

#30 ~ 2/23/2024

ISSS Education meeting #30

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/-mGnxOvkV9U>

Notes

- Begin recording
- 📁 2024 Projects

Agenda

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To add

-

Cognitive Systems Modeling

- The 🇩🇪 George Mobus textbook — kept neutral in terms of “What Knowledge Looks Like”.
 - It is nuts and bolts about e.g. Representation of the knowledge base.
- Hence the proposed concept of the knowledge base —

Figure 5.1 This is map of PROCESSES, not the Things.

- This may be related, or same, as what brain does (as systems modeler).
- People may develop Modeling Machines — with such characters, using digital, synthetic, quantum computation.
- Of the brain —
 - The participating neural circuits, which would be included within the boxes/etc, are distributed and dynamic.
 - For example here, the knowledgebase is about the function of encoding relevant information (in the mammal brain that is contained across regions — there is no 1:1 mapping with neuroanatomy).
 - Ray Jackendoff on Fundamentals of Language. He often talks about these functions of/how they work in Language production. Modularity. Systems representation.
 - → Back to Systemese, Language of Thought — As he goes into e.g. Lexical and Phrasal semantics — George sees this as where, when, how the linkage of meaning across multiple fields, actually operates. Envisions the Linguistics research program: How to bring the Neurolinguistic of RJ et al. together with the idea of, Where/How in the brain is the template for system boundary and flows.
- Recognizing something there that is informational — then building and modifying the cognitive structures of what is there and being learned.
- Believe: the evolution and development of the brain has already figured out how to encode realities into a model. That/Those world models, are used for pragmatic ends, being successful in live.
- What is means for us as society — we have a large-scale modeling capacity similar/analogous to brain. Thus we have the basis for a long-term sustained existence. And to fulfill a purpose of a sentient species, in maintaining a planet.
 - He has written of Gaia’s Mind, previous papers and presentations.
 -
 -
- Parcels.
 - <https://direct.mit.edu/netn/article/5/1/211/97535/Parcels-and-particles-Markov-blankets-in-the-brain>
 -
 -
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 -

#31 ~ 3/1/2024

ISSS Education meeting #31

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/b164by1zdtQ>

Notes

- Begin recording @ ASC-60_brochure_2024-02-12_web.pdf
- 📁 2024 Projects
- DC in June. ISSS & ASC

- Randall — INCOSE in July, Dublin — Tutorial; AI agents, semantic computing, bioinspired design. And alongside other activities.
 - Active Inference — [Generative Research Teams](#) — tools and frameworks from here.
 - Case studies in bio-inspired design & the transfer into Engineering for meeting aspirational goals, value-sensitive design.
 - Identified values, social norms, system design Requirements Engineering.
 - In leveling up skillsets of Systems Engineers. Concepts underlying the agents.
 - Bridging the knowledge gaps. And how/whether to bridge, without respecting, surveying, and mapping the gaps?
 - Wrapping these into toolkits and/or sets of discussion.
 - 🗣️ [Language Models](#) — interdisciplinary activity.
 - The Stream of Thought. The Stream of Words, words, words.
- Use cases:
 - Site remediation — AI agent for developing a strategy.
 - Ecological disaster, wildfire. Create unique conditions. Need to improve the responsivity
 - Autonomous vehicles
- Archiving [@Developing uses for ISSS Archives](#)
- Language & Life
 - Gordon Pask & Conversation theory, Interfaces — e.g. in different disciplines, Peace studies.
 - Cast and Extend — Dave Douglass is working on this code & front end.
 - Dave scanned & OCR'ed the 4 big works of Pask. And there is so much more in the archive, not scanned, not OCR, cross-references. English-German translation.
 - Also lots of work with the Spatial Web IEEE 2874 work, the communication layer. They are doing some details in some areas, however not all.
 - Languages of Interrogation & Command.
 - Adam Pease & SUMO has been helpful on some connections here.
 - Work on — SUMO + Active Inference Ontology + specialized command languages +
 - Mobile autonomy will require much more development on QUESTIONS and COMMANDS. From words on a

plane → into the capacity for exchanging/co-creating the programs on the fly, consistent with compliance.

- Active Inference + Cybernetics + Spatial Web
- Creating the contracts on the fly given context & certificates.
- There are amateur drones in the space. We have to coordinate among, between, and within. Now who is in position for what? Shall we instantiate that and communicate that?
- Logics of Commands — Pask references this very often. [eFLINT](#). Spatial Web, VERSES, IEEE working on HSML/HSTP.
- Readiness levels (social, natural).
 - Abstractions of policy in modeling.
 - Agents, Persona. Multi-mappings within the
-

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To add

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#32 ~ 3/22/2024

ISSS Education meeting #32

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/k65UVI87LY4>

Notes

- Begin recording @ ASC-60_brochure_2024-02-12_web.pdf
- 📁 2024 Projects
- DC in June. ISSS & ASC

- Engineer the knowledge before teaching it.
- Rob's trip to 🏠 Len Troncale office.
 - Working out an expeditious way to surface what has come before, with various Education and related Systems work. That is not as honorable as we could do it.

ActiveInferenceInstitute/ISSS

Owner: ActiveInferenceInstitute • Star count: 0 • Created: Fri, Mar 22, 2024

ISSS

 github.com

- .
- .

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To add

-

#33 ~ 4/12/2024

ISSS Education meeting #33

Meeting recording

-

Notes

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- 📁 2024 Projects
- DC in June. ISSS & ASC

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To add

-

#34 ~ 4/26/2024

ISSS Education meeting #34

Meeting recording

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Notes

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- 📁 2024 Projects
- DC in June. ISSS & ASC 📅 June 2024

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- <https://github.com/ActiveInferenceInstitute/ISSS>
- <https://www.incose.org/communities/working-groups-initiatives/natural-systems>
 - RxInfer
- ✍️ ISSS June 2024 Workshop for DC
- Randall — workshop for the systems engineers (July 6 in Dublin, Ireland).
 - What do they want to learn about?
 - Active Inference, and AI agents in systems engineering.
- What
- <https://zenodo.org/records/11062810> Aligning Spatial Web Terms to SUMO Creators — David Douglass
- .

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#35 ~ 5/17/2024

ISSS Education meeting #35

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/ZAi0n9wxrM0>

Notes

- Begin recording
- 📁 2024 Projects
- DC in June. ISSS & ASC 📅 June 2024
- Engineer the knowledge before teaching it.
- von Bertalanffy

Agenda

1. Welcome & Introductions (anything to add before we begin recording?)
 - a. Begin recording
2. Update and fine-tune 📄 Coda Education
3. Any news, updates, or questions about 📄 Education at 🌐 ISSS (📄 Participating in ISSS Education)
 - a. Add Notes and links above.
4. Review and work on (add, update, remove)

To add

-

#36 ~ 5/31/2024

ISSS Education meeting #36

Meeting recording

-

Notes

- Begin recording
- 📁 2024 Projects
- DC in June. ISSS & ASC 📅 June 2024
- Engineer the knowledge before teaching it.
- von Bertalanffy

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To add

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Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions

📅 Education 🗺️ Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions are areas/archetypes/patterns. There is much addition, lumping/splitting, and rearranging to be done! **Please make additions, edits, and comments as you see fit!**

Some 📅 Education Aspects & Initiatives are assigned to a particular Project or area, others are Unassigned (and therefore not actively being considered). If you want to get involved with any Project, or activate any of the Unassigned areas, let us know by comment here in the Coda, or email to education@iss.org

Education Aspects & Initiatives

Project	Single word	Name	Notes	Next step
▼ 🗺️ Crossover for EDU from KE 2	Videos	Video evaluation & improved presentation	📄	Currently being addressed by 🗺️ Crossover for EDU from KE
	Web	ISSS web presence as a hub for systems knowledge	📄	Currently being addressed by 🗺️ Crossover for EDU from KE
▼ 📅 Systems Science 1	Research	There is always a need for ongoing education about various systems theories and practices.	📄	
▼ 🗺️ Participating in ISSS Education 1	Onboarding	Logistical improvements to the ISSS Education effort to improve quality and quantity of engagement	📄	
▼ Unassigned 21	Adventures	Field trips to real Systems — Farm, prison, transit, factory, etc	📄	
	Applications	Training and case studies on applied Systems approaches	📄	
	Bridges	Building better bridges and ties with external organizations and institutions	📄	
	Cities	Beverly Pasian — Smart cities, Projects and quality of life. Development of curriculum.	📄	
	Consulting	Intellectual gap in management scholarship & practice related to Systems	📄	
	Crises	Raise awareness & action related to critical global situations (e.g. energy, climate, sustainability, peace, attention)	📄	
	Games	Generate systems games	📄	
	Health	Personal and Systemic Health	📄	
	Intergenerational	Connections among ages	📄	
	Mentorship	Mentorship, Facilitation, Apprenticeship	📄	
	Neighborhoods		📄	
Participation	Co-creation, Community practices, engagement, Diversity, Equity, Inclusion	📄		

Platforms	Connections via platforms (e.g. Discord)		
Projects	Learning by doing, on co-creative projects		
Readings	Core reading list — Curation and presentation of papers		
SIG	Education SIG		Determine the status of current relevant SIG
Standards			
Symposia	Symposia and events		
Trainings	Course materials & trainings. Teacher trainings.		
Visualization	Developing visualizations to convey various concepts and dynamic ideas		
Youth	Connecting with young people. Schools, doctoral students.		

....

Educational planning criteria, for different familiarities/ages.

Jessie Henshaw, [@Gerald R Midgley](#) — Natural systems in context, systems with indeterminate behavior

Peter — Systems Literacy.

Rob Young

[@Patrick Hoverstadt](#)

assume you are already aware of this:

<https://www.instituteforapprenticeships.org/apprenticeship-standards/systems-thinking-practitioner/>

the standard was built on the SCiO systems competency framework:

<https://www.systemspractice.org/page/scio-competency-framework-professional-qualification>

this is available to anyone and for those in England it is a government subsidised programme available here:

<https://cherithsimmons.co.uk/level-7-system-thinking-practitioner-apprenticeship/>

Happy to discuss so as to not reinvent already turning wheels if that would help?

@Michael C Jackson Here are details of a course in 'critical systems thinking' that we have finally got together and will run from October. It may be of interest to ISSS members and I'm open to collaboration. <https://www.thecsi.io/introductoryprogram>

@Dave Snowden We have a broad range of training materials in the field of naturalising sense-making/anthro-complexity and an operation to support that - happy to look at collaboration. We've also run research seminars for academics linked to the [EU Field Guide](#) and distributed ethnography/abductive research. Doing that in Melbourne at the end of the month and Hull later in the year. There are also a large number of Universities who are members of the Centre and use the tools for research at all levels

Crossover for EDU from KE

Ongoing project

https://coda.io/d/ISSS-Knowledge-Engineering_dPEy1CASvfl/Knowledge-Engineering-Overview_suNUS#_IusHe

Metadata for each resource (table from Knowledge Engineering)

 Not synced yet

Type	Name of Field	Example	Notes
▼ Full resource 1	Full data		
▼ Metadata 10	Link		
	Title		
	Type of resource		
	Metadata		
	Ownership		
	Rights		
	Access		
	Responsibilities		
	Ontology tags	Terms such as Systems	
	Identifiers	DOI, ISBN, etc	
▼ Template 1	Template type	Person, Resource, Software, Theory	
▼ Scholarship 1	Summaries		

Open Letter to ISSS members and beyond

 Daniel Ari Friedman

[@R. Don Peel, P.Geo](#)

“We cannot solve our problems with the same thinking we used when we created them.” Albert Einstein

“What we call science is a very narrow patriarchal project for a very short period of history” Vandana Shiva

These two quotes lead one to question, how well is the mainstream education system faring in aligning thinking patterns with systems sciences or more holistic approaches to learning?

The roots of mainstream education can be traced back to when Horace Mann introduced the Prussian model to America in 1852. By 1918, the USA adopted the educational framework Nationwide. It appears the intention of the Prussian model was to unify the social values of a national community by educating everyone under a common curriculum, developed by the national authority. Today, that model of learning has spread to encompass most of the global populations. The rationale for using this model are linked to developing social stability, civic virtue, meritocracy, economic efficiency, social mobility, and freedom.

However, resistance to this top-down curricula development approach came in the forms of alternative education, such as Waldorf (1919), Montessori (1911 in USA) and homeschooling. Instead of developing common knowledge dictated by an authority, these approaches instill more freedom of thought by allowing individuals to tap into their own innate talents and enhance those abilities. Sir Ken Robinson’s, “Do schools kill creativity?” (one of the most viewed TED Talks), and the RSA Animate of Robinson’s perspective “Changing Education Paradigms” are worthy analyses to consider in assessing how a common top-down approach versus a freedom of thought or knowledge diversity approach, supports systems thinking.

Most professional associations are governed by people educated through the mainstream institutions, especially educational professionals who perpetuate the mainstream approach. Some institutions are recognizing the need to integrate more interdisciplinary course work to break down the subject/disciplinary, siloed/reductionist approach to learning. Some teachers are spending large amounts of time and energy in attempting to tie together different subjects, from math to language, to make them more meaningful to the students. Such approaches still alienate students from their innate abilities. From an economic efficiency standpoint, it is better for society to dictate and direct the types of career paths that draw the highest earnings. From this approach the careers in medicine, law, and accounting are eagerly sought by people interested in achieving prosperous and powerful positions. It has become apparent the ecosystems of the world are under threat under this career paradigm, which gave rise to the notion of “sustainable development”. Sustainable development depends on a more holistic or systems science approach as it relies on the balancing of social, economic and environmental values in all development decisions.

The global response to achieve sustainable development has been stalled by the economic-driven mindset of the policy and curricula developers, as witnessed in the wave of cognitive dissonance actions by most modern day civilians. The COVID-19 pandemic allowed many global ecosystems to restore or regenerate after the industrial complex was slowed down by the worldwide lockdowns. Improved air quality was witnessed globally. Students were obliged to learn from family members or school via online platforms.

In Canada, the Truth and Reconciliation initiative has shaken Canadian society to the core. Revealing the history of the Indigenous Peoples, related to the development of Canada, have enlightened many Canadians that the foundational democratic process in nation building, was far from being democratic. The Indian Act (1876) basically forced all indigenous peoples to assimilate into Eurocentric values without input or consent to such a policy. Residential schools are now a legacy of genocide leaving a historical festering wound on democratic development. How different are residential schools and current public schools in their approach in propagating democratic processes? The commonality of both is to assimilate students into a value system that has been deemed the best for society. Students with more freedom to engage in local community building, instead of saddled with the parameters of school confinement, would be an approach that allows a more democratic involvement of all members of society. Can society adopt a more systems sciences to trigger holistic concepts, such as sustainable development, under the framework of a career-orientated, patriarchal mindset?

Coincidentally, the values the Indigenous peoples lived by for hundreds of generations, are reflected in the United Nations sustainable development framework. Basically, sustainable development or “Traditional Knowledge” are a systems science approach to knowledge development. In Canada, the recommendations of Truth and Reconciliation initiative include changing curricula by calling “upon the federal, provincial, and territorial governments, in consultation and collaboration with Survivors, Aboriginal peoples, and educators to:

- I. Make age-appropriate curriculum on residential schools, Treaties, and Aboriginal peoples’ historical and contemporary contributions to Canada a mandatory education requirement for Kindergarten to Grade Twelve students.
- II. Provide the necessary funding to post-secondary institutions to educate teachers on how to integrate Indigenous knowledge and teaching methods into classrooms.
- III. Provide the necessary funding to Aboriginal schools to utilize Indigenous knowledge and teaching methods in classrooms.
- IX. Establish senior-level positions in government at a deputy minister level or higher dedicated to Aboriginal content in education” (Wilson-Raybould 2022).

As a practicing “professional geoscientist”, with two Master degrees focused on sustainable development, I have corresponded with a message to my professional association to consider assessing the educational system of a possible need for an educational paradigm shift to respond to the increasing current global concerns, especially pertaining to the professions of geoscience. The concerns are definitely linked to the current human modus operandi with their effects on nature (Peel 2022). My messages have been responded to and sidelined as a responsibility or role beyond the mandate of the Association.

This begs the question, can the International Society of Systems Sciences use these recommendations and the emerging educational movement to “project-based learning” (e.g. Moonshot Incubator), as leverage in influencing and promoting primary learning techniques (K-12) that support the evolution of systems sciences? How can the public educational component get the attention, the subject requires, at June’s ISSS Annual Conference?

References

- Moonshot Incubator. (2016). Moonshot Incubator & Moonshot Laboratory Trailer. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RMETH9d7vAg>
- Peel, D. (2022). Student Motivated Education. E-Tips. Creston Valley Advance, September 14, 2022 edition, <https://www.crestonvalleyadvance.ca/opinion/e-tips-student-motivated-education/>
- Robinson, K. (2007). Do schools kill creativity? <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iG9CE55wbtY>
- RSA Animate (2010). Changing Education Paradigms. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zDZFcdGpL4U&t=13s>
- Wilson-Raybould, J. (2022). True Reconciliation: How to Be a Force for Change. McClelland & Stewart. Canada.

Transformative Education

<https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-981-19-3258-8>

- 2022
- Transformative Education for Regeneration and Wellbeing

A Critical Systemic Approach to Support Multispecies Relationships and Pathways to Sustainable Environments

- [Janet J. McIntyre-Mills,](#)
- [Yvonne Corcoran-Nantes](#)

📎 [978-981-19-3258-8.pdf](#)

📎 [978-981-19-3258-8.epub](#)

Curriculum

- .
- .
- [@Lynn Rasmussen](#) —
 - In area of system literacy.
 - Come back when the release date is known.
 - This content may facilitate webinar and short talk (modular descriptions).
-

Systems Census

Frontend of Site:

https://coda.io/d/Systems-Education-Interface_ds_yfXJ8UY/Home_subW9#_luqEQ

[Link to take survey](#)

Systems Census Form

Who is completing this form?

Name and email address if relevant. This information will not be shared in public, the only contact information shared publicly will be that provided for the Organization/Program below.

What is the name of the Organization offering the Program?

What is the Organization's phone number?

What is the Organization's mailing address?

What is the Organization's contact email address?

What is the Organization's website?

What is the name of the Program?

What is the contact email for the Program?

What type of Program is it, in terms of emphasis and structure?

What is the length, intensity, and frequency of the Program?

Does completion of the Program provide any type of certification or degree?

How many students are enrolled in the Program per year?

How many teachers/educators are in the Program?

What are prerequisites of the Program?

What are completion requirements of the Program?

What skills do graduates learn or develop in?

What job opportunities are projected for those who complete the Program?

What educational methods and practices are used in the Program?

Does the Program or Organization offer any consulting services?

What is the total estimated financial cost of the Program in US dollars?

Are financing options available for the Program?

What is the primary language of instruction of the Program?

To what extent are computers/programming used or required in the Program?

Optional: What educational resources are used in the Program?

▼ Systems Education Form ~ Results

Distribution	Distribution version	Who is completing th	Organization Name	Organization mailing
<input type="checkbox"/>	3/2/2023 11:55:02 AM	Tom Flanagan	Inst. 21st Century Agoras 2	Trflanagan@aol.com
<input type="checkbox"/>	3/2/2023 2:39:20 PM	ray.ison@open.ac.uk	The Open University (UK)	Walton Hall, Milton Keynes, MK7 6AA UK
<input type="checkbox"/>	3/3/2023 5:25:16 AM	umpleby@gmail.com	George Washington University	Dept. of Management, GWU, Wash. DC 20052
<input type="checkbox"/>	3/3/2023 5:34:21 AM	Applied systemics thinking	Systemic Development Associates	5 Argyle Street, Vincentia NSW Australia 2540

Optional: provide a selected list of publications by Program educators.

Optional: provide a selected list of research programs conducted in the Program

Optional: provide a selected list of publications or topics by Program students.

Do you have any other information to provide, or questions for the organizers of this form?

Submit

3/5/2023 3:00:55 PM

Sophie Georgiou / gs@goaisetting.eu

HSSS

University Pireaus
Themistokleio
Building
Mastering Program
CSAP
17 str, Kyra tis Ro
18451 Nikaia -
Greece

3/9/2023 11:21:32 AM

Wayne Wakeland

Portand State
University

not needed

3/13/2023 11:35:23 AM

Organizers@complexityadventures.com

Complexity
Adventures

false

Gerald Midgley
g.r.midgley@hull.ac.uk

Centre for Systems
Studies, University
of Hull

Cottingham Road,
Hull, East Yorkshire,
HU6 7RX, UK

false

Rajneesh Chowdhury
(R.Chowdhury.1@bham.ac.uk)

Birmingham
Leadership Institute
(University of
Birmingham, UK)

University of
Birmingham,
Edgbaston,
Birmingham, B15
2TT, UK

Editorial Interface ~ Systems Education Form

Distribution	Distribution version	Time completed	Who is completing this	Verified?	Status	Organization Name	Organization mailing	Organization phone n	Organization email
<input type="checkbox"/>	3/2/2023 11:55:02 ...	3/2/2023 11:55:02 ...	Tom Flanagan	Unverified	Mostly complete	Inst. 21st Century Agoras 2	Trflanagan@aol.com	5508-264-0066	Trflanagan@aol.com
<input type="checkbox"/>	3/2/2023 2:39:20 ...	3/2/2023 2:39:20 ...	ray.ison@open.ac.uk	Unverified	Mostly complete	The Open University (UK)	Walton Hall, Milton Keynes, MK7 6AA UK	https://www.open.ac.uk/contact	martin.reynolds@open.ac.uk
<input type="checkbox"/>	3/3/2023 5:25:16 AM	3/3/2023 5:25:16 AM	umpleby@gmail.com	Unverified	Mostly Incomplete	George Washington University	Dept. of Management, GWU, Wash. DC 20052	571-305-0085	umpleby@gmail.com
<input type="checkbox"/>	3/3/2023 5:34:21 A...	3/3/2023 5:34:21 A...	Applied systemics ...	Unverified	Mostly complete	Systemic Development Associates	5 Argyle Street, Vincentia NSW Australia 2540	+614518528165	sda@besystems.com
<input type="checkbox"/>	3/5/2023 3:00:55 ...	3/5/2023 3:00:55 ...	Sophie Georgiou / gsc	Unverified	Mostly complete	HSSS	University Pireaus Themistokleio Building Mastering Program CSAP 17 str, Kyra tis Ro 18451 Nikaia - Greece	0030 6940022366	csap@hsss.gr
<input type="checkbox"/>	3/9/2023 11:21:32 ...	3/9/2023 11:21:32 ...	Wayne Wakeland	Unverified	Mostly complete	Portland State University	not needed	503-880-0613	wakeland@psu.edu

<input type="radio"/>	3/13/2023 11:35:23...	3/13/2023 11:35:23...	Organizers@complex	Unverified	Mostly complete	Complexity Adventures			Hello@ComplexAdventures.c
<input type="radio"/>	false	3/16/2023 11:53:29...	Gerald Midgley g.r...	Unverified	Mostly complete	Centre for Systems Studies, University of Hull	Cottingham Road, Hull, East Yorkshire, HU6 7RX, UK	+(0)1482 466311	g.r.midgley@hull.ac.uk
<input type="radio"/>	false	3/24/2023 2:16:02 ...	Rajneesh Chowdh...	Unverified	Mostly complete	Birmingham Leadership Institute (University of Birmingham, UK)	University of Birmingham, Edgbaston, Birmingham, B15 2TT, UK	0121 414 3344	bl@bham.ac.uk

FOR DISTRIBUTION (Systems Education Interface)

FOR DISTRIBUTION ~ Systems Education Form

Organization Name	Organization mailing :	Organization phone n	Organization email	Organization website	Program name	Program contact ema	Program type	Program length/inten	Program i
Inst. 21st Century Agoras 2	Trflanagan@aol.com	5508-264-0066	✉ Trflanagan@aol.com	🌐	Structured Democratic Dialogue Training	✉ Trflanagan@aol.com	Group support for abductive systems thinking	5 days	Access to communi
The Open University (UK)	Walton Hall, Milton Keynes, MK7 6AA UK	https://www.open.ac.uk/contact	✉ martin.reynolds@open.ac.uk	🌐	Systems Thinking in Practice (STIP)	✉ martin.reynolds@open.ac.uk	Post Graduate	Not specified	PG Cert; MSc
George Washington University	Dept. of Management, GWU, Wash. DC 20052	571-305-0085	✉ umpleby@gmail.com	🌐		✉ umpleby@gmail.com	publications by Stuart Umpleby		
Systemic Development Associates	5 Argyle Street, Vincentia NSW Australia 2540	+614518528165	✉ sda@besystemics.com	🌐	Applied Systemics Thinking	✉ sda@besystemics.com	Experiential Blended Learning	Standard Course 8 Weeks	Certificat completic

HSSS	University Pireaus Themistokleio Building Mastering Program CSAP 17 str, Kyra tis Ro 18451 Nikaia - Greece	0030 6940022366	csap@hsss.gr		Certified Systemic Analyst Professional	an@hsss.eu	According to my experience the program today offers "Systemic Awareness" only in Gr And a small science of a mininum anorganised surface level of systemic thinking education. That is why tuition fees are so low It is time to get deeper in terms of structure. For me it is important to give empasis on the mindset and examine : "How migh we change the behaviors" & "Which mindset and structure are needed it for that ;" so as to align with further society needs or give the chance to some students to dive deeper in system sciences	Yes it doe It gives : (of System Profesion some cas Certificat Lisence ir
------	---	-----------------	--	---	--	--	---	--

Portand State University	not needed	503-880-0613	wakeland@pdx.edu		Systems Science Program	wakeland@pdx.edu	graduate degrees, certificates & systems minor	Phd 5+ years, MS 2 yrs, certs 1 yr	see above
Complexity Adventures			Hello@ComplexityAdventures.com">Hello@ComplexityAdventures.com		Complexity Adventures	Hello@ComplexityAdventures.com">Hello@ComplexityAdventures.com	Learning by Doing, event-based cohort	Weekend synchronous activities, with pre- Summit events	No

Centre for Systems Studies, University of Hull	Cottingham Road, Hull, East Yorkshire, HU6 7RX, UK	+ (0)1482 466311	g.r.midgley@hull.ac.uk	PhD Systems Science	doctoralcollege@hull.ac.uk	Research-orientated PhD, with just a small handful of generic taught courses.	Three years full-time, with one extra writing-up year if necessary; or five years part-time, with two extra writing up years if necessary. Most supervision is done electronically, and you can live anywhere in the UK. However, we can no longer take students living overseas, unless they are willing to come to the UK for their studies.	PhD
Birmingham Leadership Institute (University of Birmingham, UK)	University of Birmingham, Edgbaston, Birmingham, B15 2TT, UK	0121 414 3344	bli@bham.ac.uk	MSc/Lt Systems Thinking and Leadership Practitioner	bli@bham.ac.uk	Systems thinking, leadership practice, attention/perception	2.5 years. Repeats every year.	PGDip, L7 Apprentic

Census Copypasta

Would it be possible for you to add the details of each of these programs (missing values are OK), [via the form](#), or by referring a knowledgeable person [to this page](#)?

Because the programs sound good & it would be best to have the full information entered by someone directly.

If you are ever available, we have weekly meetings on Thursdays at 11am PT (I can add you to a calendar event if you want), talking about this project & open to input/contributions.

Survey Questions

Starting with [1985 document](#) questions, then we can develop further, and send (with letter) to

☑ [Systems Organizations, Universities, Programs](#) .

- Test the survey on sample — get their feedback on response to questions.
 - Will update after the survey beta testing is live.
- Long-term contact for the survey is education@isss.org .

Systems Education Survey

Area		Question data	Questions asked as
▼ Survey meta-data	2	Completed by....	Who is completing this survey?
		Date completed	Autofilled
▼ Organization information	5	Organization name	What is the name of the Organization?
		Organization mailing address	What is the Organization's mailing address?
		Organization phone number	What is the Organization's phone number?
		Organization contact email	What is the Organization's contact email address?
		Public link	What is the Organization's website?
▼ Program information	19	Program name	What is the name of the Program?
		Program contact email	What is the contact email for the Program?
		Program type	What type of Program is it, in terms of emphasis and structure?
		Location	Is the Program local, all-online, or hybrid?
		Department	What department or sector is the Program, within the Organization?
		Program length/intensity	What is the length and intensity of the Program?
		Associated certifications and/or degrees	Does completion of the Program provide any type of certification or degree?
		Number of Students per year	How many students are enrolled in the Program per year?
		Number of Teachers	How many teachers/educators are in the Program?
		Pre-requisites	What are prerequisites of the Program?
		Completion requirements	What are completion requirements of the Program?
		Skills of Graduates	What skills do graduates learn or develop in?
		Projected Job Opportunities	What job opportunities are projected for those who complete the Program?

		Methods	What educational methods and practices are used in the Program?
		Consulting Programs	Does the Program offer any consulting services?
		Program cost and financing information	What is the cost of the Program?
		Program cost and financing information	Are financing options available for the Program?
		Language of program	What is the primary language of instruction of the Program?
		Computational basis	To what extent are computers/programming used or required in the Program?
▼ Extra resource collection	5	Resources used	What educational resources are used in the Program?
		Selected List of Publications by Faculty	Optional: provide a selected list of publications by Program educators.
		Selected List of Research Programs Conducted	Optional: provide a selected list of research programs conducted in the Program
		Selected List of Dissertation/Thesis/Essay Topics	Optional: provide a selected list of publications or topics by Program students.
		Any other information to add?	Do you have any other information to provide?

Survey Outreach Copy

Getting to understand the landscape of Systems Education Programs

Hello,

This email is being sent out as a “Systems Education Census” project from [ISSS](#) and being provided as service to the broader Systems community.

Anecdotally, there is a strong sentiment shared in the Systems Science community that our Educational offerings are not as accessible, rigorous, discoverable, or integrated as we would like them to be.

To this end, the goal of this Census is to **increase the visibility of various Systems Education programs around the world**. Responses to the survey are viewable at the [interactive interface here](#), and when you add your program in, the information will be available at the public site pending confirmation (note: *this is a work in progress as of March 2023, and being sent out to ISSS members for initial populating*).

Listing of your Systems Educational Program (whether it is in an academic institution, or other organization) will increase its visibility with those who are interested in learning, and therefore contribute to a vibrant and accessible Systems community.

Here is the [link to take the survey](#).

We would deeply appreciate your response to the survey, and forwarding along of this message to anyone else who you'd like to see represented.

With any questions or comments, please contact us at education@iss.org

Thank you,

ISSS Education

-
- ISSS members
 - Social media
 - Target [Systems Organizations, Universities, Programs](#)

Systems Organizations, Universities, Programs

Add:

<https://help.cabreraresearch.org/what-are-good-phd-programs-in-systems-or-systems-thinking>

Systems Education Programs

Name	Country	Link	Type of Program	Notes	Contact	Category
Portland State University	USA		MS, PhD			
Open University	UK		MSc			
AFSCET	France					
University of Hull Centre for Systems Studies	UK					
Binghamton University	USA		Graduate certificate, Ms, PhD			
Cornell University	USA		PhD			
University of Michigan	USA		Graduate certificate			
University of Ottawa	USA		Ms			
Systems Innovation						
Sante Fe Institute						
System Dynamics Society						
Complexity Adventures	Online		Community of practice			

- Many programs

- MIT has program for teaching systems, in grammar school. Jay Forester. They've had a series of conference with teachers, series of papers on teaching systems — This is the "Creative Learning Exchange". <http://www.clexchange.org/>
- Peter Senge — Compassionate Systems — International Baccalaureate schools.
- Systems Biology Institute in Washington.
- General conundrum — no single "theory" to point to.
 - e.g. at Hull — why not taught in college? No [Systems Science](#) that is a consensus.
- Australian National University, and Rutgers, and a group in Paris — Held a workshop on "Ethics and Algorithms", [@Peter D Tuddenham](#) went to some.
 - Relationship between Cybernetics and Systems came to the fore.
 - Area of Algorithms and Ethics, hot/important topic, demands a Systems perspective.
- <https://arxiv.org/abs/2212.01354> Designing Ecosystems of Intelligence from First Principles. — December 2022.
 - Connections with Cybernetics.
- Portland
- ..

<https://www.isss.org/education/> —

•

View of University Systems Program

Name	Country	Link	Type of Program	Notes	Contact
Portland State University	USA				
Open University	UK				
AFSCET	France				
University of Hull Centre for Systems Studies	UK				
Binghamton University	USA				
Cornell University	USA				
University of Michigan	USA				
University of Ottawa	USA				
Systems Innovation					
Sante Fe Institute					
System Dynamics Society					

Complexity
Adventures

Online

Community of
practice

Alexander Lazlo ~ Letter of advice for Systems learners

Hi _____ !

How nice to hear from you. And great to hear that you are completing your bachelor's studies and moving on with great momentum straight into graduate studies! There are a few social systems change management/leadership type programs that I can recommend, though some are more oriented to doctoral studies while other offer good master's programs as well.

So, if I understand correctly, you are searching for programs of higher education that combine a focus on pragmatic skill sets with a more systemic (wholistic and integral) approach, like you found at CIIS, for example. Okay, so here's what I'd recommend. By way of background to my recommendation, I should say that my perspective derives from the graduate program I designed, implemented, and directed for four years. I can't remember if I told you about that, but it was in the area of *Leadership and Systemic Innovation* here in Argentina at the Buenos Aires Institute of Technology (ITBA). Although I am no longer associated with that program or involved with that institute, I designed the program to foster systemic innovation in socio-technical systems in ways that empower and engage both. As a colleague of mine, Dino Karabeg, put it so well recently, the idea behind the program was to move from a focus on things like Big Data, to a timely engagement with dynamic information ecosystems through Smart Data, and eventually to the Smart Systems that express the deepest potential of networked evolutionary learning ecosystems (ELCs). To do so, we recognized the need to *be the systems we want to see in the world*, as they saying goes. Accordingly, the six areas of focus of the program I designed were:

- Systems Thinking
- Collective Intelligence
- Empathetic Learning
- Intrepid Spirit
- Design Thinking
- Experimental Prototyping

There are a couple of programs in Europe that are interesting and nearer to you than CIIS. One of them relates to the Bertalanffy Center for the Study of Systems Science, of which I am President. You can find information on our offer at the following URL:

- <http://www.bcscss.org/research/grants-and-prizes/ludwig-von-bertalanffy-phd-scholarship/>

Another one is at the systems program of the University of Hull in England. They have a Centre for Systems Studies and a focus area on "Systems Thinking, Cybernetics, Complexity, Problem Structuring & Information Systems" that's interesting. You can find out more here —

- <https://www.hull.ac.uk/work-with-us/research/groups/centre-for-systems-studies>

There a general list of academic resources, programs and options that is more or less maintained on the ISSS website here —

- <https://www.iss.org/students/>

In addition, you may wish to check out Saybrook University (<https://www.saybrook.edu/academic-affairs/areas/olt>) and I suppose you've already explored the offer at CIIS (

<http://www.ciis.edu/academics/graduate-programs/transformative-leadership/about-the-program>) - both of which have several programs in systems thinking and related studies.

There are other programs elsewhere in the world, but many of these that I've listed above allow you to study "at a distance" with only occasional "residential conferences" once or twice a year that you must attend.

I hope this helps you in your exploration of possible pathways for your graduate studies.

Cheers,

~ *Alexander Laszlo*

ISSS Education Services

Herospace

Coda Education

- Coda 101
 - Introduction to Coda — How to use it.
 - Pricing & Use
 - Features
 - Functionality
 - Within a page
 - Roles of Outlining
 - Within a document
 - ..
 - Across documents
 - ..
 - Coda and.....
 - Gantt chart
 - Accessibility
 - Augmentation & Time
 - 2 minutes
 - 25 minutes
 - Day — 90 minutes.
 - Month
 - Augmentations and Integrations.
 - OpenAI
 - Websites (standalone, and embed/subdomain).
 - Educational use cases for Coda
 - Courses —
 - Book → Curriculum Syllabus → Production of presentations and problem-project pedagogy
 - [George Mobus](#) working on the Master's Level course curriculum (his books, and complementary/extending materials).
 - Institute
 - Santa Fe Institute
 - Ontology
 - Transcription
 - Curation
 - Summarization
 - Publishing

Towards a Common Core

What information to onboard to Towards a Common Core

- Videos?
 - <https://youtu.be/FdWaDqMfnwk>
- Project charter/catechism?

Gary Smith

- Yesterday there was an event, ~23 educators, sySTEAM, Gary, Daniel, Jen, others. The talks were recorded, not the roundtable <https://youtu.be/FdWaDqMfnwk>. It was a scene-setting event and evaluating people's level of interest.
- We have some ideas on working with sySTEAM and a variety of ideas came forth for concrete.
 - Paper — Position on ? Education ? Candidate laws ?
 - [Education](#) materials for School ages.
 - [Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions](#)
- Apparent — Enthusiasm at the table, could mean that the deliverables could expand beyond the core = Scope/Mission Creep.
 - We want to have an inclusive and participatory space where people can contribute what/how/when they want, to the “Core” (which can have different versioning and manifestations) and what is not in the core.
- Caitlyn Singam added valuable comments and questions about the MoU.
- Creative Commons —
 - Someone could make a commercial product on it, with attribution.
- “Towards a common core for systems education”
 - The project is anchored in a bilateral agreement between INCOSE and ISSS.
 - Then could be secondary MoU with other stakeholders or bodies.
- Next steps 8-31-2023 —
 - Jen and Gary are reviewing the ISSS-INCOSE MoU in the coming days, revising and agreeing.
 - With the MoU we could then proceed with synchronous + asynchronous collaboration.
 - It is a conversation with Caitlyn about ways of working, sySTEAM processes
 - [Education](#) :: INCOSE : sySTEAM
 - [Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions](#)
-

Systems Literacy

- For Peter, it is on the agenda to curate and compile what has been done with [🔗 Systems Literacy](#) .
- Lynn's field guide, working with Peter, coming out of the ISSS 2018 conference.
- <https://networkliteracy.org/>

Questions

@joe velikovsky explored these questions here: <https://on-writing.blogspot.com/2024/08/on-systems-education.html>
(August 15, 02024)

ISSS Education ~ Questions

Question	Notes	Tags	Text
What are the five most important things each participant thinks to consider, to advance the value of ISSS learning among its members or separately among the public at large?	☰	Grounding	
How to get all ages involved in Education?	☰		
How to get all time zones & global regions involved in Systems learning and applying?	☰		
Who needs systems theory and is prepared to put in a minimum effort to learn something new?	☰	Audience	
How are people learning at the moment?	☰	Alignment	
What could we do to positively influence the system?	☰	Outcomes	
How can the ISSS make systems science ideas and material more surveyable?	☰	functionality	
What does Systems Education bring to those who feel like they work in narrow, boring, disciplinary, specific, or situational tasks?	☰	Value Proposition	
What does Systems Education bring to those who feel like their work is chaotic, overwhelming, transdisciplinary, multifaceted, and wide open?	☰	Value Proposition	
What is the role of ISSS?	☰	Alignment	
What materials can be provided to teachers in different situations?	☰	Alignment	
How can Systems education be aligned with teacher training courses?	☰	Alignment	
Who do we want to teach?	☰	Audience	
By thinking of learning as a system of practice with feedback loops into deeper learning, how can we help individuals prime the pump?	☰	functionality	
Education Strategy. What is the strategy for education that will be used to guide this work?	☰	Grounding	
What can we borrow from other projects / other work that will make this eaier?	☰	Alignment	

Systems Tools, Courses, Resources, Organizations

From [@Shirley Bekins](#)

Resources/tools/skills: There are many online resources and tools. I enjoyed Omidyar's Systems Practice course (free), Sterman's Business Dynamics textbook also the course materials and some lectures are available at MIT opencourseware. I know you're already well-versed in the systems theory canon of works so won't repeat.

Skills/tools: Systems dynamics modeling platforms accessible without advanced mathematics

Continued: Stella, Vensim, etc.

Agent-based modelling esp in Netlogo,

Game theory

Also: Engineering for a Safer World, Systems Thinking Applied to Safety by Nancy G. Leveson. Recommended by a scholar as a useful framework to apply to AI systems, specifically written for critical safety systems. I'm reading to apply the framework to the Rainier Valley section of the Sound Transit light rail system in Seattle, an at-grade rail section with a large number of deaths/accidents/near misses!

From [@Gary Smith](#) [SystemMystery](#) [@Games](#)

 [SystemMystery game-2016.07.24_ISSSV2.pptx](#)

See file from [@Scott Jackson](#)

ISSS Education Topics

Definition of System

INCOSE Baseline Definition

Characteristics

Parts

Interactions

Emergence

Types

Real

Conceptual

Mathematical

ISSS Baseline Definition

Why Baselines Should be Different

ISSS Baseline Suitable for Scientific Investigation

Differences from INCOSE Baseline

Delete Mode of Description from INCOSE definition

Not a useful concept

Add Hierarchy

Cited by Bertalanffy

Property of all systems

Not limited to real systems

Concept of Non-Systems

Properties of Non-Systems

Lack at least one characteristic

Why study non-systems

To show their value

Problematique

What is our Problem?

World-Wide Problems

Hunger

War

Etc

Systems Science

- “Systems”
 - Any time we have more than 1 thing, it is easy to say System.
 - In [Systems Science](#) we are looking for what is true and rigorous, about Systems.
 - Search for classes “Systems” (e.g. at [UDC](#))
 - Operating System — Functional composition of what you want it to do. Few people are looking as e.g. OS as Hierarchy, Network. Thus there are analyses that do not get done.
 - George’s approach: Bringing the principles into play, understand the properties/systemness of the OS — then it can be linked to experiences in people’s lives.
 - Hence, any area of study where they are working on a System (e.g. Food system, Nursing system). — Then what aspects of Systemness are being considered.
 - [Systems Science](#) as a discipline (as a meta-discipline). Then people can apply more broadly to what is called ____ Systems.
 - A Systems Scientist — as consultants called in to other areas, as part of team/business environment. Then can go into other Sciences, other areas — “we think we have a system” here, if something
 - <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41562-019-0626-2> What happened to cognitive science?
 - Volk <https://www.amazon.com/Metapatterns-Across-Space-Time-Mind-ebook/dp/B0753M84Z2>
 - Pattern Language for Cognitive Science/Security <https://coda.io/@aien/cogsec-atlas/patterns-26>
-
- Cart & Horse...
- [Systems Science](#) as a discipline
 - And this is to the point of what having an ISSS is about.
- IFSR conversation in 3/2023 & Many other notes here and elsewhere — George; futures among Systems ramifications/subdisciplines will be perilous without consilience/consolidation. We are not on a path of effectiveness of “Systems Anything” without reconciliation among these different manifestations.
- Carries over more broadly into the area of Education — Cybernetics is embedded within [Systems Science](#), it is not a separate topic.
- There is also a political aspect on this, it is frustrating.
 - 1950’s — “Continental” (philosophical) and/vs. “American” versions (nuts and bolts), also other research trajectories weaving in and out.
 - Maps, lineages of research, to the core of some’s frustrations: conversations on the stage and in the room, with political view on what Systems Science was about → Leading Peter into the Systems Literacy journey.
- On the plus side, there are developments coming from the outside, of extant [Systems Science](#) specific institutions. There are people working in integrative approaches to understanding, so there can be hope that some popularizing work can reinvigorate traditional societies.
- Federations of Similarities/Dissimilarities, Shared action, Commons, etc.
- Ensure clear thinking on different topic areas.
- Capra Course — “Systems View Of” (Life) as opposed to “Systems Science”, “Thinking”, “Change” —
 - So in ISSS course development, considerations of course For, audience, topics.
- Differences in world’s peoples approaches towards learning and being systematic/systemic. How these knowledge traditions are brought together with sensitivity, is key topic for Systems Science and Education, the role of Wisdom.

- Does wisdom come from science?
 - George — Subconscious regions may have possibility of refined veridical models (intuitions driven by that grasp, are worthy intuitions). Many scientists begin their path from intuitions, with intuitive feeling about phenomena then testing paths of experiments (e.g. Mathematician and conjecture).
 - So there is a role for intuitive understanding, as long as the subconscious models resulting in intuitive thoughts, are based upon the actual reality Out There (objective that becomes subjective).
 - Systems Thinking: the way the brain works to grasp and assemble patterns into models via sensemaking.

Systems Change

- Wanting/Having/Selling their perspective/approach to be grounded in [Systems Science](#)
- Perspective of the [Systems Education Directory](#)

Systems Engineers

- Rediscovering [Systems Science](#)
- Members of INCOSE — not as engaged with Science, yes with applied understandings from George's book/communications.
- Systems Science beginnings has already taken place, Engineers can help AND don't have to reinvent the Science.
- ISSS with many practitioners..... George on the Science/Thinking ISSS swap.
- Focusing on real achievable things to do
- To pursue this holistically as education arm of the ISSS — How can we get sub-committees in [Education](#)
 - Young & Old (e.g. K-12 // Adult)
 - [George Mobus](#) and [@Shingai Thornton](#)
 - Lynn — Literacy with younger learners

Systems Practitioners

- Consultants et al.
 - Systems Sensibility/Awareness/Literacy
 - Common/Commons perspective on [Systems Science](#) — sensitive to why/how actions have consequences and so forth.
 - [Systems Science](#) shared with Daniel and Shingai. Systems Science is the new liberal arts, it gives you the broadest possible set of thinking tools. Instead of thinking of going into a profession, think about being a problem-solver with these skills.
 - <https://faculty.washington.edu/gmobus/Admin/SystemsScience/explainingSystemsScience.html>
 - Why universities in general, and UW Tacoma in specific, should have [Systems Science](#) programs.
 - If you could get a degree, motivated by the idea that you can use this to get good jobs — then, eventually it moves into the Masters/PhD as well as earlier into lifelong learning.
 - Microcredentials (work for technical skills, how might it work in systems science/literacy?).
 - <https://www.instituteforapprenticeships.org/apprenticeship-standards/systems-thinking-practitioner-v1-1>
 - Applying [Systems Science](#) to the origin of life problem. Something that George continues to work on. Diagramming of core metabolism as coupled work processes.
 - Electron bifurcation — coupling the Exo- and Endergonic reaction (up and down the Free Energy // Information-Heat variables). Key system property with not wasting energy, energy optimization, path of least action.

- Origin of life is phase transition of Universe. Some are researching Metabolism as it is today, taking it apart, finding the essential parts, the core core set of reactions. That's the auto-catalytic/autopoietic aspect of self-/re-construction/composition.
- It can be graduate school type problem to begin to scope/address this 📖 [Systems Science](#) question/problem. Multi-disciplinary effort already and with significance (bio-geo-chemistry and other Subject Matter work), this project is trying to put it in the framework of System/Systemness. The do use the term System and features/aspects like composition/nesting, however the discussion often stays within the biochemistry/reductionist paradigm.
- Then the Systems Science can produce informed accounts and experimental suggestions for the field of Origin of Life. This is / can be empirical and explicit. This gives utility for those in the lab work to connect with broader Systems area.
 - ▼ Charles Darwin closed the last paragraph of the first edition, (publication date 24 November 1859), of his *On the Origin of Species* with this sentence:-
 - *There is grandeur in this view of life, with its several powers, having been originally breathed into a few forms or into one; and that, whilst this planet has gone cycling on according to the fixed law of gravity, from so simple a beginning endless forms most beautiful and most wonderful have been, and are being, evolved.*
- Abductive reasoning, coming to the front of process in deep analysis. Looking/Mapping phenomena — What would explain how this got to be this way (inputs, causes, etc). As per George's deep analysis: starting backwards and coming to inputs, enforces/supports multiple pathways of different backwards/causal understanding. In terms of sub-systems too (nested generative models and blanket).
- Deduction/Induction + Abduction
 - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WKjqw3My_xM
<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12304-021-09432-0> 2021 Active Inference and Abduction, Ahti-Veikko Pietarinen & Majid D. Beni.
 - Robert Rosen: Recursion, recursion? Abduction? — One of the few who worked with the formal systems tools.
- Gary Smith did the panel: Scientific Foundations of Systems Engineering. After the talk there was interest and he saw the educators with booths as well. What are their current thinkings around integrating 📖 [Systems Science](#) into 📖 [Education](#)?
 - Common Core — for returning and reusing, and diverging (open source?)
 - August 29th — Some dozens of Systems/Education-interested people will try to get to:
 - Work together or 3 or 4 common slides
 - Supporting text
 - Key references.
 - Then this will be commonly referred-to materials
 - This also starts the Education Materials committee
 - 🌐 [ISSS](#) facilitates these committees
 - Relevant VP as co-chair.
 - Then the main influx of participation is the educational bodies.
 - What changes our ways of working here in 📖 [Education](#)?
 - Education SIG activity?
 - Education open house/space (some monthly open space for presentations and updates).
 - Education committee:
 - Educational materials
 - To draw materials together of/from.... Curriculum around....?

-
- Professionalization
- Synthesis work about Systems Science frameworks (SIG or Research network?)
- Theory-Practice interface.
- SySTEAM (STEM and Arts) — Katelyn Singham (?) a Maryland graduate student. This work already has complementary focus and different backgrounds. 🌐 ISSS highlights Systems Science and this can be a positive synergy in the ecosystem.
- 📖 Systems Science entails a lot of learning, practicing, doing, trying. We do 🏫 Education for many reasons, and there is multi-lateral and emergent relation among e.g. Science, Education, Research, Application, Thinking.
 - Working through the problems in reality. The graphics do not (cannot) simply pop out of a slide. There is a method. Keeping multiple aspects in mind. No single English term captures the phenomena and simultaneous multiscale dynamics.
 - Read George's book.
- <https://event.fourwaves.com/n2conference/pages>
 - Human social system & Noosphere — how can it become a positive governance element for planet earth.
 - Terrence Deacon and others
 - This can come about through participatory knowing/working with 📖 Systems Science

Janos Korn

- General points from [@Janos Korn](#) —
 - Who do we want to teach?
 - What to teach? What materials, methods, models?
 - What is the result?
 - ISSS issue — There is no symbolic structure that is capable of being taught — All the diagrams are nice, but there is no symbolic structure, as in some Sciences. This is what we are looking for. Well-established how to develop a symbolic structure for Systems Science.
 - Thinks — Systems teaching should be developed (by whom?) to be taught to all ages. Starting with young, like Math.

[@Janos Korn](#) paper

[PAPER 1 ISSS NEW JUN 2022.pdf](#)

[PAPER 1, ISSS, HOLXXCZ 1, APR 2023.pdf](#)

- [Science and Design of Problem Solving Systems by Janos Korn](#)

Len Troncale

- Rob went to the office. There were interesting education documents.
- Various important conference.
 - They had a Systems Paradigm, 1977 Denver, 500 pages of Proceedings and many topics.
 - Canadian, proceeding and applications of systems.
 - 1982 on Systems Methodology.
 - Far west region as well.
- Integrated Science and General Education — 10 year program
 - There is a curriculum around Isomorphic approaches. Some semesters/years of materials.
 - The Survey of [Snow 1989](#) below.
- There could be parallel work with SIGs, in assigning publications.
- .

📎 ScanMarch2024Pete... docx

- Initially we had the Education/KnowledgeEngineering pendulum. And now we are converging again, and moving towards the accessibility and applicability.

We are making a system that:

1. Visits a website URL and recursively clicks through links, looking for PDF and other document formats.
2. Downloads all documents discovered, and archives them with rigorous metadata.
3. Keeping the original file while also converting all files into clean and scannable versions which can have all text and figures extracted.
4. Deploy an OCR recognition model to extract all text in the PDF.
5. If possible, use screenshots to extract all the Figures with captions.

Scan March 2024 Peter Tuddenham

- [1975 6th Annual Conference Far West Region](#)
 - <https://www.isss.org/regional-conferences/>
 - https://www.isss.org/editor_upload/File/Regional%20Conferences/1975%206th%20Annual%20Conference%20Far%20West%20Region.pdf
- [1977 Proceedings The General Systems Paradigm: Science of Change and Change of Science - Denver](#)
 - <https://www.isss.org/proceedings/>
 - https://web3.isss.org/1977meet/ISSS_Proceedings_Denver_1977.pdf
- [1987 Canada and NE US Region Proceedings: Foundations and Applications of General Systems Theory with a Focus on Education](#)
 - <https://www.isss.org/regional-conferences/>
 - https://www.isss.org/editor_upload/File/Regional%20Conferences/1987_ISG_SR_Canada_and_NEUS_Region_Proceedings.pdf
- [1982 26th Meeting International Conference on Systems Methodology and SGSR Annual Meeting](#)
 - <https://www.isss.org/meeting-programs/>
 - https://www.isss.org/editor_upload/File/Programs%20and%20Abstracts/1982_ISSS_Conference_and_Meeting_Program.pdf
- [2015 Program and Abstracts Governing the Anthropocene: the greatest challenge for systems thinking in practice?](#)
 - <https://www.isss.org/meeting-programs/>
 - https://www.isss.org/editor_upload/File/Programs%20and%20Abstracts/2015%20Program%20Book.pdf

6. Provide descriptive statistics on all language analysis.

@ Education in the Systems Sciences 1989.pdf

Snow 1989

Not synced yet

Name of Field	Snow_1989
Full data	@ Education in the S...pdf
Link	
Title	Education in the Systems Sciences
Type of resource	Annotated Guide
Metadata	
Ownership	
Rights	
Access	
Responsibilities	
Ontology tags	Education, Systems Sciences
Identifiers	
Template type	
Summaries	

Len videos

- Part 1a: <https://youtu.be/ZEUCXrKiVfY> for past ISSS Attempts

Part 1b: <https://youtu.be/2UKcUqVvzss> for ISGE

See [Len videos](#)

- Not all have seen the YouTube which were shared with Daniel.
- In [Len videos](#) — Can see many of the works that were done earlier in ISSS. Unfortunately, many of the efforts met with failure (warning).
- Also about the fate of Systems Education in the past. It was not ignored — in fact there were departments (dissolved). Instructive to understand how/why they dissolved.
- In terms of Materials:
 - Videos on are the [Website](#) (under Library tab)
 - The physical documents shown in videos/ [Len videos](#) need to be digitized and documented. How can this be achieved?
 - Are they relevant? A lot of the institutes are now dissolved. Still of course there is historical relevance.
 - They will be sent to Peter and Back.
- In terms of Strategy
 -
 -
 -

Systems Education Workshop- Part 1 - Len Troncale

[@Len Troncale](#)

<https://youtu.be/ZEUCXrKiVfY> — 1:40:45

-

- Why called Experiments?
 - Presentation and talk, and for students — One to many.

- Do not use this widely.
- Prepare for legacy from the Outset
- Surviving experiments — some universities
- Stealth Systems Science for Every University
 - No institutional memory.

Four experiments

ISGE NEED FOR PRODUCTS

- ▶ Every College Student Must Take 4 Courses in Science to Graduate; This Product Satisfies That Requirement
- ▶ Sci General Education 10% of Every Students College Requirement
- ▶ BUT U.S. Science Literacy Very Low
- ▶ Driving Intense Search for Workable Alternatives
- ▶ Our Data Shows ISGE One Answer

— though science literacy is slow.

b. Idea: Teach sciences with systems science, Arts, Humanities

ISSTEM Who Systems Education?

BASIC IDEA

G.S. Teach the Connected, Separated, Isolated Topics as a System, not a Subject

MANY ANIMATIONS FROM THE START

INTEGRATED SCIENCE FOR GENERAL EDUCATION

ISGE FOUR REVOLUTIONS NEEDED

- ▶ **Need 1: Significant Integration of Courses**
- ▶ **ISGE Completely Reorganizes Sci Curriculum and Requires Simultaneous, Connected, Relevant**
- ▶ **Need 2: Interdisciplinary New T.M. Methods**
- ▶ **Math/med: Computer Based, Personal Tutoring**
- ▶ **Complex Learning, Active Discovery Learning**
- ▶ **Need 3: Universal Assessment Tools**
- ▶ **That Overcome Post Assessment Barriers & Limits**
- ▶ **Need 4: An Emphasis on Skills**
- ▶ **Real-Use Production, Problem Solving, Entrepreneurial Science and Technology**

Next Generation Science Standards: Cross Cutting Concepts

Official Federal Document & Education Standards ca. 2018

- Notice almost one-for-one the same as Nature's Enduring Patterns (NEP) & ISGE
- Both emphasize patterns & Sys focus
- Because ISGE is so based on the Natural Sciences and because NEP is basically systems all
- Main difference is to clarify and be precise. (omniphysics was unclear in great detail judgement)
- Notice both ISGE and NEP have many more patterns to follow way beyond these from 2018 (ahead of its time)

NGSS NCC	NEP (Truncate)
Patterns	Patterns
Cause and effect	Cause
Systems and Systems models	Systems
Scale and proportion	Hierarchy
Energy and matter	Energy flows
Structure and function	Cycles
Stability and change	Feedback
	Evolution
	Stability

— Causal isomorphisms — Bayes Graphs.

g. Multiscale systems as transdisciplinary settings for modeling.

ISGE COURSE ORGANIZATION

Curriculum would take full academic year

- Would satisfy ALL of the Science GE requirements for the B.A. or B.S. UG degree at any U.S. University/College
- Revolutionary knowledge, applicable & transformative
- Very busy per week assignments
- Wide Variety of Learning methods/techniques

LA182: SEVERAL WAYS TO DO SYNTHESIS, INTEGRATION, UNIFICATION

- ▶ **Integrative Themes == Genl Systems (ecophysics)**
- By their very nature are integrative because they are cross-disciplinary, a comparison of all natural and human systems, from molecules to galaxies
- ▶ **Links**
- Similarity between phenomena (ATM) & science (ecophysics) for the foundation of genetics for traits & ecosystems, for photosynthesis, and animal metabolism
- ▶ **Connections**
- Similarity between phenomena in DIFFERENT systems (ecophysics, hypercycles in society and how they relate to a variety of models)
- ▶ **Bridges (between natural eye & human eye)**
- For example similarities between DNA evolution, genes, or metabolic genetic code, and music
- ▶ **Domain Integrators**
- Like continental drift unifying much of geology or genetics explaining much of biology, important that students become conscious of this.

Education

i.

Funding

j. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Adobe_Authorware — then had to program that in C++ and Java

k. Example with Hierarchical systems, Lessons for Human Civilization, Cycles

l.

CA example Teaching students who are going to become teachers.

m. Rating scales of 7's.

n.

Grades

o. Evaluations were very positive,

p. Multimedia, Neuroscience, Attention management, Cognitive science in education, multiscale/dynamical/interactable engaging experiences.

q. Also patentable innovations

- i. Cube Companion, with personality
- ii. Interviews
- iii. Information Travelers
- iv. MindMETAPHORS captured in Pictures

r. Interesting differences between predictions in the 1990's, and how things are developing now in the 2020's.

s. Large addressable markets/populations, and spin-offs, and more.

t.

Caveats

Second video

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2UKcUqVvzss> 1:03:41

-

Overview

Second Experiment

- Different focus — UCSD talks, regarding USSO
- Then conclusions in Systems Education at ISSS

-

Regarding Santa Fe Institute (SFI) — for sure the evaluation of Len is correct here, the month long course is not General Systems oriented.

- Len has a book to publish, many works which should be integrated and attributed.

Fall 1986 — UCSD, example of syllabus:

- “Systems Science is Meta-Science”
- Listing many modern Systems and Systemists.

Experiment 3

-

— explaining how engineering depends on science (in relationship of e.g. cybernetics).

- Isomorphies. Systems Process theory.
- >50 hours of lectures

-

-

Science of Systems

Experiment 4 — ISSS Education studies.

-

ISSS Systems Education Products I. & II. 1976
2nd interim report

 - Look at title focused on GST; my early years
 - My IAS \$400,000 from DOE in the 70's for NMEE
 - H.E.W. later transferred project to BBFVL
 - My IAS used wide range of systems processes to teach Env. Educ.
 - Env. Educ. Spread rapidly since then but never with total systems emphasis
 - This NOT disseminated
 - 1st & 2nd reports in ISSP-IBO Archives & Suppl.'s

1976 publication — Never circulated?

-

ISSS Systems Education Products III. 1979 Report

-

ISSS Systems Education Products IV. THE HIGH SCHOOL ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION TEACHER TRAINING MODEL

-

ISSS Systems Education Products V. 1985 DRAFT PROCEEDINGS (unabridged)

 - GLOBAL Workshop on Systems Science Education
 - Held in Long Beach, California
 - Sponsored by ISSS
 - All ISSS Attendee's
 - 18 SysSci Education Programs Described
 - More than 300 pages
 - Distribution: Only to Participants?

-

ISSS Systems Education Products VI. A Teacher's Toolkit Program Review

-

ISSS Systems Education Products VIII. Education in the Systems Sciences

And several others (well, many others!).

-

ISSS Systems Education Products VII. Many deaths

Diagnosis — Deaths.

Recommendations!

-

DO THESE THINGS?

 - Don't change administrative responsibilities too high enough
 - Be awarded LOTS of FEDERAL funding
 - Plan early for legacy & succession
 - Must recognize or enable 2000+ years old for Systems Sciences
 - Must acquire resources (PERSONNEL, BUSINESS) systems science
 - Get beyond local systems
 - Be not satisfied with local systems

How can the Education project learn from and assist @Len Troncale, in the end of 2022 and heading into 2023?

- Peter was in Portland State University — Systems Science department — Working to create a page, on ISSS Website, for that program.

◦ They can take Undergraduate students, Bachelor's Minor, Masters, PhD — In Systems Science.

- .
- .
- .

Len Troncale Archive

Daniel and Sasha went to Claremont on June 24, 2024, to meet with Luke Friendshuh and pick up some materials from [Len Troncale](#).

Currently the 11 boxes (10 boxes of unique content with lids, 11th box of extra Behavioral journal article (“baseball cards”) are being stored in downtown Davis, CA, USA.

Ongoing work is connecting this with Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository

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D1

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SGSR 1986 part I-II

SGSR 1987 I-II, supp.

SGSR 1988

SSS 1989 I, II, III, IV

D2

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Budapest sept

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small program

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participant list

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+ program (2x)

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ISSS 1998 Abstracts

ISSS 2009 Programs/Abstr.

ISSS 2011 prog/Abstr.

ISSS 2014 prog/Abstr

ISSS 2004 prog/Abstr

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Science

~1973 - 1990

Gary Smith

Review [Key diagrams](#) and [Systems Science architecture](#) from Gary Smith

Jessie Henshaw

[@Jessie Henshaw](#)

I'd like to help build materials and methods for teaching and observing natural systems in context. Please share links with me and let me know about your plans.

As I mentioned in the Zoom meeting today, both Gerald Midgley [@Gerald R Midgley](#) and I have spent our lives studying Robert Rosen's types of natural systems in context. I have a large body of unread research, much of it on general theory, which unfortunately seems too unexpected for the traditional model-based systems research community to be interested in. I've referenced most of the papers and studies worth mentioning below with an (*) and date referring to the same numbering in my [chronological publications list](#). My credentials are at the top of the same web page [JLH Research Publication](#). My research and discussion site and other links are at [Reading Nature's Signals](#).

My simplified research story:

My systems research goes back to the late 1970s (*1977-1), stemming from instrumented microclimate field studies of the organization of indoor climates of solar homes in the Denver and Santa Fe area. They were notable for changing organization several times a day as the sun rose and set. The work produced a limited series book called "An Unhidden Pattern of Events" (*1979-5), referring to the ubiquitous chain of growth systems seen beginning and ending of organizational events. My first two published papers coming from it were for the ISSS 1985 meeting (then called SGSR) (*1985-1 & -2). The papers were listened to with interest, and people remarked on the amazing, reported detail one can observe. But they were dismissed as science, and there were no questions or discussions of them, despite many efforts.

My main mathematical and theoretical work continued through the 1990s, first with mathematical software, which I developed for studying the emerging dynamics of recorded natural systems. The shapes of the dynamics regularly matched the kinds of systems found causing them. I wrote a summary of the programming of the diagnostic analysis tools and some studies, along with a major theorem on the nature of change (*1995-1). The theorem is simple but proves a counter-intuitive result, so has been difficult to explain. It starts by showing that to satisfy energy conservation, energy flows cannot change instantaneously. That sets the stage for showing that it also implies that changes in energy must start and stop by growth processes. I now explain the phenomenon, also universally observed, as coming from growth processes being organizational developments, not numerical or statistical. I now further simplify that to saying that mathematical models describe nature as operating by "cause and effect," whereas natural systems, as we see them working, develop and work by "find and connect." We do that ourselves, of course.

I did numerous studies and wrote papers in the late 90s, one was then included in a book (*1999-1, -2). That explained my "derivative reconstruction" algorithms for recreating the third derivative flowing shapes in intermittent data curves, carefully stripping away local higher derivative noise, a non-distorting kind of curve smoothing. My largest study and paper started in 1997 and showed that a plankton speciation event a half million years ago occurred by an accumulating series of growth and collapse processes of new forms of the later stable new plankton. The 12th draft submitted for publication and rejected was in 2007 (*2007-1).

Two published papers in a scientific philosophy journal (*2008-2, 2010-3) discussed evidence of the active learning of ecosystems and how models can show the learning pressures on systems of fixed design. Other explorations from the period are (*2008-1, 2009-1, -2, 2010-1, -2, -4, 2011-3, 2012-1). My most widely referenced publication was a collaborative paper on measuring the global energy cost of wind farm energy sources (*2011-1). That was followed by a paper resubmitted for publication three times on how sustainability errs in trusting efficiency as an energy use constraint when it's very generally a stimulus. The difference comes from businesses thinking of the whole effect (stimulus) and sustainability designers thinking of the unit effect (reduction), and the two groups and the scientists not able to communicate if they do.

In 2012 I also began my work at the UN as an NGO representative helping to draft the US SDGs, a wonderful learning experience but also very disappointing. The SDGs are a badly designed set of goals that include the main cause of the inequities as one of the cures, and had to give much of the work to non-regenerative industrial investors. UN-related short studies worth mentioning are (*2011-3, 2012-1, 2013-1, 2014-1,-2,-3). Beginning to see language as the greater of the systems

science problems, research friends let me to Christopher Alexander's universal system design language, writing papers for major conferences (*2015-1, -2) and publishing a monograph of those two papers (2019-1).

Studies on regenerative development (*2018-2), the coupling of growth and climate (*2019-2), and the economics of timing the end of growth (2020-1) Helped me find a new language for writing more traditional systems papers again, after a 33yr break. Those were "[Systems thinking for Systems making](#)" (*2018-1) for System's Practice and Action Research and "[Understanding Nature's Purpose in starting all new Lives with Compound Growth](#)" and "[Holistic Natural Systems – Design and Steering](#)" for the prior two ISSS meetings (*2021-1, 2022-1).

As contributors to [the ISSS Systems Education Survey](#), might you respond to another question? Do you distinguish between the study of system theory and the working organization of working systems in context?

I'm an ISSS member studying and writing on the versatile design principles of natural systems and how to communicate insights into their designs to other audiences. There's a barrier to overcome between thinking of systems as abstract mental models, detached from their contexts, and as organizations of working relationships in context.

I gave a [talk in September](#) on how natural language seems constructed to give meanings to terms connecting the systems of experience in context with our minds. There's also a possibility of using natural language to refer to principles of natural system design that non-scientists might more easily understand. It could also help scientists see more of what our theories have been leaving out and also help make science more relevant.

My current work is in my research journal below. A compact list of [my basic research](#) writings on natural systems physics and design science might be a good reference.

George Mobus

<https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-030-93482-8>

978-3-030-93482-8_....pdf

Systems Science: Theory, Analysis, Modeling, and Design

George E. Mobus George Mobus

The present work has gone far beyond my initial vision. The Introduction explains the nature of deep understanding and the reasons why we need to strive for it in our knowledge of systems. Part I, then, covers the theoretical framework for obtaining that knowledge. It establishes the ontology of systems and provides the logical structure of systemness that permits us to examine any system and gain knowledge about it in a structured way (a system of system knowledge).

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- ▼ George's corpus as entry point, "World according to George", then George and Friends, then etc...
 - ▷ Does not want it simply about him. Agrees this is a starting point, perhaps not called as such. George's neighborhood. Preserving claims and semantics.
 - ▷ The claim that George et al. made was, this is the first comprehensive Textbook-like work on the whole of [Systems Science](#) . There are so many books out there, written by so many authors from the angle of their own, even if called e.g. "Introduction to Systems Science", or "Facets of". They tried to do a well-rounded and comprehensive synthetic work.

GM Chapter 3

Chapter 3

- The things are organized into categories based on similarities and differences. That organization points to a hierarchy of complexity. In this chapter, we will propose an ontology of systemness that accounts for the organization. We say “an” ontology because there have been many attempts throughout human history to establish such an organization. This chapter focuses on an ontology that is guided in formation by the principles of systems science covered in the last chapter. Again, this is not a first such attempt. We will acknowledge a few more recent attempts in this chapter but will not present a history of the developments in ontology as this can be found in many sources.
- We start the chapter making such commitments at the most fundamental level of existence and then derive all else from there.
- We call it “Ontogenesis” and describe the mechanisms (like variation, combination, emergence, and selection) that generate new things and new levels of organization.
- 3.1 — Ontology is the study of what exists.
- We will be using concepts from a field of mathematics called category theory. However, we will not delve into the more arcane aspects of the field. In Chap. 4, we will be developing a mathematical description of systems using set and graph theories. Those familiar with category theory will grasp the derivations. Our position, for the present, is that category theory is a little “too” abstract for the development of a theory that can be grasped by the average reader for whom this book is intended—for readers interested in knowing how to apply category theory to the structures we will be exploring.
- The concept of “an” ontology is adopted in the field of information science primarily for the purpose of categorization and logical linking as in the above example of “is-a-kind-of.”
 - **Comment — this is only a certain kind of declarative ontology (e.g. that make claims about what is a part, or type, or some other thing). We can contrast this approach, with the logical Ontology approach taken by Adam Pease in the SUMO project <https://www.ontologyportal.org/> .**
- Basically, we assert that the language/ ontological representations need to be a hybrid between algorithmic computation and natural language so that the ideas of systemness can move freely between the world of computer simulations and human understanding — **Agreed with this.**
- The first is what we will call the “category” of things. Categories are abstract types of things. A common example of categories is the phylogenetic tree of life. The binomial nomenclature method of naming species is predicated on a hierarchy of types. We humans are a type of primate. Primates are a type of mammal, and so on.
- 3.1.1 Categories and Type Hierarchies
 - The terms category and type are somewhat interchangeable with caution.
- 3.1.2 Recurring Patterns at All Scales
- 3.1.3 Origins of Things: A Universal Process
- 3.2 What Is “a” System Ontology, and Why Does It Matter?
 - We have claimed that systemness, the “property” of being a system, as described by the 12 principles in Chap. 2 and to be formally defined in the next chapter, is the fundamental organizing principle of the Universe.
 - As one way to see how this claim comes about, we will describe the process of auto-organization of smaller, simpler system objects into larger, more complex systems with emergent properties and behaviors.
 - If the concepts being explored by cosmology and quantum physics are reasonably close to reality, then the cycle would seem to “start” at some fundamental scale (the Planck scale?) of space and time with pre-particle entities (Unger and Smolin 2015)....For our purposes we will need to assume that something like this had to have happened to get the whole process started

- The main topic of this book is the description and explanation of a methodology (set of methods) that can be used to acquire knowledge of how things in the Universe work. Further claimed is that this methodology rests on understanding “things” as systems, that systems interact with other systems and in doing so form a larger, encompassing supra-system, that systems are composed of subsystems (down to an atomistic level), and that this hierarchical structure encompasses everything from the Universe as a whole (closed) system down to the uncountable number of fundamental particles and energy packets that have auto-organized to form the complexity of the Universe that we (as systems that can contain models of other systems) observe in the present.
 - The claim(s) thus made is (are) unprovable and, more importantly, un-falsifiable as it (they) stand. This puts the whole issue of systemness into the realm of philosophy, metaphysics, as a starting point.
 - Systems science begins at the point where falsifiability of hypotheses becomes possible. That is after we have established a set of “axioms”¹³ generated from the claim of systemness and then set out to test whether this or that aspect of a specific system of interest (SOI) fails, upon proper testing, to be falsified. The program for generating axioms from the principles of systemness is beyond the scope of this work. However, we do need to ground the rest of the book in a philosophical treatment to show the justifications for what follows.
- 3.2.1 System Philosophy
 - In this chapter, we will develop a set of terms that cover objects, relations, actions, transformations, quantifications, and categorizations that constitute at least a beginning of a system ontology.
 - One of the reviewers of an earlier draft of this chapter introduced the author to a more universal approach to an upper ontology, the General Formal Ontology (GFO). After a review of its approach it appears that there are many aspects of GFO that map to the system ontology developed here. It is certainly conceivable that both approaches have many aspects in common because both are attempts to find the ultimate nature of what exists. One substantive difference, however, is that the GFO started out with an assumption of formality, using first-order logic. The system ontology presented in this chapter started with an assumption that imposing such a formality too soon might foreclose the exploration of interesting ideas that cannot be immediately captured in a formal language of that sort. The use of formalism (set and graph theories) in the next chapter is used primarily to capture descriptions of systemness without the restrictions imposed by an axiomatic system. We believe that at some point such a system will be developed but hope it will be after there is a broad understanding of the general terrain.
 - Yes. SUMO is a development from GFO, because SUMO enables higher-order reflexive/recursive logic. Thus from my understanding SUMO is the most advanced (but not most-used in large-scale data applications) ontology offering. I am excited about these directions involving Logics and Ontology, imbued with the Systems approach. And I am not sure what strategies will delay/avert the challenge of axiomatic lock-in.
 - 3.2.1.1 Metaphysics

- Figure 3.1

Fig. 3.1 These are the claimed substances that exist (have ontological status). The substances in the solid boxes have understood relations and interactions. The dotted-lined box indicates that our knowledge of these substances is still developing

- The starting point is that the Universe is composed of matter and energy, that both come in discrete packets — *Is this an evidence-supported view? And/or is this something axiomatic (taken without specific evidence), which might risk “imposing such a formality too soon might foreclose the exploration of interesting ideas”, however in the space of energy-ontologies, rather than formal ontologies?*
- 3.2.1.2 Cosmological Ontology
 - Our metaphysical claim is that the entire Universe is comprised of these substances interacting with one another such that structures composed of matter and energy evolve toward greater organization over time through a process of auto-organization, emergence, and subsequent selection 23—a process we have dubbed ontogenesis (see below).
 - 23 — Mobus and Kalton (2015), Chaps. 10 and 11) explicate these processes as they pertain to how matter and energy interact, mediated by information to produce more complex dissipative structures that, in turn, interact at a new level of organization. The degree to which such structures are dissipative is a measure of the entity’s “knowledge” of the interaction. See also the sections below regarding ontological information and knowledge.

- Figure 3.2

- 3.2.1.2.1 Ontological Information

- In this work we follow the basic insight of Shannon (Shannon and Weaver 1949) that information is the measure of uncertainty regarding the state of a message, or the next "symbol" to be received in a message stream, which is a property of the receiver (e.g., the ribosome) and not of the sender (the DNA).
- Another mistake made in the use of the word information in common usage is to intermingle the notion of "meaning" with information.
- The ontological status of information derives from the fact that messages have causal power to change a physical structure. This is, however, a strange kind of causal power. It is not a result of the intentions of a transmitter/sender, but rather it is based on the ignorance of the receiver.
- Real work is accomplished in making these alterations, so energy is consumed and heat dissipated. Afterward, the structure is a priori prepared to dissipate future flows of energies without having to do additional work. Information is the capacity to cause changes in receiving systems that better prepare that system for future messages (minimize surprise). The change in the structure of the receiver that reflects this preparation is what we call knowledge.
- For sure this is consistent with the Free Energy Principle formalisms, and Bayesian Mechanics, and the work of e.g. Jim Crutchfield on thermo-informational engines.

- 3.2.1.2.2 Ontological Knowledge

- According to ancient Vedic literature,³¹ "Richo aksare parame vyoman," "Knowledge is structured in consciousness (Rig Veda I.164.39 as translated by Maharishi Mahesh Yogi, 1974)." The key word here is "structured." The theory of knowledge, ordinarily the subject of epistemology (discussed below), is rising to the level of science with the recognition that knowledge is encoded in the actual physical structures of systems,³² and thus acquires ontological status (Principle 7 in Chap. 2).

▪ Figure 3.3

Fig. 3.3 This figure shows the time course events when a recipient receives a message from a sender. A sender encodes a message based on its current state, which may be different from the recipient’s knowledge of the sender’s state as coded in the recipient system’s internal structure. The message would therefore contain an amount of information representing the degree and direction of difference. The interpreter (blue small circle) uses that information to direct a work flow modifying the internal structure. If at a later time the very same encoded message is received again it does not contain information because there is no difference and the energy that would have gone to do additional work is simply dissipated, or conserved for future use

- According to the Vedic tradition, this is the essence of consciousness and so everything in the Universe is conscious (see the next section on panpsychism). What we call human consciousness is just a complex version of universal consciousness. What we claim here is much less expansive. We do claim that information and knowledge, and their interactions, do have ontological status.
- Leaving aside the nature of consciousness for the moment, we note that it is nevertheless a phenomenon of the brain.
- In Fig. 3.2b we see some of the transformational (generation of) relations. The right side of the diagram shows that information receipt generates knowledge construction in the receiver. This means that the receiving system possessed an a priori low expectation of the messages communicated from sender to receiver. Since the “amount” of information in a message is inversely proportional to that expectation, the receiver has to respond by reconfiguring its own structure to become more dissipative (Mobus and Kalton 2015, Chap. 7). That is, it is better able to pass through the energy flows that are the result of information (perhaps through amplification) so that next time the same message is received it is less likely to cause a similar amount of change in the structure. What Fig. 3.2b shows is the iterative cycle of information–knowledge construction mediated by the roles of matter and energy
- The pattern of message receipt and reconfiguration (even if marginal or miniscule) embodies the gaining of knowledge (even if fleeting) and repeats at every level of organization in the Universe.
- One further note, on the nature of knowledge as structural configuration; it does not generally persist. Entropy prevails in the end.
- 3.2.1.2.3 Panpsychism
 - Recall the last section opened with a quotation from the ancient Vedic texts, the Upanishads, regarding knowledge, structure, and consciousness? There has been an on-going debate, mostly among philosophers of

science but also some physicists, that consciousness is a property of the Universe, indeed probably the key property.

- It would then be reasonable to argue that the consciousness that is so evident in living systems is actually rooted in a basic capacity of elements in the Universe to “sense” and change in accordance with what they sense.
- How the fundamental units of reality combine and construct higher levels of organization, complexity, and capacity to construct knowledge is a central concern of ontology or ontological development, here termed ontogeny.

▪ 3.2.1.3 Ontogeny: A First Pass

- The central question here is: How do systems of increasing complexity arise out of the four (or six) fundamental substances in the first place? In other words, where and how do systems originate and develop into their stable forms and functions? How does complexity increase over the history of the Universe?
- The process of ontogeny is a natural consequence of the interplay between matter, energy, information, and knowledge, which is the final product of the process.

◦ 3.2.1.4 System Epistemology

- The bulk of this book is actually about system epistemology or more specifically how we humans gain knowledge of systems. Using the to-be-developed ontology (this chapter) and a formal definition of system (developed in Chap. 4), we will generate an organized structure that is modifiable in the sense of learning described above.
- This structure, which we will implement in a database, the structure of which is similar to our brains, will be predisposed to receive information about a specific system, the system of interest, generated from the act of analysis (in the broad sense). We call this structure a knowledgebase.
- The key to system epistemology is recognizing that the gaining and storing of knowledge in the knowledgebase is accomplished using a language of system that is completely comprehensible to human beings. In the next chapter where we develop this language, we show how the language of system is already grasped subconsciously by humans and thus becomes accessible consciously by making the nature of the language explicit through systems science and the ontology (terms) translated into a spoken language (in this case English).

◦ 3.2.1.4.1 The Role of Modeling

- All systems are initially observed from the “outside.” That is, the scientist has access to monitoring the inputs and outputs (behavior) of the system but does not immediately have access to internals of the system that generate that behavior. — **Markov Blanket.**
- Let us be very clear. A mental concept is a model implemented in dynamical neural structures. Any person's conceptualization of the world and the things in it is, in fact, a mental model of that world. Computational models are, effectively, extensions of mental model, formalized and encoded in a modeling language (mathematics or something like systems dynamics) but, nevertheless, are just models of the systems of interest in the world. Models built on deeper knowledge of causal processes within the systems are generally better for capturing the predictive or anticipated behavior of the systems and this is what the sciences strive for.

◦ 3.2.1.4.2 Inquiry

- Usually, such explorations can be related to searches for food or other rewards but they are undirected (foraging for example). But in humans, exploration and inquiry seem more opportunistic; that is, there is no direct benefit sought, but just some information that might come in handy some day! Humans have been labeled “informavores!”

◦ 3.2.1.4.3 Knowledge Gets Refined and Expanded

◦ 3.2.1.4.4 Learning Systems' Learning Systems (No this is not a typo)

- No this is not a typo. Here we refer to the idea of systems that can learn actually going through the process of learning other systems (improve their models of other systems; Principle 9 in Chap. 2). This is the basic model of systems epistemology. Systems of sufficient complexity (like our brains) are capable of constructing models of all other systems, including supra-systems, by improving and expanding on a fundamental “system” template. Our

effort will be to show how this basic model can be replicated in an artifactual system (the knowledgebase fed by systems analysis).

- Even the simplest sensor–decider–actor brains (in fat worms for example) are themselves input–process–output devices and that is the fundamental template definition of a system! By virtue of having a primitive brain, a fat worm possesses a model of self and a primitive model of its world (e.g., mud as a medium/food).
- This being so, we are now in a position to tackle the problem of developing a universal ontology of system.
- 3.2.1.4.5 Leveraging Isomorphic Structures and Functions
- 3.2.2 Examples of Developing a System Ontology
 - The desire to construct an ontology that captures the essence of human thinking is not at all new. For example, Gottfried Leibniz (1646–1716), who we will refer to below, pursued a “Characteristica universalis,” or a universal language of science, that would unify all of the pursuits of the sciences.
 - 3.2.2.1 Miller’s Living Systems Theory

Table 3.1 Miller’s basic concepts include what we are calling a system top-level ontology for living systems (complex adaptive and evolvable systems)

Miller’s basic concepts (Chap. 3)
Space and time
Matter and energy
Information
System
Structure
Process
Types
Level
Echelon
Supra-system
Subsystem and component
Transmission in concrete systems
Steady state

- 3.2.2.2 Troncale’s System Process Theory
 - Lenard Troncale (Troncale 1978a, b; Friendshuh and Troncale 2012) and co-workers have been working on the concept of systems as processes (systems process theory [SPT] and systems of systems process theory [SoSPT], see below).
 - Troncale also points out a basic problem with ontologies. Ontologies are built with words, and words are notoriously changeable in meaning. (Troncale 1993). The selection of a lexicon that is truly representative of an ontology is not a trivial problem. — **SUMO is defined according to logical relationships, not human-interpreted lexical semantics.**
 - 3.2.2.3 INCOSE: Systems Science Working Group Effort
 - The International Council for Systems Engineering (INCOSE) has had difficulty describing a discipline of systems engineering owing, in part, to a poor consensus on what systems science actually is and what parts of systems science should inform the engineering of the products systems engineers produce. And this comes from a poor consensus on what a system is!
 - It is a little cart-before-the-horse to have engineers define a scientific subject area in this way. However, given that the need is extremely great (systems engineering is going to happen regardless of the state of a system ontology!) it is not entirely unprecedented. And, as it happens, many high-level systems thinkers have been

involved in the effort so there is a high degree of expectation that the work will produce useful insights. As of this writing, the authors' own efforts are being invited to be incorporated in the effort. So, this chapter and the next will become part of the process within INCOSE to build a universal ontology (and language) of systems.

- 3.2.2.4 Natural Semantic Meta-Language
- 3.2.2.5 System Dynamics (SD)
 - DYNAMO, his early language, used a lexicon based on the idea that all systems involve flows of matter, energy, and messages, or, more generically, just flows of stuff and influence. It also involves the states of reservoirs or "stocks" of stuff that rise and fall relative to the flow rates of inputs versus outputs. He defined regulators or "valves" that controlled the rate of flows as well as sensors and control decisions that would change the settings on the valves.
- 3.2.2.6 H.T. Odum's Energetics

- 3.2.2.7 WordNet
 - <https://aclanthology.org/2019.gwc-1.25.pdf> Commonsense Reasoning Using WordNet and SUMO: a Detailed Analysis
- 3.2.2.8 Strong Movement Toward a General (Universal) Ontology of System
- 3.3 Ontogenesis: The Origin and Development of Systems
 - 3.3.1 The Ontogenic Cycle
 - The ontogenic cycle is the process whereby "things" that exist at a level of organization interact with one another. Some things interact strongly, for example forming strong bonds or mutual dependencies that will hold them together in space over time.

◦ 3.3.1.1 The Basic Process

Fig. 3.6 The ontogenic cycle is depicted. This cycle produces ever more complex systems from simpler systems as long as there is a flow of high-potential energy from a localized source through the system and out to a general sink, as is the case for the Earth system. (Figure modified from Mobus and Kalton (2015), Fig. 10.3, p. 471))

- Figure 3.7

Fig. 3.7 The continuous pass through the ontogenic cycle produces a spiral of ever-increasing complexity as the general ontology of the Universe

- Figure 3.8

Fig. 3.8 The primordial conditions before the onset of the ontogenic cycle just at the onset of auto-organization

- Figure 3.9

Fig. 3.9 Ontogenesis: (a) the pre-life pathway to greater complexity; (b) the evolutionary pathway to greater complexity of living systems through biological evolution. The surrounding ovals in the A sequence represent effective boundaries where the connections between entities as components create a unity. The boundaries indicated in the B sequence may represent actual boundaries like cell membranes. This figure depicts just the formation of stable structures, those having significant duration given the milieu in which they formed. A more complete picture would show many unstable formations (at a specific time) hovering around the stable ones that will later disintegrate and many components that have not been incorporated into more complex structures owing to the specific conditions of the milieu

- In the following section, we sketch the elaboration of structures, forms, and functions in a hierarchy of complexity as ontogenesis produced the Universe we witness today.
- 3.3.1.2 Levels of Organization
 - Figures 3.10, 3.11 and 3.12 show some relations between “things” that show progressively greater complexity as new levels of organization (to which they belong) emerge. We will discuss the progressive origins of these things below as well as the levels of organization and emergences. Figure 3.10 presents the purely physical (i.e., subatomic and atomic) entities that end up producing both large-scale entities like galaxies and small-scale entities like gases and rocky bodies through chemical interactions.

◦ Figure 3.10

Fig. 3.10 Levels of Organization starting with the lowest levels—the “Purely Physical”—and showing the generation of the biological levels. Note that this does not reflect a simple linear evolution, but that multiple kinds of subsystems have emerged and co-evolved over time. The boxes are labeled with the kinds of “things” that exist at any given level. Those things tend to continue to

◦ Figure 3.11

Fig. 3.11 The continuation of emergence of levels of organization after the emergence of life. Living cells rapidly diversified through the Darwinian mechanism of descent with modification (i.e., gene mutations). The great Linnaean Kingdoms (along the bottom) originated during the earliest era of life as a result of modification and selection (discussed below). The various dashed

◦ Figure 3.12

Fig. 3.12 The levels of organization for humans grow quite complex but can be summarized by the historical “ages” that paleontologists and historians consider. This characterization of the Neolithic and Bronze–Iron ages is derived from Scott (2017). The highest level of organization is represented by a world in which the whole of humanity is integrated into a single “Global Human Social System,” which will be addressed in Chaps. 7 and 9, and the Postscript

- So, with the origin and development of life, we go into the realm of the complex adaptive and evolvable systems (CAES) mentioned in the Introduction, again in Chap. 2, and to be refined in Chap. 6.
- The Ecos is an alternative and broader name for the whole Earth system (which includes Luna and Sol having major input influences on what happens on the surface of the Earth) not in opposition to the popular term, Gaia (Lovelock and Margulis 1974), but as a way to situate Gaia as the physiology of a larger phenomenon (c.f. Volk 1998).
- 3.3.1.3 Energy Flow: A Prerequisite to the Generation of Structures and Levels of Organization
- 3.3.1.4 Auto-Organization: Creating Structure.
- 3.3.1.5 Emergence: New Structures and New Interactions
- 3.3.1.6 Selection
 - We view selection as an all-encompassing process in which the context or environmental conditions operate on emergent forms to destroy those that are susceptible (i.e., denature proteins that are not stable) and leave in place those that are thermodynamically or physiologically, or sociologically, stable. The survivors are free to interact and start the next phase of ontogenesis; to produce the next level of organization.
 - The result of selection is the basis for the next round of ontogenesis. That which proves effective, and survives within the context of the environment created by the level of organization, participates in the next round of auto-organization. The ontogenesis of new levels of organization thus emerges and the Universe experiences new levels of complexity. Hence, Figs. 3.6 and 3.7 and the framework they invoke.
- 3.3.2 Other Takes on Ontogenesis
 - This view of increasing complexity is neither new nor unique to our conceptualization. In fact, many authors have examined this apparent trajectory of the evolving Universe. In this section we examine a number of previous or current

concepts of how the Universe is evolving toward increasing complexity and, especially, as represented by the evolution of life and humanity on the planet Earth.

- 3.3.2.1 The Noosphere: Teilhard de Chardin
- 3.3.2.2 Combogenesis
- 3.3.2.3 Emergence by Continuous Integration and Diversification
- 3.4 An Ontological Framework
 - In this section, we will provide an ontological framework that asserts that what can exist in this evolving Universe, made of matter and energy, organized by knowledge and information, is systems. Put differently, matter and energy interact according to the influences of knowledge and information to produce systems at all scales of space and time, at all levels of emergent organization, and complexity.
 - 3.4.1 The Framework, Its Purpose, and Its Justifications
 - Figure 3.13

- The framework for the system ontology is shown in Fig. 3.13. This may be called a conceptual model in that it demonstrates not only the ontological commitments but also how they are organized. The figure is a graph representation of elements (nodes) and their relations (edges) along with category names and organizing labels (levels).

- Elements (nodes in the directed graph) in all capital letters denote terms that will be used in the top-level ontology of systems. These are the things that exist by virtue of the Universe organizing as it does, through auto-organization, emergence, and evolution (Mobus and Kalton 2015, Chaps. 10 and 11), which we are now calling the ontogenic cycle in Sect. 3.3.1. These are the core things that we will look for in our analysis of systems regardless of the level of organization or complexity. As we will show in the next chapter, for example, the element labeled COMPONENT at Level + 1 may be readily seen as a subsystem of the system at Level 0. That component/subsystem would then be subject to the same analysis imposed by the framework in the figure. It will become the system of interest and be its own Level 0. The analysis simply reapplies the conceptual framework with the previous SYSTEM becoming the new ENVIRONMENT
- The framework is composed of three aspects. The first aspect, the nodes in the graph, is the set of ontological elements themselves. The second, signified by the words on the left side of the graph, is the ROLES that the items in that region (horizontal level) of the graph play. The third aspect shows the higher–lower relation that frames the system hierarchy; the level numbers are relative positions in the hierarchy
- Starting at the top, the ENVIRONMENT encases and defines both the CONTEXT and the MEANING of the system of interest (SOI). This is designated as Level – 1, or one level up.⁶⁷ It is also often referred to as the supra-system. Level 0 is that of the SOI, the system that we seek to understand and model. Level + 1 is one level down from the SOI meaning the level of organization in which we find the internal components and their interactions—that which gives rise to the SOI behavior and defines its boundary.
- In the next section we will elaborate on all of the elements, relations, and categorizations illustrated in Fig. 3.13
- 3.4.2 The Aspects
 - 3.4.2.1 The Ontological Elements of the Framework
 - In the section below, “The System Ontology”, we will define and describe these elements and their expansion into sub-elements that exist. Here we provide a brief explanation of the major elements in the framework in preparation for that expansion
 - 3.4.2.1.1 ENVIRONMENT
 - In this structure the top or highest element is the environment. This is the suprasystem that encloses the system of interest (see Fig. 3.4). Environments are, by definition, more complex than the SOI. This is because that larger system contains the SOI, which is then a subsystem, as well as other systems interacting with the original SOI. Hence, the complexity of the environment includes the complexity of the various subsystems.
 - 3.4.2.1.1.1 CONTEXT
 - This refers to the set of conditions that obtain at a time instant relevant to the dynamics of the SOI. The environment in an evolving Universe is continually changing in so many various complex ways, so contexts also change.⁶⁸ The fundamental context is that of the various other systems with which the SOI interacts in an on-going way. These are the sources of inputs and the sinks for outputs across the system boundary.⁶⁹ Other sources, not necessarily recognized as an identifiable nature, may affect a system through what we will call a “disturbance.”
 - 3.4.2.1.1.2 MEANING
 - In our system ontology, we consider MEANING to describe a set of conditions that have a trinary affective influence on a system.
 - 3.4.2.1.2 SYSTEM
 - This ontological element is quite obviously the core of the whole enterprise. There are three ways to view a system of interest: as a process, as an object, and as an entity.
 - 3.4.2.1.2.1 PROCESS
 - All systems within the Universe are open to input and output flows of at least one of: material, energy, or messages (which are special forms of material/energy flows). Systems process or transform the inputs into outputs. The collective effect of the process is also called the “function” of the system. The processes inherent in the bits and pieces of a rock, strong chemical bonding, produce its qualities of hardness and stability over time (soft sandstone notwithstanding). The processes of digestion in your alimentary track function to acquire nutrients for your body's maintenance.

- 3.4.2.1.2.2 TYPE
 - We are using the term “type” here in a very general way. It can refer to a category, which is usually found in a hierarchical structure, or it can refer to what we are calling an “archetype” (see Chap. 10 for an elaboration on the concept of archetypes).
- 3.4.2.1.2.3 ENTITY
 - An entity is a concrete system that does something actual, having causal effect on other entities or objects in its environment. Concrete systems are real and identifiable as unique, at least within a minimal category. That is, a system as an entity is an actual thing in itself and not something like a category (though it belongs to a type).
- 3.4.2.1.2.4 BEHAVIOR
 - All systems display activity on some time scale. They interact with other systems by virtue of properties of their boundaries and their components (below).
- 3.4.2.1.2.5 BOUNDEDNESS
 - All systems are delineated from their environments by virtue of coherence of the components. We can talk about this as providing an “effective” boundary. In some systems this will manifest as a physical barrier demarking the insides of the system from its environment, such as the case of cell membrane.
 - The Boundary “Problem”
 - Figure 3.14

- 3.4.2.1.2.6 COMPONENT
 - All systems contain components that internally operate (behave) to produce the process that the system entails. Components may themselves be systems, or atomic, i.e., irreducible.
- 3.4.2.1.2.7 INTERACTION
 - All systems interact with other systems to some extent or another. There are no isolated systems. Interactions result from properties of their boundaries and processes.
- 3.4.2.2 Roles

- All of these elements play various roles within the framework.
- 3.4.2.2.1 Teleonomy —
- Referring to the interactions between the environment and the SOI (Level – 1 to Level 0 in Fig. 3.3): The term “teleonomy” is used to designate something like a “purpose.” Purpose is a highly problematic concept, both philosophically and practically. Do systems have a purpose? Does the environment have a purpose? Does either serve a purpose? Purpose implies intention. Pre-Darwin, the organization of the world was easily explained by the intentions of God. Post-Darwin the situation has gotten more complicated. Systems exist and persist in their environments as a result of performing some kind of function that is beneficial, ultimately to the supra-system.
- Nature bats last, and always wins.
- Living and supra-living systems (e.g., organizations) are certainly purposeful in doing what they have to in order to stay alive (operate) and procreate (profit/grow). They are adaptive and evolvable systems that can reconfigure their internals to meet new challenges.
- 3.4.2.2.2 Qualities
 - This refers to the set of aspects that confer systemness on a “thing.”
- 3.4.2.2.3 Attributes
 - We attribute systemness to an entity (or process) based on the fact that what is perceived by another system (we humans for example) is the behavior of a bounded object. When we cannot know directly what is going on inside the object, we can still infer something is happening inside by virtue of sensing what is going in from the outside and what is coming out from within, or, in other words, crossing the boundary, and this includes the responses to forces as well as the production of forces applied to entities in the environment.
- 3.4.2.2.4 Composition
 - The boundary of the system keeps the contents in and the rest of the environment not needed as resources out. A system is composed of components that have interactions with one another. They are linked by various ways, forces, and flows of substances.
- 3.4.2.3 Levels
 - The concept of levels in a hierarchy is quite natural.

• Figure 3.15

Fig. 3.15 This depicts a “map” of system hierarchy (see Fig. 3.14). Level 0 is the SOI. Components (C1 and C2) along with relations (arrows labeled R) constitute the next level down, L + 1. The environment is the next level up, L – 1

- 3.4.3 Using the Framework — This describes how to use the framework
- 3.4.3.1 Applying the Principles at Level – 1 in the Framework
 - We are now in a position to attempt an organization of ontological elements using the framework and examining various proposed elements from the numerous methods discussed above and examined elsewhere. Our starting point is to use Level – 1, the ENVIRONMENT, and Level 0, the existence of a SYSTEM, with the role of CONTEXT and MEANING, focusing our attention on the Purpose of the system.
- 3.4.3.2 Applying the Principles at Level 0 in the Framework
- 3.4.3.3 Applying the Principles at Level 1 in the Framework
- 3.4.4 Upper Ontology
 - What we have accomplished at this point is the construction of an “upper” ontology or the base concepts that are used to derive all other concepts of that which exists in the real world. The framework we employed has provided us with a basic vocabulary of highest-order categories of those things that exist. The work ahead, then, is to construct the “lower” ontology for systemness, e.g., identifying specific categories of things that have specific kinds of causal effect in the world.

Table 3.2 Examples of that which has existence (ontological status) at Level – 1 in the framework

Existence of	
Objects (Substance)	System of Interest, Sources, Sinks, Channels, Material, Energy, Messages
Relations	Source-Of, Sink-For, Relative Position in Space, Relative Activity in Time
Actions (Work)	Applies Force, Moves, Accepts-From, Exports-To, Reacts-To

Table 3.3 Examples of that which has existence (ontological status) at Level 1 in the framework

Existence of	
Objects	Subsystems, Components, Atomic Processes, Channels, Material, Energy, Messages, Stocks/Reservoirs
Relations	Source-Of, Sink-For, Relative Position in Space, Relative Activity in Time
Actions (work)	Applies Force, Moves, Accepts-From, Exports-To, Reacts-To

Note that basically the same ontological items are repeated at this level. Sources and Sinks are replaced by subsystems and components

- Note that it is “-1” and “+1” — see Figure 3.16 for picture focused on SOI.
- 3.4.5 System Domain Ontology
- 3.4.6 Discipline Domain Ontologies
- 3.5 The System Ontology
 - Thus, we will now develop the ontology of systems and derive a terminology that is applicable to any kind of system at any level of complexity. This ontology will be the basis for the development of the lexicon of a system language (SL), to be developed in the next chapter
- 3.5.1 Background Categories
 - 3.5.1.1 Space
 - 3.5.1.2 Time
 - 3.5.1.3 Space-Time.
- 3.5.2 Framework Elements
- 3.5.2.1 ENVIRONMENT
 - Every SOI is embedded in a larger system, the supra-system. Generally, the SOI will interact directly with only a few other subsystems of the same level of organization status and/or atomic components (see below). The environment contains all of the sources of inputs (matter, energy, and messages) and the sinks for outputs (same substances). It also contains all of the channels (or fields) through which flows occur. The entities of the environment connect directly with the boundary of the SOI.
- 3.5.2.2 SYSTEM: The Root Category

◦ Figure 3.16

Fig. 3.16 The Environment-SOI-Subsystems hierarchy represented as a tree structure shows the levels of organization in a complex system. The labels in the various nodes below the root node (SOI) are used to distinguish each subsystem or atomic component and preserve the ordering of the

◦ 3.5.2.2.1 PROCESS

◦ Figure 3.17

Fig. 3.17 All processes transform low-quality material, energy, or messages into high-quality versions of the same. Work processes require the input of high-potential energy to drive the work itself. In doing work, according to the Second Law of Thermodynamics, some of the energy does not accomplish work, but is transformed to a low-potential form—waste heat. The work produces a “product” or high-quality material, or high-potential energy, or messages of greater use (higher information content) downstream. Material transformations involve some material waste products while energy transformations produce a greater proportion of waste heat

◦ Figure 3.18

- 3.5.2.2.2 OBJECT
 - Every real system has physical extent in an appropriate frame of reference. It takes up space and has duration. No two objects may occupy the same space at the same time.
 - There is, however, a situation in which some systems can “seem” to occupy the same space. This occurs when the boundary of an object is fuzzy, that is, the boundary may soften or morph for some period of time. One of the best, and most dramatic, examples of this is when a single person (or a group of individuals) moves from one system in which they participate to another
- 3.5.2.2.3 ENTITY
 - 3.5.2.2.3.1 Actor
 - 3.5.2.2.3.2 Agent
 - A special pattern of an information processing subsystem is a decision maker. The decision maker takes in information from the environment, processes this information in the context of a decision model, and generates a “decision.” The latter is output that is coupled with an effector subsystem to cause behavior to occur. The nature of agents and agency will be covered in Chap. 12.
- 3.5.2.2.4 COMPONENT

Figure 3.19

- 3.5.2.2.5 INTERACTION
 - 3.5.2.2.5.1 Networks (Principle 3)
 - 3.5.2.2.5.2 Complexity (Principle 5)
 - 3.5.2.2.5.3 Hierarchies (Principle 2)
 - 3.5.2.2.5.4 Messages (Principle 7)
- 3.6 Putting It All Together
- 3.6.1 Terminology
 - The point of an ontological study is to determine the existence of objects, their relations with one another, their effects on one another, and their overall structure in time and space. The second point is to assign terms (symbolic names) to these objects, relations, and actions, and to determine legitimate connections between the terms, in other words, the syntax of a language. That will be the task tackled in the next chapter where we elaborate an initial lexicon and syntax of the system language.
 - This work requires establishing a hierarchy of abstractions, such as the idea that there is a universal concept of a movement or "fow" of something (material, energy, or message) that sits atop a Space-Time coordinate structure (a Newtonian version) or a set of distinctive kinds of channels (a relativistic version). A fow of material is distinguished from a fow of energy
- 3.6.1.1 The Natural Language Version of Terms

- Thus, the terms in our ontology of system will attempt to be English words that represent the most abstract conceptualization of the system term relating to the systemese concept.
- 3.6.1.2 A Basic Example of the English Ontology of Systems
 - Finally, we list here a set of terms along with their hierarchical relations derived from using the framework described in Sect. 3.4. This list is not meant to be exhaustive, but it includes some of what we believe to be the most useful concepts in understanding concrete complex systems.
 -
 - These basic concepts of what exists will be expanded throughout the book, but will be given more definitive status in the next chapter.
- 3.6.2 Accounting for Everything
- 3.7 Summary of Ontology and Ontogeny

GM Chapter 4

- Includes the mathematical framework for describing systems.
- Set theory & Graph theory.
- The chapter is about languages for the systems (math, natural language, visual, etc.).
 - Math description is the basis of formal definition. So there can be alignment of shared reference frame for e.g. “component”.
 - Relations among the modalities, gives more holistic understandings of systems/systemsness.
 - Then can communicate and translate among/on/in those spaces; improved (understanding of) bandwidth.
 - In natural language, always the questions of Lexical Semantics. In order to make sure were sharing the same kind of information.
- J. Franklin, Aristotle, reality, mathematics
 - *“An Aristotelian Realist Philosophy of Mathematics: Mathematics as the Science of Quantity and Structure”*
 - Linking to real things; numbers/geometries of things. Simpler maths. Then higher maths build on top.
 - Franklin talks about the units of Things out there. How does the cognitive/conscious system do visual thing identification/clustering/typing/etc. How about the distinct objects in/out there?
 - Identification of e.g. depth of field, Compositionality, conformance/deviance to a norm or standard.
 - Natural & Social Sciences — some of the domains like Information/Complexity/Systems are the Formal science (includes Math).
 - <https://www.sup.org/books/title/?id=2003> **Homo Sacer, Agamben**
- 20 marbles in the set — intuitive natural language aspects of set/category theory.
- Boundaries & to the above
 - Boundaries (modeled on Bayesian graph as Markov Blanket).
 - As one is perceiving sensory patterns (e.g. correlated movement of pixels) in light of embodied/learned reference frames (e.g. depth perception) — posit that there are Neural circuits that do primary visual activities like Edge, Gradient, On-Off/Off-On, etc.
 - So for some low-level features there may be more canalization of the visual/object identification. The information flows forward, has articulation/factorization with the What and Where dorsal/ventral stream in the mammalian brain.
 - Object/Entity of primary ontological status.
 - Bottom layer of the neural net, direct connection to Observation, higher levels of the Neural net / Bayes graph / etc. → higher-order representations. Abstraction.
 - What about Sequences, time-as-process, imperatives/directives, non/propositional knowledge.
 - Some on sequencing is on 1st and this book.
 - Pre-frontal (hierarchical nesting)
 - Cerebellum, encoded programs/procedures in what happens next (B matrix / causal / transition model).
 - Dynamics, Initial conditions, Boundary conditions; System
- Different areas of maths, different axiomatic bases.
 - Any given axiom set constrains to within that math area. The instruments/tools. Different fields of math, back to Franklin — people are good at small numbers of things. Coarse-graining and intuitions. Different types of infinity.
 - The formal theories/methods can be good to do.
 - Self-Identifying objects.... Higher/alternative dimensions

- Operational closure — Autopoiesis, Kant, Organismality.
 - Set of frames — have we got all the frames arising in the universe were discussing.
 - Statistical: Sampling from stationary?
 - <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26370801#>: “Kant’s Concept of Organism Revisited”
 - Identification of Space and Time
 - Formal is just one aspect of Systems Science
 - Cognitive as only one step/aspect of the OODA loop. Still Action in reality, anchors back to
 - “The Origin of Concepts”, Susan Carey (2009), Oxford
 - Where do the concepts come from; how are they formed.
 - There is innate aspect & learned.
 - Taking numbers, and patterns.
 - Both of George’s books discuss Concepts as systems instantiated in neural networks; how they are formed and learned at different levels in the hierarchy.
 - Fido the 🐶, Mammals as a class. Similar across instances.
 - Part 3 in current book (no promises!) — Complex Adaptive Evolvable Systems.
 - Living Systems theory + etc. — tie to cognition & eventually to consciousness.
 - Can see a living thing, human, as complex system with new cognitive structures giving rise to new/different enacted behaviors.
 - Cognitive Science & Systems Science
 - Relationship between computations (e.g. in the digital, neural, etc) — Information Processing.
 - [Chris Fields 2023 course](#).
 - Understanding what Information is, & what it is not. Information & Knowledge.
 - See how the brain is processing these concepts, and treat it as CAES Archetype model — all the component that need to be in any CAES. The forms will differ though will be there. That schema guides how/where to look for the brain.
 - For example governance and strategic management. Consider the prefrontal cortex discussion above — organizer of strategic manipulation of the concepts and models that we already have. What if in the distant future, this or that happens.
 - Cognition in the human brain is natural. Look at the details.
 - General Systems Science
 - Cognitive Science are a viewpoint/perspective. Other frames are needed.
 - Systems Science is both Ontology and Epistemology.
 - An expanded Cognitive Science into e.g. Concepts
 -
-

Chapter 4

A Model of System and a Language to Represent It

- We propose a mathematically based definition of system based on the ontological framework developed in the last chapter. Finally, we use the semantics, syntax, and lexical elements from the ontology and the model of the human systems to

propose a formal (but extensible) language of system.

- 4.1 In This Chapter

- In the last chapter, we developed a set of terms and relations representing the elements of systemness. It was shown how systems come into existence in the real universe by a process of ontogenesis that started with the Big Bang and fundamental particles (matter-like entities) and forces (energy-like) mediated by information and constructing structures that encode knowledge about the history of things. That process did not stop with, for example, the creation of atoms. Indeed, we suspect it continues today so long as **free energy** is available to do the work needed for construction.
- In this chapter, we turn to the use of ontology in devising the one key tool we need in order to express all of the elements of systemness, a language of systems.
- This language is very special as a tool for communications between humans, and between humans and machines. That is, the language of systems possesses both the characteristics of a natural language for expressing systems and the characteristics of a formal language (both mathematics and computation) making it useful in constructing computer models for simulation of the systems we are gaining deep understanding about.
- That is, the language we use for thought is based on systemness. This includes native or innate concepts and built-in mental computations enacting the constructs of systems and their behaviors.
- The systemese hypothesis leads us to the idea that our natural languages are extensions of the fundamental elements.
- Once we have a clear idea of how language works to communicate ideas about systemness we turn to a more direct way to use the ontology

- 4.2 The Communication of Ideas

- Any attempt to produce a language of systems needs to be based on our understanding of human cognition and the nature of public language. Our goal is to link how people communicate ideas about the world to one another and the ability to describe the structures and functions of systems. Additionally, our goal is to formalize the language in such a way that humans can communicate with computers (and vice versa) efficiently and effectively. So, our first task is to consider how ideas are communicated.
- Ideas are mental states that involve the composition of several concepts into single modules of thought. Sentences spoken in public languages express ideas.
- Time and space do not permit a full accounting of mentation here. What follows is a brief outline of the major aspects as related to conscious thought and language.

- 4.2.1 Representations of Concepts, Beliefs, and Ideas

- 4.2.1.1 Concepts

- The mind holds units of thought that correspond with things in the world and we call them concepts. Cognitive scientists and linguists have studied how human beings possess, construct, or form concepts through learning processes, and how they then use concepts to compose ideas that can be shared through language with other humans.

- 4.2.1.1.1 Conceptual Hierarchies

- 4.2.1.1.2 Innate vs. Learned Concepts

- As mentioned above, human beings, and presumably many other kinds of animals, come with built-in, or innate concepts of the most important things in the world that they will need to interact with from an early point in their development. Some of these, such as the “object” concept mentioned above, are already at work in very young infants. There is evidence that the concepts of “causality,” “agent,” “agency,” and “intentionality” are at work at an early age as well (cf., Carey 2009).
- What we don’t come with is specific concepts of particular objects and agents. These have to be constructed through experience with the world.
- And they learn the rules for composing these concepts into ideas, the syntax of their native language.

- 4.2.1.2 Ideas

- Sentences such as “Bob believes Jane believes he likes her,” express how one person can possess a model/concept of another person’s mind, called “theory of mind,” or “folk psychology” in the cognitive science literature (recall Principle #9 in Chap. 2). That sentence also reveals another important aspect of human cognition. The use of the word “believes” reflects on the fact that people are not just conscious (of things in the world) but of their own thoughts (recall Principle #10). They are “self-conscious.”
- 4.2.1.3 Beliefs
 - We will not have a great deal to say about beliefs (as opposed to concepts) other than to recognize that what one believes about the nature of a conceptual object or agent is, or can be, quite idiosyncratic, path dependent on the sequences of experiences one has with the subjects of concepts
- 4.2.2 Names of Things—Abstraction and Language
 - Names of things, relations, and actions are special abstract concepts. They are formed in auditory processing space and are composed of phonemes produced by auditory feature detectors.
 - Words are abstract and mostly arbitrary representations in the brain. But they are associated, through learning, with the actual iconic image of the concept representation in memory. Humans can create other abstract symbols, letters to represent phonemes (or combinations thereof) and written sequences of letters to represent the words.
- 4.2.3 Language of Thought and Innate Concepts.

Figure 4.1

Fig. 4.1 Various processing modules communicate between each other coordinating external communications

- The use of a LOT engine for production of complex concepts starts with the innate archetype concepts discussed above, even before it is used to connect those concepts as ideas (and possibly beliefs).
- As originally conceived, LOT is a computational theory of mind (CMT) where computation is taken to be an algorithmic manipulation of strings of “symbols” (something Fodor seemed to have both asserted and denied!) That neural representations of concepts (things in the world) are very clearly consistent subnetworks of fring patterns constructed either from innate concepts or from learned ones, they can be construed as being symbol-like (cf., Abdou et al. 2018; Brodt et al. 2018). That there is some internal syntax for combining these symbol-like fring patterns into composite patterns in a kind of sequential stimulation, one can say that the brain does indeed compute an internal language to produce constructs that make sense, that is, have semantic content and fulfill pragmatics.
- 4.2.4 The Systemese Hypothesis
 - This hypothesis may be considered speculative, of course. But the existence of some kind of LOT along with an examination of a few of the known innate concepts lends strong support for the idea that LOT is system syntax and those core concepts are system archetypes.
 - Our immediate interest in the systemese hypothesis is in devising a public language (using English names of things, though this is not required) of systems that is based on the ontology framework and embodies the systems structure/function syntax so that human beings can describe systems and their behaviors to other humans and to machines. Both humans and machines (computers) can form representations of the described systems and achieve a more consistent communication between systems in the world, systems in the mind, systems in the abstract, and systems in computer code.
 - That language must include an innate representation of containment and a model of a generic or archetypical container (as mentioned above). It includes an attribute of capacity, which is a variable. Now when a child encounters a real container in the world, they do not have to wonder what on earth it is, their archetype model provides the answer—the syntax and the semantics. The brain builds a higher-level archetype using the sensory attributes of the particular container.

- In sum, then, systemese consists of a set of innate archetype concepts (models) that evolved to reflect the systems (and components of systems) that exist in the environments of animals with which they have to interact.
 - These concepts come with built-in syntactical rules for combination that preserve the semantics and pragmatics of the situations in the world. All animals with brains of any complexity “think” in their version of systemese, and this is not a conscious process.
 - Humans, on the other hand, have an extraordinarily complex environment—complex systems with which to interact—and accordingly have a much more sophisticated set of innate concepts with which to construct more complex thoughts. Moreover, humans possess a supervening concept encoding mechanism that associates specific auditory patterns (speech) with complex constructions, and these become the names given to things, relations, and actions—language.
- 4.3 A Formal Definition of System
 - We are now ready to develop a formal definition of a system that, along with the ontological commitments of the last chapter, will be the basis for producing a language for systems. This language will be used to guide analysis of systems, since the definition tells us what we should be looking for, and to build models of systems at various levels of abstraction.
 - There is a point we need to be clear about. What is being presented here is, itself, a concept about what a system consists of, how it is composed. It is not being represented as the “general theory of systems,” though it might be a candidate for that title. It is based on having made the ontological commitments from Chap. 3 and following them to their “logical” conclusions. That being said, we are fairly certain that if there is a general systems theory, as posited by von Bertalanffy, for example, then it is likely to look something like this. Many theorists have attempted to define systemness in a formal way and suggested that their definition constituted the general theory. Some of them have shared common approaches (e.g., using set theoretical language) yet after nearly six decades, no universal agreement over what exactly “system” means has emerged in the scientific literature. The reader may recall from the discussion in the Preface regarding the way we “talk” about systems science that we regard the latter as more of a meta-science than just another kind of science. Which means that systems science theories are not ordinary theories at all, but metaphysical theories. Ergo, any definition of system must simply accept some ontological (and epistemological) commitments and then get on with it. Only in successes with usage over an extended time will the veracity (or acceptance) of a definition be turned into a meta-theory, i.e., a general theory of systems.
 - The definition is given in three complimentary (should be complementary?) forms: verbal, graphical, and mathematical. All three forms provide views of the system definition that provide access to stakeholders from different backgrounds. The mathematical definition is needed in order to create an abstract representation of the system definition that can be directly applied to creating a language of system (hereafter called SL)
- 4.3.1 Verbal
 - The lexicon of SL is taken from the primitive and derived elements in Chap. 3. All verbal descriptions use those lexical elements as the skeleton of meaningful statements. For example, in describing a subsystem that processes material inputs (with energy) to produce a product output we would simply say something like: “Process M takes in materials A and B from sources 1 and 2 along with energy E from source 3 to make product Z with waste product X going to sinks 5 and 6 respectively, at an efficiency of 68%.”
 - The verbal descriptions start with the lexical elements acting as placeholders for specific items, such as material A is a placeholder for “water” in the above example. With each additional statement, the system description gets refined. As the deconstruction of the system proceeds, sub-paragraphs are added, each describing the subsystem at a lower level of detail.

Figure 4.2 Verbal descriptions have relations that map to the system language

4.3.2 Graphical

- Following the age-old dictum that “A picture is worth a thousand words,” SL provides a graphical way to express systems. This has actually been done in most modeling languages such as Stella (for system dynamics), and SysML. Various kinds of diagrams can be produced to capture the system as a model. Figure 4.3 provides a graphical version of the system paragraph from above.

Figure 4.3

4.3.3 A Mathematical Structure Defining a System

- A formal language is based on the existence of a formal structure into which elements of the language fit (see Pragmatics section below). For example, a computer programming language is based on a formal structure involving arithmetic, logic, and conditional flow control (e.g., IF-THEN) used to describe data processing algorithms. These are realized in an actual computer architecture based on the theory of computation (e.g., the Turing Machine formalism and the von Neumann architecture).
- Deriving a definition of system from the principles and the ontology, a system S is a 7-tuple:

$$S_{i,l} = C, N, G, B, T, H, \Delta t_{i,l} \quad (4.1)$$

- where i and l are indexes. The entire tuple, and essentially all tuples in equations, should have $\langle \rangle$ brackets, Set notation. The index i is a subsystem index and the index l is the level of organization in the system-subsystem hierarchy. Both are 0 for the initial system of interest, $S_{0,0}$ is the designated SOI. Recall from the previous chapter that the ontological framework specified that the SOI be designated as level 0. This will make sense in this definition as we show how the system definition leads to a natural way to deconstruct the component/interaction level (+1) in the framework. Several later chapters in the book will describe the application of these equations (and the knowledgebase described in Chap. 8) to even more complex adaptive and evolvable systems (CAESs) described in Part III.

4.3.3.1 Structural Skeleton

C is a set of components and their “type” along with membership functions in the event the set is fuzzy, that is, the components may have partial inclusion.

$$C_{i,l} = \left\{ (c_{i,1,l}, e_{i,1,l}, m_{i,1,l}), (c_{i,2,l}, e_{i,2,l}, m_{i,2,l}), \dots (c_{i,k,l}, e_{i,k,l}, m_{i,k,l}), \dots (c_{i,n,l}, e_{i,n,l}, m_{i,n,l}) \right\}_l \quad (4.2)$$

Figure 4.4

Figure 4.5

Figure 4.6

4.3.3.2 Interactions

4.3.3.2.1 Between Components Internally

Figure 4.7

4.3.3.2.2 Between Environment and Components of S

Figure 4.8

4.3.3.3 Boundary

- Up to this point the definition of system should resemble those given in most accounts whether in mathematical form or not. Languages for modeling systems, such as system dynamics (SD) utilize the same sets of elements as described so far but not in this mathematical form. At this point we start to depart from historical accounts of system definitions as will be explained along the way. The first departure involves the concept of a boundary. If you recall from the last

chapter, we claimed that boundedness is a real element (has first-class ontological status). Boundedness constructs effective boundaries to systems

- For purposes of analysis and design, we will make boundaries explicit elements of a system definition. The boundary, B in Eq. 4.1, at level I, then is a tuple. That is:

Figure 4.9

Fig. 4.9 Interfaces are associated with the boundary of a system. Here they are shown as rounded rectangles that penetrate the boundary and act as pass-ways for inputs and outputs

- Essentially complete mapping to the “Thing” of Free Energy Principle, these are complementary approaches.

Figure 4.10

Fig. 4.10 Interfaces are represented generically (a) showing the general form of the interface between the outside world and, in this case, an intake process that then supplies the substance flow to the parent process (or SOI). (b) Provides some details of a more complex interface. For example, an active membrane pore on the surface of a cell. The aperture is the main channel control device (here shown as a “ball valve”). Many interfaces are subsystems (processes) in their own right and so will have additional “equipment” devoted to regulating the flow of the substance. Other elements in the figure (e.g., sensor, buffer, and regulator) will be explained below

Figure 4.11

Fig. 4.11 As Simonian complexity explodes up the levels of organization (and complexity), the logarithm of that value rises linearly and gaps (probably exaggerated) in the measure are seen at the major transitions, where the graph line (blue) appears indicates a range of complexities within the various domains

Figure 4.12

Fig. 4.12 An emerg sensing mechanism resulting from the composition of four atomic work processes. The circuit can be used by, for example, a homostat, a cybernetic feedback control

Figure 4.13

Fig. 4.13 These are some of the icons used to represent elements of the system language

Figure 4.14

Figure 4.15

Figure 4.16

- At present it includes such properties as porosity (0 being completely non-porous) and “perceptive fuzziness,” meaning the degree to which it is easily perceived; 0 being able to identify and locate in space the separator between inside and outside any number greater than 0 but less than 1 being the degree to which a physical phenomenon corresponding to “keeping the insides in and the outsides out.”
 - This paper <https://arxiv.org/abs/2207.07620> Weak Markov Blankets in High-Dimensional, Sparsely-Coupled Random Dynamical Systems (2022) — introduced the “Blanket Index”, between 0 and 1, to describe exactly what is being suggested here.

Figure 4.17

- As a rule of thumb, the interfaces for more complex systems tend to be more complex themselves. A simple opening in the wall of a hut functions as a door, but it allows anyone (or anything) to walk through.¹³ An actual hinged door, with door

knobs inside and out, and an internal lock mechanism (keyed from the outside) in a modern (and more complex) structure is a bit more complex and has a controlled entry/exit protocol. Entries and exits from airport departure/arrival gates have become exceedingly complex with separate entry and exit paths required by security needs.

- 4.3.3.4 Transformations

- This is, effectively, an abstract model of the transformation that will be refined as the deconstruction process continues. One of the advantages of following this framework is that the higher-level transformations get refined by discovery of the lower-level ones. Once more is known about the internal transformations of subsystems and their combined effects, the higher-level model can be made more rigorous (Principle 12 in Chap. 2). This recursive improvement tracks the deconstruction all the way down to the leaf nodes in the system tree.
- When system engineers believe they are obtaining such a specification (e.g., in requirements gathering), they are often faced later with discontinuities between expectations and actualities that are highly disruptive to design projects. With the approach of deep analysis promoted in this book (top-down deconstruction of transformations and bottom-up refinement) the engineering process will be following a formal procedure that they often end up following informally anyway!
 - I believe this corresponds to a hierarchical predictive coding scheme, implemented sequentially via a cognitive agent or team, by their regime of attention to the system of interest.

- 4.3.3.5 Memory

- 4.3.3.6 Time

- 4.3.3.6.1 Time Indexing

- 4.3.3.6.2 Cyclic Intervals

- There are instances when the periodicity of a cycle may be varied in a constrained-random fashion, using, for example, the bounded Monte Carlo method.
- In FEP we can use a sampling-based Monte Carlo approach, and/or a Variational Inference approach.

- 4.3.3.7 Considering Very Complex Systems

- Complexity is a very difficult concept and the word itself has many different senses. Intuitively most people have the notion that if something has many parts (i.e., subsystems) and many interactions (i.e., flows) between the parts and many interactions with its environment, then it is complex. There are many different ways to characterize the complexity of a system.
- Here we investigate two complementary approaches.
 - The first looks at what we can consider “structural” complexity using the above-mentioned intuition.
 - The second approach looks at dynamic or “behavioral” complexity, that is, how are the behaviors of the complex system in relation to their environmental interactions. Both include consideration for the number of states that a system can be in, but behavioral complexity looks only at the states of interactions with the environment.

- 4.3.3.7.1 Simonian Complexity

- There are two fundamental aspects that go into defining complexity: structural complexity and functional complexity. One deals with the hierarchy of modules and submodules and the other deals with what each module does. The former is exposed by the structural decomposition process outlined in Chap. 6. The latter is much more difficult to estimate. For our purposes here, we will use the concept of a state space to approximate the metric of functional complexity.

- 4.3.3.7.2 Behavioral Complexity

- Behavioral complexity can be far more difficult to characterize compared with structural complexity. The behaviors of a system are related, clearly, to the number of states the system might be in as described above. However, there are possibilities of transitions from internal states that are not easily modeled by finite state machines, even probabilistic machines. Among these possibilities is behavior resulting from internal non-linearities, resulting, for example, in chaotic behaviors. That is, if one captures time series data on the externally displayed states of a system, they describe a chaotic attractor basin in phase space.

- 4.3.3.8 Ontogenesis of Greater Complexity
 - We now turn attention to the problem of how to use our ontological framework, understanding of ontogenesis, and our formal framework for describing systemness to create a way to describe all systems, but particularly able to describe even the most complex systems we encounter. We need a language.
- 4.4 Toward a Language of Systems
 - Armed with the mathematical structure described in Eq. 4.1 and subsequent equations, along with the ontological commitments in Chap. 3, we are in a position to design a formal language of systems (SL). With such a language we will be able to describe, in principle, any system in any domain, for example, biological or sociological. The language uses generic terms to represent various elements of systemness, for example, nouns like “process” to embody a system that does work and “fow” to embody the movement of materials, energies, and messages. Its syntax is based on allowable patterns or relations, for example, a work process that varies a fow (e.g., a valve or resistor) cannot be put inside a stock; it has to be inserted into the fow.
- 4.4.1 Semantics
 - SL is a “description” language. It is used to describe structures, relations, functions, and the other items in the ontology of Chap. 3. This is different from a typical programming language, which is designed to “describe” algorithms, or sequences of steps in a data manipulation process. An algorithmic description language (i.e., programming language like JavaScript) is incorporated into SL to specify the operations of behaviors of the various elements, such as interface protocols. Relations between elements are built into the syntax (see below).
 - 4.4.1.1 Lexical Elements
 - 4.4.1.2 Descriptions
 - 4.4.1.2.1 Components
 - 4.4.1.2.2 Flows
 - 4.4.1.2.3 Behaviors
 - 4.4.1.3 Syntax
- 4.5 Example
 - As mentioned above, SL is a description language; it has more in common with document description languages like hypertext markup language (HTML) used to describe web pages for display in browsers than with conventional programming languages
 - . Combined with a scripting language like JavaScript, which is used to specify behaviors within the web page environment, a markup-like language is quite powerful in providing form and function in models. SL has much in common with HTML, or more correctly with the Extended Markup Language (XML), which is a superset of HTML. Below we provide a very simplified example of a system described in a markup language we’ll refer to as sysXML to give some idea of how this computational platform can be used to do so. We should emphasize that this exercise is just a preliminary concept of how SL might be implemented and is as much a playful exploration as a serious example.
 - Figures 4.11, 4.12, 4.13 and 4.14 provide examples of a system of interest in SL graphics along with some of the captured data, that is, labels. Listings 4.1, 4.2, 4.3 and 4.4 show the sysXML output from the captured data as organized in the knowledgebase after analysis. The system is analyzed following the procedures given in Chap. 6, in a top-down decomposition with the analytical engine capturing the results into the knowledgebase format that will be described in more detail in Chap. 8. From there, it is possible to generate a systems dynamics-like simulation model and produce a human- (and machine-) readable sysXML specification as shown below.
- Listing 4.1 The XML output from the knowledgebase of the description of the Steel-Plant system. This shows the opening of the description (an SOI with id of SO) and its main environment (level-1) sources, sinks, and flows.
- XML code uses tag elements to denote the structural element being described. We have defined the tag “SOI” to represent the start of a system description document. Tags are demarcated by the “<” and “>” characters and the end of a description is given with the tags “:” The other entities included within the brackets are called attributes. Here the majority of attributes are “name,” “id” (meaning the identification number in prefix dotted number format), “type” and “subtype.” The

latter two attributes may be present multiple times since elements might have more principle and subordinate characteristics that need to be identified. The words in all capital letters are predefined attribute values that largely follow the ontology of the last chapter. We suspect that all readers will have no trouble interpreting the tags and their contents (which are for the most part simple strings, but also additional tags that are part of the content of superior tags—which are indented to show their subordination).

- Figure 4.14 represents what a user/analyst would see on a screen using the analytical engine we will describe in Chap. 6. They would drag elements to their positions and be prompted for the names/identifications of the elements along with other attributes as shown in Table 4.1. Later, the system would produce the code in Listing 4.1.
- Listing 4.2 Boundary description (note the indentation level is the same as the) tags.
- In Fig. 4.16 we begin the process of exposing the internal subsystems of the Steel-Plant SOI. In this depiction, we have identified four internal subsystems of interest, three associated with the environment-boundary interfaces and one, the production shop that interacts with the three
- Listing 4.3 This listing does not show the whole system but does show how the components, fows, and other objects in Eq. 4.1 are represented.
- Listing 4.4 This listing shows how the subsystems are treated. In this listing we decompose the Iron-Inventory, identified as CO.1 in Fig. 4.17.
- 4.6 Conclusion
 - In this chapter, we have covered a number of closely related topics surrounding the concept of a language of systems. We started by describing systems thinking. First, we considered the way in which some people can think explicitly about systemness. This has been the standard way of looking at it. But we then claimed that there is another way to look at thinking itself as implicit systems thinking. That is, our brains already communicate among various representational modules based on the kinds of systems constructs explored in the last chapter. Many linguistics researchers and philosophers of mind believe that every human brain has a subconscious language of thought that supports the symbolic module interchanges/integrations. We suggested that this is actually “systemese,” the mental language.
 - Now that we have a language, we turn to a somewhat more detailed examination of the entire understanding process showing how the various pieces operate and fit together. That will be the subject of Chap. 5.
- .
- .
- .

GM Chapter 5

GM Chapter 8

Articles for Systems Science

From [George Mobus](#)

 [SystemsThinkingArticle1.doc](#)

 [SystemsThinkingArticle2.doc](#)

 [SystemsThinkingArticle3.doc](#)

 [SystemsThinkingArticle4.doc](#)

What I will try to do is edit the four together as an essay vs. article, removing the obviously no longer valid bits about a program at UWT. Not familiar with this Zenodo so will leave the disposition up to you. If it isn't too long it might fit as a Perspective for Science or something.

Charlie Hall

▼ Charlie Hall — Limits of Growth.

- ▷ This is in some past Saturday ISSS sessions
- ▷ All the work may not make a difference if we do not attend to limits of growth.

▼ General topics and considerations — people who have done a lot of work in [Broken link](#)

- ▷ When someone does not have the energy to extensively comment.
- ▷ The only way to prove/validate this technology is to probe with alternative views. To challenge what is being done with Systems, with what is meant.
- ▷ Can prompt new connections in the work and have the person validate this.
- ▷ Various attempts to draw up lists of the Systems Theory candidates. By what criteria do we judge these theories from/with?
- ▷ Survey of the criteria, and cross reference across frameworks. Has anyone done a review/meta-analysis of this?

▼ [Len Troncale](#) may have done this work, on General General Theory

- ▷ What would a general systems theory look like if you bumped into it?
- ▷ George never described the theory of systems, it is a framework for systemness. May be hard to escape some linguistic baggage.
- ▷ Absolute General — Applies to all kinds of systems, across fields of study. Science studies things, [Broken link](#) has to study across these systems.
- ▷ the general theory of systems may end up being a system
- ▷ Tied to a person — “X’s theory of...”, it is like a menu. Choosing from columns at the restaurant. There is a strong attitude in [ISSS](#) and around, of Theoretical and Methodological Pluralism (see: Helen Longino on Scientific pluralism). There are various applicable theories and methods. However all equal credit in evaluation or presentation, is untenable.
- ▷ Shingai’s most recent blog post [Systemism as Ideology](#).
- ▷ as per the theory of motivated numeracy, the more logical cased you are the more able you are to fool yourself on emotionally charged issues
- ▷ [The Rise of Systems Theory: An Ideological Analysis by Robert Lilienfeld](#)
- ▷ Fun to imagine, the debates among different systems scientists.
- ▷ so, how can we get a half consensus on what body of works to get started with, or is the plan to be more random?
- ▷ <https://home.nomic.ai/wiki> && <https://atlas.nomic.ai/>
- ▷ <https://zenodo.org/record/8025957> Comments on AI Accountability Policy Submitted to NTIA Docket 2023-0005-0001 by IRSIRI, All, PFH, and COGSEC
- ▷ Systems intelligence can help us understand situations/consequences.
- ▷ Small Is Beautiful, 25th Anniversary Edition: Economics As If People Mattered: 25 Years Later: <https://www.amazon.com/Small-Beautiful-25th-Anniversary-Commentaries/dp/0881791695>
- ▷ We could do the reverse? Have ISSS members provide commentaries on current emerging work?
- ▷ Cynthia Kurtz, Participatory narrative inquiry.
- ▷ <https://www.goodreads.com/book/show/22392219-working-with-stories-in-your-community-or-organization>
- ▷ Real test: adding another perspective/corpus to the initial testing one, and understand/evaluate the changes. We are talking about words used, in describing the same thing (e.g. Claire used some other term for Systemness). “That’s what I’m talking about”. In Europe they talk of “Systemics”.

- ▷ Would applying the tool to the different corpuses, of research work, start to converge on a more limited/delineated set of terms. <https://www.ontologyportal.org/> and WordNet.

▼ Broken link

▼ Randall & Gary Smith — working with GPT4 on developing articles.

- ▷ From meeting 1-2 weeks ago, and processing the results of the exercise.
- ▷ What are features to consider when designing/exploring how to use such methods?
- ▼ They adapted some of the concepts that Gary was working with, and related it to a narrative discussion of Broken link . So it bears on:
 - ▷ Developing content (humans using tools).
 - ▷ Not differentiating LLM in principle for other tools like e.g. spellcheck (that wouldn't be subject to human review and consideration).
 - ▷ It is an exercise in creativity, creative thinking, creative (and accurate writing) in describing our understandings of the concepts.
- ▷ Developing citations.... in response to the set of activities in the experiment.
- ▼ Randall noticed that in developing the prompt, and developing responses to varieties of prompts — Text was returned that looked like citations, though not checked. Not always transparent as to where the linkages are. Could be a lot of work to authenticate the reference materials
 - ▼ Can spot citations that are valid — get initial judgement around whether the output is valid.
 - ▷ George, students are very good in recognizing the structure of a paper in terms of Citations, References, etc. They start putting things in. There are ways to determine whether a citation is valid. For example what we would expect of a referee in a journal article — enough familiarity with a field, to rapidly determine whether it is relevant.
 - ▷ It depends on how zoomed in & technical the references and citations are. This also requires work and expertise, which is a limiting resource in many cases.
 - ▼ The person who is generating the prompt and looking for an output — needs to be adequately grounded in the subject matter they are looking for, so they can make valid assertions.
 - ▷ Is this practical? — For any given individual to know all of that existing (training) information, and evaluate novelty/relevance.
 - ▷ Usage of knowledge structures, possibly in rhetorical assertion architecture (e.g. [TrustFinder](#)) linking citation to context.
 - ▷ Developing semantic provenance systems for integrity of the informational supply chains.
 - ▼ Prompt flow:
 - ▷ Analyze the above text and simply list everything that looks like it is a citation or reference.
 - ▷ For the list of citations, please use web lookup to investigate whether each citation is available on the public internet. Return two lists, one of valid citations (all metadata information in the citation is true and available) and one of invalid citations (not able to be found on the public internet).
 - ▷ For the list of valid citations.....
 - ▷ For the list of invalid citations.....
 - ▷ What is an appropriate level of due diligence?
 - ▼ We could take a look at Broken link and Proceedings. Look at the citation networks — how often do newer papers utilize the older citations?
 - ▷ Combine the semantic/language analyses with bibliometric analysis

- ▷ Also there is this “dark matter” of citations, the invisible (though possibly assailable) influence of different language use on every expression. Preserving the integrity of the original works while utilizing some aspects of their specific contributions.
- ▷ Source tagging/embeddings.
- ▷ Temporal tagging/embeddings

▼ Language Models =/= Knowledge Model

- ▷ In observing the children and grandchildren developing — to an extent repeating their context's ways of talking. And how they connect sentence & intelligence with language processing.
- ▷ Exploring this relationship of LLM & multiple Knowledge models
- ▷ Current model's input is (labeled) text, this seems to go far/fast in some (not all!) context.
- ▼ Generation of discussions within ISSS and outside / on the interface. Hopefully we show up well here.
 - ▷ To what extent, comments spoken/written yesterday, reflect generalized fear/anxiety around AI/technology, rather than specific aspects of Language Models.
- ▷ The biggest fear with AI is fear itself | De Kai | TEDxSanMigueldeAllende
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WU-RUIZWkio>
- ▷ Humans have a natural tendency to see sentience in inanimate objects. This might be a basis for seeing intentions in AIs

▼ Language models.

- ▷ Predominant in people's thinking.
- ▷ Large tech companies also integrating into their technology.
- ▷ Education is/was formulated around making the information more accessible.
- ▷ This may also tie in to the physics of ‘perception’ of actions, context, etc. that I am delving into...
- ▷ Possible for us (ISSS) to explore and even use an open source language model server/system such as Bloom
- ▷ <https://techcrunch.com/2022/07/12/a-year-in-the-making-bigsciences-ai-language-model-is-finally-available/>

▼ Ways in which LLM exploration, touches on transdisciplinary understandings (Broken link), getting at different understandings.

▼ Interface — To what extent is it Technology, Human focused?

- ▼ Where we are e.g. composing papers or texts with LLM, it is our partner/co-creator in meaning-making. We are talking with each other, looking at text.
 - ▷ This can be addressed with OBS virtual camera (need to start this before the meeting).
 - ▷ How do we work with AI?

▼ Pattern Languages, College of Exploration, Meta-Design, settings. This is why we split the two conversations into Broken link and Education.

- ▷ There is a lot of Resources out there, and Technologies (previous digitization efforts).
- ▷ We can do a lot of work to facilitate the human, and make it work well. The human experience of being together. Online is a helpful way to do it, meeting in person is usually inviable.
- ▷ Consideration of the relationship between Humans and Machine — ongoing struggle of the 250 years of Systems and Cybernetics. What we are facing with the archives — unless we can use machines to help us bootstrap the synthesis of all these individual human products, trying to stand on each other's shoulders (language issues! people don't build on each other's work). There is an opportunity to provide synthesis and overview, a periodic table of system, things that always became reduced down to individual works and starting from scratch. Limitations of the capabilities of individual humans.

- ▷ The exciting challenge and opportunity for LLM, and the imperative in the ISSS, is for those who have asked philosophical questions, language, decision-making — imperative to make the work accessible. Some have been working on synthesis projects for many years. The synthesis is a massive challenge.
- ▷ Redundancy in conversation — same pieces going around and around. Something needs to move?
- ▷ Hierarchy theory, Ontology of language, semantic webs — all are conjoined in this area.
- ▼ Language-as-such has properties that are not the same as e.g. manifest linear strings of symbols or phonemes.
 - ▷ As an Area of Inquiry, Language is holographic.
 - ▷ So LLM inputs (indeed any inputs based upon biological system) are holographic. LLM can rapidly access information, in the holographic encounter. The output is again linearized.
- ▼ Three Systemic Models
 - ▷ **Theoretical frames:** What is an LLM? What are the domains? What constitutes the Holographic/Linear components?
 - ▷ **Interactive study:** Second level Systems community can explore — how are such models used in co-creation of Meaning and Realities? Experimental.
 - ▷ **A question of pragmatic utility:** How does the ISSS use ISSS agenda.
- ▷ 1. How do LLM work (technical discussion)?
- ▷ 2. What is our relationship/engagement with the tools AND broader systems?
- ▼ 3. How does this relate to Broken link, Languageing, Systemese, the ways in which language shapes worlds?
 - ▷ Possible Broken link around Language, how/what is used.
 - ▷ From the munching of words, towards integrated information? The information is holographic?
 - ▼ Language, and culture, as holographic relationships — organized as a whole, these systems have a holographic capacity. And this is captured in some ways via the modeling and training.
 - ▷ Also this may divert/overcomplicate things — the LLM is using Vector Embeddings. Holographic properties; various ways/instances of both/all of this, and nuance.
 - ▷ Not overcomplicating the language, even about LLM. With basic understanding, metaphors and mappings may come into play. Introducing new allusive/related terms, may or may not help any given person.
 - ▷ LLM are a technique nested within larger scope of computational statistical modeling. So various Map-Territory considerations and otherwise.
- ▼ 4. What to do with our ISSS Archives and Broken link
 - ▼ Here we are in ISSS with attention to e.g. members, scope of the ISSS.
 - ▷ Also there can be broader building of competence and applications.
 - ▷ So that the public is better in position to use, and have the ongoing conversations.
 - ▷ Already these models have been in used (e.g. ChatGPT current version ENDED training in 2021).
- ▼ Cultures — Inter-generational, Multi-cultural — The language use is changing. The resilience, sensitivity to difference words/sentences can be variable.
 - ▷ Incumbent on the
 - ▷ We are learning, and this is related to what questions to ask. This is not simply something in a tube that is squirted out. There are complex causes & consequences, including the dangerous.
- ▼ Project-based perspective — Making sense of the next steps.
 - ▼ Spin out proof of concept projects:

- ▼ **Demonstrations** with Education.
 - ▼ What is the operational modification that enables the rest of the ISSS to be joining into the conversation?
 - ▼ Something on the website — “have a conversation with..... James Miller”. — Something that can be offered to the membership, and make it actual and grow something.
 - ▷ Conversations of a sort with Miller, Rosen etc is a real possibility now as a target for ISSS (if one can handle the copyright issue).
 - ▼ Personalities
 - ▷ Some feelings like there is “cults of personalities” — making a point by referring to a person.
 - ▷ Example: a reviewer of George’s textbook, wanting more historical synthesis. Going back to seminal notions, and the development of their ideas. They decided, No, that is not systems science. We need to be looking at the Synthesis — how the aspects play into being a system.
 - ▷ History and Philosophy of Science is not Science.
 - ▷ What someone has stated is their expression, that is not the internal coherence of Broken link . That is a **human touchpoint, the context around the personality**, is part of this!
 - ▷
 - ▼ How to Synthesize through the whole? **The overall synthesis**, and not needing to start from scratch. Can’t we integrate their insights?
 - ▷ This is distilled into e.g. axioms, processes
 - ▼ Having both the Broken link.
 - ▷ Story-telling version of a science — other side — Textbook style literature — other side — hybrid.
 - ▷ Point of reference — as it has been, big men and big ideas. Artificial intelligence? How are we co-creating meaning?
 - ▷ To do a couple of annual meetings, to see developments/evolutions among meetings.
 - ▷ **Structured Dialog** — — Not just learning about what LLMs can do for e.g. individuals or organizations, rather more in line with the social Trintab concept.
 - ▼ FYI: The 3rd Thursday of May has been designated as Global Accessibility Awareness Day. Here is a link to the GAAD2023 events occurring today: <https://accessibility.day/events/>
 - ▷ ISSS could consider doing something in a future conference.
 - ▼ Broken link
 - ▷ See previous notes which may be well-scattered.
 - ▼ Broken link
 - ▷ Goal is to provide the infrastructure to enable the systems community to move forward.
 - ▼ Previously the entire contents of the ISSS archives were handed over.
 - ▷ Coda representation of the data is a proof of concept or draft.
 - ▷ --
 - ▼ Also Rob is developing the website for the broader community so that Broken link can be useful. Also this entails that the ISSS data is updated. More spreadsheets will be incoming.
 - ▷ Tom Marzolf may have some information and connections on this.
 - ▷ Digitization of archives. Jamie’s email, could connect with e.g. Broken link

Tom Marzolf

- ▼ 🌐 Tom Marzolf — Systems <https://web3.iss.org/marzolf-nov2021/index.html>
- ▼ Tom, discussing — it is a one-person model, at a2hosting.com, and displayed on the front page of iss.org — in the “World of Systems” box
 - ▷ They also talked about another modeling software.
 - ▷ Wanting to ensure that ISSS has the ability to continue this work and model.
 - ▷ Tom started studying, keeping notes, ideas — fragmented across files. As a modeler, in day job, he envisioned a single model that captured everything, that was adaptable, non-redundant, etc. Tom developed a model to do this.
 - ▷ Universe, in a systems-oriented perspective. — To do this, focusing on the simpler starter area of “Systems Commons”
- ▼ Tom is fine with making a copy available.
 - ▷ There is a lot of information that is in there, and also can be developed further.
 - ▷ Tom can send Peter the current version, and source code.
- ▷ It is up all the time while working, and captures something every day. What is currently available on the ISSS Website is more than a year old (there are some updates and additions). What is currently there, is simpler and focuses on non-controversial facts.
- ▷ Schema
- ▼ Classes
 - ▷ People
 - ▷ Documents
 - ▷ Websites
 - ▷ Quotations
- ▼ Written in UML
 - ▷ Some costly modeling tools do use this (IBM Rational). However also it can be exported and used in other programs (cheaper or free tools).
 - ▷ With Bruce M., is was possible to export from modeling software
- ▼ Can it become a ISSS model, not just a single-person model?
 - ▷ There has to be some coordination — e.g. some central person? Github? Other coordinating mechanism.
- ▼ What is the functionality?
 - ▷ Export — puts into standard UML format.
 - ▼ Organizing the whole —
 - ▷ Building on this Synthesis, so that work does not start from scratch.
 - ▷ So that we build together. Problem: Everything becomes custom.
 - ▷ Tom’s work has a critical mass
 - ▷ Len, Francois, and other archival projects/attempts.
 - ▷ Topos Institute — Archival developments and challenges, even with the narrower (still broad) question of system.
 - ▷ So coming up with an archiving approach, getting a critical mass.
 - ▷ Concept mapping

- ▼ Finding information, and continuing to update it, so it becomes a standard source of information.
 - ▷ About People, Organizations, Ideas, etc.
 - ▷ Quotations (organized in some way by subject).
 - ▷ Gradually organizing into e.g. Disciplines, Themes (including 🗃️ Education), keeping this adaptable. Needs to be kept adaptive.
 - ▷ Simulation (not currently used).
 - ▷ Domain-specific ontologies that can map together (not currently used).
- ▷ Rigor and evidence-based aspect of Tom's work. In the Holism SIG — what Tom brings in to “System”, “Dimension” as evidence to keep things grounded in discussions. This is what the discipline needs in the work; a structured ontology, and a reminder about how we can operate as Systems Science investigators.
- ▷ What we want — all these things like quotations, citations, etc (historical) and the concepts (e.g. George's textbook) and the coherent paths that link them together
- ▼ If we start with a structure of the core principles and concepts, then have linkages with the Entities/Objects in Tom's database. Start with a skeleton of the fundamentals of systems, then use this to branch out.
 - ▷ Someone is researching “Holarchy” — who has researched this, and what other related concepts exist?
 - ▷ Start with the core integration? Starting with a collection of things?
 - ▷ This is the meta-root of the issue..... And there en-lies the challenge.
 - ▷ Starting with a core knowledge model, then developing and integrating. Rather than continuing this argument, how/should something be included?
 - ▷ Everyone who has written about Systems has foregrounded the topics, with different intentions and outcomes.
 - ▷ Views & Viewpoints. Working with patterns, coming from different viewpoints, why they have different preferences.
 - ▷ What is the Thing they are looking at? We only know their traces.
 - ▷ Outcome oriented — what should/could be known at the end of High School here or there?
- ▼ Multiple rendering/realizations.
 - ▷ Warfield, Structured dialogs. Leveraging tools for common reference.

Yiannis

- ▼ yesterday had a Structured Democratic Dialog (SDD), Chris Smerald was there, watch this space.
 - ▷ There is a link to some outcomes, [a google document is being created for this](#).
 - ▷ They start with a Question, then some Suggestions, and details like How it would work & What would be needed.

Jamie Rose

.....

Website

- i. [@Peter D Tuddenham](#) started two education pages on ISSS (education, members education)

Website Documentation

General ISSS Website Documentation and Notes

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1CqVX6POobXkaH1YdhJhQ9_-nW7ocKInleUfXDB-grJo/edit

Documentation folder

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1Aa28M40xSAXGa3_q3kgPNgXj98iPy4Q4

MediaWiki

Role of wiki.iss.org for educational purposes — Starting with people

Note — Also discussed in Knowledge Engineering.

https://coda.io/d/ISSS-Knowledge-Engineering_dPEy1CASVfL/MediaWiki_su55x#_JurWL

Yearbook

GENERAL SYSTEMS Yearbook of the International Society for the Systems Sciences Founded by LUDWIG von BERTALANFFY (1901-1972) and ANATOL RAPOPORT (1911-) Volume XXXII 1989 Edited by Howard T. Odum Environmental Engineering Sciences University of Florida Gainesville, FL 32611

📎 General+Systems+Volume+XXXII.pdf

<https://www.isss.org/admin2/filemanager/document.php?d=7736663100195086536>

Standards

- Next generation science standards: <https://www.nextgenscience.org/>
 - Educational materials for teachers
- .

Education Overview

The [ISSS Education Directory](#) provides an [Education Overview](#) on this Coda document.

ISSS Education Directory

Department		Name	Description
▼ Education Overview	4	Education Overview	This very Education Overview page — here you are!
		ISSS	Details on ISSS , for example links and By-laws
		Education People	Table of People ~ ISSS Education
		Notes	Unsorted and sundry Notes
▼ Education	4	Education	Summary page of Education initiatives at ISSS
		Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions	Holding Education Aspects & Initiatives , actual and suggested
		? Questions	? Questions to keep in mind for Systems Education
		Systems Tools, Courses, Resources, Organizations	Systems Tools, Courses, Resources, Organizations , skills, settings, and more.
▼ Communications	2	Communications	Coordination center for Education Communications
		VP Education copypaste	VP Education copypaste for ease of copy-and-paste

Below, this description came from the old bylaws, and is in revisions for Policies and Procedures at ISSS.

Educational Programs and Materials Committee

- The goal of the committee will be to promote the exchange, development, and application of system science education materials for the benefits of the affiliates and the general membership of the ISSS.
- This committee shall be composed of the VP for Systems Education (as Co-Chairperson) and individuals representing various educational programs and producers of educational materials and such other members as the President shall appoint. The [other co-] Chairperson shall be elected by the committee for a five-year term.
- [various ways to update and evolve this writing, as we e.g. interface in open and participatory settings, engage with partners, etc...]

-
-
-
-
- From the old ISSS Bylaws: <https://www.iss.org/by-laws/>

- **Education and ISSS overall Objectives**

- 2.2 Objectives. The following objectives are specific to the overall purpose:
 - 7. To develop, to encourage the development of, and to provide for programs of [education](#) in systems thinking and application.
 - 8. To perform, encourage, and provide for charitable, scientific, literary, and [educational](#) acts and works.

- **VP of Education ~ role description**

- 4.6.3.8 Vice-President for Communication and Systems [Education](#).
 - a. The Vice-President for Systems [Education](#) is responsible for facilitating systems [education](#) by reviewing and communicating practices and standards for high-quality systems [education](#).
 - b. The Vice-President for Systems [Education](#) shall study and report on [educational](#) initiatives in systems [education](#) worldwide.
 - c. The Vice-President for Systems [Education](#) will advocate for special issues of journals, focusing on systems [education](#).

- **The committee for Educational Programs**

- 4.8.5 [Educational](#) Programs and Materials Committee.
 - This committee shall be composed of the VP for Communications and Systems [Education](#) (as Co-Chairperson) and individuals representing various [educational](#) programs and producers of educational materials and such other members as the President shall appoint. The Chairperson shall be elected by the committee for a five year term.

- **ISSS and Education**

- 6.5.3 Scholarly and [educational](#) publications should be promoted by the Society.

Education People

People ~ ISSS Education

Name	Last contact	Next contact	Interest	Status	Notes	Drafting	Short note & Next step	Email
Raphael Arar	6/16/2024		Yes	Available to help				
Craig Lindell	6/16/2024		Yes	Available to help				
Graeme Nicholas	6/16/2024		Yes	Available to help			See "Latest Publications"	
James Rose	6/16/2024		Yes	Available to help			8/18/22 Sent link for time to meet	
Shann Turnbull	6/16/2024		Yes	Available to help			8/18/22 Sent link for time to meet	
Swaminathan Natarajan	6/16/2024		Yes	Available to help			Keep posted, very interested to help	
Roelien Goede	6/16/2024		Yes	Available to help				
Marty Jacobs	6/16/2024		Yes	Available to help			8/18/22 Sent link for time to meet	
George Mobus	6/16/2024		Yes	Available to help				
Dave Gould	6/16/2024		Yes	Available to help				
Peter Robertson	6/16/2024	9/27/2022	Yes	Available to help			8/23/2022 had meeting — available to be contacted regarding his programs, etc.	
Shae Brown	6/16/2024		Yes	Available to help				
Don Peel	6/16/2024		Yes	Available to help				
Peter D Tuddenham	6/16/2024		Yes	Available to help			Keep posted (ISSS officer)	
Eun Jai	6/16/2024		Yes	Available to help				
Jennifer Makar	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Bill Shireman	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Scott Jackson	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Stuart Umpleby	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Pille Bunnell	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted			Keep posted (12/2022 or after)	
Michele Friend	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted			Keep posted (ISSS officer)	
Haider Al-Shareefy	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted			Keep connected with Tech and Publicity	
Len Troncale	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted			Watch his videos when he sends them.	
William Smith	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Alexander N. Christakis	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Liesbeth Feikema	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Wilma Coetzee	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Steven Schneider	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted			Awaiting a fuller response	
Charles A. Hall	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Benjamin Taylor	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Alex Barnes	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted			Email Early September	

Shaun Applegate-Swanson	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted			Email Early September	
Gerald R Midgley	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Shirley Bekins	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted			Email Early September	
Jan Borda	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Paul Barnett	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Tony Markatos	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Patrick Hoverstadt	6/16/2024	9/7/2022	Yes	Keep posted			— SCiO	
Luis Sambo	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted			Keep updated in beginning of 2023	
Prashun Duuta	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Gary Smith	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted			Email Early September	
Michael C Jackson	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted			Email Early September	
Dave Snowden	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted			Email Early September	
Daniel Sanderson	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted			Planksip	
Janos Korn	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Shingai Thornton	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
David Pinto	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted			Squale	
Chris Smerald	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Chris Skelly	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
John & Pam	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Julia Brodsky	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Narayan Wang	6/16/2024	11/2/2022	Yes	Keep posted				
Peter Bond	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Javier Calvo-Amodio	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Marc Pierson	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Yiannis Laouris	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Jessie Henshaw	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Karl Hebenstreit	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Sa Liu	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Lynn Rasmussen	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Daniel F	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Rob Young	6/16/2024		Yes	Keep posted				
Kerry Turner	6/16/2024							
Dennis	6/16/2024							

- Dave Douglass (In), extensive work with discourse analysis and cybernetics specifically).
- Adam Pease (SUMO)

Notes

- Starting to make Systems video?
 - [@Videos](#)
- systemigrams (Boardman & Sauser) — Hugh D. Lester on LinkedIn
- **Systems Thinking has some great concepts and I've endeavoured, over the years, to integrate this thinking into my work on organisational (mainly process) improvement. I have found this difficult as there does not seem to be a methodology and toolset for any practical application. I've used Inisght Maker (free online stock and flow and agent-based modelling) to capture causal loop models, but I feel that Systems Thinking needs to have a Lean six sigma style methodology and Minitab style tool. I appreciate the difference between deterministic and probabilistic modelling and I know ST and LSS are quite different but, at the moment ST feels a bit like a 'smoke and mirrors' conjuring trick where practitioners can twist and turn anyway they like to claim they are wise after the event. Some standard approach, modelling standard and useful toolset needs to emerge to make it relevant. Maybe such things exist and I am not aware of them - please let me know if this is the case.**
- .
 - We can not really use analysis because if we break up a system with out giving up front priority to interrelationships when we later go to add in the relationships the result is going to be a complex mess
 - We can not use synthesis by itself because in order to "lump" the parts together we need to first have a break up into parts.
 - So how do we hands-on, specifically, concretely DO a logical, natural break up of the system?
- .
- .

Participating in ISSS Education

- Live Education meetings
- Get familiar with the Coda and add resources/details anywhere (request edit access if needed)
- Explore and reflect on the [? Questions](#)
- Review the [👉 Education Aspects, Initiatives, Dimensions](#) and see if you want to join any ongoing projects, or activate some other area.
- ????? — If you have some other interest or excitement about Education at the end of 2022 or ideas for 2023, then please get in contact and let's work to structure the collaboration.

Knowledge Engineering

Knowledge has to be structured in order to be meaningful.

Live Knowledge Engineering Meetings

Video playlists and Meetings.

 [Live Education meetings](#)

https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL36GDzgkIWrmJvnc_xwIZiJFcgK0FQbx7

 [Live Knowledge Engineering Meetings](#)

https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL36GDzgkIWrlMofRzb0h2qqwi_pjabb8t

2022

#1 September 8, 2022

Meeting transcript & recording

- <https://youtu.be/8-oCW7YrBEo>

Feedback before the meeting

- @Yiannis: I would like to propose and discuss the benefits of using a well-known, crowd-sourcing system such as MediaWiki as the best possible choice for this task.
- @Olaf: set realistic expectations and objectives, and work on concrete tasks step by step. Perhaps first inventories and update what there is already, after which next steps can be undertaken. what does ISSS want to offer to its members and the professional community in terms of knowledge sharing? Does it coincide with, overlap or repeat what other systems clubs are doing?

Agenda & Notes

- Welcome & Introductions
 - @Peter D Tuddenham over the last 4 years has done work on structuring information (Wikis, many PDF, 200+ Video recordings, etc etc — Presenting the work of last ~64 years in ISSS, in more accessible and effective manner.). So it is urgent to be indexing and improving this informational resource — for ISSS members, Systems community, and Beyond. So it is essential for people's active contributions — we'll be having this rhythm every 2 weeks, and working/learning by doing.
 - MediaWiki is install on the ISSS servers — currently slight DNS issue? Drupal issue? Could be opportunity for Yiannis to be carrying out one of multiple approaches.
 - in impact consulting in non-profit and government sectors regarding systems change. 30+ experience in information management consulting. Data, conceptual, semantic, information modeling.
 - @Roelien will be around in supporting role, busy works with other ISSS responsibilities, providing important visibility/moderation/input as we develop.
 - — Future Worlds Center is organization in research and practical interventions. Sustainable Dev Goals, Education, etc. Strong believe in that Systems Science is needed now more than ever — Starting within. Communication among us, and this includes knowledge accessibility. Sharing links, a repository of education materials. Strong believer in Open Source & MediaWiki (allows mobilization and updating along with other large-scale collaboration projects — TEMPLATE and the CATEGORY). Can help with MediaWiki and other helps.
 - @Roelien: This is a great idea! I made a template for SIGS - which was not adopted. But I think it is case of lack of interest rather than poor strategy.
 - @Dennis — Perhaps not helpful in the technical side, however given the people and context — Editing, suggesting, commenting (not always positively), may be a great role (longest-standing member of ISSS with eclectic background).
 - Maybe could start with 3 heavily-blocked words or sentences — 9 key words in Systems Science. Then there could be another list of current, and classical authors.
 - Terms explained in different ways (extensible knowledge graph architectures)....going to the right and seeing different/deeper explanations. Here we start to also have links to other sources and external references.
 - Communication with all kinds of people (in pubs etc.).

- Why 3's and 9's — 3 is the minimum number of things to use, and beyond 9 can become unwieldy. — What are the 3 messages for ISSS? Expanding fractally etc., in communication.
- — Retired software engineer with experience in modeling. Initially, separate files for different sources. Then has been working in integrated file architectures — [Link to homepage](#). PEOPLE, DOCUMENTS, QUOTATIONS, THEMES, etc — and hundreds of Instances of these kinds of Entities. Using an IBM product, Rational Systems — Exporting in XML or otherwise? Gary Smith with BAE?
- @Katrina — Researcher with technical skills. Knowledge in the realm of web design, MySQL, server stacks, password protected files outside of the internet, HTML/CSS. New member in ISSS, and excited with many of these affordances and directions.
- @Daniel
- @Michael — Community of scientists and the acceptance of Systems ideas. Very specific task.
- Thoughts on ways of working:
 - Overview of Coda initial structuring
 - Synchronous/Asynchronous participation
- [KM as a project](#)
 - Addressing comments from participants above
 - <https://www.iss.org/knowledge-engineering/> —
 - Appreciated by some that there is openness in the beginning! Allowing for many directions and not over-specifying things (even regarding [Approaches](#))
 - At ISSS — Individuals decide one day to make a difference. The strategy is coordinated at the organizational scale by the Board of Directors.
 - There is already too much material...how to edit down ...and place in some kind of nesting system....also need to use everyday vocabulary as far as possible....also I would like us to use lots of IKONS.....
 - Index?
 - Searching PDF?
- .@ Roelien: Design challenge is representative of the web problem - but also for the entire discipline! So, the aim of the mini-symposia is also sense-making!
- Creating a structure in a secure place? Then with the structure making it public?

To-Do

- Creating the [Strategy](#) (approaching this as a Design and Accessibility challenge).
- Building [Modular Outcomes](#)

#2 September 22, 2022

Meeting transcript & recording

- Only @Daniel joined, so there was no recording.

To-do

- Working towards a Strategy (approaching this as a Design and Accessibility challenge).
- Continuing to specify Modular Outcomes and their dependences/flexibilities.

Agenda & Notes

- Developed Modular Outcomes
- Prepared for #3 October 6, 2022

#3 October 6, 2022

Meeting transcript & recording

- <https://youtu.be/nLgJHAHjz0Q>

Feedback before the meeting

- .

General status and to-do

- @Daniel record solo video with updates on [🔧 Overview](#) and [🗨️ Ways to participate](#)

Agenda & Notes

- Assess the Active [📄 #3 Modular Outcomes](#)

#3 Modular Outcomes

Status	To discuss	Name	Area	Log
Done	<input type="checkbox"/>	Develop Timeline for 2023		
Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance		
Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meetings	🗨️ Ways to participate	
Done	<input type="checkbox"/>	Receipt of General Systems spreadsheet from Rob		
Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Research Unified storage solution for ISSS		
Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Discussion of the rights and responsibilities of ISSS archive material		
Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding exploration		
Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Front end for ISSS archives		
Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Developing uses for ISSS Archives		

#4 October 20, 2022

Meeting transcript & recording

- .

Feedback before the meeting

- .

General status and to-do

- .

Agenda & Notes

- Welcome and Introductions.
-
- Assess the Active [W4 Modular Outcomes](#) and [Modular Outcomes](#) more generally.
 - [Wiki Templates](#) — [@Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance](#)
 - [@Peter T](#) and [@Yiannis](#) met.
 - Notes are taken in [Wiki Templates](#) .
- Overview and Tour
 - [Strategy](#) — [@Develop Timeline for 2023](#)
 - [ISSS Resources](#) — [f.](#)
 - [Systems Science](#) — [f.](#) — and connect with [Education](#)
-

W4 Modular Outcomes

Status	To discuss	Name	Area	Log	Pr
Done	<input type="checkbox"/>	Develop Timeline for 2023	Strategy		
Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance	MediaWiki		
Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meetings	Ways to participate		
Done	<input type="checkbox"/>	Receipt of General Systems spreadsheet from Rob	Systems Community All		
Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Research Unified storage solution for ISSS	Strategy		
Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Discussion of the rights and responsibilities of ISSS archive material	Systems Community All		
Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding exploration	Strategy		

Active

Front end for ISSS archives

Active

Developing uses for ISSS Archives

#5 November 3, 2022

Meeting transcript & recording

- <https://youtu.be/3x2Z26uUvxE>

Feedback before the meeting

- .

General and to-do

- <https://coevolving.com/blogs/> — @David , collaborating with Ben Taylor on <https://stream.syscoi.com/> (Benjamin posts more!)
 - All creative commons
 - <http://coevolving.com/aalto/> — Courses taught at Aalto University.
 - 2010 <http://coevolving.com/aalto/201010-cs0004/> (first iteration of Systems Thinking 1)
 - 2011 <http://coevolving.com/aalto/201102-cs0005/> (first iteration of Systems Thinking 2)
 - 2016 <http://coevolving.com/aalto/201602-st2-muo-e8004/> (Systems Thinking 2)
 - <http://coevolving.com/utoronto/201801-SystemsThinking-SystemsDesign/> — University of Toronto.
 - <https://coevolving.com/blogs/index.php/archive/tag/ocadu-sfi/> OCAD University, 4 lectures in the Systemic Design course in the master's program in Strategic Foresight and Innovation
 - History — Started in 2010-11, Alta courses. David was there at Alta a lot, at there is a YouTube and Vimeo. All is captured and available. "Creative Sustainability" program, at the merger of Business, Design, Engineering — CS had req. of two Systems Thinking courses. David was there as student and teacher. Was 80% at IBM, wrote the course, then Gary Metcalf taught. Susu Nousala went from Finland, China, a journey <https://nousala.com/talo/> , <https://csrp.institute/online/>, took over. In 2016 — those at Alta were pushed out, the last teaching was in 2016 "System Thinking 2", and U Toronto Course is "System Thinking 1".
 - <https://www.youtube.com/c/DavidIng>
 - When David taught — they thought Systems Thinking could be 1 & 2 of 5. Then that was changed later to 4 & 5. Mindset course was to get ready for Systems Thinking, without the language. Then by the time it comes back later, there is more familiarity (showing the research/rigor of Systems).
 - 2018 — Prof who usually taught had injury, taught at U Toronto on short call.
 - 2014-2017 — David focused more on Pattern Language and Federated Wiki, less on systems sciences
 - ISSS 2019 Corvallis presentations <https://coevolving.com/blogs/index.php/archive/open-learning-commons-digital-life-collective/>
 - <http://daviding.wiki.openlearning.cc/view/welcome-visitors> —
 - <https://discuss.openlearning.cc> Open Learning Commons, with the support of Robert Best <https://www.linkedin.com/in/robest/?originalSubdomain=ca> , he's a regular on Ward Cunningham weekly meetings, and uses Telegram a lot
 - <https://diglife.com> A UK-based cooperative that provides hosting for open source tools, including Mattermost
 - <http://systemschanges.com/online/> since 2019 has been using diglife.com and openlearning.cc
 - Systems Changes Learning Circle chats on Mattermost <https://chat.diglife.coop> since 2019
 - <https://qoto.org/@daviding> shows a good Mastodon instance for people interested in science

- There's been a Dokuwiki on [isss.org](https://projects.isss.org) since 2006? <https://projects.isss.org/doku.php> . Security used to be linked to Drupal.
- Around Toronto, Systems Thinking Ontario <https://wiki.st-on.org>
- Internet — Between networks
 - The structures change. Blog, because reflecting what one knows at time. Should change faster than Wiki.
- Editor at wikipedia https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Marcel_Douwe_Dekker — Content of Wikipedia. Has been curator of Systems content <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/User:Mdd>

Agenda & Notes

- Welcome and Introductions.
- Goal: Prepare for the upcoming ISSS Saturday 7am PT, 40 minute session.
 - ..
 - .
- Assess the Active [#5 Modular Outcomes](#) and [Modular Outcomes](#) more generally.
 - [Strategy](#) — [@Develop Timeline for 2023](#)
 - [Wiki Templates](#) — [@Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance](#)
 - [ISSS Resources](#) — [f.](#)
 - Scope the <https://web3.isss.org/km/> and integrate to Tabular form (with network view or export).
 - [Systems Science](#) — [f.](#) — and connect with [Education](#)
-

#5 Modular Outcomes

Status	To discuss	Name	Area	Log	Pr
Done	<input type="checkbox"/>	Develop Timeline for 2023	Strategy		
Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance	MediaWiki		
Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meetings	Ways to participate		
Done	<input type="checkbox"/>	Receipt of General Systems spreadsheet from Rob	Systems Community All		
Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Research Unified storage solution for ISSS	Strategy		
Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Discussion of the rights and responsibilities of ISSS archive material	Systems Community All		
Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding exploration	Strategy		
Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Front end for ISSS archives	Systems Community All		
Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Developing uses for ISSS Archives	Systems Community All		

#6 November 17, 2022

Meeting transcript & recording

- <https://youtu.be/ftrIV9pBIbA>

Feedback before the meeting

- .

General and to-do

-

Agenda & Notes

- Welcome and Introductions.
- [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#) Update on 'SCA Systems Community Repository' initiative, Rob Young @Rob
 - (~20 minutes)
 - [Draft presentation](#)

 [SCA Systems Community Repository v1p0-ISSS.pdf](#)

- Rob's presentation
- @Shingai
- ...
- Assess the Active [Modular Outcomes](#) more generally.
 - [Strategy](#) — @Develop [Timeline for 2023](#)
 - [Wiki Templates](#) — @Improve the use and usability of the [ISSS MediaWiki instance](#)
 -
 - Scope the <https://web3.iss.org/km/> and integrate to Tabular form (with network view or export).
 - [Education](#)
-

#6 Modular Outcomes

Status	To discuss	Name	Area	Log
Done	<input type="checkbox"/>	Develop Timeline for 2023		
Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance		
Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meetings		
Done	<input type="checkbox"/>	Receipt of General Systems spreadsheet from Rob		

Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Research Unified storage solution for ISSS		
Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Discussion of the rights and responsibilities of ISSS archive material		
Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding exploration		
Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Front end for ISSS archives		
Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Developing uses for ISSS Archives		

#7 December 1, 2022

Meeting transcript & recording

-

Feedback before the meeting

- .

General and to-do

- Work and volunteering.
 - Motivation and mutual accountability.
 - Making relevant today, everything
- Gordon Pask, Conversation Theory.
 - Paul Pangaro <https://www.pangaro.com/>
 - Dave Douglass <http://crisiscenter.us/>
- Chatbots and AI 🗣️ Chat AI
 - <https://chat.openai.com/> — incredible improvements in large language models. Behind the scenes, surely they and others have more powerful models with e.g.
 - Knowledge Bases
 - People
 - Multimedia (e.g. Stable Diffusion).
- Knowledge Engineering, Education
 - Applied implementations of Systems
 - Knowledge Engineering is a specific instance/application.
 - We can integrate chat-AI type systems to make it engaging.
 - Have a conversation with the ISSS?
- Education
 - Have a Systems Conversation, introductory experience, Cyber-Learning educational experience.
 - Rather than the “watch my powerpoint/video”
 - Allows the single learner or facilitated-group to have a conversation, this is collective intelligence development.
- Host a conversational interface on the website?
 - Bringing forward the record, in terms of memory.
 - Trained on specific aspects of the ISSS corpus — developing this capability.
 - Ocean Literacy — different lists, concepts, etc.
 - Enterprise-grade trained Chatbots.
- Cyber-Systems, Systems and Cybernetics, Cybernetics Systems
 - Communication and Control.
 - Len's work, identifying system processes.

- Creating a way to engage with the body of knowledge called systems — on ISSS and in the broader sense.
- To encourage thinking not in the abstract (unless it is needed, e.g. in an intention didactic fashion).
 - Explain Predict Design Control — Imperatives of Science
 - Aesthetics? E.g. style transfer models (who is the owner of the artistic style?).
- Broken link
 - Stable Diffusion <https://huggingface.co/spaces/stabilityai/stable-diffusion>
- Notes on [George Mobus Ontology Chapters 3 and 4](#).
- Applications
 - <https://passion.io/>
 - <https://bubble.io/>
- .
- .
- .

Agenda & Notes

- Welcome and Introductions.
- [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#) Update on 'SCA Systems Community Repository' initiative, Rob Young @Rob
 - (~20 minutes)
 - [Draft presentation](#)
 - 📎 SCA Systems Community Repository v1p0-ISSS.pdf
- Rob's presentation
- @Shingai
- ...
- Assess the Active [Modular Outcomes](#) more generally.
 - [Strategy](#) — [@Develop Timeline for 2023](#)
 - [Wiki Templates](#) — [@Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance](#)
 -
 - Scope the <https://web3.iss.org/km/> and integrate to Tabular form (with network view or export).
 - [Education](#)
-

#7 Modular Outcomes

Status	To discuss	Name	Area	Log
Done	<input type="checkbox"/>	Develop Timeline for 2023		
Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance		

Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meetings	Ways to participate	
Done	<input type="checkbox"/>	Receipt of General Systems spreadsheet from Rob	Systems Community All	
Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Research Unified storage solution for ISSS	Strategy	
Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Discussion of the rights and responsibilities of ISSS archive material	Systems Community All	
Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding exploration	Strategy	
Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Front end for ISSS archives	Systems Community All	
Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Developing uses for ISSS Archives	Systems Community All	

#8 December 15, 2022

Meeting transcript & recording

- <https://youtu.be/AnPbfm2r9Nk>

Feedback before the meeting

- .

General and to-do

- [A Passion for Adult Learning: How the Fielding model is transforming doctoral education](#)
- .
- .
- .

Agenda & Notes

- Welcome and Introductions.
- Infrastructure
 - <https://www.nsf.gov/pubs/2023/nsf23533/nsf23533.htm>
 - <https://www.nist.gov/system/files/white-ieee-hst-09.pdf>
- Program of deliverables for 2023.
 - At this point — all volunteer, so some Milestones can be challenging to meet.
 - Even with small number — possible to seek funding for certain activities.
 - First step — One Pager on the project scope.
 - Position paper — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.
 - Coupled Human And Natural Systems (CHANS) — Coupling systems, in life and ontologies.
- **ISSS**
 - **Fundamentals of storage**
 - Assessment & Documentation of the ISSS Catalog (@Rob)
 - ISSS internal repository and breadth of knowledge (and less tangible, general systems theory).
 - Accessibility and Humanness — Involves searching via Catalog/Index (library model).
 - Activities — Many possible projects.
 - Ingress and storage of materials
 - Annotation, Tagging, Marking, Linking
- **Collaborative**
 - **Other Archival efforts in the space**
 - Connect with **Fundamentals of storage** (interoperability)
 - @Peter R EU-S Systemic — Hellenic Systems Sciences — Archiving Project.

- Relevant to bring into our awareness.
- Using the [MIT DSpace](#) process for compiling the materials.
- American Society for Cybernetics.
 - Gordon Pask (Conversation Theory) — Paul Pangaro (also @Vienna), seeing possible opportunity for dialogic interface.
 - Possible funding opportunity.
- **Development of Interfaces**
 - traditional Database with search
 - Large Language Models // Chat interface (in [Coda](#) or otherwise)
 - Custom corpus
 - Formal knowledge model ([SUMO](#), other approaches).
- .
- **#6 - 12/8/2022**
- Review previous **#7 December 1, 2022**
- Assess the Active **Modular Outcomes** more generally.
 - **Strategy** — [@Develop Timeline for 2023](#)
 - **Wiki Templates** — [@Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance](#)
 - **ISSS Resources** —
 - Scope the <https://web3.iss.org/km/> and integrate to Tabular form (with network view or export).
 - **Education**
-

#7 Modular Outcomes 2

Status	To discuss	Name	Area	Log
Done	<input type="checkbox"/>	Develop Timeline for 2023		
Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance		
Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meetings		
Done	<input type="checkbox"/>	Receipt of General Systems spreadsheet from Rob		
Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Research Unified storage solution for ISSS		
Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Discussion of the rights and responsibilities of ISSS archive material		
Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding exploration		
Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Front end for ISSS archives		
Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Developing uses for ISSS Archives		

2023

#9 January 12, 2023

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/breebWSUacl>

Feedback before the meeting

- .

General and to-do

-
- .
- .

Agenda & Notes

- Welcome to 2023 and Introductions.
- View towards Education
- Consider changing to Infrastructure? Including Website?
- Creating a video summary within next days, to send out to ISSS and Knowledge Engineering People
- Program of deliverables for 2023.
 - At this point — all volunteer, so some Milestones can be challenging to meet.
 - Even with small number — possible to seek funding for certain activities.
 - Coupled Human And Natural Systems (CHANS) — Coupling systems, in life and ontologies.
- Using a Gantt Chart
- **KM as a project**
 - **ISSS**
 - **ISSS Collections**
 - Fundamentals of storage
 - Assessment & Documentation of the ISSS Catalog (@Rob)
 - ISSS internal repository and breadth of knowledge (and less tangible, general systems theory).
 - Accessibility and Humanness — Involves searching via Catalog/Index (library model).
 - Activities — Many possible projects.
 - Ingress and storage of materials
 - Annotation, Tagging, Marking, Linking
 - Connect with **Fundamentals of storage** (interoperability)
 - **Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository**
 - Previously a presentation was made at this meeting.

- End of 2022 — @Rob provided a spreadsheet with list of assets.
 - Framing — seeing this as a year's trial.
 - Focus: Delivering content to who is responsive.
 - Partnership — Whatever the ISSS finds useful, as content. Then we can work together and plan it.
 - Soon — will be providing updated spreadsheet.
 - We can give feedback on staging of different works.
 - Collections are ongoing (as long as content production continues). There is just a large backlog.
 - Total storage
 - Currently the SCA is only reference/pointer to the organization's storage.
 - **Single unified ISSS storage**
 - Rob's SCA schema
 - Organization (unique entity, could be ISSS or another, or a person).
 - Collections (grouped under a theme, like Yearbooks, Proceedings, Bulletins, Mini-Symposium, Newsletter)
 - Content itself — identified by standard metadata by type.
 - Registers (simple lists — e.g. Systems Blogs, other archives)
 - Broad plans.
 - 1. Continuing content, along lines of ISSS Archive
 - Do we have all Collections at ISSS?
 - Within Collection — do we have all Content metadata?
 - Basic Document details — Collection, Title, Authors, Year.
 - Coverage of Entities: Collections, Authors
 - Collections: Proceedings and Conferences, Newsletters, General Systems Yearbooks.
 - Full text where possible (including information on e.g. IP / availability).
 - Understanding of where the coverage is total vs. incomplete.
 - Conversion to a format, and/or annotation, to allow syntactic or semantic search.
 - 2. Developing a website, to have go-to place for accessing what SCA is delivering.
- **Collaborative**
- **Other Collaborative, non-archival/SCA efforts in the space**
 - @Peter R EU-S Systemic — Hellenic Systems Sciences — Archiving Project.
 - Relevant to bring into our awareness.
 - Using the MIT DSpace process for compiling the materials.
 - American Society for Cybernetics.
 - Gordon Pask (Conversation Theory) — Paul Pangaro (also @Vienna), seeing possible opportunity for dialogic interface.
 - Possible funding opportunity.
 - **Development of Interfaces**
 - traditional Database with search
 - Interactive interfaces (Coda)
 - Large Language Models // Chat interface (in Coda or otherwise)

- Custom corpus
- Formal knowledge model ([SUMO](#), other approaches).
- **Writing.**
 - First step — One Pager on the project scope.
 - **Position paper** — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.
 - Would require an actual way forward.
- [#6 - 12/8/2022](#)
- Review previous meeting
- Assess the Active [#9 Modular Outcomes](#) and [Modular Outcomes](#) more generally.
 - [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)
 - Usage of [Chat AI](#):
 - [Strategy](#) — [@Develop Timeline for 2023](#)
 - [Wiki Templates](#) — [@Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance](#)
 - [ISSS Resources](#) —
 - Scope the <https://web3.iss.org/km/> and integrate to Tabular form (with network view or export).
 - [Systems Science](#) — and connect with [Education](#)
-

#9 Modular Outcomes

Area	Status	To discuss	Name
▼ Strategy 3	Done	<input type="checkbox"/>	Develop Timeline for 2023
	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Research Unified storage solution for ISSS
	Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding exploration
▼ MediaWiki 1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
▼ Ways to participate 1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meet
▼ Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository 4	Done	<input type="checkbox"/>	Receipt of General Systems spreadsheet from Rob
	Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Discussion of the rights and responsibilities of ISSS archive material
	Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Front end for ISSS archives
	Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Developing uses for ISSS Archives

- Using a Gantt Chart

#10 January 26, 2023

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/touQzNsvkys>

Feedback before the meeting

- .

General and to-do

- .

Agenda & Notes

- View towards [ABC Education](#)
- [KM as a project](#)
 - **Primary direction: ISSS Collections**
 - See [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#) and [ISSS @ SCA](#), with [@Rob Young](#).
 - [@Receipt of General Systems spreadsheet from Rob](#) — from previous time. Sending a second spreadsheet, being a detailed list of 32 volumes of yearbook (not done yet).
 - First deliverable — [Inventory across Collections \(D221220A\)](#)
 - Second deliverable — [@Receipt of General Systems spreadsheet from Rob](#)
 - Making more useful
 - Index
 - Saving the material [Full texts of the yearbooks](#)
 - Digitization of what only exists in the Physical form.
 - Categorization? Tagging
 - Coda interface with [Inventory across Collections \(D221220A\)](#) and Yearbook contents
 - DOI?
 - Bibliographic database integration — Index information is safe.
 - Then there might be a paywall (e.g. Wiley, ISSS, membership, etc)
 - Non-Profit — For acquiring funding?
 - strategy wise. I think search functionality is key. good searches, but also assistance coming up with good searches. "professional keywords"/what search phrases have been used that have some regularity, etc.
 - [@Funding exploration](#)
 - **Secondary directions: Collaborative**
 - Other Collaborative, non-archival/SCA efforts in the space

- [@Peter R EU-S Systemic](#) — Hellenic Systems Sciences — Archiving Project.
 - MIT DSpace process for compiling the materials. <https://wiki.lyrasis.org/display/DSPACECRIS>
- American Society for Cybernetics.
 - Gordon Pask (Conversation Theory) — Paul Pangaro, possible opportunity for dialogic interface.
 - Other Universities, Libraries, Repositories.
- Possible funding opportunities
- **Development of Interfaces**
 - Traditional Database with search
 - Interactive interfaces (Coda)
 - Large Language Models // Chat interface (in [Coda](#) or otherwise)
 - Custom corpus
 - Formal knowledge model ([SUMO](#), other approaches).
- **Writing.**
 - First step — One Pager on the project scope.
 - Position paper — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.
 - Would require an actual way forward.
- Assess the Active [#10 Modular Outcomes](#) and [Modular Outcomes](#) more generally.
 - [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)
 - [Strategy](#) — [@Develop Timeline for 2023](#)
 - [Wiki Templates](#) — [@Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance](#)
 - [ISSS Resources](#) —
 - Scope the <https://web3.iss.org/km/> and integrate to Tabular form (with network view or export).
 - [Systems Science](#) — and connect with [Education](#)

#10 Modular Outcomes

Area		Status	To discuss	Name
▼ MediaWiki	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
▼ Ways to participate	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meet
▼ Strategy	2	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Research Unified storage solution for ISSS
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding exploration
▼ Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository	3	Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Discussion of the rights and responsibilities of ISSS archive material
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Front end for ISSS archives
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Developing uses for ISSS Archives

- Using a Gantt Chart
- Usage of [Chat AI](#)

#11 February 9, 2023

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/R5OaNTR58Fo>

Feedback before the meeting

- .

General and to-do

- ISSS Archive Interface: https://coda.io/d/ISSS-Archive-Interface_daDW68lgalJ/Home_sunhx#_lu_tj
 - Full text?
 - Copyright and access.
 - Value of the knowledge repository — going back to the beginnings of the Systems movement.
 - Compare with Bertalanffy archives.
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.iss.org/primer2/>
 - <https://www.iss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>
- [Complexity Digest](#)
- What makes knowledge, knowledge?
 - Part of it is accessibility and linkages to other things.
 - Topology of information/semantic architecture — Small world.
 - Hyper-Index — Index of all books/papers/etc. Retain the publication meta-data, and provide a hyper-searchable index. Searching for a subject/topic, results in database query that can be parametrized with various characteristics. https://evolutionnews.org/2013/01/what_can_we_lea/
- Large Language Model
- .
- .
- .

Agenda & Notes

- View towards [APC Education](#)
- Future of Interface <https://calendar.umd.edu/future-of-interface-workshop>
 - [@Karl](#) presenting to General Services Administration, line of command of Chief Data/Privacy Offices, reporting to division about this workshop.
 - Can people with disabilities participate in virtual reality?

- Section 508 Compliance around accessibility.
- 🗄️ **KM as a project**
 - **Primary direction: ISSS Collections**
 - See 🗄️ [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#) and 🗄️ [ISSS @ SCA](#), with [@Rob Young](#).
 - [@Receipt of General Systems spreadsheet from Rob](#) — from previous time. Sending a second spreadsheet, being a detailed list of 32 volumes of yearbook (not done yet).
 - First deliverable — 🗄️ [Inventory across Collections \(D221220A\)](#)
 - Second deliverable — [@Receipt of General Systems spreadsheet from Rob](#)
 - Making more useful
 - strategy wise. I think search functionality is key. good searches, but also assistance coming up with good searches. "professional keywords"/what search phrases have been used that have some regularity, etc.
 - Index
 - Saving the material [Full texts of the yearbooks](#)
 - Digitization of what only exists in the Physical form.
 - Categorization? Tagging
 - Coda interface with 🗄️ [Inventory across Collections \(D221220A\)](#) and Yearbook contents
 - DOI?
 - Bibliographic database integration — Index information is safe.
 - Then there might be a paywall (e.g. Wiley, ISSS, membership, etc)
 - **Secondary directions: Collaborative**
 - [Other Collaborative, non-archival/SCA efforts in the space](#)
 - [@Funding exploration](#)
 - Non-Profit — For acquiring funding?
 - [@Peter R EU-S Systemic — Hellenic Systems Sciences — Archiving Project.](#)
 - [MIT DSpace](https://wiki.lyrasis.org/display/DSPACECRIS) process for compiling the materials. <https://wiki.lyrasis.org/display/DSPACECRIS>
 - American Society for Cybernetics.
 - Gordon Pask (Conversation Theory) — Paul Pangaro, possible opportunity for dialogic interface.
 - Other Universities, Libraries, Repositories.
 - Possible funding opportunities
 - [Development of Interfaces](#)
 - Traditional Database with search
 - Interactive interfaces (Coda)
 - Large Language Models // Chat interface (in [Coda](#) or otherwise)
 - Custom corpus
 - Formal knowledge model ([SUMO](#), other approaches).
 - [Writing.](#)
 - First step — One Pager on the project scope.
 - Position paper — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.
 - Would require an actual way forward.
- Assess the Active 🗄️ [#11 Modular Outcomes](#) and 🗄️ [Modular Outcomes](#) more generally.

- Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository
- Strategy — @Develop Timeline for 2023
- Wiki Templates — @Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
- ISSS Resources —
 - Scope the <https://web3.iss.org/km/> and integrate to Tabular form (with network view or export).
- Education

#11 Modular Outcomes

Area		Status	To discuss	Name
▼ MediaWiki	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
▼ Ways to participate	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meet
▼ Strategy	2	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Research Unified storage solution for ISSS
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding exploration
▼ Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository	3	Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Discussion of the rights and responsibilities of ISSS archive material
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Front end for ISSS archives
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Developing uses for ISSS Archives

- Using a Gantt Chart
- Usage of Chat AI

#12 February 23, 2023

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/3Gr1yOMFK5s>

Feedback before the meeting

- .

General and to-do

- ISSS Archive Interface: https://coda.io/d/ISSS-Archive-Interface_daDW68lgaJ/Home_sunhx#_lu_tj
 - Full text?
 - Copyright and access.
 - Value of the knowledge repository — going back to the beginnings of the Systems movement.
 - Compare with Bertalanffy archives.
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.iss.org/primer2/>
 - <https://www.iss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>
- Complexity Digest
- .
- <https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.07842> [Submitted on 15 Feb 2023] Augmented Language Models: a Survey
- .

Agenda & Notes

- View towards Education
 - Look at Survey — what can we ask about Knowledge resources?
- During March
 - Communication to ISSS members and public
 - Short YouTube video showing the interface
 - Link to interface
 - Ways to contribute
- **Primary direction: ISSS Collections**
 - See ISSS @ SCA, with @Rob Young.
 - 2/23/2023 notes
 - Website in development

- Underlying index to source materials, hosted by Organizations (divided into Collections of knowledge assets, and Registers of lists).
- One of the Register, is a list of courses and events.
- As a use case — someone is interested in doing MS/PhD in the Systems field, I am looking for something in X area/online, and I want to see their curriculum.
- There is a wider associated lists — events and conferences — also could be done like the Education survey. — Identify registration deadlines, early bird discounts, paper submission.
- Previous Rob effort — scraped higher education course listings, for Systems. Many of the courses found were Computer Systems, Systems Engineering. — another way to populate these lists.
- The course-type programs ([survey here](#)) are more durable and long-term. Whereas events are more ephemeral.
- Making the [Interface](#) more useful
 - strategy wise. I think search functionality is key. good searches, but also assistance coming up with good searches. "professional keywords"/what search phrases have been used that have some regularity, etc.
 - Index
 - Saving the material [Full texts of the yearbooks](#)
 - Digitization of what only exists in the Physical form.
 - Categorization? Tagging
 - Coda interface with [Inventory across Collections \(D221220A\)](#) and Yearbook contents
 - DOI?
 - Bibliographic database integration — Index information is safe.
 - Then there might be a paywall (e.g. Wiley, ISSS, membership, etc)
- **Secondary directions: Collaborative**
 - [Other Collaborative, non-archival/SCA efforts in the space](#)
 - [@Funding exploration](#)
 - Non-Profit — For acquiring funding?
 - [@Peter R EU-S Systemic](#) — Hellenic Systems Sciences — Archiving Project.
 - [MIT DSpace](https://wiki.lyrasis.org/display/DSPACECRIS) process for compiling the materials. <https://wiki.lyrasis.org/display/DSPACECRIS>
 - American Society for Cybernetics.
 - Gordon Pask (Conversation Theory) — Paul Pangaro, possible opportunity for dialogic interface.
 - Other Universities, Libraries, Repositories.
 - Possible funding opportunities
 - [Development of Interfaces](#)
 - Traditional Database with search
 - Interactive interfaces (Coda)
 - Large Language Models // Chat interface (in [Coda](#) or otherwise)
 - Custom corpus
 - Formal knowledge model ([SUMO](#), other approaches).
 - [Writing](#).
 - First step — One Pager on the project scope.
 - Position paper — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.

- Would require an actual way forward.
- Assess the Active [#11 Modular Outcomes 2](#) and [Modular Outcomes](#) more generally.
 - [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)
 - [Strategy](#) — [@Develop Timeline for 2023](#)
 - [Wiki Templates](#) — [@Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance](#)
 - [ISSS Resources](#) —
 - Scope the <https://web3.iss.org/km/> and integrate to Tabular form (with network view or export).
 - [Systems Science](#) — and connect with [Education](#)
-

#11 Modular Outcomes 2

Area		Status	To discuss	Name
▼ MediaWiki	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
▼ Ways to participate	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meet
▼ Strategy	2	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Research Unified storage solution for ISSS
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding exploration
▼ Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository	3	Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Discussion of the rights and responsibilities of ISSS archive material
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Front end for ISSS archives
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Developing uses for ISSS Archives

- Using a Gantt Chart
- Usage of [Chat AI](#)

#13 March 9, 2023

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/nFj02UQL134>

Feedback before the meeting

- .

General and to-do

- ISSS Archive Interface: https://coda.io/d/ISSS-Archive-Interface_daDW68lgaJ/Home_sunhx#_lu_tj
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.iss.org/primer2/>
 - <https://www.iss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>
- Complexity Digest

Agenda & Notes

- View towards 🎓 Education
 - Systems Education.
- Purpose of 📄 KM as a project
- During March
 - Communication to ISSS members and public
 - Short YouTube video showing the interface
 - Link to interface
 - Ways to contribute
- Chat security on the listing
 - Video chats, the link was viewable.
-
-
-
- **Primary direction: ISSS Collections**
 - See 📄 Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository and 🌐 ISSS @ SCA, with @Rob Young.
 - 2/23/2023 notes
 - Website in development

- Underlying index to source materials, hosted by Organizations (divided into Collections of knowledge assets, and Registers of lists).
- One of the Register, is a list of courses and events.
- As a use case — someone is interested in doing MS/PhD in the Systems field, I am looking for something in X area/online, and I want to see their curriculum.
- There is a wider associated lists — events and conferences — also could be done like the Education survey. — Identify registration deadlines, early bird discounts, paper submission.
- Previous Rob effort — scraped higher education course listings, for Systems. Many of the courses found were Computer Systems, Systems Engineering. — another way to populate these lists.
- The course-type programs ([survey here](#)) are more durable and long-term. Whereas events are more ephemeral.
- Making the [Interface](#) more useful
 - strategy wise. I think search functionality is key. good searches, but also assistance coming up with good searches. "professional keywords"/what search phrases have been used that have some regularity, etc.
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 - Bibliographic database integration — Index information is safe.
 - Then there might be a paywall (e.g. Wiley, ISSS, membership, etc)
- **Secondary directions: Collaborative**
 - [Other Collaborative, non-archival/SCA efforts in the space](#)
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 - Other Universities, Libraries, Repositories.
 - Possible funding opportunities
 - [Development of Interfaces](#)
 - Traditional Database with search
 - Interactive interfaces (Coda)
 - Large Language Models // Chat interface (in [Coda](#) or otherwise)
 - Custom corpus
 - Formal knowledge model ([SUMO](#), other approaches).
 - [Writing.](#)
 - First step — One Pager on the project scope.
 - Position paper — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.

- Would require an actual way forward.
- Assess the Active [#13 Modular Outcomes](#) and [Modular Outcomes](#) more generally.
 - [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)
 - [Strategy](#) — [@Develop Timeline for 2023](#)
 - [Wiki Templates](#) — [@Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance](#)
 - [ISSS Resources](#) —
 - Scope the <https://web3.iss.org/km/> and integrate to Tabular form (with network view or export).
 - [Systems Science](#) — and connect with [Education](#)
-

#13 Modular Outcomes

Area		Status	To discuss	Name
▼ MediaWiki	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
▼ Ways to participate	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meet
▼ Strategy	2	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Research Unified storage solution for ISSS
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding exploration
▼ Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository	3	Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Discussion of the rights and responsibilities of ISSS archive material
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Front end for ISSS archives
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Developing uses for ISSS Archives

- Using a Gantt Chart
- Usage of [Chat AI](#)

#14 March 23, 2023

Meeting recording

- https://youtu.be/UJkJH_G791I

After the meeting

- Sent 📧 March 23, 2023

General and to-do

- ISSS Archive Interface: https://coda.io/d/ISSS-Archive-Interface_daDW68lgaJ/Home_sunhx#_lu_tj
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.iss.org/primer2/>
 - <https://www.iss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>
- Complexity Digest
- .
- .

Agenda & Notes

- View towards 🎓 Education
 - Systems Education.
- Purpose of 📄 KM as a project
- .
- 📁 Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository
 - Rob currently working on the website, coming in the next few weeks.
 - Will be updated to our group, and to the SCA newsletter.
- Explosion of Language models.
 - Predominant in people's thinking.
 - Large tech companies also integrating into their technology.
 - 📄 KM as a project is/was formulated around making the information more accessible.
 - Cultures — Inter-generational, Multi-cultural — The language use is changing. The resilience, sensitivity to difference words/sentences can be variable.
 - Incumbent on the 🦋 Systems Science in the frameworks we present forward.
 - Stigmergy :) 🐜
 - This may also tie in to the physics of 'perception' of actions, context, etc. that I am delving into...
 - Can we have a session around this specifically — This will be #16 (April 20th 2023 at 18 UTC)

- Hello all,
- On April 20th 2023, at 18 UTC, in the Knowledge Engineering project at ISSS ([add links](#))
- We will be have an hour-long “positive entanglement” around the topic of Large Language Models and Systems Science, with attention to how these models can be applied with the [ISSS Archives](#), in service of accessibility, rigor, and applicability.
- Also
 - Post-script is a 📄 [Test on Material recommendation](#) — we brought in some notes from our meeting today,
- Announcing this to message boards.
- Recommendation of materials for different levels of Inquiry and Action?
 - Appropriateness of documents.
 - What is appropriate for different paths/contexts in education and research?
 - Given membership in ISSS and broader Systems Science — we have everyone across axes of participation/experience/backgrounds/etc.
 - So how to help navigate the spectrums and types of materials?
 - How to match to the capabilities of the person to be dealing with? Fitness.
 - This is big and developing topic — going hand in hand with development.
 - How Can we use it? Is.
 - How Should we use it? Ought.
 - What resources are available?
 - Development of the resource — being able to support different use cases.
 - Many proposals for ideas — important to have filtering process, for priority, attention, funding, etc.
 - Education stream provides many focused questions
 - Capturing initiatives or proposals — for people to volunteer for.
 - Starting to form collaborative framework to help people in their initiatives.
 - False positive // False negative.
 - Organizational learning curve — building the capabilities and maturities, to play role in supporting initiatives in the systems community.
- Strategies
- James Greer Miller — Living Systems Theory — 🦋 [Systems Science](#)
 - Peter got some lectures and interviews — transcribed
 - Can we have ISSS transcripts fed in, to have collective intelligence
- Sand Talk: How Indigenous Thinking Can Save the World, by Tyson Yunkaporta
- Decolonizing Methodologies: Research and Indigenous Peoples — by Linda Tuhiwai Smith

📎 [linda-tuhiwai-smith-decolonizing-methodologies-research-and-indigenous-peoples.pdf](#)

- **Primary direction: ISSS Collections**

- See 📄 [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#) and 🗺️ [ISSS @ SCA](#), with [@Rob Young](#).
 - See previous meeting notes

- Making the [Interface](#) more useful
- **Secondary directions: Collaborative**
 - [Other Collaborative, non-archival/SCA efforts in the space](#)
 - [Development of Interfaces](#)
 - Traditional Database with search
 - Interactive interfaces (Coda)
 - Large Language Models // Chat interface (in [Coda](#) or otherwise)
 - Custom corpus
 - Formal knowledge model ([SUMO](#), other approaches).
 - [Writing.](#)
 - First step — One Pager on the project scope.
 - Position paper — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.
 - Would require an actual way forward.
- Assess the Active [#14 Modular Outcomes](#) and [#14 Modular Outcomes](#) more generally.
 - [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)
 - [Strategy](#) — [@Develop Timeline for 2023](#)
 - [Wiki Templates](#) — [@Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance](#)
 - [ISSS Resources](#) —
 - Scope the <https://web3.iss.org/km/> and integrate to Tabular form (with network view or export).
 - [Systems Science](#) — and connect with [Education](#)

#14 Modular Outcomes

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- Using a Gantt Chart
- Usage of [Chat AI](#)

Test on Material recommendation

Material recommendation is a matter of matching the level of insights of the audience with the suitability of the chosen material. It follows then, that different materials will be more suitable for different people.

The **International Systems Science Society (ISSS)** provides an opportunity to navigate the spectrum of options for different participant levels. ISSS offers both education streams and research streams, so this allows for the development of specific resources for the promotion of the different use cases.

Furthermore, it is important to be able to recognize **false positives and false negatives** when navigating the training material and other resources. False positives mean that materials are not suitable for the intended target audience whereas false negatives indicate mismatches with the capabilities of the person dealing with the material. This can lead to individuals spending valuable time on topics outside their expertise.

Organizational learning curves are also a key part of the development of the ISSS program. As people progress through the materials, the community can gain valuable insight into the best ways to support initiatives within the systems thinking realm. Building the capabilities and maturities of members is paramount in this development process.

In conclusion, material recommendations depend fully on matching the knowledge of the audience with the suitability of the chosen material. It is important to consider false positives and false negatives in the recommendation process and is essential to build organizational learning curves as the ISSS program develops. This will ensure that everyone is able to get the most out of their experience with the ISSS program.

#15 April 6, 2023

Meeting recording

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Feedback before the meeting

- .

General and to-do

- ISSS Archive Interface: https://coda.io/d/ISSS-Archive-Interface_daDW68lgalJ/Home_sunhx#_lu_tj
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.iss.org/primer2/>
 - <https://www.iss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>
- Complexity Digest
- .
- Generalized Notation Notation (GNN)
 - Knowledge should be structured — in our databases, as well as in our brains.
 - GNN is targeting Active Inference. George Mobus has developed nomenclature and systemese. The structure of the brain, reflecting understandings of systems.
- Upcoming LLM events 📅 [LLM & ISSS](#)
 -
 - .
 - .
 -

Agenda & Notes

- View towards 🎓 Education
 - Systems Education.
- Purpose of 📚 KM as a project
-
- 🏢 Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository
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 - Organizational learning curve — building the capabilities and maturities, to play role in supporting initiatives in the systems community.
- Strategies
- James Greer Miller — Living Systems Theory — 🦋 [Systems Science](#)
 - Peter got some lectures and interviews — transcribed
 - Can we have ISSS transcripts fed in, to have collective intelligence

- Sand Talk: How Indigenous Thinking Can Save the World, by Tyson Yunkaporta
- Decolonizing Methodologies: Research and Indigenous Peoples — by Linda Tuhiwai Smith

📎 linda-tuhiwai-smith-decolonizing-methodologies-research-and-indigenous-peoples.pdf

- **Primary direction: ISSS Collections**

- See 📖 [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#) and 🗣️ [ISSS @ SCA](#), with [@Rob Young](#).
 - See previous meeting notes
- Making the [Interface](#) more useful
- **Secondary directions: Collaborative**
 - **Other Collaborative, non-archival/SCA efforts in the space**
 - **Development of Interfaces**
 - Traditional Database with search
 - Interactive interfaces (Coda)
 - Large Language Models // Chat interface (in [Coda](#) or otherwise)
 - Custom corpus
 - Formal knowledge model ([SUMO](#), other approaches).
 - **Writing.**
 - First step — One Pager on the project scope.
 - Position paper — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.
 - Would require an actual way forward.
- Assess the Active 📖 [#14 Modular Outcomes 2](#) and 🗣️ [Modular Outcomes](#) more generally.
 - 📖 [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)
 - 🗣️ [Strategy](#) — [@Develop Timeline for 2023](#)
 - 📖 [Wiki Templates](#) — [@Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance](#)
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 - Scope the <https://web3.iss.org/km/> and integrate to Tabular form (with network view or export).
 - 🗣️ [Systems Science](#) — and connect with 🗣️ [Education](#)

#14 Modular Outcomes 2

Area	Status	To discuss	Name
▼ 📖 MediaWiki 1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
▼ 🗣️ Ways to participate 1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meet
▼ 🗣️ Strategy 2	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Research Unified storage solution for ISSS
	Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding exploration

▼ Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository	3	Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Discussion of the rights and responsibilities of ISSS archive material
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Front end for ISSS archives
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Developing uses for ISSS Archives

- Using a Gantt Chart
- Usage of Chat AI

#16 April 20, 2023

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/JXQcH7-DZpl>

📎 meeting_saved_chat.txt

Feedback before the meeting

- .

General and to-do

- ISSS Archive Interface: https://coda.io/d/ISSS-Archive-Interface_daDW68lgaIJ/Home_sunhx#_lu_tj
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.iss.org/primer2/>
 - <https://www.iss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>
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Agenda & Notes

- ▷ Purpose of 📄 KM as a project & View towards 🎓 Education
- ▼ 📄 LLM & ISSS
 - ▷ Following on from yesterday's session
 - ▷ To what extent, comments spoken/written yesterday, reflect generalized fear/anxiety around AI/technology, rather than specific aspects of Language Models.
 - ▷ In observing the children and grandchildren developing — to an extent repeating their context's ways of talking. And how they connect sentience & intelligence with language processing.
 - ▼ Language Models =/= Knowledge Model
 - ▷ Exploring this relationship of LLM & multiple Knowledge models
 - ▷ Current model's input is (labeled) text, this seems to go far/fast in some (not all!) context.
 - ▷ Generation of discussions within 🌐 ISSS and outside / on the interface. Hopefully we show up well here.
 - ▷ The biggest fear with AI is fear itself | De Kai | TEDxSanMigueldeAllende
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WU-RUIZWkio>

- ▷ Humans have a natural tendency to see sentience in inanimate objects. This might be a basis for seeing intentions in AIs
- ▼ Language models.
 - ▷ Predominant in people's thinking.
 - ▷ Large tech companies also integrating into their technology.
 - ▷ [KM as a project](#) is/was formulated around making the information more accessible.
 - ▷ This may also tie in to the physics of 'perception' of actions, context, etc. that I am delving into...
 - ▷ Possible for us (ISSS) to explore and even use an open source language model server/system such as Bloom
 - ▷ <https://techcrunch.com/2022/07/12/a-year-in-the-making-bigsciences-ai-language-model-is-finally-available/>
- ▼ Ways in which LLM exploration, touches on transdisciplinary understandings ([Systems Science](#)), getting at different understandings.
 - ▼ Interface — To what extent is it Technology, Human focused?
 - ▼ Where we are e.g. composing papers or texts with LLM, it is our partner/co-creator in meaning-making. We are talking with each other, looking at text.
 - ▷ This can be addressed with OBS virtual camera (need to start this before the meeting).
 - ▷ How do we work with AI?
 - ▼ Pattern Languages, [@Peter T](#) College of Exploration, Meta-Design, settings. This is why we split the two conversations into [KM as a project](#).
 - ▷ There is a lot of Resources out there, and Technologies (previous digitization efforts).
 - ▷ We can do a lot of work to facilitate the human, and make it work well. The human experience of being together. Online is a helpful way to do it, meeting in person is usually inviable.
 - ▷ Consideration of the relationship between Humans and Machine — ongoing struggle of the 250 years of Systems and Cybernetics. What we are facing with the archives — unless we can use machines to help us bootstrap the synthesis of all these individual human products, trying to stand on each other's shoulders (language issues! people don't build on each other's work). There is an opportunity to provide synthesis and overview, a periodic table of system, things that always became reduced down to individual works and starting from scratch. Limitations of the capabilities of individual humans.
 - ▷ The exciting challenge and opportunity for LLM, and the imperative in the [ISSS](#), is for those who have asked philosophical questions, language, decision-making — imperative to make the work accessible. Some have been working on synthesis projects for many years. The synthesis is a massive challenge.
 - ▷ Redundancy in conversation — same pieces going around and around. Something needs to move?
 - ▷ Hierarchy theory, Ontology of language, semantic webs — all are conjoined in this area.
 - ▼ Language-as-such has properties that are not the same as e.g. manifest linear strings of symbols or phonemes.
 - ▷ As an Area of Inquiry, Language is holographic.
 - ▷ So LLM inputs (indeed any inputs based upon biological system) are holographic. LLM can rapidly access information, in the holographic encounter. The output is again linearized.
 - ▼ Three Systemic Models
 - ▷ **Theoretical frames:** What is an LLM? What are the domains? What constitutes the Holographic/Linear components?
 - ▷ **Interactive study:** Second level Systems community can explore — how are such models used in co-creation of Meaning and Realities? Experimental.
 - ▷ **A question of pragmatic utility:** How does the ISSS use [ISSS](#) agenda.

- ▷ 1. How do LLM work (technical discussion)?
- ▷ 2. What is our relationship/engagement with the tools AND broader systems?
- ▼ 3. How does this relate to [Systems Science](#), Language, Systemese, the ways in which language shapes worlds?
 - ▷ Possible [Education](#) around Language, how/what is used.
 - ▷ From the munching of words, towards integrated information? The information is holographic?
 - ▼ Language, and culture, as holographic relationships — organized as a whole, these systems have a holographic capacity. And this is captured in some ways via the modeling and training.
 - ▷ Also this may divert/overcomplicate things — the LLM is using Vector Embeddings. Holographic properties; various ways/instances of both/all of this, and nuance.
 - ▷ Not overcomplicating the language, even about LLM. With basic understanding, metaphors and mappings may come into play. Introducing new allusive/related terms, may or may not help any given person.
 - ▷ LLM are a technique nested within larger scope of computational statistical modeling. So various Map-Territory considerations and otherwise.
- ▼ 4. What to do with our ISSS Archives and [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)
 - ▼ Here we are in ISSS with attention to e.g. members, scope of the ISSS.
 - ▷ Also there can be broader building of competence and applications.
 - ▷ So that the public is better in position to use, and have the ongoing conversations.
 - ▷ Already these models have been in used (e.g. ChatGPT current version ENDED training in 2021).
 - ▼ Cultures — Inter-generational, Multi-cultural — The language use is changing. The resilience, sensitivity to difference words/sentences can be variable.
 - ▷ Incumbent on the
 - ▷ We are learning, and this is related to what questions to ask. This is not simply something in a tube that is squirted out. There are complex causes & consequences, including the dangerous.
 - ▼ Project-based perspective — Making sense of the next steps.
 - ▼ Spin out proof of concept projects:
 - ▼ **Demonstrations** with [KM as a project](#).
 - ▼ What is the operational modification that enables the rest of the ISSS to be joining into the conversation?
 - ▼ Something on the website — “have a conversation with..... James Miller”. — Something that can be offered to the membership, and make it actual and grow something.
 - ▷ Conversations of a sort with Miller, Rosen etc is a real possibility now as a target for ISSS (if one can handle the copyright issue).
 - ▼ Personalities
 - ▷ Some feelings like there is “cults of personalities” — making a point by referring to a person.
 - ▷ Example: a reviewer of George’s textbook, wanting more historical synthesis. Going back to seminal notions, and the development of their ideas. They decided, No, that is not systems science. We need to be looking at the Synthesis — how the aspects play into being a system.
 - ▷ History and Philosophy of Science is not Science.
 - ▷ What someone has stated is their expression, that is not the internal coherence of [Systems Science](#) . That is a **human touchpoint, the context around the personality**, is part of this!

- ▼ How to Synthesize through the whole? **The overall synthesis**, and not needing to start from scratch. Can't we integrate their insights?
 - ▷ This is distilled into e.g. axioms, processes
 - ▼ Having both the **Systems Science**.
 - ▷ Story-telling version of a science — other side — Textbook style literature — other side — hybrid.
 - ▷ Point of reference — as it has been, big men and big ideas. Artificial intelligence? How are we co-creating meaning?
 - ▷ To do a couple of annual meetings, to see developments/evolutions among meetings.
 - ▷ **Structured Dialog** — — Not just learning about what LLMs can do for e.g. individuals or organizations, rather more in line with the social Trintab concept.
 - ▷
 - ▷
- ▼ **Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository**
 - ▷ Rob currently working on the website, coming in the next few weeks.
 - ▷ Will be updated to our group, and to the SCA newsletter.
 - ▷ Recommendation of materials for different levels of Inquiry and Action?
 - ▷ Appropriateness of documents.
 - ▷ What is appropriate for different paths/contexts in education and research?
 - ▷ Given membership in ISSS and broader Systems Science — we have everyone across axes of participation/experience/backgrounds/etc.
 - ▷ So how to help navigate the spectrums and types of materials?
 - ▷ How to match to the capabilities of the person to be dealing with? Fitness.
 - ▼ This is big and developing topic — going hand in hand with development.
 - ▷ How Can we use it? Is.
 - ▷ How Should we use it? Ought.
 - ▼ What resources are available?
 - ▷ Development of the resource — being able to support different use cases.
 - ▷ Many proposals for ideas — important to have filtering process, for priority, attention, funding, etc.
 - ▷ Education stream provides many focused questions
 - ▷ Capturing initiatives or proposals — for people to volunteer for.
 - ▷ Starting to form collaborative framework to help people in their initiatives.
 - ▷ False positive // False negative.
 - ▷ Organizational learning curve — building the capabilities and maturities, to play role in supporting initiatives in the systems community.
- ▼ Strategies
 - ▼ James Greer Miller — Living Systems Theory — **Systems Science**
 - ▷ Peter got some lectures and interviews — transcribed
 - ▷ Can we have ISSS transcripts fed in, to have collective intelligence
 - ▷ Sand Talk: How Indigenous Thinking Can Save the World, by Tyson Yunkaporta

▷ Decolonizing Methodologies: Research and Indigenous Peoples — by Linda Tuhiwai Smith

▼ **Primary direction: ISSS Collections**

▼ See [ISSS @ SCA](#), with [@Rob Young](#).

▷ See previous meeting notes

▷ Making the [Interface](#) more useful

▼ **Secondary directions: Collaborative**

▷ [Other Collaborative, non-archival/SCA efforts in the space](#)

▼ [Development of Interfaces](#)

▷ Traditional Database with search

▷ Interactive interfaces (Coda)

▼ Large Language Models // Chat interface (in [Coda](#) or otherwise)

▷ Custom corpus

▷ Formal knowledge model ([SUMO](#), other approaches).

▼ [Writing](#).

▷ First step — One Pager on the project scope.

▼ Position paper — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.

▷ Would require an actual way forward.

▼ Assess the Active [Modular Outcomes](#) more generally.

▷ [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)

▷ [Strategy](#) — [@Develop Timeline for 2023](#)

▷ [Wiki Templates](#) — [@Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance](#)

▼ [ISSS Resources](#) —

▷ Scope the <https://web3.iss.org/km/> and integrate to Tabular form (with network view or export).

▷ [Education](#)

▷

#14 Modular Outcomes 3

Area	Status	To discuss	Name
▼ MediaWiki 1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
▼ Ways to participate 1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meet
▼ Strategy 2	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Research Unified storage solution for ISSS
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▼ Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository 3	Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Discussion of the rights and responsibilities of ISSS archive material
	Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Front end for ISSS archives
	Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Developing uses for ISSS Archives

- Using a Gantt Chart

- Usage of 🗨️ Chat AI

#17 May 4, 2023

Meeting recording

- https://youtu.be/g_NW4eAW948

Feedback before the meeting

- .

General and to-do

- ISSS Archive Interface: https://coda.io/d/ISSS-Archive-Interface_daDW68lgaJ/Home_sunhx#_lu_tj
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.iss.org/primer2/>
 - <https://www.iss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>
-
- <https://twitter.com/DrJimFan/status/1649458864742432785>
 - .
 - .
- ISSS Conference

Agenda & Ongoing Notes

- ▷ Purpose of 📖 KM as a project & View towards 🎓 Education
- ▼ 📖 LLM & ISSS
 - ▷ Following on from yesterday's session
 - ▷ To what extent, comments spoken/written yesterday, reflect generalized fear/anxiety around AI/technology, rather than specific aspects of Language Models.
 - ▷ In observing the children and grandchildren developing — to an extent repeating their context's ways of talking. And how they connect sentience & intelligence with language processing.
 - ▼ Language Models =//= Knowledge Model
 - ▷ Exploring this relationship of LLM & multiple Knowledge models
 - ▷ Current model's input is (labeled) text, this seems to go far/fast in some (not all!) context.
 - ▷ Generation of discussions within 🌐 ISSS and outside / on the interface. Hopefully we show up well here.
 - ▷ The biggest fear with AI is fear itself | De Kai | TEDxSanMigueldeAllende
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WU-RUIZWkio>
 - ▷ Humans have a natural tendency to see sentience in inanimate objects. This might be a basis for seeing intentions in AIs
 - ▼ Language models.

- ▷ Predominant in people's thinking.
- ▷ Large tech companies also integrating into their technology.
- ▷ 🗄️ **KM as a project** is/was formulated around making the information more accessible.
- ▷ This may also tie in to the physics of 'perception' of actions, context, etc. that I am delving into...
- ▷ Possible for us (ISSS) to explore and even use an open source language model server/system such as Bloom
- ▷ <https://techcrunch.com/2022/07/12/a-year-in-the-making-bigsciences-ai-language-model-is-finally-available/>
- ▼ Ways in which LLM exploration, touches on transdisciplinary understandings (🦋 **Systems Science**), getting at different understandings.
 - ▼ Interface — To what extent is it Technology, Human focused?
 - ▼ Where we are e.g. composing papers or texts with LLM, it is our partner/co-creator in meaning-making. We are talking with each other, looking at text.
 - ▷ This can be addressed with OBS virtual camera (need to start this before the meeting).
 - ▷ How do we work with AI?
 - ▼ Pattern Languages, @Peter T College of Exploration, Meta-Design, settings. This is why we split the two conversations into 🎓 **Education** and 🗄️ **KM as a project**.
 - ▷ There is a lot of Resources out there, and Technologies (previous digitization efforts).
 - ▷ We can do a lot of work to facilitate the human, and make it work well. The human experience of being together. Online is a helpful way to do it, meeting in person is usually inviable.
 - ▷ Consideration of the relationship between Humans and Machine — ongoing struggle of the 250 years of Systems and Cybernetics. What we are facing with the archives — unless we can use machines to help us bootstrap the synthesis of all these individual human products, trying to stand on each other's shoulders (language issues! people don't build on each other's work). There is an opportunity to provide synthesis and overview, a periodic table of system, things that always became reduced down to individual works and starting from scratch. Limitations of the capabilities of individual humans.
 - ▷ The exciting challenge and opportunity for LLM, and the imperative in the 🌐 **ISSS**, is for those who have asked philosophical questions, language, decision-making — imperative to make the work accessible. Some have been working on synthesis projects for many years. The synthesis is a massive challenge.
 - ▷ Redundancy in conversation — same pieces going around and around. Something needs to move?
 - ▷ Hierarchy theory, Ontology of language, semantic webs — all are conjoined in this area.
 - ▼ Language-as-such has properties that are not the same as e.g. manifest linear strings of symbols or phonemes.
 - ▷ As an Area of Inquiry, Language is holographic.
 - ▷ So LLM inputs (indeed any inputs based upon biological system) are holographic. LLM can rapidly access information, in the holographic encounter. The output is again linearized.
 - ▼ Three Systemic Models
 - ▷ **Theoretical frames**: What is an LLM? What are the domains? What constitutes the Holographic/Linear components?
 - ▷ **Interactive study**: Second level Systems community can explore — how are such models used in co-creation of Meaning and Realities? Experimental.
 - ▷ **A question of pragmatic utility**: How does the ISSS use 🗄️ **LLM & ISSS**, to augment presentations, enrich the discourse, further the 🌐 **ISSS** agenda.
- ▷ 1. How do LLM work (technical discussion)?
- ▷ 2. What is our relationship/engagement with the tools AND broader systems?
- ▼ 3. How does this relate to 🦋 **Systems Science**, Languageing, Systemese, the ways in which language shapes worlds?

- ▷ Possible 🎓 Education around Language, how/what is used.
- ▷ From the munching of words, towards integrated information? The information is holographic?
- ▼ Language, and culture, as holographic relationships — organized as a whole, these systems have a holographic capacity. And this is captured in some ways via the modeling and training.
 - ▷ Also this may divert/overcomplicate things — the LLM is using Vector Embeddings. Holographic properties; various ways/instances of both/all of this, and nuance.
 - ▷ Not overcomplicating the language, even about LLM. With basic understanding, metaphors and mappings may come into play. Introducing new allusive/related terms, may or may not help any given person.
 - ▷ LLM are a technique nested within larger scope of computational statistical modeling. So various Map-Territory considerations and otherwise.
- ▼ 4. What to do with our ISSS Archives and 📚 Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository
 - ▼ Here we are in ISSS with attention to e.g. members, scope of the 🌐 ISSS.
 - ▷ Also there can be broader building of competence and applications.
 - ▷ So that the public is better in position to use, and have the ongoing conversations.
 - ▷ Already these models have been in used (e.g. ChatGPT current version ENDED training in 2021).
 - ▼ Cultures — Inter-generational, Multi-cultural — The language use is changing. The resilience, sensitivity to difference words/sentences can be variable.
 - ▷ Incumbent on the 🦋 Systems Science in the frameworks we present forward & Stigmergy :) 🐜
 - ▷ We are learning, and this is related to what questions to ask. This is not simply something in a tube that is squirted out. There are complex causes & consequences, including the dangerous.
 - ▼ Project-based perspective — Making sense of the next steps.
 - ▼ Spin out proof of concept projects:
 - ▼ Demonstrations with 📖 LLM & ISSS applied to 🌐 ISSS content and materials. This will be continued, concomitant with how many people come to 📖 KM as a project.
 - ▼ What is the operational modification that enables the rest of the 🌐 ISSS to be joining into the conversation?
 - ▼ Something on the website — “have a conversation with..... James Miller”. — Something that can be offered to the membership, and make it actual and grow something.
 - ▷ Conversations of a sort with Miller, Rosen etc is a real possibility now as a target for ISSS (if one can handle the copyright issue).
 - ▼ Personalities
 - ▷ Some feelings like there is “cults of personalities” — making a point by referring to a person.
 - ▷ Example: a reviewer of George’s textbook, wanting more historical synthesis. Going back to seminal notions, and the development of their ideas. They decided, No, that is not systems science. We need to be looking at the Synthesis — how the aspects play into being a system.
 - ▷ History and Philosophy of Science is not Science.
 - ▷ What someone has stated is their expression, that is not the internal coherence of 🦋 Systems Science . That is a human touchpoint, the context around the personality, is part of this!
 - ▷
 - ▼ How to Synthesize through the whole? The overall synthesis, and not needing to start from scratch. Can’t we integrate their insights?
 - ▷ This is distilled into e.g. axioms, processes
 - ▼ Having both the 🦋 Systems Science and the History/Philosophy of 🦋 Systems Science.

- ▷ Story-telling version of a science — other side — Textbook style literature — other side — hybrid.
 - ▷ Point of reference — as it has been, big men and big ideas. Artificial intelligence? How are we co-creating meaning?
 - ▷ To do a couple of annual meetings, to see developments/evolutions among meetings.
 - ▷ **Structured Dialog** — f — Not just learning about what LLMs can do for e.g. individuals or organizations, rather more in line with the social Trintab concept.
 - ▷
 - ▷
- ▼ **Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository**
 - ▷ Rob currently working on the website, coming in the next few weeks.
 - ▷ Will be updated to our group, and to the SCA newsletter.
 - ▷ Recommendation of materials for different levels of Inquiry and Action?
 - ▷ Appropriateness of documents.
 - ▷ What is appropriate for different paths/contexts in education and research?
 - ▷ Given membership in ISSS and broader Systems Science — we have everyone across axes of participation/experience/backgrounds/etc.
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 - ▷ Sand Talk: How Indigenous Thinking Can Save the World, by Tyson Yunkaporta
 - ▷ Decolonizing Methodologies: Research and Indigenous Peoples — by Linda Tuhiwai Smith
- ▼ **Primary direction: ISSS Collections**
 - ▼ See **Rob Young**.
 - ▷ Making the **Interface** more useful

▼ Secondary directions: Collaborative

- ▷ Other Collaborative, non-archival/SCA efforts in the space

▼ Development of Interfaces

- ▷ Traditional Database with search

- ▷ Interactive interfaces (Coda)

- ▼ Large Language Models // Chat interface (in [Coda](#) or otherwise)

- ▷ Custom corpus

- ▷ Formal knowledge model ([SUMO](#), other approaches).

▼ Writing.

- ▷ First step — One Pager on the project scope.

- ▼ Position paper — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.

- ▷ Would require an actual way forward.

- ▼ Assess the Active [#14 Modular Outcomes 4](#) and [Modular Outcomes](#) more generally.

- ▷ [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)

- ▷ [Strategy](#) — [@Develop Timeline for 2023](#)

- ▷ [Wiki Templates](#) — [@Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance](#)

- ▼ [ISSS Resources](#) —

- ▷ Scope the <https://web3.iss.org/km/> and integrate to Tabular form (with network view or export).

- ▷ [Systems Science](#) — and connect with [Education](#)

- ▼ [f.](https://web3.iss.org/marzolf-nov2021/index.html) — Systems <https://web3.iss.org/marzolf-nov2021/index.html>

- ▼ Tom, [@Peter T](#), [@Gary](#) discussing — it is a one-person model, at [a2hosting.com](#), and displayed on the front page of [iss.org](#) — in the “World of Systems” box

- ▷ They also talked about another modeling software.

- ▷ Wanting to ensure that [ISSS](#) has the ability to continue this work and model.

- ▷ Tom started studying, keeping notes, ideas — fragmented across files. As a modeler, in day job, he envisioned a single model that captured everything, that was adaptable, non-redundant, etc. Tom developed a model to do this.

- ▷ Universe, in a systems-oriented perspective. — To do this, focusing on the simpler starter area of “Systems Commons”

- ▼ Tom is fine with making a copy available.

- ▷ There is a lot of information that is in there, and also can be developed further.

- ▷ Tom can send Peter the current version, and source code.

- ▷ It is up all the time while working, and captures something every day. What is currently available on the ISSS [Website](#) is more than a year old (there are some updates and additions). What is currently there, is simpler and focuses on non-controversial facts.

- ▷ Schema

- ▼ Classes

- ▷ People

- ▷ Documents

- ▷ Websites

- ▷ Quotations

- ▼ Written in UML

- ▷ Some costly modeling tools do use this (IBM Rational). However also it can be exported and used in other programs (cheaper or free tools).
- ▷ With Bruce M., it was possible to export from modeling software
- ▼ Can it become a ISSS model, not just a single-person model?
 - ▷ There has to be some coordination — e.g. some central person? Github? Other coordinating mechanism.
- ▼ What is the functionality?
 - ▷ Export — puts into standard UML format.
 - ▼ Organizing the whole —
 - ▷ Building on this Synthesis, so that work does not start from scratch.
 - ▷ So that we build together. Problem: Everything becomes custom.
 - ▷ Tom's work has a critical mass
 - ▷ Len, Francois, and other archival projects/attempts.
 - ▷ Topos Institute — Archival developments and challenges, even with the narrower (still broad) question of system.
 - ▷ So coming up with an archiving approach, getting a critical mass.
 - ▷ Concept mapping
 - ▼ Finding information, and continuing to update it, so it becomes a standard source of information.
 - ▷ About People, Organizations, Ideas, etc.
 - ▷ Quotations (organized in some way by subject).
 - ▷ Gradually organizing into e.g. Disciplines, Themes (including [KM as a project](#)), keeping this adaptable. Needs to be kept adaptive.
 - ▷ Simulation (not currently used).
 - ▷ Domain-specific ontologies that can map together (not currently used).
- ▷ Rigor and evidence-based aspect of Tom's work. In the Holism SIG — what Tom brings in to “System”, “Dimension” as evidence to keep things grounded in discussions. This is what the discipline needs in the work; a structured ontology, and a reminder about how we can operate as Systems Science investigators.
- ▷ What we want — all these things like quotations, citations, etc (historical) and the concepts (e.g. George's textbook) and the coherent paths that link them together
- ▼ If we start with a structure of the core principles and concepts, then have linkages with the Entities/Objects in Tom's database. Start with a skeleton of the fundamentals of systems, then use this to branch out.
 - ▷ Someone is researching “Holarchy” — who has researched this, and what other related concepts exist?
 - ▷ Start with the core integration? Starting with a collection of things?
 - ▷ This is the meta-root of the issue..... And there en-lies the challenge.
 - ▷ Starting with a core knowledge model, then developing and integrating. Rather than continuing this argument, how/should something be included?
 - ▷ Everyone who has written about Systems has foregrounded the topics, with different intentions and outcomes.
 - ▷ Views & Viewpoints. Working with patterns, coming from different viewpoints, why they have different preferences.
 - ▷ What is the Thing they are looking at? We only know their traces.
 - ▷ Outcome oriented — what should/could be known at the end of High School here or there?
- ▼ Multiple rendering/realizations.
 - ▷ Warfield, Structured dialogs. Leveraging tools for common reference.

#14 Modular Outcomes 4

Area		Status	To discuss	Name
▼ MediaWiki	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
▼ Ways to participate	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meet
▼ Strategy	2	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Research Unified storage solution for ISSS
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		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Developing uses for ISSS Archives

- Using a Gantt Chart
- Usage of Chat AI

#18 May 18, 2023

Meeting recording

- https://youtu.be/SU6WSPH_FgE

Feedback before the meeting

- .

General and to-do

- ISSS Archive Interface: https://coda.io/d/ISSS-Archive-Interface_daDW68lgaJ/Home_sunhx#_lu_tj
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.iss.org/primer2/>
 - <https://www.iss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>
- ISSS Conference?

Agenda & Ongoing Notes

- ▷ Purpose of 📖 [KM as a project](#) & View towards 🎓 [Education](#)
- ▼ 📖 [LLM & ISSS](#)
 - ▼ Randall & Gary Smith — working with GPT4 on developing articles.
 - ▷ From meeting 1-2 weeks ago, and processing the results of the exercise.
 - ▷ What are features to consider when designing/exploring how to use such methods?
 - ▼ They adapted some of the concepts that Gary was working with, and related it to a narrative discussion of 📖 [Systems Science](#) . So it bears on:
 - ▷ Developing content (humans using tools).
 - ▷ Not differentiating LLM in principle for other tools like e.g. spellcheck (that wouldn't be subject to human review and consideration).
 - ▷ It is an exercise in creativity, creative thinking, creative (and accurate writing) in describing our understandings of the concepts.
 - ▷ Developing citations.... in response to the set of activities in the experiment.
 - ▼ Randall noticed that in developing the prompt, and developing responses to varieties of prompts — Text was returned that looked like citations, though not checked. Not always transparent as to where the linkages are. Could be a lot of work to authenticate the reference materials
 - ▼ Can spot citations that are valid — get initial judgement around whether the output is valid.
 - ▷ George, students are very good in recognizing the structure of a paper in terms of Citations, References, etc. They start putting things in. There are ways to determine whether a citation is valid. For example what we would expect of a referee in a journal article — enough familiarity with a field, to rapidly determine whether it is relevant.

- ▷ It depends on how zoomed in & technical the references and citations are. This also requires work and expertise, which is a limiting resource in many cases.
- ▼ The person who is generating the prompt and looking for an output — needs to be adequately grounded in the subject matter they are looking for, so they can make valid assertions.
 - ▷ Is this practical? — For any given individual to know all of that existing (training) information, and evaluate novelty/relevance.
- ▷ Usage of knowledge structures, possibly in rhetorical assertion architecture (e.g. [TrustFinder](#)) linking citation to context.
- ▷ Developing semantic provenance systems for integrity of the informational supply chains.
- ▼ Prompt flow:
 - ▷ Analyze the above text and simply list everything that looks like it is a citation or reference.
 - ▷ For the list of citations, please use web lookup to investigate whether each citation is available on the public internet. Return two lists, one of valid citations (all metadata information in the citation is true and available) and one of invalid citations (not able to be found on the public internet).
 - ▷ For the list of valid citations.....
 - ▷ For the list of invalid citations.....
 - ▷ What is an appropriate level of due diligence?
 - ▼ We could take a look at [Yearbooks \(SCA-ISSS-GSY-D230207A\)](#) and Proceedings. Look at the citation networks — how often do newer papers utilize the older citations?
 - ▷ Combine the semantic/language analyses with bibliometric analysis
 - ▷ Also there is this “dark matter” of citations, the invisible (though possibly assayable) influence of different language use on every expression. Preserving the integrity of the original works while utilizing some aspects of their specific contributions.
 - ▷ Source tagging/embeddings.
 - ▷ Temporal tagging/embeddings
- ▼ Language Models \neq Knowledge Model
 - ▷ In observing the children and grandchildren developing — to an extent repeating their context’s ways of talking. And how they connect sentience & intelligence with language processing.
 - ▷ Exploring this relationship of LLM & multiple Knowledge models
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 - ▼ Spin out proof of concept projects:
 - ▼ [Demonstrations](#) with [KM as a project](#).
 - ▼ What is the operational modification that enables the rest of the ISSS to be joining into the conversation?
 - ▼ Something on the website — “have a conversation with..... James Miller”. — Something that can be offered to the membership, and make it actual and grow something.
 - ▷ Conversations of a sort with Miller, Rosen etc is a real possibility now as a target for ISSS (if one can handle the copyright issue).
 - ▼ Personalities
 - ▷ Some feelings like there is “cults of personalities” — making a point by referring to a person.
 - ▷ Example: a reviewer of George’s textbook, wanting more historical synthesis. Going back to seminal notions, and the development of their ideas. They decided, No, that is not systems science. We need to be looking at the Synthesis — how the aspects play into being a system.
 - ▷ History and Philosophy of Science is not Science.
 - ▷ What someone has stated is their expression, that is not the internal coherence of [Systems Science](#) . That is a [human touchpoint, the context around the personality](#), is part of this!
 - ▷
 - ▼ How to Synthesize through the whole? [The overall synthesis](#), and not needing to start from scratch. Can’t we integrate their insights?
 - ▷ This is distilled into e.g. axioms, processes
 - ▼ Having both the [Systems Science](#).
 - ▷ Story-telling version of a science — other side — Textbook style literature — other side — hybrid.
 - ▷ Point of reference — as it has been, big men and big ideas. Artificial intelligence? How are we co-creating meaning?

- ▷ To do a couple of annual meetings, to see developments/evolutions among meetings.
 - ▷ **Structured Dialog** — — Not just learning about what LLMs can do for e.g. individuals or organizations, rather more in line with the social Trintab concept.
- ▼ FYI: The 3rd Thursday of May has been designated as Global Accessibility Awareness Day. Here is a link to the GAAD2023 events occurring today: <https://accessibility.day/events/>
 - ▷ ISSS could consider doing something in a future conference.
- ▼ **Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository**
 - ▷ Rob currently working on the website, coming in the next few weeks.
 - ▷ Will be updated to our group, and to the SCA newsletter.
 - ▷ Recommendation of materials for different levels of Inquiry and Action?
 - ▷ Appropriateness of documents.
 - ▷ What is appropriate for different paths/contexts in education and research?
 - ▷ Given membership in ISSS and broader Systems Science — we have everyone across axes of participation/experience/backgrounds/etc.
 - ▷ So how to help navigate the spectrums and types of materials?
 - ▷ How to match to the capabilities of the person to be dealing with? Fitness.
 - ▼ This is big and developing topic — going hand in hand with development.
 - ▷ How Can we use it? Is.
 - ▷ How Should we use it? Ought.
 - ▼ What resources are available?
 - ▷ Development of the resource — being able to support different use cases.
 - ▷ Many proposals for ideas — important to have filtering process, for priority, attention, funding, etc.
 - ▷ Education stream provides many focused questions
 - ▷ Capturing initiatives or proposals — for people to volunteer for.
 - ▷ Starting to form collaborative framework to help people in their initiatives.
 - ▷ False positive // False negative.
 - ▷ Organizational learning curve — building the capabilities and maturities, to play role in supporting initiatives in the systems community.
- ▼ Strategies
 - ▼ James Greer Miller — Living Systems Theory — **Systems Science**
 - ▷ Peter got some lectures and interviews — transcribed
 - ▷ Can we have ISSS transcripts fed in, to have collective intelligence
 - ▷ Sand Talk: How Indigenous Thinking Can Save the World, by Tyson Yunkaporta
 - ▷ Decolonizing Methodologies: Research and Indigenous Peoples — by Linda Tuhiwai Smith
- ▼ **Primary direction: ISSS Collections**
 - ▼ See **ISSS @ SCA**, with [@Rob Young](#).
 - ▷ Making the **Interface** more useful
- ▼ **Secondary directions: Collaborative**
 - ▷ **Other Collaborative, non-archival/SCA efforts in the space**
 - ▼ **Development of Interfaces**

- ▷ Traditional Database with search
- ▷ Interactive interfaces (Coda)
- ▼ Large Language Models // Chat interface (in [Coda](#) or otherwise)
 - ▷ Custom corpus
 - ▷ Formal knowledge model ([SUMO](#), other approaches).
- ▼ Writing.
 - ▷ First step — One Pager on the project scope.
 - ▼ Position paper — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.
 - ▷ Would require an actual way forward.
- ▼ Assess the Active [#18 Modular Outcomes](#) and [Modular Outcomes](#) more generally.
 - ▷ [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)
 - ▷ [Strategy](#) — [@Develop Timeline for 2023](#)
 - ▷ [Wiki Templates](#) — [@Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance](#)
 - ▼ [ISSS Resources](#) —
 - ▷ Scope the <https://web3.iss.org/km/> and integrate to Tabular form (with network view or export).
 - ▷ [Systems Science](#) — and connect with [Education](#)
- ▼ [f.](#) — Systems <https://web3.iss.org/marzolf-nov2021/index.html>
 - ▼ Tom, [@Peter T](#), [@Gary](#) discussing — it is a one-person model, at [a2hosting.com](#), and displayed on the front page of [iss.org](#) — in the “World of Systems” box
 - ▷ They also talked about another modeling software.
 - ▷ Wanting to ensure that [ISSS](#) has the ability to continue this work and model.
 - ▷ Tom started studying, keeping notes, ideas — fragmented across files. As a modeler, in day job, he envisioned a single model that captured everything, that was adaptable, non-redundant, etc. Tom developed a model to do this.
 - ▷ Universe, in a systems-oriented perspective. — To do this, focusing on the simpler starter area of “Systems Commons”
 - ▼ Tom is fine with making a copy available.
 - ▷ There is a lot of information that is in there, and also can be developed further.
 - ▷ Tom can send Peter the current version, and source code.
 - ▷ It is up all the time while working, and captures something every day. What is currently available on the ISSS [Website](#) is more than a year old (there are some updates and additions). What is currently there, is simpler and focuses on non-controversial facts.
 - ▷ Schema
 - ▼ Classes
 - ▷ People
 - ▷ Documents
 - ▷ Websites
 - ▷ Quotations
 - ▼ Written in UML
 - ▷ Some costly modeling tools do use this (IBM Rational). However also it can be exported and used in other programs (cheaper or free tools).
 - ▷ With Bruce M., is was possible to export from modeling software

- ▼ Can it become a ISSS model, not just a single-person model?
 - ▷ There has to be some coordination — e.g. some central person? Github? Other coordinating mechanism.
- ▼ What is the functionality?
 - ▷ Export — puts into standard UML format.
 - ▼ Organizing the whole —
 - ▷ Building on this Synthesis, so that work does not start from scratch.
 - ▷ So that we build together. Problem: Everything becomes custom.
 - ▷ Tom’s work has a critical mass
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 - ▷ So coming up with an archiving approach, getting a critical mass.
 - ▷ Concept mapping
 - ▼ Finding information, and continuing to update it, so it becomes a standard source of information.
 - ▷ About People, Organizations, Ideas, etc.
 - ▷ Quotations (organized in some way by subject).
 - ▷ Gradually organizing into e.g. Disciplines, Themes (including KM as a project), keeping this adaptable. Needs to be kept adaptive.
 - ▷ Simulation (not currently used).
 - ▷ Domain-specific ontologies that can map together (not currently used).
- ▷ Rigor and evidence-based aspect of Tom’s work. In the Holism SIG — what Tom brings in to “System”, “Dimension” as evidence to keep things grounded in discussions. This is what the discipline needs in the work; a structured ontology, and a reminder about how we can operate as Systems Science investigators.
- ▷ What we want — all these things like quotations, citations, etc (historical) and the concepts (e.g. George’s textbook) and the coherent paths that link them together
- ▼ If we start with a structure of the core principles and concepts, then have linkages with the Entities/Objects in Tom’s database. Start with a skeleton of the fundamentals of systems, then use this to branch out.
 - ▷ Someone is researching “Holarchy” — who has researched this, and what other related concepts exist?
 - ▷ Start with the core integration? Starting with a collection of things?
 - ▷ This is the meta-root of the issue..... And there en-lies the challenge.
 - ▷ Starting with a core knowledge model, then developing and integrating. Rather than continuing this argument, how/should something be included?
 - ▷ Everyone who has written about Systems has foregrounded the topics, with different intentions and outcomes.
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- ▼ Multiple rendering/realizations.
 - ▷ Warfield, Structured dialogs. Leveraging tools for common reference.

#18 Modular Outcomes

Area		Status	To discuss	Name
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▼ Ways to participate	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meet
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		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Front end for ISSS archives
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Developing uses for ISSS Archives

- Using a Gantt Chart
- Usage of Chat AI

#19 June 1, 2023

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/GnoMDLW5Eio>

Feedback before the meeting

- .

General and to-do

- ISSS Archive Interface: https://coda.io/d/ISSS-Archive-Interface_daDW68lgaJ/Home_sunhx#_lu_tj
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.iss.org/primer2/>
 - <https://www.iss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>
- ISSS Conference?
- John Sowa talk on LLM/GPT
- Special Session of the Ontolog Forum on GPT
 - https://ontologforum.com/index.php/ConferenceCall_2023_05_31
- [Most recent Education meeting](#)

Agenda & Ongoing Notes

- ▷ Purpose of Education
- ▼ LLM & ISSS
 - ▼ Randall & Gary Smith — working with GPT4 on developing articles.
 - ▷ From meeting 1-2 weeks ago, and processing the results of the exercise.
 - ▷ What are features to consider when designing/exploring how to use such methods?
 - ▼ They adapted some of the concepts that Gary was working with, and related it to a narrative discussion of [Systems Science](#) . So it bears on:
 - ▷ Developing content (humans using tools).
 - ▷ Not differentiating LLM in principle for other tools like e.g. spellcheck (that wouldn't be subject to human review and consideration).
 - ▷ It is an exercise in creativity, creative thinking, creative (and accurate writing) in describing our understandings of the concepts.
 - ▷ Developing citations.... in response to the set of activities in the experiment.
 - ▼ Randall noticed that in developing the prompt, and developing responses to varieties of prompts — Text was returned that looked like citations, though not checked. Not always transparent as to where the linkages are. Could be a lot of work to authenticate the reference materials

- ▼ Can spot citations that are valid — get initial judgement around whether the output is valid.
 - ▷ George, students are very good in recognizing the structure of a paper in terms of Citations, References, etc. They start putting things in. There are ways to determine whether a citation is valid. For example what we would expect of a referee in a journal article — enough familiarity with a field, to rapidly determine whether it is relevant.
 - ▷ It depends on how zoomed in & technical the references and citations are. This also requires work and expertise, which is a limiting resource in many cases.
 - ▼ The person who is generating the prompt and looking for an output — needs to be adequately grounded in the subject matter they are looking for, so they can make valid assertions.
 - ▷ Is this practical? — For any given individual to know all of that existing (training) information, and evaluate novelty/relevance.
 - ▷ Usage of knowledge structures, possibly in rhetorical assertion architecture (e.g. [TrustFinder](#)) linking citation to context.
 - ▷ Developing semantic provenance systems for integrity of the informational supply chains.
 - ▼ Prompt flow:
 - ▷ Analyze the above text and simply list everything that looks like it is a citation or reference.
 - ▷ For the list of citations, please use web lookup to investigate whether each citation is available on the public internet. Return two lists, one of valid citations (all metadata information in the citation is true and available) and one of invalid citations (not able to be found on the public internet).
 - ▷ For the list of valid citations.....
 - ▷ For the list of invalid citations.....
 - ▷ What is an appropriate level of due diligence?
 - ▼ We could take a look at [Yearbooks \(SCA-ISSS-GSY-D230207A\)](#) and Proceedings. Look at the citation networks — how often do newer papers utilize the older citations?
 - ▷ Combine the semantic/language analyses with bibliometric analysis
 - ▷ Also there is this “dark matter” of citations, the invisible (though possibly assailable) influence of different language use on every expression. Preserving the integrity of the original works while utilizing some aspects of their specific contributions.
 - ▷ Source tagging/embeddings.
 - ▷ Temporal tagging/embeddings
- ▼ Language Models \neq Knowledge Model
 - ▷ In observing the children and grandchildren developing — to an extent repeating their context's ways of talking. And how they connect sentience & intelligence with language processing.
 - ▷ Exploring this relationship of LLM & multiple Knowledge models
 - ▷ Current model's input is (labeled) text, this seems to go far/fast in some (not all!) context.
 - ▼ Generation of discussions within [ISSS](#) and outside / on the interface. Hopefully we show up well here.
 - ▷ To what extent, comments spoken/written yesterday, reflect generalized fear/anxiety around AI/technology, rather than specific aspects of Language Models.
 - ▷ The biggest fear with AI is fear itself | De Kai | TEDxSanMigueldeAllende
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WU-RUIZWkio>
 - ▷ Humans have a natural tendency to see sentience in inanimate objects. This might be a basis for seeing intentions in AIs
- ▼ Language models.

- ▷ Predominant in people's thinking.
- ▷ Large tech companies also integrating into their technology.
- ▷ 🗄️ **KM as a project** is/was formulated around making the information more accessible.
- ▷ This may also tie in to the physics of 'perception' of actions, context, etc. that I am delving into...
- ▷ Possible for us (ISSS) to explore and even use an open source language model server/system such as Bloom
- ▷ <https://techcrunch.com/2022/07/12/a-year-in-the-making-bigsciences-ai-language-model-is-finally-available/>
- ▼ Ways in which LLM exploration, touches on transdisciplinary understandings (🦋 **Systems Science**), getting at different understandings.
 - ▼ Interface — To what extent is it Technology, Human focused?
 - ▼ Where we are e.g. composing papers or texts with LLM, it is our partner/co-creator in meaning-making. We are talking with each other, looking at text.
 - ▷ This can be addressed with OBS virtual camera (need to start this before the meeting).
 - ▷ How do we work with AI?
 - ▼ Pattern Languages, @Peter T College of Exploration, Meta-Design, settings. This is why we split the two conversations into 🎓 **Education** and 🗄️ **KM as a project**.
 - ▷ There is a lot of Resources out there, and Technologies (previous digitization efforts).
 - ▷ We can do a lot of work to facilitate the human, and make it work well. The human experience of being together. Online is a helpful way to do it, meeting in person is usually inviable.
 - ▷ Consideration of the relationship between Humans and Machine — ongoing struggle of the 250 years of Systems and Cybernetics. What we are facing with the archives — unless we can use machines to help us bootstrap the synthesis of all these individual human products, trying to stand on each other's shoulders (language issues! people don't build on each other's work). There is an opportunity to provide synthesis and overview, a periodic table of system, things that always became reduced down to individual works and starting from scratch. Limitations of the capabilities of individual humans.
 - ▷ The exciting challenge and opportunity for LLM, and the imperative in the 🌐 **ISSS**, is for those who have asked philosophical questions, language, decision-making — imperative to make the work accessible. Some have been working on synthesis projects for many years. The synthesis is a massive challenge.
 - ▷ Redundancy in conversation — same pieces going around and around. Something needs to move?
 - ▷ Hierarchy theory, Ontology of language, semantic webs — all are conjoined in this area.
 - ▼ Language-as-such has properties that are not the same as e.g. manifest linear strings of symbols or phonemes.
 - ▷ As an Area of Inquiry, Language is holographic.
 - ▷ So LLM inputs (indeed any inputs based upon biological system) are holographic. LLM can rapidly access information, in the holographic encounter. The output is again linearized.
 - ▼ Three Systemic Models
 - ▷ **Theoretical frames**: What is an LLM? What are the domains? What constitutes the Holographic/Linear components?
 - ▷ **Interactive study**: Second level Systems community can explore — how are such models used in co-creation of Meaning and Realities? Experimental.
 - ▷ **A question of pragmatic utility**: How does the ISSS use 🗄️ **LLM & ISSS**, to augment presentations, enrich the discourse, further the 🌐 **ISSS** agenda.
- ▷ 1. How do LLM work (technical discussion)?
- ▷ 2. What is our relationship/engagement with the tools AND broader systems?
- ▼ 3. How does this relate to 🦋 **Systems Science**, Languageing, Systemese, the ways in which language shapes worlds?

- ▷ Possible 🎓 Education around Language, how/what is used.
- ▷ From the munching of words, towards integrated information? The information is holographic?
- ▼ Language, and culture, as holographic relationships — organized as a whole, these systems have a holographic capacity. And this is captured in some ways via the modeling and training.
 - ▷ Also this may divert/overcomplicate things — the LLM is using Vector Embeddings. Holographic properties; various ways/instances of both/all of this, and nuance.
 - ▷ Not overcomplicating the language, even about LLM. With basic understanding, metaphors and mappings may come into play. Introducing new allusive/related terms, may or may not help any given person.
 - ▷ LLM are a technique nested within larger scope of computational statistical modeling. So various Map-Territory considerations and otherwise.
- ▼ 4. What to do with our ISSS Archives and 📚 Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository
 - ▼ Here we are in ISSS with attention to e.g. members, scope of the 🌐 ISSS.
 - ▷ Also there can be broader building of competence and applications.
 - ▷ So that the public is better in position to use, and have the ongoing conversations.
 - ▷ Already these models have been in used (e.g. ChatGPT current version ENDED training in 2021).
 - ▼ Cultures — Inter-generational, Multi-cultural — The language use is changing. The resilience, sensitivity to difference words/sentences can be variable.
 - ▷ Incumbent on the 🦋 Systems Science in the frameworks we present forward & Stigmergy :) 🐜
 - ▷ We are learning, and this is related to what questions to ask. This is not simply something in a tube that is squirted out. There are complex causes & consequences, including the dangerous.
 - ▼ Project-based perspective — Making sense of the next steps.
 - ▼ Spin out proof of concept projects:
 - ▼ Demonstrations with 📖 LLM & ISSS applied to 🌐 ISSS content and materials. This will be continued, concomitant with how many people come to 📖 KM as a project.
 - ▼ What is the operational modification that enables the rest of the 🌐 ISSS to be joining into the conversation?
 - ▼ Something on the website — “have a conversation with..... James Miller”. — Something that can be offered to the membership, and make it actual and grow something.
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- ▼ **Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository**
 - ▷ See previous notes in **#18 May 18, 2023**
 - ▼ June 1, 2023
 - ▼ Previously the entire contents of the **ISSS** archives were handed over.
 - ▷ Coda representation of the data is a proof of concept or draft.
 - ▷ Other archivists may be interested in Coda.
 - ▷ Also we may be able to use **LLM & ISSS** in this utilization. Conversation, voices with the past.
 - ▼ **@Developing uses for ISSS Archives --**
 - ▷ **Ask Education for questions.** We're going to use this questions on preliminary set of available documents.
 - ▷ What questions do you want to ask of the **Systems Science** corpus?
 - ▷ We will do better in planning Educational materials if we can ___ better.
 - ▷ Course work for using ChatGPT for understanding how it works, for using it as a tool rather than a cheat).
 - ▷ How can we come up with Generative work in the spirit of **Systems Science** and that helps learn Systems?
 - ▷ We need help using the ISSS Archives
 - ▷ We need help using LLM to survey and leverage the ISSS Archives.
 - ▷ We need questions that people want to ask to Knowledge systems about Systems Science and/or different domains.
 - ▷ Also Rob is developing the website for the broader community so that **Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository** can be useful. Also this entails that the ISSS data is updated. More spreadsheets will be incoming.
- ▼ **Primary direction: ISSS Collections**
 - ▼ See **ISSS @ SCA**, with **@Rob Young**.
 - ▷ Making the **Interface** more useful
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- Usage of Chat AI

#20 June 15, 2023

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/7rD665o53ac>

@ meeting_saved_chat.txt

Feedback before the meeting

- .

General and to-do

- ISSS Archive Interface: https://coda.io/d/ISSS-Archive-Interface_daDW68lgaJ/Home_sunhx#_lu_tj
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.iss.org/primer2/>
 - <https://www.iss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>
- ISSS Conference?
- John Sowa talk on LLM/GPT
- Special Session of the Ontolog Forum on GPT
 - https://ontologforum.com/index.php/ConferenceCall_2023_05_31
- [Most recent Education meeting](#)
- **Sacred Unity : Further Steps to an Ecology of Mind**, Gregory Bateson (Author), Rodney E Donaldson (Author)
- ..

Agenda & Ongoing Notes

- ▷ Purpose of [Education](#)
- ▼ @Yiannis yesterday had a Structured Democratic Dialog (SDD), Chris Smerald was there, watch this space.
 - ▷ There is a link to some outcomes, [a google document is being created for this](#).
 - ▷ They start with a Question, then some Suggestions, and details like How it would work & What would be needed.
- ▼ George's corpus as entry point, "World according to George", then George and Friends, then etc...
 - ▷ Does not want it simply about him. Agrees this is a starting point, perhaps not called as such. George's neighborhood. Preserving claims and semantics.
 - ▷ The claim that George et al. made was, this is the first comprehensive Textbook-like work on the whole of [Systems Science](#) . There are so many books out there, written by so many authors from the angle of their own, even if called e.g. "Introduction to Systems Science", or "Facets of". They tried to do a well-rounded and comprehensive synthetic work.

▼ Charlie Hall — Limits of Growth.

- ▷ This is in some past Saturday ISSS sessions
- ▷ All the work may not make a difference if we do not attend to limits of growth.

▼ General topics and considerations — people who have done a lot of work in [✖ Systems Science](#)

- ▷ When someone does not have the energy to extensively comment.
- ▷ The only way to prove/validate this technology is to probe with alternative views. To challenge what is being done with Systems, with what is meant.
- ▷ Can prompt new connections in the work and have the person validate this.
- ▷ Various attempts to draw up lists of the Systems Theory candidates. By what criteria do we judge these theories from/with?
- ▷ Survey of the criteria, and cross reference across frameworks. Has anyone done a review/meta-analysis of this?

▼ [Len Troncale](#) may have done this work, on General General Theory

- ▷ What would a general systems theory look like if you bumped into it?
- ▷ George never described the theory of systems, it is a framework for systemness. May be hard to escape some linguistic baggage.
- ▷ Absolute General — Applies to all kinds of systems, across fields of study. Science studies things, [✖ Systems Science](#) has to study across these systems.
- ▷ the general theory of systems may end up being a system
- ▷ Tied to a person — “X’s theory of...”, it is like a menu. Choosing from columns at the restaurant. There is a strong attitude in [ISSS](#) and around, of Theoretical and Methodological Pluralism (see: Helen Longino on Scientific pluralism). There are various applicable theories and methods. However all equal credit in evaluation or presentation, is untenable.
- ▷ Shingai’s most recent blog post [Systemism as Ideology](#).
- ▷ as per the theory of motivated numeracy, the more logical cased you are the more able you are to fool yourself on emotionally charged issues
- ▷ [The Rise of Systems Theory: An Ideological Analysis by Robert Lilienfeld](#)
- ▷ Fun to imagine, the debates among different systems scientists.
- ▷ so, how can we get a half consensus on what body of works to get started with, or is the plan to be more random?
- ▷ <https://home.nomic.ai/wiki> && <https://atlas.nomic.ai/>
- ▷ <https://zenodo.org/record/8025957> Comments on AI Accountability Policy Submitted to NTIA Docket 2023-0005-0001 by IRSIRI, All, PFH, and COGSEC
- ▷ Systems intelligence can help us understand situations/consequences.
- ▷ Small Is Beautiful, 25th Anniversary Edition: Economics As If People Mattered: 25 Years Later: <https://www.amazon.com/Small-Beautiful-25th-Anniversary-Commentaries/dp/0881791695>
- ▷ We could do the reverse? Have ISSS members provide commentaries on current emerging work?
- ▷ Cynthia Kurtz, Participatory narrative inquiry.
- ▷ <https://www.goodreads.com/book/show/22392219-working-with-stories-in-your-community-or-organization>
- ▷ Real test: adding another perspective/corpus to the initial testing one, and understand/evaluate the changes. We are talking about words used, in describing the same thing (e.g. Claire used some other term for Systemness). “That’s what I’m talking about”. In Europe they talk of “Systemics”.
- ▷ Would applying the tool to the different corpuses, of research work, start to converge on a more limited/delineated set of terms. <https://www.ontologyportal.org/> and WordNet.

▼ LLM & ISSS

- ▼ Randall & Gary Smith — working with GPT4 on developing articles.
 - ▷ From meeting 1-2 weeks ago, and processing the results of the exercise.
 - ▷ What are features to consider when designing/exploring how to use such methods?
- ▼ They adapted some of the concepts that Gary was working with, and related it to a narrative discussion of [Systems Science](#). So it bears on:
 - ▷ Developing content (humans using tools).
 - ▷ Not differentiating LLM in principle for other tools like e.g. spellcheck (that wouldn't be subject to human review and consideration).
 - ▷ It is an exercise in creativity, creative thinking, creative (and accurate writing) in describing our understandings of the concepts.
- ▷ Developing citations.... in response to the set of activities in the experiment.
- ▼ Randall noticed that in developing the prompt, and developing responses to varieties of prompts — Text was returned that looked like citations, though not checked. Not always transparent as to where the linkages are. Could be a lot of work to authenticate the reference materials
 - ▼ Can spot citations that are valid — get initial judgement around whether the output is valid.
 - ▷ George, students are very good in recognizing the structure of a paper in terms of Citations, References, etc. They start putting things in. There are ways to determine whether a citation is valid. For example what we would expect of a referee in a journal article — enough familiarity with a field, to rapidly determine whether it is relevant.
 - ▷ It depends on how zoomed in & technical the references and citations are. This also requires work and expertise, which is a limiting resource in many cases.
 - ▼ The person who is generating the prompt and looking for an output — needs to be adequately grounded in the subject matter they are looking for, so they can make valid assertions.
 - ▷ Is this practical? — For any given individual to know all of that existing (training) information, and evaluate novelty/relevance.
 - ▷ Usage of knowledge structures, possibly in rhetorical assertion architecture (e.g. [TrustFinder](#)) linking citation to context.
 - ▷ Developing semantic provenance systems for integrity of the informational supply chains.
- ▼ Prompt flow:
 - ▷ Analyze the above text and simply list everything that looks like it is a citation or reference.
 - ▷ For the list of citations, please use web lookup to investigate whether each citation is available on the public internet. Return two lists, one of valid citations (all metadata information in the citation is true and available) and one of invalid citations (not able to be found on the public internet).
 - ▷ For the list of valid citations.....
 - ▷ For the list of invalid citations.....
 - ▷ What is an appropriate level of due diligence?
- ▼ We could take a look at [Yearbooks \(SCA-ISSS-GSY-D230207A\)](#) and Proceedings. Look at the citation networks — how often do newer papers utilize the older citations?
 - ▷ Combine the semantic/language analyses with bibliometric analysis
 - ▷ Also there is this “dark matter” of citations, the invisible (though possibly assayable) influence of different language use on every expression. Preserving the integrity of the original works while utilizing some aspects of their specific contributions.

- ▷ Source tagging/embeddings.
- ▷ Temporal tagging/embeddings
- ▼ Language Models \neq Knowledge Model
 - ▷ In observing the children and grandchildren developing — to an extent repeating their context's ways of talking. And how they connect sentience & intelligence with language processing.
 - ▷ Exploring this relationship of LLM & multiple Knowledge models
 - ▷ Current model's input is (labeled) text, this seems to go far/fast in some (not all!) context.
 - ▼ Generation of discussions within ISSS and outside / on the interface. Hopefully we show up well here.
 - ▷ To what extent, comments spoken/written yesterday, reflect generalized fear/anxiety around AI/technology, rather than specific aspects of Language Models.
 - ▷ The biggest fear with AI is fear itself | De Kai | TEDxSanMigueldeAllende
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WU-RUIZWkio>
 - ▷ Humans have a natural tendency to see sentience in inanimate objects. This might be a basis for seeing intentions in AIs
- ▼ Language models.
 - ▷ Predominant in people's thinking.
 - ▷ Large tech companies also integrating into their technology.
 - ▷ KM as a project is/was formulated around making the information more accessible.
 - ▷ This may also tie in to the physics of 'perception' of actions, context, etc. that I am delving into...
 - ▷ Possible for us (ISSS) to explore and even use an open source language model server/system such as Bloom
 - ▷ <https://techcrunch.com/2022/07/12/a-year-in-the-making-bigsciences-ai-language-model-is-finally-available/>
- ▼ Ways in which LLM exploration, touches on transdisciplinary understandings (Systems Science), getting at different understandings.
 - ▼ Interface — To what extent is it Technology, Human focused?
 - ▼ Where we are e.g. composing papers or texts with LLM, it is our partner/co-creator in meaning-making. We are talking with each other, looking at text.
 - ▷ This can be addressed with OBS virtual camera (need to start this before the meeting).
 - ▷ How do we work with AI?
 - ▼ Pattern Languages, @Peter T College of Exploration, Meta-Design, settings. This is why we split the two conversations into KM as a project.
 - ▷ There is a lot of Resources out there, and Technologies (previous digitization efforts).
 - ▷ We can do a lot of work to facilitate the human, and make it work well. The human experience of being together. Online is a helpful way to do it, meeting in person is usually infeasible.
 - ▷ Consideration of the relationship between Humans and Machine — ongoing struggle of the 250 years of Systems and Cybernetics. What we are facing with the archives — unless we can use machines to help us bootstrap the synthesis of all these individual human products, trying to stand on each other's shoulders (language issues! people don't build on each other's work). There is an opportunity to provide synthesis and overview, a periodic table of system, things that always became reduced down to individual works and starting from scratch. Limitations of the capabilities of individual humans.
 - ▷ The exciting challenge and opportunity for LLM, and the imperative in the ISSS, is for those who have asked philosophical questions, language, decision-making — imperative to make the work accessible. Some have been working on synthesis projects for many years. The synthesis is a massive challenge.
 - ▷ Redundancy in conversation — same pieces going around and around. Something needs to move?

- ▷ Hierarchy theory, Ontology of language, semantic webs — all are conjoined in this area.
- ▼ Language-as-such has properties that are not the same as e.g. manifest linear strings of symbols or phonemes.
 - ▷ As an Area of Inquiry, Language is holographic.
 - ▷ So LLM inputs (indeed any inputs based upon biological system) are holographic. LLM can rapidly access information, in the holographic encounter. The output is again linearized.
- ▼ Three Systemic Models
 - ▷ **Theoretical frames:** What is an LLM? What are the domains? What constitutes the Holographic/Linear components?
 - ▷ **Interactive study:** Second level Systems community can explore — how are such models used in co-creation of Meaning and Realities? Experimental.
 - ▷ **A question of pragmatic utility:** How does the ISSS use **ISSS** agenda.
- ▷ 1. How do LLM work (technical discussion)?
- ▷ 2. What is our relationship/engagement with the tools AND broader systems?
- ▼ 3. How does this relate to **Systems Science**, Languageing, Systemese, the ways in which language shapes worlds?
 - ▷ Possible **Education** around Language, how/what is used.
 - ▷ From the munching of words, towards integrated information? The information is holographic?
- ▼ Language, and culture, as holographic relationships — organized as a whole, these systems have a holographic capacity. And this is captured in some ways via the modeling and training.
 - ▷ Also this may divert/overcomplicate things — the LLM is using Vector Embeddings. Holographic properties; various ways/instances of both/all of this, and nuance.
 - ▷ Not overcomplicating the language, even about LLM. With basic understanding, metaphors and mappings may come into play. Introducing new allusive/related terms, may or may not help any given person.
 - ▷ LLM are a technique nested within larger scope of computational statistical modeling. So various Map-Territory considerations and otherwise.
- ▼ 4. What to do with our ISSS Archives and **Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository**
 - ▼ Here we are in ISSS with attention to e.g. members, scope of the **ISSS**.
 - ▷ Also there can be broader building of competence and applications.
 - ▷ So that the public is better in position to use, and have the ongoing conversations.
 - ▷ Already these models have been in used (e.g. ChatGPT current version ENDED training in 2021).
- ▼ Cultures — Inter-generational, Multi-cultural — The language use is changing. The resilience, sensitivity to difference words/sentences can be variable.
 - ▷ Incumbent on the
 - ▷ We are learning, and this is related to what questions to ask. This is not simply something in a tube that is squirted out. There are complex causes & consequences, including the dangerous.
- ▼ Project-based perspective — Making sense of the next steps.
 - ▼ Spin out proof of concept projects:
 - ▼ **Demonstrations** with **KM as a project**.
 - ▼ What is the operational modification that enables the rest of the **ISSS** to be joining into the conversation?
 - ▼ Something on the website — “have a conversation with..... James Miller”. — Something that can be offered to the membership, and make it actual and grow something.

- ▷ Conversations of a sort with Miller, Rosen etc is a real possibility now as a target for ISSS (if one can handle the copyright issue).
- ▼ Personalities
 - ▷ Some feelings like there is “cults of personalities” — making a point by referring to a person.
 - ▷ Example: a reviewer of George’s textbook, wanting more historical synthesis. Going back to seminal notions, and the development of their ideas. They decided, No, that is not systems science. We need to be looking at the Synthesis — how the aspects play into being a system.
 - ▷ History and Philosophy of Science is not Science.
 - ▷ What someone has stated is their expression, that is not the internal coherence of [✂ Systems Science](#) . That is a **human touchpoint, the context around the personality**, is part of this!
 - ▷
- ▼ How to Synthesize through the whole? **The overall synthesis**, and not needing to start from scratch. Can’t we integrate their insights?
 - ▷ This is distilled into e.g. axioms, processes
- ▼ Having both the [✂ Systems Science](#) and the History/Philosophy of [✂ Systems Science](#).
 - ▷ Story-telling version of a science — other side — Textbook style literature — other side — hybrid.
 - ▷ Point of reference — as it has been, big men and big ideas. Artificial intelligence? How are we co-creating meaning?
- ▷ To do a couple of annual meetings, to see developments/evolutions among meetings.
- ▷ **Structured Dialog** — *f.* — Not just learning about what LLMs can do for e.g. individuals or organizations, rather more in line with the social Trintab concept.
- ▼ FYI: The 3rd Thursday of May has been designated as Global Accessibility Awareness Day. Here is a link to the GAAD2023 events occurring today: <https://accessibility.day/events/>
 - ▷ ISSS could consider doing something in a future conference.
- ▼ **Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository**
 - ▷ See previous notes in **#18 May 18, 2023**
 - ▼ June 1, 2023
 - ▼ Previously the entire contents of the ISSS archives were handed over.
 - ▷ Coda representation of the data is a proof of concept or draft.
 - ▷ Other archivists may be interested in Coda.
 - ▷ Also we may be able to use **LLM & ISSS** in this utilization. Conversation, voices with the past.
 - ▼ **@Developing uses for ISSS Archives --**
 - ▷ **Ask Education for questions.** We’re going to use this questions on preliminary set of available documents.
 - ▷ What questions do you want to ask of the [✂ Systems Science](#) corpus?
 - ▷ We will do better in planning Educational materials if we can ___ better.
 - ▷ Course work for using ChatGPT for understanding how it works, for using it as a tool rather than a cheat).
 - ▷ How can we come up with Generative work in the spirit of [✂ Systems Science](#) and that helps learn Systems?
 - ▷ We need help using the ISSS Archives
 - ▷ We need help using LLM to survey and leverage the ISSS Archives.

- ▷ We need questions that people want to ask to Knowledge systems about Systems Science and/or different domains.
 - ▷ Also Rob is developing the website for the broader community so that
 - ▣ [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#) can be useful. Also this entails that the ISSS data is updated. More spreadsheets will be incoming.
- ▼ **Primary direction: ISSS Collections**
 - ▼ See [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#) and [ISSS @ SCA](#), with [@Rob Young](#).
 - ▷ Making the [Interface](#) more useful
- ▼ **Secondary directions: Collaborative**
 - ▷ [Other Collaborative, non-archival/SCA efforts in the space](#)
 - ▼ **Development of Interfaces**
 - ▷ Traditional Database with search
 - ▷ Interactive interfaces (Coda)
 - ▼ Large Language Models // Chat interface (in [Coda](#) or otherwise)
 - ▷ Custom corpus
 - ▷ Formal knowledge model ([SUMO](#), other approaches).
 - ▼ **Writing.**
 - ▷ First step — One Pager on the project scope.
 - ▼ Position paper — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.
 - ▷ Would require an actual way forward.
- ▼ Assess the Active [#20 Modular Outcomes](#) and [Modular Outcomes](#) more generally.
 - ▷ [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)
 - ▷ [Strategy](#) — [@Develop Timeline for 2023](#)
 - ▷ [Wiki Templates](#) — [@Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance](#)
 - ▼ [ISSS Resources](#) —
 - ▷ Scope the <https://web3.iss.org/km/> and integrate to Tabular form (with network view or export).
 - ▷ [Systems Science](#) — and connect with [Education](#)
- ▼ [f.](https://web3.iss.org/marzolf-nov2021/index.html) — Systems <https://web3.iss.org/marzolf-nov2021/index.html>
 - ▼ Tom, [@Peter T](#), [@Gary](#) discussing — it is a one-person model, at [a2hosting.com](#), and displayed on the front page of [iss.org](#) — in the “World of Systems” box
 - ▷ They also talked about another modeling software.
 - ▷ Wanting to ensure that [ISSS](#) has the ability to continue this work and model.
 - ▷ Tom started studying, keeping notes, ideas — fragmented across files. As a modeler, in day job, he envisioned a single model that captured everything, that was adaptable, non-redundant, etc. Tom developed a model to do this.
 - ▷ Universe, in a systems-oriented perspective. — To do this, focusing on the simpler starter area of “Systems Commons”
 - ▼ Tom is fine with making a copy available.
 - ▷ There is a lot of information that is in there, and also can be developed further.
 - ▷ Tom can send Peter the current version, and source code.
 - ▷ It is up all the time while working, and captures something every day. What is currently available on the ISSS [Website](#) is more than a year old (there are some updates and additions). What is currently there, is simpler and focuses on non-controversial facts.

- ▷ Schema
- ▼ Classes
 - ▷ People
 - ▷ Documents
 - ▷ Websites
 - ▷ Quotations
- ▼ Written in UML
 - ▷ Some costly modeling tools do use this (IBM Rational). However also it can be exported and used in other programs (cheaper or free tools).
 - ▷ With Bruce M., it was possible to export from modeling software
- ▼ Can it become a ISSS model, not just a single-person model?
 - ▷ There has to be some coordination — e.g. some central person? Github? Other coordinating mechanism.
- ▼ What is the functionality?
 - ▷ Export — puts into standard UML format.
 - ▼ Organizing the whole —
 - ▷ Building on this Synthesis, so that work does not start from scratch.
 - ▷ So that we build together. Problem: Everything becomes custom.
 - ▷ Tom's work has a critical mass
 - ▷ Len, Francois, and other archival projects/attempts.
 - ▷ Topos Institute — Archival developments and challenges, even with the narrower (still broad) question of system.
 - ▷ So coming up with an archiving approach, getting a critical mass.
 - ▷ Concept mapping
 - ▼ Finding information, and continuing to update it, so it becomes a standard source of information.
 - ▷ About People, Organizations, Ideas, etc.
 - ▷ Quotations (organized in some way by subject).
 - ▷ Gradually organizing into e.g. Disciplines, Themes (including [KM as a project](#)), keeping this adaptable. Needs to be kept adaptive.
 - ▷ Simulation (not currently used).
 - ▷ Domain-specific ontologies that can map together (not currently used).
- ▷ Rigor and evidence-based aspect of Tom's work. In the Holism SIG — what Tom brings in to “System”, “Dimension” as evidence to keep things grounded in discussions. This is what the discipline needs in the work; a structured ontology, and a reminder about how we can operate as Systems Science investigators.
- ▷ What we want — all these things like quotations, citations, etc (historical) and the concepts (e.g. George's textbook) and the coherent paths that link them together
- ▼ If we start with a structure of the core principles and concepts, then have linkages with the Entities/Objects in Tom's database. Start with a skeleton of the fundamentals of systems, then use this to branch out.
 - ▷ Someone is researching “Holarchy” — who has researched this, and what other related concepts exist?
 - ▷ Start with the core integration? Starting with a collection of things?
 - ▷ This is the meta-root of the issue..... And there en-lies the challenge.

- ▷ Starting with a core knowledge model, then developing and integrating. Rather than continuing this argument, how/should something be included?
- ▷ Everyone who has written about Systems has foregrounded the topics, with different intentions and outcomes.
- ▷ Views & Viewpoints. Working with patterns, coming from different viewpoints, why they have different preferences.
- ▷ What is the Thing they are looking at? We only know their traces.
- ▷ Outcome oriented — what should/could be known at the end of High School here or there?
- ▼ Multiple rendering/realizations.
 - ▷ Warfield, Structured dialogs. Leveraging tools for common reference.

#20 Modular Outcomes

Area		Status	To discuss	Name
▼ MediaWiki	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
▼ Ways to participate	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meet
▼ Strategy	2	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Research Unified storage solution for ISSS
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding exploration
▼ Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository	3	Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Discussion of the rights and responsibilities of ISSS archive material
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Front end for ISSS archives
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Developing uses for ISSS Archives

- Using a Gantt Chart
- Usage of Chat AI

Subject: [ontolog-forum] John Henry Holland AI - notes

From: ontolog-forum@googlegroups.com [mailto:ontolog-forum@googlegroups.com] On Behalf Of Mike Peters

Sent: 03 June 2023 10:18

To: ontolog-forum

Subject: [ontolog-forum] John Henry Holland AI - notes

The previous post was very long so I started a new thread to make any discussion easier for people.

The AI is called

With Delphi [HYPERLINK "https://www.withdelphi.com/"https://www.withdelphi.com](https://www.withdelphi.com/)

I opened a free account and created an AI called John Henry Holland based on the resources list on his Wikipedia page.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/John_Henry_Holland

and uploaded every PDF of his writings which were then processed by the AI system.

<https://www.withdelphi.com/talk/john-henry-holland>

I then wrote basic questions and got great written answers.

Notes:

I thought this is a fantastic use of AI for enabling self-learning.

It only used the text written by John Henry Holland

It solved my problem of where to start.

I can see the possibility of creating AI for other scientists and mathematicians, uploading their books and papers, and then asking lots of questions. Richard Feynman, Murray Gell Mann etc

Mike Peters

#21 June 29, 2023

Meeting recording

- https://youtu.be/_kRolgipov8

Feedback before the meeting

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General and to-do

- ISSS Archive Interface: https://coda.io/d/ISSS-Archive-Interface_daDW68lgalJ/Home_sunhx#_lu_tj
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.iss.org/primer2/>
 - <https://www.iss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>
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Agenda & Ongoing Notes

- Purpose of Education
- **Primary direction: ISSS Collections**
 - See ISSS @ SCA, with @Rob Young.
 - Making the [Interface](#) more useful
- **Secondary directions: Collaborative**
 - Other Collaborative, non-archival/SCA efforts in the space
 - Development of Interfaces
 - Traditional Database with search
 - Interactive interfaces (Coda)
 - Writing.
 - One Pager on the project scope.
 - Position paper — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.
- Assess the Modular Outcomes.
 - Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository
 - Strategy — @Develop Timeline for 2023
 - Wiki Templates — @Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
 - ISSS Resources — Scope the <https://web3.iss.org/km/> and integrate to Tabular form (with network view or export).
 - Education

#21 Modular Outcomes

Area		Status	To discuss	Name
▼ MediaWiki	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
▼ Ways to participate	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meet
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		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding exploration
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		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Front end for ISSS archives
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Developing uses for ISSS Archives

- Using a Gantt Chart
- Usage of Chat AI

#22 July 13, 2023

Meeting recording

- https://youtu.be/jJL_McmvBCA

Feedback before the meeting

- .

General and to-do

- ISSS Archive Interface: https://coda.io/d/ISSS-Archive-Interface_daDW68lgaJ/Home_sunhx#_lu_tj
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.iss.org/primer2/>
 - <https://www.iss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>

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Agenda & Ongoing Notes

- Purpose of 🗄️ KM as a project & View towards 🎓 Education
- **Primary direction: ISSS Collections**
 - See 🗄️ Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository and 🗄️ ISSS @ SCA, with @Rob Young.
 - Making the Interface more useful
- **Secondary directions: Collaborative**
 - Other Collaborative, non-archival/SCA efforts in the space
 - Development of Interfaces
 - Traditional Database with search
 - Interactive interfaces (Coda)
 - Writing.
 - One Pager on the project scope.
 - Position paper — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.
- From Chris
 - I cannot make today's call but I wanted to give some feedback. I have two threads (but they are linked):
 - collaboration - especially group and
 - accessing the databases in a research / large language model way.
 - I also spoke to Peter Tuddenham as part of my inquiry about both. I have agreed to focus on finding things related / relevant to [Human Systems Inquiry](#) (Related to but not limited to the SIG).

- I am thinking of the Knowledge engineering project as a place that provides tools and data, but maybe the tools can be appropriate for data outside the ISSS database.
 - Yes, this makes sense for KE as developing enabling systems, and tools that apply to [ISSS Resources](#) and elsewhere.
- If we make it easy for people to learn from each other on clever ways to sift through systems research and also helped them share knowledge and work together generally, that could be self sustaining?
- Are there off the shelf apps that could help with simple collaboration?
 - In business world, people have made many attempts at building collaboration suites.
 - Substack chat, Discord, Discourse, other platforms for communication, Notion
 - It really depends on how people are to collaborate and why.
 - Repository
 - Calendar
 - Video meetings
 - Documents
 - The motivations of people in collaborations
 - Depends centrally on wanting to have community + wanting to accomplish something personal/group.
- How can we help curate walled gardens and prompt engineering that make llm's more accessible.
 - Part of this is about whether we can train/use LLM on paywalled content (walled gardens).
 - Another aspect is about enabling people to generate
- Even a marketplace of sharing tips and tricks, examples, etc?
 - Unique advantage / selling point for people to join their community. Standards, mentoring.
 - Systems science..... Having conceptual integration and synthesis work ABOUT [Systems Science](#) is a narrow adoption work — Tools, methods, etc. — Then the broader adoption can occur.
- Who are we looking to collaborate with?
 - Collaboration ON [Systems Science](#) with [Systems Science](#)
 - Collaboration explicitly WITH [Systems Science](#) about other domains
 - Collaboration that does not explicitly use/consider [Systems Science](#)
 - What about inter/transdisciplinary studies? E.g. someone who recognizes SS when they see it, sees their work and can connect it to the official literature (e.g. Cybernetics, Big History, [Gregg Henriques](#)) — When we see this, we can make contact with the people. You are doing great work and it is systems oriented.
 - Content → Semantic embedding and/or usage of Systems Ontology → Attention Ranking → Contact → Systems Adjacency Scores.
 - Bibliography → What are they reading or referencing?
 - Tom's System Types. And database with people, years, organizations, quotations. The version on the webpage now is ~1 year old, then a new version may be arising. Incremental feedback through taking in information. Getting to the ideas. Take in someone ideas, and connect them. Multiple definitions.
- [Systems Science](#)
 - Systemsness, rather than definition of System — allows us to specify what we mean by this. Pinning down what the characteristics are.
 - George's teachings, ranging from the non-science or in science undergraduates, to those in the computer science majors specifically (was more technical work to do, and application to computer systems).
- Assess the [Modular Outcomes](#).

- Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository
- Strategy — @Develop Timeline for 2023
- Wiki Templates — @Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
- ISSS Resources — Scope the <https://web3.iss.org/km/> and integrate to Tabular form (with network view or export).
- Education

#21 Modular Outcomes 2

Area		Status	To discuss	Name
▼ MediaWiki	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
▼ Ways to participate	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meet
▼ Strategy	2	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Research Unified storage solution for ISSS
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding exploration
▼ Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository	3	Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Discussion of the rights and responsibilities of ISSS archive material
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Front end for ISSS archives
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Developing uses for ISSS Archives

- Using a Gantt Chart
- Usage of Chat AI

#23 July 27, 2023

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/o0banZ2FWkM>

Feedback before the meeting

- .

General and to-do

- ISSS Archive Interface: https://coda.io/d/ISSS-Archive-Interface_daDW68lgaJ/Home_sunhx#_lu_tj
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.iss.org/primer2/>
 - <https://www.iss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>
-

Agenda & Ongoing Notes

- Purpose of 🗄️ KM as a project & View towards 🎓 Education
- ▼ **Primary direction: ISSS Collections**
 - ▷ See 🗄️ Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository and 🗄️ ISSS @ SCA, with @Rob Young.
 - ▷ Making the Interface more useful
- ▼ **Secondary directions: Collaborative**
 - ▷ Other Collaborative, non-archival/SCA efforts in the space
 - ▼ **Development of Interfaces**
 - ▷ Traditional Database with search
 - ▷ Interactive interfaces (Coda)
 - ▼ **Writing.**
 - ▷ One Pager on the project scope.
 - ▷ Position paper — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.
- ▼ From Chris 🗄️ #22 July 13, 2023
 - ▼ I cannot make today's call but I wanted to give some feedback. I have two threads (but they are linked):
 - ▷ collaboration - especially group and
 - ▷ accessing the databases in a research / large language model way.
 - ▷ I also spoke to Peter Tuddenham as part of my inquiry about both. I have agreed to focus on finding things related / relevant to [Human Systems Inquiry](#) (Related to but not limited to the SIG).

- ▼ I am thinking of the Knowledge engineering project as a place that provides tools and data, but maybe the tools can be appropriate for data outside the ISSS database.
 - ▷ Yes, this makes sense for KE as developing enabling systems, and tools that apply to [ISSS Resources](#) and elsewhere.
 - ▷ If we make it easy for people to learn from each other on clever ways to sift through systems research and also helped them share knowledge and work together generally, that could be self sustaining?
- ▼ Are there off the shelf apps that could help with simple collaboration?
 - ▷ In business world, people have made many attempts at building collaboration suites.
 - ▷ Substack chat, Discord, Discourse, other platforms for communication, Notion
 - ▼ It really depends on how people are to collaborate and why.
 - ▷ Repository
 - ▷ Calendar
 - ▷ Video meetings
 - ▷ Documents
 - ▼ The motivations of people in collaborations
 - ▷ Depends centrally on wanting to have community + wanting to accomplish something personal/group.
- ▼ How can we help curate walled gardens and prompt engineering that make llm's more accessible.
 - ▷ Part of this is about whether we can train/use LLM on paywalled content (walled gardens).
 - ▷ Another aspect is about enabling people to generate
- ▼ Even a marketplace of sharing tips and tricks, examples, etc?
 - ▷ Unique advantage / selling point for people to join their community. Standards, mentoring.
 - ▷ Systems science..... Having conceptual integration and synthesis work ABOUT [Systems Science](#) is a narrow adoption work — Tools, methods, etc. — Then the broader adoption can occur.
- ▼ Who are we looking to collaborate with?
 - ▷ Collaboration ON [Systems Science](#) with [Systems Science](#)
 - ▷ Collaboration explicitly WITH [Systems Science](#) about other domains
 - ▼ Collaboration that does not explicitly use/consider [Systems Science](#)
 - ▼ What about inter/transdisciplinary studies? E.g. someone who recognizes SS when they see it, sees their work and can connect it to the official literature (e.g. Cybernetics, Big History, [Gregg Henriques](#)) — When we see this, we can make contact with the people. You are doing great work and it is systems oriented.
 - ▷ Content → Semantic embedding and/or usage of Systems Ontology → Attention Ranking → Contact → Systems Adjacency Scores.
 - ▷ Bibliography → What are they reading or referencing?
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- ▼ [Systems Science](#)
 - ▷ Systemsness, rather than definition of System — allows us to specify what we mean by this. Pinning down what the characteristics are.
 - ▷ George's teachings, ranging from the non-science or in science undergraduates, to those in the computer science majors specifically (was more technical work to do, and application to computer systems).
- ▼ From Chris for [#23 July 27, 2023](#)

- ▷ I saw last week's recording and it was a very interesting session. Thanks. Thinking about collaboration and relevance felt like a good grounding. I liked the point about people making collaboration work, not technology, but some basic tools are necessary.
- ▼ I have started prepping to try some llm and non-llm explorations of the database. I found a few collections of tools and some discussions by searching Coda for the phrase LLM (some are below). Are there any other places I should be visiting to get grounded on getting started please?
 - ▷ In Coda: [LLM & ISSS](#), [ISSS-LLM-GPT](#) and also play around with Coda AI!
 - ▷ The most updated list for LLM tools I have is in the [Supplemental Information of the GRT paper](#)
- ▼ I was not sure if there is good voice to text capability in the Coda list, but if not, I would appreciate any tips you might have. E.g., Otter.ai or something else?
 - ▷ We don't have speech to text going in Coda right now.
 - ▷ [LemuR](#), [otter.ai](#), [ActInf Journal Utilities use WhisperAI](#) — depends how much programming you want to do.
 - ▷ For standard use, word processor, google docs, they probably work fine.

▼ Naming

- ▷ "Sorting Things Out — Classification and its consequences" Geoffrey C. Bowker and Susan Leigh Star
- ▷ Naming issue. Always a naming problem, people have multiple names & this reflects worldview. Plurality of world views.
- ▷ Capture of knowledge. Data entry. Time and energy
- ▷ Monitoring, Moderating, quality control, information supply chain.

▼ Interoperability, credible exit.

- ▷ [Text encoding initiative](#)

▼ Planning for transfer of Tom's database.

- ▼ RSAD source code (should be stored)
 - ▷ HTML export for web
 - ▷ UML export
- ▷ Updated copy ([November 2021 version](#)).
- ▷ IBM software, Rational System Architect & Design (RSAD).

• [Sending update about next 2 weeks & change calendar events to Jitsi.](#)

• [Pathways to Open Source Ecosystems](#)

- Assess the [Modular Outcomes](#).
 - [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)

- Strategy — @Develop Timeline for 2023
- Wiki Templates — @Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
- ISSS Resources — Scope the <https://web3.iss.org/km/> and integrate to Tabular form (with network view or export).
- Education

#21 Modular Outcomes 3

Area		Status	To discuss	Name
▼ MediaWiki	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
▼ Ways to participate	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meet
▼ Strategy	2	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Research Unified storage solution for ISSS
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding exploration
▼ Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository	3	Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Discussion of the rights and responsibilities of ISSS archive material
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Front end for ISSS archives
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Developing uses for ISSS Archives

- Using a Gantt Chart
- Usage of Chat AI

#24 August 24, 2023

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/8kiPZjLaQmM>

Feedback before the meeting

- .

General and to-do

- ISSS Archive Interface: https://coda.io/d/ISSS-Archive-Interface_daDW68lgaJ/Home_sunhx#_lu_tj
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.iss.org/primer2/>
 - <https://www.iss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>
- .
- .

Agenda & Ongoing Notes

- Purpose of 📖 KM as a project & View towards 🎓 Education
- ▼ **Primary direction: ISSS Collections**
 - ▷ See 📖 Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository and 🌐 ISSS @ SCA, with @Rob Young.
 - ▷ Making the Interface more useful
- ▼ **Secondary directions: Collaborative**
 - ▷ Other Collaborative, non-archival/SCA efforts in the space
 - ▼ **Development of Interfaces**
 - ▷ Traditional Database with search
 - ▷ Interactive interfaces (Coda)
 - ▼ **Writing.**
 - ▷ One Pager on the project scope.
 - ▷ Position paper — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.
- ▼ From Chris 📖 #22 July 13, 2023
 - ▼ I cannot make today's call but I wanted to give some feedback. I have two threads (but they are linked):
 - ▷ collaboration - especially group and
 - ▷ accessing the databases in a research / large language model way.
 - ▷ I also spoke to Peter Tuddenham as part of my inquiry about both. I have agreed to focus on finding things related / relevant to [Human Systems Inquiry](#) (Related to but not limited to the SIG).

- ▼ I am thinking of the Knowledge engineering project as a place that provides tools and data, but maybe the tools can be appropriate for data outside the ISSS database.
 - ▷ Yes, this makes sense for KE as developing enabling systems, and tools that apply to [ISSS Resources](#) and elsewhere.
 - ▷ If we make it easy for people to learn from each other on clever ways to sift through systems research and also helped them share knowledge and work together generally, that could be self sustaining?
- ▼ Are there off the shelf apps that could help with simple collaboration?
 - ▷ In business world, people have made many attempts at building collaboration suites.
 - ▷ Substack chat, Discord, Discourse, other platforms for communication, Notion
 - ▼ It really depends on how people are to collaborate and why.
 - ▷ Repository
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 - ▼ The motivations of people in collaborations
 - ▷ Depends centrally on wanting to have community + wanting to accomplish something personal/group.
- ▼ How can we help curate walled gardens and prompt engineering that make llm's more accessible.
 - ▷ Part of this is about whether we can train/use LLM on paywalled content (walled gardens).
 - ▷ Another aspect is about enabling people to generate
- ▼ Even a marketplace of sharing tips and tricks, examples, etc?
 - ▷ Unique advantage / selling point for people to join their community. Standards, mentoring.
 - ▷ Systems science..... Having conceptual integration and synthesis work ABOUT [Systems Science](#) is a narrow adoption work — Tools, methods, etc. — Then the broader adoption can occur.
- ▼ Who are we looking to collaborate with?
 - ▷ Collaboration ON [Systems Science](#) with [Systems Science](#)
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 - ▼ What about inter/transdisciplinary studies? E.g. someone who recognizes SS when they see it, sees their work and can connect it to the official literature (e.g. Cybernetics, Big History, [Gregg Henriques](#)) — When we see this, we can make contact with the people. You are doing great work and it is systems oriented.
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- ▼ [Systems Science](#)
 - ▷ Systemsness, rather than definition of System — allows us to specify what we mean by this. Pinning down what the characteristics are.
 - ▷ George's teachings, ranging from the non-science or in science undergraduates, to those in the computer science majors specifically (was more technical work to do, and application to computer systems).
- ▼ From Chris for [#24 August 24, 2023](#)

- ▷ I saw last week's recording and it was a very interesting session. Thanks. Thinking about collaboration and relevance felt like a good grounding. I liked the point about people making collaboration work, not technology, but some basic tools are necessary.
- ▼ I have started prepping to try some llm and non-llm explorations of the database. I found a few collections of tools and some discussions by searching Coda for the phrase LLM (some are below). Are there any other places I should be visiting to get grounded on getting started please?
 - ▷ In Coda: [LLM & ISSS](#), [ISSS-LLM-GPT](#) and also play around with Coda AI!
 - ▷ The most updated list for LLM tools I have is in the [Supplemental Information of the GRT paper](#)
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 - ▷ We don't have speech to text going in Coda right now.
 - ▷ [LemuR](#), [otter.ai](#), [ActInf Journal Utilities use WhisperAI](#) — depends how much programming you want to do.
 - ▷ For standard use, word processor, google docs, they probably work fine.
- ▼ Naming
 - ▷ "Sorting Things Out — Classification and its consequences" Geoffrey C. Bowker and Susan Leigh Star
 - ▷ Naming issue. Always a naming problem, people have multiple names & this reflects worldview. Plurality of world views.
- ▷ Capture of knowledge. Data entry. Time and energy
- ▷ Monitoring, Moderating, quality control, information supply chain.
- ▼ Interoperability, credible exit.
 - ▷ [Text encoding initiative](#)
- ▼ Planning for transfer of Tom's database.
 - ▼ RSAD source code (should be stored)
 - ▷ HTML export for web
 - ▼ UML export
 - ▷ August 24, 2023 — Tom has done this export. It is data-only, not with diagrams (they can be generated from the data — all the relational content is captured, however the Perspectives/View fine-tuning is not part of the export).
 - ▷ The Views show subsets of data with visual accessibility. This is a vital part, and part of keeping it adaptable / without redundancy. The relationality is defined once.
 - ▼ Can we store specifications for the view, using the system's base format itself?
 - ▷ Perhaps the Names of the view could be captured.
 - ▷ Consider the view about a Person. Information about person, link to page/Wikipedia, information on their bibliography, Quotations, and so on.
- ▼ Updated copy ([November 2021 version](#)).
 - ▷ This is stored in cloud format.
 - ▼ Directories
 - ▼ Views
 - ▷ One file for each view.
 - ▼ HTML packages directory
 - ▷ This is from UML in the tool, converted to HTML
 - ▷ If you have it all together, it is accessible.

- ▷ IBM software, Rational System Architect & Design (RSAD).
- [Pathways to Open Source Ecosystems](#)
- [Education ~ sysXML](#)
 - Shingai built a Github organization https://github.com/system-language_
 - What else is needed for onboarding?
 - We can move the contents on the chapters/etc into the Github.
 - Movement within and beyond 🌐 [ISSS](#) participation — Peter encourages this.
 - How do people engage in the book (and topics) in order to work with the code?
 - At this stage, [BlockScience](#) is curious. They are doing model-based systems design, categorical cybernetics in the meta-governance space <https://metagov.org/>
 - sysXML office hours, with Shingai as host/co-host. George is standing by!
- Meetings and broader participation
 - Think about even these conversations & related aspects of e.g. facilitation and convening?
 - Using Github keeps things open and can have e.g. Software, Websites.
 - George; sysXML and beyond does have to open up. It is not a condition of open source participation to be ISSS member of course.
 - With Michelle and Gary — Setting up the committee pages along the lines of SIG.
 -
- Chris S
 - I had somehow found myself on Jitsi, but I cannot find a record of my comments.
 - Basically I had a go with querying the [ISSS archives](#) to identify material related to human systems enquiry. This failed because I did not see a way to search the text. If the PDF's have not been scanned that greatly limits what is possible. **Correct, the full PDF are not available through that interface.**
 - What has been done, from Rob.
 - Peter T et al. have been digitizing the material (documents, reports). However this has not been OCR'ed and had the text curated.
 - The Indexing work of 📖 [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#) is at the Bibliographic level, not a full scan. We have the full 🌐 [ISSS](#) surveying at the Bibliographic level as of August 2023.
 - So, the question is how to integrate the full texts, with the bibliographic records, given e.g. different access/licencing to text
 - Human Systems Inquiry SIG — short of reading all, what can we do? How do we determine which even records are relevant?
 - Getting the full texts into the 📖 [LLM & ISSS](#) and 📖 [LLM tools](#) → Increasing access to 🦋 [Systems Science](#) work
 - Some sites have put in the abstracts and abstractions.
 - This also invokes e.g. Ontology discussions.
 - Moving towards open science/education/research with the materials that can.
 - Creating an Author Ontology. —
 - Janet & Michael Singer —
 - ISSS Archives are a research resource. Then capture anything relating to HSI SIG 🌐 [ISSS](#) and supply that to a meta-index that captures all of this tagging, upper ontology, etc. — Main idea is to put in the work to make the archive accessible so that SIG's and researchers can do the work (we're making the enabling system for these usages).

- I thought the only way to get some gains was to profile HIS generally on the web with author names and titles, then use that trained search against ISSS index info.
- Requesting that people can submit information for publication through
- Language models
 - <https://www.cursor.sh/>
 - On research generally, I had a conversation with a friend (David Gurteen) about the idea of collaborative research using chat GPT. there seems to be a huge potential to create a research level playing field through translation and context adjusting capabilities. this could be a really interesting focus
- Assess the [📦 Modular Outcomes](#).
 - [📁 Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)
 - [📄 Strategy — @Develop Timeline for 2023](#)
 - [📖 Wiki Templates — @Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance](#)
 - [🏠 ISSS Resources](#) — Scope the <https://web3.iss.org/km/> and integrate to Tabular form (with network view or export).
 - [🔗 Systems Science](#) — and connect with [🎓 Education](#)

#21 Modular Outcomes 4

Area		Status	To discuss	Name
▼ 📖 MediaWiki	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
▼ 📄 Ways to participate	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meet
▼ 📄 Strategy	2	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Research Unified storage solution for ISSS
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding exploration
▼ 📁 Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository	3	Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Discussion of the rights and responsibilities of ISSS archive material
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Front end for ISSS archives
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Developing uses for ISSS Archives

- Using a Gantt Chart
- Usage of [🗨️ Chat AI](#)

#25 September 21, 2023

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/HwT2jho0RcU>

Feedback before the meeting

- .

General and to-do

- ISSS [Archive Interface](#)
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.iss.org/primer2/>
 - <https://www.iss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>
- .
- .

Agenda & Ongoing Notes

- Purpose of Education
- ▼ **Primary direction: ISSS Collections**
 - ▷ See [ISSS @ SCA](#), with [@Rob Young](#).
 - ▷ Making the [Interface](#) more useful
- ▼ **Secondary directions: Collaborative**
 - ▷ [Other Collaborative, non-archival/SCA efforts in the space](#)
 - ▼ [Development of Interfaces](#)
 - ▷ Traditional Database with search
 - ▷ Interactive interfaces (Coda)
 - ▼ [Writing.](#)
 - ▷ One Pager on the project scope.
 - ▷ Position paper — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.
- ▼ [From Chris & Discussion](#)
 - ▷ [Language Models](#)
- ▼ [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)
 - ▷ Rob discussing the [Systems Science](#).
 - ▷ People are discussing the Conferences as being some key texts to pursue. Peter has the 2017 conference
- ▷ [Thomas Marzolf's Model](#)
- ▼ Different discussion topics:

▼ Naming

- ▷ “Sorting Things Out — Classification and its consequences” Geoffrey C. Bowker and Susan Leigh Star
- ▷ Naming issue. Always a naming problem, people have multiple names & this reflects worldview. Plurality of world views.

▼ Interacting systems

- ▷ Information being captured/transmitted in terms of knowledge structures (from Active Inference representing the path of least action from some cognitive space / generative model).

▷ Capture of knowledge. Data entry. Time and energy

▷ Monitoring, Moderating, quality control, information supply chain.

▷ Interoperability, credible exit.

▷ [Text encoding initiative](#)

◦ [Pathways to Open Source Ecosystems](#)

◦ [Education ~ sysXML](#)

- Shingai built a Github organization https://github.com/system-language_
- What else is needed for onboarding?
- We can move the contents on the chapters/etc into the Github.
- Movement within and beyond ISSS participation — Peter encourages this.
- How do people engage in the book (and topics) in order to work with the code?
- At this stage, [BlockScience](#) is curious. They are doing model-based systems design, categorical cybernetics in the meta-governance space <https://metagov.org/>
- sysXML office hours, with Shingai as host/co-host. George is standing by!

◦ Meetings and broader participation

- Think about even these conversations & related aspects of e.g. facilitation and convening?
- Using Github keeps things open and can have e.g. Software, Websites.
- George; sysXML and beyond does have to open up. It is not a condition of open source participation to be ISSS member of course.
- With Michelle and Gary — Setting up the committee pages along the lines of SIG.

• Assess the [Modular Outcomes](#).

- [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)
- [Strategy — @Develop Timeline for 2023](#)
- [Wiki Templates — @Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance](#)
- [ISSS Resources](#) — Scope the <https://web3.iss.org/km/> and integrate to Tabular form (with network view or export).
- [Education](#)

#21 Modular Outcomes 5

Area	Status	To discuss	Name
▼ MediaWiki 1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
▼ Ways to participate 1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meet

▼ Strategy	2	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Research Unified storage solution for ISSS
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding exploration
▼ Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository	3	Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Discussion of the rights and responsibilities of ISSS archive material
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Front end for ISSS archives
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Developing uses for ISSS Archives

- Using a Gantt Chart
- Usage of Chat AI

#26 October 5, 2023

Meeting recording

- https://youtu.be/vcRb_nOHWOY
- Patterns in 📖 KM as a project

Feedback before the meeting

- .

General and to-do

- ISSS [Archive Interface](#)
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.iss.org/primer2/>
 - <https://www.iss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>
-

Agenda & Ongoing Notes

- Purpose of 📖 KM as a project & View towards 🎓 Education
- ▼ **Primary direction: ISSS Collections**
 - ▷ See 📖 [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#) and 🌐 [ISSS @ SCA](#), with [@Rob Young](#).
 - ▷ Making the [Interface](#) more useful
- ▼ **Secondary directions: Collaborative**
 - ▷ [Other Collaborative, non-archival/SCA efforts in the space](#)
 - ▼ [Development of Interfaces](#)
 - ▷ Traditional Database with search
 - ▷ Interactive interfaces (Coda)
 - ▼ [Writing.](#)
 - ▷ One Pager on the project scope.
 - ▷ Position paper — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.
- ▼ 🗣️ [From Chris & Discussion](#)
 - ▷ 🗣️ [Language Models](#)
- ▼ 📖 [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)
 - ▷ Rob discussing the 📖 [Ontology](#) for 🗣️ [Systems Science](#).
 - ▷ People are discussing the [Conferences](#) as being some key texts to pursue. Peter has the 2017 conference
- ▷ 🗣️ [Thomas Marzolf's Model](#)

▷ [🏠 FedWiki](#)

▼ Different discussion topics:

▼ Naming

- ▷ “Sorting Things Out — Classification and its consequences” Geoffrey C. Bowker and Susan Leigh Star
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- ▷ [Text encoding initiative](#)
 - [Pathways to Open Source Ecosystems](#)
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 - With Michelle and Gary — Setting up the committee pages along the lines of SIG.
- Assess the [📄 Modular Outcomes](#).
 - [📁 Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)
 - [📄 Strategy](#) — [@Develop Timeline for 2023](#)
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 - [🦋 Systems Science](#) — and connect with [🎓 Education](#)

#21 Modular Outcomes 6

Area	Status	To discuss	Name
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▼ MediaWiki	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
▼ Ways to participate	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meet
▼ Strategy	2	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Research Unified storage solution for ISSS
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding exploration
▼ Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository	3	Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Discussion of the rights and responsibilities of ISSS archive material
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Front end for ISSS archives
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Developing uses for ISSS Archives

- Using a Gantt Chart
- Usage of Chat AI

#27 October 19, 2023

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/EIA07MOoTQ>
- Patterns in KM as a project

Feedback before the meeting

- .

General and to-do

- ISSS [Archive Interface](#)
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.iss.org/primer2/>
 - <https://www.iss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>
-

Agenda & Ongoing Notes

- Purpose of Education
- ▼ **Primary direction: ISSS Collections**
 - ▷ See [ISSS @ SCA](#), with [@Rob Young](#).
 - ▷ Making the [Interface](#) more useful
- ▼ **Secondary directions: Collaborative**
 - ▷ [Other Collaborative, non-archival/SCA efforts in the space](#)
 - ▼ [Development of Interfaces](#)
 - ▷ Traditional Database with search
 - ▷ Interactive interfaces (Coda)
 - ▼ [Writing.](#)
 - ▷ One Pager on the project scope.
 - ▷ Position paper — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.
- ▼ [From Chris & Discussion](#)
 - ▷ [Language Models](#)
- ▼ [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)
 - ▷ Rob discussing the [Systems Science](#).
 - ▷ People are discussing the [Conferences](#) as being some key texts to pursue. Peter has the 2017 conference
- ▷ [Thomas Marzolf's Model](#)

▷ [🏠 FedWiki](#)

▼ Different discussion topics:

▼ Naming

- ▷ “Sorting Things Out — Classification and its consequences” Geoffrey C. Bowker and Susan Leigh Star
- ▷ Naming issue. Always a naming problem, people have multiple names & this reflects worldview. Plurality of world views.

▼ Interacting systems

- ▷ Information being captured/transmitted in terms of knowledge structures (from Active Inference representing the path of least action from some cognitive space / generative model).

▷ Capture of knowledge. Data entry. Time and energy

▷ Monitoring, Moderating, quality control, information supply chain.

▷ Interoperability, credible exit.

▷ [Text encoding initiative](#)

◦ [Pathways to Open Source Ecosystems](#)

◦ [Education ~ sysXML](#)

- Shingai built a Github organization https://github.com/system-language_
- What else is needed for onboarding?
- We can move the contents on the chapters/etc into the Github.
- Movement within and beyond [ISSS](#) participation — Peter encourages this.
- How do people engage in the book (and topics) in order to work with the code?
- At this stage, [BlockScience](#) is curious. They are doing model-based systems design, categorical cybernetics in the meta-governance space <https://metagov.org/>
- sysXML office hours, with Shingai as host/co-host. George is standing by!

◦ Meetings and broader participation

- Think about even these conversations & related aspects of e.g. facilitation and convening?
- Using Github keeps things open and can have e.g. Software, Websites.
- George; sysXML and beyond does have to open up. It is not a condition of open source participation to be ISSS member of course.
- With Michelle and Gary — Setting up the committee pages along the lines of SIG.

• Assess the [📄 Modular Outcomes](#).

- [📁 Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)
- [📄 Strategy — @Develop Timeline for 2023](#)
- [📄 Wiki Templates — @Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance](#)
- [🏠 ISSS Resources](#) — Scope the <https://web3.iss.org/km/> and integrate to Tabular form (with network view or export).
- [🦋 Systems Science](#) — and connect with [🎓 Education](#)

#21 Modular Outcomes 7

Area	Status	To discuss	Name
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▼ MediaWiki	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
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		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Front end for ISSS archives
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Developing uses for ISSS Archives

- Using a Gantt Chart
- Usage of Chat AI

#28 November 2, 2023

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/AuDWjzHdBeo>

Feedback before the meeting

- .

General and to-do

- ISSS [Archive Interface](#)
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.isss.org/primer2/>
 - <https://www.isss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>
-
-
-

Agenda & Ongoing Notes

- Purpose of 📖 **KM as a project & View towards 🎓 Education**
- 11/2/2023
 - From George — [The Essential David Bohm](#) connect to Active Inference in Chapter 2.
 - Peter made a 2 minute video introduction to 🦋 [Systems Science](#) with 🗣️ [Language Models](#).
 - Efficient search of documents we have
 - (A future time) — Ontology.
 - P3IF
 - <https://zenodo.org/records/10034512> The Properties, Processes, and Perspectives Inter-Framework (P3IF): Multiplexing interdisciplinary requirements frameworks to manage information risk and foster cognitive security

- At ISSS [Education](#)
 - Perspectives:
 - Learner, Researcher....
 - Multiple viewpoints, Orthogonal consideration
 - Processes (Verbs):
 - Ingressing of new data, Searching for data, Analysis (Comparison).
 - Properties (Adjective):
 - e.g. Confidentiality, Integrity, Accessibility.
- Value-sensitive design → Going about finding requirements through values.
 - Which perspectives are considered, related to expectations/norms for current or future situations. That is implemented through Processes, which relate/reflect to Properties.
 - Integrated framework coming from amalgamation/visualization of multiple frameworks.
 - Evolutions and Developments of frameworks. What contributes to what?
-
- ▼ **Primary direction: ISSS Collections**
 - ▷ See [ISSS @ SCA](#), with [@Rob Young](#).
 - ▷ Making the [Interface](#) more useful
- ▼ **Secondary directions: Collaborative**
 - ▷ [Other Collaborative, non-archival/SCA efforts in the space](#)
 - ▼ [Development of Interfaces](#)
 - ▷ Traditional Database with search
 - ▷ Interactive interfaces (Coda)
 - ▼ [Writing.](#)
 - ▷ One Pager on the project scope.
 - ▷ Position paper — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.
 - ▷ [Language Models](#)
- ▼ [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)
 - ▷ Rob discussing the [Systems Science](#).
 - ▷ People are discussing the Conferences as being some key texts to pursue. Peter has the 2017 conference
- ▷ [Thomas Marzolf's Model](#)
- ▷ [FedWiki](#)
- ▼ Different discussion topics:
 - ▼ Naming
 - ▷ “Sorting Things Out — Classification and its consequences” Geoffrey C. Bowker and Susan Leigh Star
 - ▷ Naming issue. Always a naming problem, people have multiple names & this reflects worldview. Plurality of world views.
 - ▼ Interacting systems
 - ▷ Information being captured/transmitted in terms of knowledge structures (from Active Inference representing the path of least action from some cognitive space / generative model).
 - ▷ Capture of knowledge. Data entry. Time and energy

- ▷ Monitoring, Moderating, quality control, information supply chain.
 - ▷ Interoperability, credible exit.
 - ▷ Text encoding initiative
 - Pathways to Open Source Ecosystems
 - Education ~ sysXML
 - Shingai built a Github organization https://github.com/system-language_
 - What else is needed for onboarding?
 - We can move the contents on the chapters/etc into the Github.
 - Movement within and beyond 🌐 ISSS participation — Peter encourages this.
 - How do people engage in the book (and topics) in order to work with the code?
 - At this stage, [BlockScience](#) is curious. They are doing model-based systems design, categorical cybernetics in the meta-governance space <https://metagov.org/>
 - sysXML office hours, with Shingai as host/co-host. George is standing by!
 - Meetings and broader participation
 - Think about even these conversations & related aspects of e.g. facilitation and convening?
 - Using Github keeps things open and can have e.g. Software, Websites.
 - George; sysXML and beyond does have to open up. It is not a condition of open source participation to be ISSS member of course.
 - With Michelle and Gary — Setting up the committee pages along the lines of SIG.
- Assess the 🧩 Modular Outcomes.
 - 🏢 Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository
 - 📄 Strategy — @Develop Timeline for 2023
 - 📖 Wiki Templates — @Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
 - 🌐 ISSS Resources — Scope the <https://web3.iss.org/km/> and integrate to Tabular form (with network view or export).
 - 🦋 Systems Science — and connect with 🎓 Education

#21 Modular Outcomes 8

Area		Status	To discuss	Name
▼ 📖 MediaWiki	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
▼ 🗨️ Ways to participate	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meet
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▼ 🏢 Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository	3	Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Discussion of the rights and responsibilities of ISSS archive material
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Front end for ISSS archives
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Developing uses for ISSS Archives

- Using a Gantt Chart
- Usage of 🗨️ Chat AI

#29 November 16, 2023

Meeting recording

- https://youtu.be/F17KLpkWu_0

Feedback before the meeting

- .

General and to-do

- [ISSS Archive Interface](#)
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.isss.org/primer2/>
 - <https://www.isss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>
- 📖 [The Ideal of Coherence Executive Report - Excerpt 2023](#)

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Agenda & Ongoing Notes

- Purpose of 📖 [KM as a project & View towards 🎓 Education](#)
- 11/2/2023
-
- ▼ **Primary direction: ISSS Collections**
 - ▷ See 📖 [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#) and 📖 [ISSS @ SCA](#), with [@Rob Young](#).
 - ▷ Making the [Interface](#) more useful
- ▼ **Secondary directions: Collaborative**
 - ▷ [Other Collaborative, non-archival/SCA efforts in the space](#)
 - ▼ [Development of Interfaces](#)
 - ▷ Traditional Database with search
 - ▷ Interactive interfaces (Coda)
 - ▼ [Writing.](#)
 - ▷ One Pager on the project scope.
 - ▷ Position paper — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.
 - ▷ 📖 [Language Models](#)

▼ Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository

- ▷ Rob discussing the Systems Science.
- ▷ People are discussing the Conferences as being some key texts to pursue. Peter has the 2017 conference

▷ Thomas Marzolf's Model

▷ FedWiki

▼ Different discussion topics:

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- ▷ "Sorting Things Out — Classification and its consequences" Geoffrey C. Bowker and Susan Leigh Star
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▼ Interacting systems

- ▷ Information being captured/transmitted in terms of knowledge structures (from Active Inference representing the path of least action from some cognitive space / generative model).
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- Meetings and broader participation
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 - George; sysXML and beyond does have to open up. It is not a condition of open source participation to be ISSS member of course.
 - With Michelle and Gary — Setting up the committee pages along the lines of SIG.

• Assess the Modular Outcomes.

- Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository
- Strategy — @Develop Timeline for 2023
- Wiki Templates — @Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
- ISSS Resources — Scope the <https://web3.iss.org/km/> and integrate to Tabular form (with network view or export).
- Education

#21 Modular Outcomes 9

Area	Status	To discuss	Name	
▼ MediaWiki	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
▼ Ways to participate	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meet
▼ Strategy	2	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Research Unified storage solution for ISSS
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Funding exploration
▼ Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository	3	Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Discussion of the rights and responsibilities of ISSS archive material
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Front end for ISSS archives
		Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	Developing uses for ISSS Archives

- Using a Gantt Chart
- Usage of Chat AI

#30 November 30, 2023

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/vX1CEvukhp0>

Feedback before the meeting

- George's travels
 - N2 Noosphere at 100 — George long studying and thinking about this, the info-social system as organized to be the brain (classical conception) of the planet, Spaceship Earth.
 - [N2 Conference – The Noosphere at 100: The Future of Human Collective Consciousness](#)
 - One of George's contributions is from the [✖ Systems Science](#) side, developing patterns/models derived from human neurobiology (e.g. Abstractions) into generalized Systems setting.
 - [Earth in human hands](#). Homeostasis, Allostasis, Development, Autopoiesis.
 - George has explored this and presented, among elsewhere, Russia — there are analogous narratives, topics, technical elements, perspectives as e.g. Western Cybernetics, Gaia, et al. —
 - Teilhard de Chardin, Noosphere as the mental/cognitive sphere arising in observational-reflexion with the contemporary human. Some argue that this flow (e.g. of cognitive gravity, attention, etc) or Bayesian mechanics is being wasted (“as heat” in the Information Engine setting).
 - Some were/are skeptical about the literal/realist Gaia hypothesis. However there is more to it than that.
 - Peter listened to plenary & later the videos should be available.
 - Shingai joining too, Cliff Joslyn, [Sophia Town](#).
 - Intelligence & Wisdom. George wrote about this topic in terms of knowledge about prefrontal human brain cortex.
 - It is both/and (tetralemma) and beyond, not just either-or. This is manifest in brain structure and dynamics. That is why human brain is a MODEL not a METAPHOR for organizing human society — where there is not a central “govern-ment” (mind control) passing Operative laws via the narrative/structure of (...) representative democracy.
 - Some think evidence has accumulated to make evaluation of and beyond, what historical organizational structures worked how/when.
 - What is the management schema within that framework, and that nature of distributed agency. Proper decisions made at the appropriate level, multi-level policy hierarchical model. [Slides for Iris](#).
 - Where is the segue/integration with embodied cognition and brain-body (or brain-heart-hands or ...). — That is part of the purpose. That is the “management of the body”. Gaia's body, this resonating with some presentations to Russians by George. There are low-level type physiological processes locally. Some “hind brain” component is more homeostatic/allostatic physiological. The tactical view, what is happening outside of Earth? Pure mystery and/or ??? — Now for the asteroids/meteors people are developing the Sensemaking and Decision-making technical components for e.g. meteor defense.
 - George's book — Part 3 of the second book, 12: Governance
- There is ongoing work with Paul Pangaro & Cybernetics (also this is connected through Active Inference Institute). There are other activities all over in the [📖 Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository/space](#).
 - ACS — [✖ Systems Science](#) and Cybernetics — James found more through research and early Harold S Black 1927 Bell Labs, Feedback processes, in the context of communications networks challenges. Negative feedback → wiped out noise & amplification of signals.
 - [George Sarton](#), history of science also in the pre-Vienna & later Systems Theory lineage.
 - https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ralph_Hartley

- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nyquist_frequency
- Learning & Meta-Learning projects, military applications and elsewhere in livingry. Out of that grew other branches/thoughts on self-organization; E.J. Self-organizing universe in terms of multi-scale self-organization. We can't/know various aspects of the past..... Which direction(s) to go with Noo100? Grassroot, Eco, Mil, Gov, Edu, Religion, etc.
- There are written stories around e.g. Information theory, Shannon brought this together & many people of course contributed historically as well. James Miller, and interviewee in some online videos. Society of Fellows & friends with Enrico Fermi, contributing via even casual-causal
- Make it mandatory to, within 1 year, listening to the Miller interviews with ISSS founders and contemporaries, Prigogine, Skinner, et al. to understand better the vision as transformed/realized.
 - ISSS membership is not representative of broader systems projects. And also adjacencies in e.g. successful mega-science projects. What George is careful to, is that the ISSS does not have/hold that/those perspective regimes. These are things that people are using & [Systems Science](#) remains in play.
 - We are up against academia policies and norms, they are isolationist. And in spite of this, some are working across those histories/differences. Doing by virtue of recognizing the patterns.
 - How to cultivate hunger for learning & beyond, outside the bare expansion and improvement of professional development.
 - ..
 -
- ISSS — Scientists wanting to do [Systems Science](#) and those wanting more like application of Systems. And yet that may not be how [ISSS](#) is structured.
 - [ISSS](#) and related organizations, American & British Cybernetics, what governance structures/patterns as aligned how with people's sentiments/preferences/affordances.
 - 1956 [ISSS](#) — Under AAAS, post-WWII, there was total integration. They were not thinking about unifying knowledge per se, more utility/pragmatism driven. The networks & etc were enplaced in different context. There is no longer that kind of organization, in fact there is very limited power/participation on various fronts. Hence this differential/mismatch could be necessitating modern restructurings, as Epistemic/Pragmatic environment is different in e.g. 2023 vs. 1963. Vienna Circle also was dropped like a hot potato.
 - For example mandatory connections among SIGs, which is currently not in word or deed of bylaws and operativity. Thus a key goal, finding unifying connections across areas, was not pursued as seriously/intensely/professionally as it could have been. Thus there is impression/mood/psychology and not with e.g. the Complexity-Math, Category Theory / Topics subject matter expertise. Not even understanding within the organization itself as an organizational Systems Analyst. James and others have been increasingly on this angle since e.g. late 2010's.
 - @Jamie - I noticed you have a 15 min slot at the next BoD meeting 11 Dec 2023: "Member Initiative Presentation 15 minutes- Jamie Rose ". Can you share what it will be about. — Professional letterhead & simple tools that James sees need for utility/alignment all over the world.
 - Otherwise it is just realistically not going to survive long. There is not a program/practice of younger people onboarding, and what to offer them professionally for what to build a future on, there is a lot to be done simultaneously. Not just the praise and positive responsive to live presentations.
 -
- Peter had email earlier with natural and synthetic text and DALL-E 3 visuals.

- ASC archives
 - CMU, All
- @Thomas writing

General and to-do

- ISSS Archive Interface
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.issss.org/primer2/>
 - <https://www.issss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>
- 📄 **The Ideal of Coherence Executive Report - Excerpt 2023**
-
-

Agenda & Ongoing Notes

- Purpose of 📄 **KM as a project & View towards 🎓 Education**
- 11/2/2023
-
- ▼ **Primary direction: ISSS Collections**
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- ▼ **Secondary directions: Collaborative**
 - ▷ **Other Collaborative, non-archival/SCA efforts in the space**
 - ▼ **Development of Interfaces**
 - ▷ Traditional Database with search
 - ▷ Interactive interfaces (Coda)
 - ▼ **Writing.**
 - ▷ One Pager on the project scope.
 - ▷ Position paper — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.
 - ▷ 📄 **Language Models**

▼ Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository

- ▷ Rob discussing the Systems Science.
- ▷ People are discussing the Conferences as being some key texts to pursue. Peter has the 2017 conference

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▷ FedWiki

▼ Different discussion topics:

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◦ Pathways to Open Source Ecosystems

◦ Education ~ sysXML

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- With Michelle and Gary — Setting up the committee pages along the lines of SIG.

• Assess the Modular Outcomes.

◦ Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository

◦ Strategy — @Develop Timeline for 2023

◦ Wiki Templates — @Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance

◦ ISSS Resources — Scope the <https://web3.iss.org/km/> and integrate to Tabular form (with network view or export).

◦ Education

#21 Modular Outcomes 10

Area		Status	To discuss	Name
▼ MediaWiki	1	Inactive	<input type="checkbox"/>	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance
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- Using a Gantt Chart
- Usage of Chat AI

#31 December 14, 2023

Meeting recording

-

General and to-do

- [ISSS Archive Interface](#)
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.issss.org/primer2/>
 - <https://www.issss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>
- 📄 [The Ideal of Coherence Executive Report - Excerpt 2023](#)

Agenda & Ongoing Notes

- **Purpose of 📄 KM as a project & View towards 🎓 Education**
- Systems Analysis of the 🧠 ISSS @ SCA project.
 - Multiple aspects of this; the Database (and schema), Website, work on per-organization basis (e.g. 🧠 ISSS and our Archives).
 - Questions of ontology/language modeling and mapping, and synthetic intelligence 📄 LLM & ISSS 📄 LLM tools, and Intellectual Property.
- [ATLAS](#)
- Possibly
-
- ▼ **Primary direction: ISSS Collections**
 - ▷ See 📄 [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#) and 🧠 [ISSS @ SCA](#), with [@Rob Young](#).
 - ▷ Making the [Interface](#) more useful
- ▼ **Secondary directions: Collaborative**
 - ▷ [Other Collaborative, non-archival/SCA efforts in the space](#)
 - ▼ [Development of Interfaces](#)
 - ▷ Traditional Database with search
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 - ▷ One Pager on the project scope.
 - ▷ Position paper — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.
 - ▷ 🧠 [Language Models](#)
- ▼ 📄 [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)
 - ▷ Rob discussing the 📄 [Ontology](#) for 🧠 [Systems Science](#).
 - ▷ People are discussing the Conferences as being some key texts to pursue. Peter has the 2017 conference
- ▼ Early December 2023 notes

- ▷ George's travels
- ▼ N2 Noosphere at 100 — George long studying and thinking about this, the info-social system as organized to be the brain (classical conception) of the planet, Spaceship Earth.
 - ▷ [N2 Conference – The Noosphere at 100: The Future of Human Collective Consciousness](#)
- ▷ One of George's contributions is from the [Systems Science](#) side, developing patterns/models derived from human neurobiology (e.g. Abstractions) into generalized Systems setting.
- ▷ [Earth in human hands](#). Homeostasis, Allostasis, Development, Autopoiesis.
- ▷ George has explored this and presented, among elsewhere, Russia — there are analogous narratives, topics, technical elements, perspectives as e.g. Western Cybernetics, Gaia, et al. —
- ▷ Teilhard de Chardin, Noosphere as the mental/cognitive sphere arising in observational-reflexion with the contemporary human. Some argue that this flow (e.g. of cognitive gravity, attention, etc) or Bayesian mechanics is being wasted (“as heat” in the Information Engine setting).
- ▷ Some were/are skeptical about the literal/realist Gaia hypothesis. However there is more to it than that.
- ▷ Peter listened to plenary & later the videos should be available.
- ▷ Shingai joining too, Cliff Joslyn, [Sophia Town](#).
- ▼ Intelligence & Wisdom. George wrote about this topic in terms of knowledge about prefrontal human brain cortex.
 - ▷ It is both/and (tetralemma) and beyond, not just either-or. This is manifest in brain structure and dynamics. That is why human brain is a MODEL not a METAPHOR for organizing human society — where there is not a central “govern-ment” (mind control) passing Operative laws via the narrative/structure of (...) representative democracy.
 - ▷ Some think evidence has accumulated to make evaluation of and beyond, what historical organizational structures worked how/when.
 - ▷ What is the management schema within that framework, and that nature of distributed agency. Proper decisions made at the appropriate level, multi-level policy hierarchical model. [Slides for Iris](#).
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- ▷ "Sorting Things Out — Classification and its consequences" Geoffrey C. Bowker and Susan Leigh Star
- ▷ Naming issue. Always a naming problem, people have multiple names & this reflects worldview. Plurality of world views.

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- ▷ Information being captured/transmitted in terms of knowledge structures (from Active Inference representing the path of least action from some cognitive space / generative model).
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- Using a Gantt Chart
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2024

Frame - Context - Thing - Partition - States

#32 January 26, 2024

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/m--U8JgX0IU>

General and to-do

- [ISSS Archive Interface](#)
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.iss.org/primer2/>
 - <https://www.iss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>

Agenda & Ongoing Notes

KM as a project & View towards Education

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- ▷ See [ISSS @ SCA](#), with [@Rob Young](#).
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- ▷ [Other Collaborative, non-archival/SCA efforts in the space](#)

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- ▷ One Pager on the project scope.
- ▷ Position paper — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.

- ▷ [Language Models](#)

▼ [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)

- ▷ Rob discussing the [Systems Science](#).
- ▷ People are discussing the Conferences as being some key texts to pursue. Peter has the 2017 conference

▼ Early December 2023 notes

- ▷ George's travels
- ▼ N2 Noosphere at 100 — George long studying and thinking about this, the info-social system as organized to be the brain (classical conception) of the planet, Spaceship Earth.
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- ▷ [Earth in human hands](#). Homeostasis, Allostasis, Development, Autopoiesis.
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- ▷ Teilhard de Chardin, Noosphere as the mental/cognitive sphere arising in observational-reflexion with the contemporary human. Some argue that this flow (e.g. of cognitive gravity, attention, etc) or Bayesian mechanics is being wasted (“as heat” in the Information Engine setting).
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Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/JPzwLI9Sq6k>

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- ISSS [Archive Interface](#)
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.iss.org/primer2/>
 - <https://www.iss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>
- https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FNgaL97_uwE ActInf GuestStream 070.1 ~ Jerry Michalski: "Practical Collective Sensemaking"
- George: **Knowledge** is structure of the **system**.
 - This (the **knowledge**/prior/QRF) is what makes it possible for new information to be triggering adaptive/**functional** behavior.
 - **Knowledge** as a **System**.
 - The purpose of a **system** is what it does (**POSIWID**) — **Functional teleology**
- GST as top level ontology
 - An upper ontology such a good fit for reality (**SUMO** upper ontology) such that lower and mid-level ontologies are fitting in.
 - And **Knowledge** Chunks also have a fundamental status ([Language Models](#))
 - In George's work on Process Representation in the Neocortex (most malleable modeling machine we have) — "Concept" for the chunking designation. Then "Concept" is a system, thus has e.g. interfaces.
 - Close eyes and imagine a Horse → Driving/Delving into the visual processing for the rendering of the horse, though the top level concept remains "Horse".
 - Frames, Perspectives — 50 people in the room.
 - — e.g. Polycomputing, Multi-Perspectival — always with observer/modeling/process.
 - Consider Tom's UML diagrams/models
 - Notes, Questions, Issue — Instances.
 - If there is the following of the principles of Systems Science — then accessing the information should be relatively straightforward.
- GST as a system. System as a System.
- Smut & Holism
- Concept as a System.
 - Whether it is Horse/Elephant — we're on the shadows of the wall
- How to appreciate the concept?
 - Not analysis of parts/subtypes.
 - Analysis & Synthesis, in Bloom's taxonomies. — Appreciation and what it can be. AIC —

-
- How to initiate analysis of a Concept as a System?
 - Starting with system of interest —
 - What constitute the parts, inputs/outputs, linkages.
 - Example: Horse as a kind of Mammal (classification hierarchy) & lateral/rhizomatic/associative mappings (heterarchy).
 - “PART/WHOLE” & “TYPE/SUBTYPE” - [Mereotopology](#)
 - Part of the horse — Leg. “Leg” is not a “type” of “horse”.
 - Tom began with the Part-Whole aspect, as this is more empirical (e.g. atoms within larger molecules).
 - Then for the Typology — this is not an empirical question. You can organize types in various ways (cars: size, mass, color, cost) — you can do this with a model.
 - People sometimes fix down to 1 way of typing, whereas good models can have flexibility here.
 - Type flexibility in living system — if they are living systems, there is a more general type of system that they are a part of.
 - [Foundations of Language - Ray Jackendoff](#)
 - a, the, this — what kinds of word?
- I need some software/ a platform to help manage a GST Candidates List:
 - 1. Which has a workflow to manage the processing for each Candidate
 - 2. Which can capture every feedback and comment on a particular Candidate
 - There is a spreadsheet — wanting automation and adding. And comments — every comment is audibly recorded and spinning out sub-discussions.
 - https://drive.google.com/file/d/16CU0_iZuJo-iXMR23unmRI8-qfmrJ21j/view
- Not relying on a tool. Rather relying on a process for structuring knowledge, as we see tools playing in.
- Coupling then through a data protocol — upon the HTML/HTTP, to the e.g. HSML/HSTP.
 - Interfaces, Boundaries — Differing from other processes in that it contains a flow protocol (matter, messages, energy).
 - Chans — Coupled Humans And Natural systems — realms of reality.
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Add row

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#21 Modular Outcomes 13

Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance

Status

Inactive

To discuss

Area

 MediaWiki

Log

See MediaWiki

People

Daniel Yiannis Peter T

- Using a Gantt Chart
- Usage of Chat AI

Apis_mellifera.sva.tc

Print View only

A1 GenelD

	A	B	C	
1	GeneID	SRR1255546	SRR1255542	S
2	CM009931.2	0.001886700851	0.001886700851	0
3	CM009932.2	0.003051360517	0.003051360517	0
4	QIUM02000220.	8.80E-18	0	
5	CM009933.2	0.002252513719	0.002252513719	

Untitled page

Classifications for G/ST.

There are types and questions about e.g. generality.

Table 1

Open Systems Theory?

Author/s

Ludwig von Bertalanffy, and others

Abstract (please be brief)

(placeholder)

More details

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_system_\(systems_theory\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_system_(systems_theory))

Discussion forum at:\ Correspondence to:

T

Source\ Added by

Rob Young

Date last updated

☐

Date first submitted

10 May 2020

#34 February 16, 2024

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/2rYY2HVUcyM>

General and to-do

- [ISSS Archive Interface](#)
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.iss.org/primer2/>
 - <https://www.iss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>
-
- https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FNgaL97_uwE ActInf GuestStream 070.1 ~ Jerry Michalski: "Practical Collective Sensemaking"
-
-
-

Agenda & Ongoing Notes

KM as a project & View towards Education

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- ▷ See [ISSS @ SCA](#), with [@Rob Young](#).
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- ▼ ISSS Structure —
 - ▷ Scientists wanting to do [✂ Systems Science](#) and those wanting more like application of Systems. And yet that may not be how [🌐 ISSS](#) is structured.
 - ▷ [🌐 ISSS](#) and related organizations, American & British Cybernetics, what governance structures/patterns as aligned how with people's sentiments/preferences/affordances.
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[🎵 sysXML notes](#)

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- [@Thomas](#) writing
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 - ▼ Naming
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#21 Modular Outcomes 14

Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance

Status

Inactive

To discuss

Area

 [MediaWiki](#)

Log

See [MediaWiki](#)

People

[Daniel](#)

[Yiannis](#)

[Peter T](#)

- Using a Gantt Chart
- Usage of Chat AI

#35 March 8, 2024

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/9QVljSks6jA>

General and to-do

- [ISSS Archive Interface](#)
- ISSS resources
 - <https://web3.isss.org/primer2/> & <https://www.isss.org/sonoma-2006-audio/>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XX61J32RT9g> ActInf GuestStream 074.1 ~ Narrative Fallacy and Other Limitations of Psychodynamic Case Formulation
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=l3rhsT-8isk> ActInf MathStream 009.1 ~ Jonathan Gorard: A computational perspective on observation and cognition
 - Previously, Friston and Wolfram had conversation. Wolfram interviewed Friston to help understand the relevance of several key ActInf/FEP topics, especially as related to the Observer modeling. And also the Wolfram side will augment and develop FEP. They have different ways of doing
 - Second-order cybernetics.
 - Wolfram + SUMO
 - Struggling to make sense of the large base. We ran their stuff into the framework and came out with some new insights, for the general/foundational part (theorem proving) and the domain applications.
 - Stuart Kauffman — possible invite for connecting to system that earn the living in the world.
 -
 - .
 - .
 -
 -
- "Four-fold Fields of Quantum Dreams"
<https://zenodo.org/records/10798145>
Daniel Friedman & Dean Tickles

A very human consideration about taking perspectives on frameworks, told through an adventure playing out in a moment at a Quantum Baseball Spring Training gym.

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Agenda & Ongoing Notes

📅 KM as a project & View towards 🎓 Education

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- ▷ Traditional Database with search
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Status

Inactive

To discuss

Area

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Log

See [📁 MediaWiki](#)

People

[Daniel](#) [Yiannis](#) [Peter T](#)

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#36 March 15, 2024

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/ZDM32ze-ckY>

Notes

- Karl/Doug/Lisa's ISSS presentation last Saturday.
- Philosophical turns in/towards Active Inference.
 - Philosophy of the Computational (Wolfram), Cognitive, Physical/Material (Info-Thermo) universe
 - Linguistic <https://press.uchicago.edu/ucp/books/book/chicago/L/bo3625825.html> Rorty.
 - Pragmatic turn <https://mitpress.mit.edu/9780262545778/the-pragmatic-turn/>
 - Scientific epistemologies — positivist, falsification (negativist), probabilities
 - Critical discourse.
 - Conversation theory and Pask.
- What do human beings deserve/reserve for themselves?
- Once a computational system returns answer — that's the answer.
 - De-contextualized from bodily/flows.
 - And yet completely contextualized internally.
- We can checkpoint this work before the ISSS conference.
- .

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[sysXML notes](#)

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▼ Interacting systems

- ▷ Information being captured/transmitted in terms of knowledge structures (from Active Inference representing the path of least action from some cognitive space / generative model).
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#21 Modular Outcomes 16

Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance

Status

Inactive

To discuss

Area

 [MediaWiki](#)

Log

See [MediaWiki](#)

People

Daniel

Yiannis

Peter T

- Using a Gantt Chart
- Usage of Chat AI

#37 April 5, 2024

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/y-aJi05s8yg>

Notes

- Active InferAnts
- ISSS conference planning / preparing
- 🇺🇸 June 2024 — We sent this email to 🇺🇸 Education People 🇺🇸 Knowledge Engineering People .
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Agenda & Ongoing Notes

📅 KM as a project & View towards 🇺🇸 Education

▼ Primary direction: ISSS Collections

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- ▷ Making the Interface more useful

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- ▷ Other Collaborative, non-archival/SCA efforts in the space
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- ▼ N2 Noosphere at 100 — George long studying and thinking about this, the info-social system as organized to be the brain (classical conception) of the planet, Spaceship Earth.
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Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance

Status

Inactive

To discuss

Area

🗄️ [MediaWiki](#)

Log

See [MediaWiki](#)

People

[Daniel](#) [Yiannis](#) [Peter T](#)

- Using a Gantt Chart
- Usage of Chat AI

#38 April 19, 2024

Meeting recording

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Notes

- [Active InferAnts](#)
- ISSS conference planning / preparing
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Agenda & Ongoing Notes

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To discuss

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People

[Daniel](#) [Yiannis](#) [Peter T](#)

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- Usage of Chat AI

#39 May 3, 2024

Meeting recording

- <https://youtu.be/w2ERMceDtzg>

Notes

- [Active InferAnts](#)
- ISSS conference planning / preparing
- [June 2024](#)
- Physical & Digital archiving.
 - Different resources and physical newsletters/books/etc [Len Troncale's](#) office being closed down soon, so we will work with Rob et al., on securing the physical components — working with the family and ownership, maintaining the chain of custody, updating the ISSS board, etc.
 - There is also [LenTroncale.com](#) .
 - Peter has done some digital archiving for e.g. Ashby.
 - How can we develop these cases, and provides services for domain-scale Physical and Digital repositories?
 - Materials are already being lost, now(s) is the time for figuring some of this out.
 - <https://www.archivematica.org/en/> open source software for physical and digital recordings.
 - From the bylaws WRT property: [ISSS](#)
 - I. To receive property, either real, personal, or mixed, by devise, bequest, or gift; to own, purchase, convey, exchange, lease, mortgage, encumber, or otherwise dispose of property, both real and personal; to borrow money, contract debts, notes, debentures, and to secure the same; to do all other acts necessary or expedient, as determined by the Board of Directors, and as permitted by law for the administration of the affairs or attainment of the overall purpose of the corporation.
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Agenda & Ongoing Notes

KM as a project & View towards Education

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#21 Modular Outcomes 19

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Status

Inactive

To discuss

Area

 [MediaWiki](#)

Log

See [MediaWiki](#)

People

Daniel

Yiannis

Peter T

- Using a Gantt Chart
- Usage of Chat AI

#40 May 24, 2024

Meeting recording

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Notes

- [Active InferAnts](#)
- ISSS conference planning / preparing
- [June 2024](#)
- Physical & Digital archiving.
 - Different resources and physical newsletters/books/etc [Len Troncale's](#) office being closed down soon, so we will work with Rob et al., on securing the physical components — working with the family and ownership, maintaining the chain of custody, updating the ISSS board, etc.
 - There is also [LenTroncale.com](#) .
 - Peter has done some digital archiving for e.g. Ashby.
 - How can we develop these cases, and provides services for domain-scale Physical and Digital repositories?
 - Materials are already being lost, now(s) is the time for figuring some of this out.
 - <https://www.archivematica.org/en/> open source software for physical and digital recordings.
 - From the bylaws WRT property: [ISSS](#)
 - I. To receive property, either real, personal, or mixed, by devise, bequest, or gift; to own, purchase, convey, exchange, lease, mortgage, encumber, or otherwise dispose of property, both real and personal; to borrow money, contract debts, notes, debentures, and to secure the same; to do all other acts necessary or expedient, as determined by the Board of Directors, and as permitted by law for the administration of the affairs or attainment of the overall purpose of the corporation.
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Agenda & Ongoing Notes

[KM as a project](#) & [View towards](#) [Education](#)

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- ▷ See [ISSS @ SCA](#), with [@Rob Young](#).
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 - ▷ [Position paper — Systems Science: Approaches, Corpus, Theory, and Practice.](#)
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To discuss

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 [MediaWiki](#)

Log

See [MediaWiki](#)

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- Using a Gantt Chart
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#41 June 7, 2024

Meeting recording

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Notes

- [Active InferAnts](#)
- June
 - <https://web.cvent.com/event/14c40a51-6d9d-4e76-bd38-872f316d2223/websitePage:0d97309b-d480-4dc8-b546-82862efe3ae9>
- ISSS conference planning / preparing
- [RxlInfer.jl](#) in [Google Colab notebook](#) for Active Inference [Drone example](#) by [Kobus E.](#)
- George - talked with Shingai, frontend/adaptation of [George Mobus](#) textbook Analysis interface with Joseph. Not yet linked to Database. [Systems Language / sysXML](#)
- Literacy
 - George wrote:
 - While working on a book chapter (title: Teaching Systems Thinking: Achieving the Outcomes Promised from Liberal Studies) re: education and systems science I was struck by a thought. We do not talk about biology thinking, or chemistry thinking, or even sociology thinking. But we do admit to literacy in all of these fields, meaning that one who is literate in biology or chemistry, etc. is capable of thinking in terms of the subject and that such thinking guides one's choices/decisions/actions (as in ocean literacy). Why do we shift the rhetoric to emphasize 'thinking' when talking about systems, do you think? I have long railed against the notion of systems thinking when that thinking is not based on the science. Should we be pushing harder on literacy, as in knowing a subject, and call into question the idea of 'thinking' solely based on a few fuzzy concepts from the field? I'm considering renaming the chapter to: Teaching Systems Literacy: Achieving the Outcomes Promised from Liberal Studies. To me the idea of literacy is much stronger than what poses as 'thinking'.
 - Thinking is/isn't. Literacy, being better at thing to do. Already thinking in terms of systems (evolutionary/ecological Systemese tendencies). Literacy & language learning/speaking. Test of systems literacy, in the application. If it can apply in practice then the literacy is good and useful.
 - What meaning is/means, Jackendoff claims a hidden/subconscious basis of meaning (without direct conscious access). Surface as within language semantics.
 - Shared meaning acquired through experience through time, inter-subjective meaning through time & different terms/etc.

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Overview

The [📖 ISSS Knowledge Engineering Directory](#) provides an [🔧 Overview](#) on this Coda document.

Key links

- <https://www.iss.org/knowledge-engineering/>

ISSS Knowledge Engineering Directory

Department	Name	Description
▼ 🔧 Overview 3	🔧 Overview	This very 🔧 Overview page — here you are!
	📖 Knowledge Engineering People	Table of 📖 People ~ ISSS Knowledge Engineering
	🎵 MediaWiki Notes	Unsorted and sundry 🎵 MediaWiki Notes
▼ 📖 KM as a project 3	? Questions	? Questions to keep in mind for Knowledge Engineering
	📖 Topics	📖 Topics , skills, settings, and more.
▼ 🚫 Broken link 1	🚫 Broken link	Coordination center for 🚫 Broken link

ISSS

- ISSS Bylaws: <https://www.iss.org/by-laws/>
- See page in [Education Coda with Bylaws](#)

Knowledge Engineering People

People ~ ISSS Knowledge Engineering

First Name	Last Name	Last contact	Next contact	Interest	Status	Notes	Short note & Next step	Email
Shae	Brown	12/16/2023		Yes				
Olaf	Brugman	12/16/2023		Yes				
Stephen	Davies	12/16/2023		Yes				
Gianni	Di Marco	12/16/2023		Yes				
Dennis	Finlayson	12/16/2023		Yes				
Daniel	Friedman	12/16/2023		Yes				
Roelien	Goede	12/16/2023		Yes				
Karl	Hebenstreit	12/16/2023		Yes				
David	Ing	12/16/2023		Yes				
Adler Looks	Jorge	12/16/2023		Yes				
Katrina	Kessler	12/16/2023		Yes				
Yiannis	Laouris	12/16/2023		Yes				
Sa	Liu	12/16/2023						
Delia Pembrey	MacNamara	12/16/2023		Yes				
Thomas	Marzolf	12/16/2023		Yes				
Gary	Metcalf	12/16/2023		Yes				
Michael	Mokiy	12/16/2023		Yes				
Sadra	Moosavi	12/16/2023		Yes				
Peter R	Robertson	12/16/2023		Yes				
James	Rose	12/16/2023		Yes				
Steve	Schneider	12/16/2023		Yes				
Bill	Smith	12/16/2023		Yes				
Dave	Thawley	12/16/2023		Yes				
Shingai	Thornton	12/16/2023		Yes				
Peter T	Tuddenham	12/16/2023		Yes				
Rob	Young	12/16/2023		Yes				

Ways to participate

- Familiarize yourself with the [Overview](#) Coda, explore different pages.
- Add yourself to the People column of the [Modular Outcomes](#) & work on a specific area (e.g. a particular project organized around a deliverable and timeline)
 - Feel free to ask if unclear where/how some desired contribution might be facilitated.
- Join [Live Knowledge Engineering Meetings](#) (calendar in [gCal format](#) and [iCal format](#)), or suggest other times.
- Read over the [Topics](#) and see if any of these areas inspire you to make additions
 - Add any kind of content, questions, resources, etc. that any future person might want to know.
 - Also reading what others have written, and making thoughtful additions, helps develop our knowledge engineering project and approach.
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KM as a project

2023 goals

- **Fundamentals of storage**
 - Assessment & Documentation of the ISSS Catalog (@Rob)
 - ISSS internal repository and breadth of knowledge (and less tangible, general systems theory).
 - Accessibility and Humanness — Involves searching via Catalog/Index (library model).
 - Activities — Many possible projects.
 - Ingress and storage of materials
 - Annotation, Tagging, Marking, Linking
 - **Other Archival efforts in the space**
 - Connect with **Fundamentals of storage** (interoperability)
 - @Peter R EU-S Systemic — Hellenic Systems Sciences — Archiving Project.
 - Relevant to bring into our awareness.
 - Using the MIT DSpace process for compiling the materials.
 - American Society for Cybernetics.
 - Gordon Pask (Conversation Theory) — Paul Pangaro (also @Vienna), seeing possible opportunity for dialogic interface.
 - Possible funding opportunity.
 - **Development of Interfaces**
 - traditional Database with search
 - Large Language Models // Chat interface (in Coda or otherwise)
 - Custom corpus
 - Formal knowledge model (SUMO, other approaches).

Some discussions on 🗨️ [Overview](#)

- Scope
- Boundaries
 - In the periphery — targeted collaborations.
 - Participation across many communities, managing time and attention. Hence the strategic importance of connections across groups.
 -
- Curation // Federation
- Engelbart — Augmenting human intelligence
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FruLFKfomK4> **Community Wisdom Gardening, from Kernel.**
<https://www.kernel.community/en/>
- Attention management

- <https://www.nirandfar.com/indistractable/>
- <https://www.buildingasecondbrain.com/>
- Cognitive modeling — Active entities, making/sensemaking stigmergic marks.
- Getting the information out of the brain and into external sources.
- Empirical support for e.g. GTD?
- Supporting employees with disabilities and differences
 - <https://www.eeoc.gov/statutes/rehabilitation-act-1973> — From 1973, reauthorized in 1998. The Rehabilitation Act of 1973
 - W3C accessibility guidelines.
 - Future of Text
 - Karl Hebenstreit wrote paper, text-based interfaces for multi-media content. One can have proprietary content as long as it is addressable/available. Separate presentation from content.
 - Neurodiverse adults, modeling of attention.
 - There are many models of disability (medical model, DSM), social model (people are disabled by societal norms).....
 - Physical/Embodied (ramps), and Sensory (captioning, transcription)
 - Words are the interlingua, a critical nexus for interoperability.
 - Many centers and areas of study and development.
 - <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8396119/> Towards a computational phenomenology of mental action: modelling meta-awareness and attentional control with deep parametric active inference
 - [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Here_Comes_Everybody_\(book\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Here_Comes_Everybody_(book)) Here Comes Everybody (book)
 - Kuhn — Copernican revolution, anomalies build up, then rip and replace. How can we move towards Accept, Elaborate, Extend?
 - Bohm and quantum physics → Dialogue
 - https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Process_ontology
- .
- .
- .
- .

Modular Outcomes

Outcomes & Objectives

Modular Outcomes

Status		Name	Depends on	Log	Area
▼ Active	4	Discussion of the rights and responsibilities of ISSS archive material		Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository	
		Funding exploration		Strategy	
		Front end for ISSS archives		Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository	
		Developing uses for ISSS Archives		Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository	
▼ Inactive	3	Improve the use and usability of the ISSS MediaWiki instance		MediaWiki	
		Facilitate asynchronous contributions in between the bi-weekly meetings		Ways to participate	
		Research Unified storage solution for ISSS		Strategy	
▼ Done	2	Develop Timeline for 2023		Strategy	
		Receipt of General Systems spreadsheet from Rob		Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository	

Approaches

 Approaches are different ways/platforms that are relevant for Knowledge Engineering

Approaches for Knowledge Engineering

Name	Link	Type	Functions	Notes
MediaWiki				
Systems Common Web				
Mind Map of ISSS resources				

Approach Type

- Type
- Mind map
- Ontology
- Data storage
- Collaborative
- Course
- Training
- User interface

Strategy

- What does 📖 [Strategy](#) look like to whom and why?
- .
- .
- .
- .
- Immediate and future use
 - Many good ideas and work — not accessible or widely circulated.
 - Kickstarting Systems — where is the body of knowledge? What are the main ideas?
- 70th anniversary of ISSS!
 - Physical library for ISSS?
 - Len's Office (both personal and ISSS), Peter's Basement.
 - Physical locations (lots of effort for famous people, others less so)
- IFSR — Pinnacle systems organization? (and other Systems/Cybernetics organizations) Involvement in this 📖 [Strategy](#) discussion?
 - Invitations are important.
 - Here is what we are doing, here is how to participate.
- **SCA at Infrastructure** — To glue all the bodies together, serving all the groups in the community.
 - Not at the leadership level.
 - Custodians/Stewards/Leads at each organization. Formal and Informal network of coordination. → Can log in, stay notified of news and events, see what other people are trying and doing.
- .
- .
- Timepoints
 - First quarter 2023 —
 - Second quarter 2023 —
 - One major timepoint for this project is the ISSS conference in South Africa in 2023.
- What does a 📖 [Strategy](#) for 🧩 [Overview](#) look like?
 - Roadmap,
 - Actionable maps
 - Models of dependencies in systems
 - Heuristics
 - Processes of feedback and change
- What kinds of 📖 [Strategy](#) and ongoing alignment/constellation, might be consistent with the vision and reality of 🧩 [ISSS](#) ?
- Milestones
 - 🗺️ [Modular Outcomes](#)

View of Modular Outcomes

Status		Name	Depends on	Log	Area
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Questions

ISSS Knowledge Engineering ~ Questions

Question	Notes	Tags
What is the function of Knowledge Engineering?		
Who will be using different functions/paths/aspects of the systems?		
Viability and costs of the ISSS and Knowledge Engineering?		
How to maintain and document high quality systems?		
How can Action Research be incorporated in Knowledge Engineering?		
What are conversations & how can they be efficacious in Education and Research?		
What will anchor the ontology created: will it just be categorisation or will it be an intuitive functional representation?		
How will the coalescence start: top down (theoretical framework filled in with details), bottom up (start from details then group them into higher structures somehow), from an algorithm (machines find patterns differently), or from a pragmatic middle already in existence (like a sister organisations project)?		
How do we understand the problem, devise a plan, and carry it out?		
How do we start using LMM's with the archive?		
How can i get notifications of the next KE meeting? (ie via calendar appointment), with the correct Zoom link? (I get ones for Education, but don't seem to get them for KE)		

Topics

Systems Science

-
- What is [🦋 Systems Science](#)? What are key paths, ways, and resources in the area?
 - See: [🏠 ISSS Resources](#)
- How does the [🔗 Overview](#) of Systems Science, relate to Systems Science as a theoretical, complex construct itself?
 -
- How does the practicing [👉 Approaches](#) of Systems Science, relate to Systems Science as a theoretical, complex construct itself?
 -
- Role of [🦋 Systems Science](#) in
 - Technical: Data architecture
 - Technical: Frontend (UI/UX)
 - Technical-Ontological: Schema for Systems Ontology (related: [Education initiatives](#) and contributions from Gary Smith).
- Which upper ontologies/schemas/approaches already exist?
 - As well as less-structured Tag systems, and other discourse/corpus analysis methods.
- Other researchers to integrate and process
 - Fritjof Capra —
 - James Greer Miller — Living Systems Theory — [🦋 Systems Science](#)
 - Viable Systems Model (VSM)
 - James N Rose - Integrity Paradigm: Redefining “Plural Entropies” ; practical universal mechanism of Order~Complexity generation [interaction~communication basis] [identifiable in original “spacetime dimensions”, and on through all hierarchies of complexities generation (human tier - sociology, information theory, competition~cooperation performance interactions).

LLM & ISSS

Session

▼ Introduction

- ▷ Welcome to the [Knowledge Engineering](#) and [Education](#) projects at ISSS.
- ▷ These projects meet weekly on Thursdays at 18 UTC (11am PT), alternating between Knowledge Engineering and Education. Everyone is welcome to join these meetings to learn more, and find out ways to synergize/collaborator. education@iss.org

▼ Background — What this session will and will not focus on.

- ▷ This session **will** explore some emerging **tools** and approaches related to Large Language Models (LLM) and the International Society for Systems Science (ISSS).
- ▼ This session **will not** initially focus on **several other important areas of LLM-ology**. We can return to these after seeing some **tools**, if we want. Please feel free to share resources/thoughts related to these important areas. Future work at ISSS and elsewhere will continue all of these threads, so

▼ Technological details

- ▷ Feb 14, 2023 “What Is ChatGPT Doing ... and Why Does It Work?” — Stephen Wolfram, blog.
- ▷ Jan 17, 2023 “**Let's build GPT: from scratch, in code, spelled out.**” — Andrej Karpathy, video.
- ▷ Jan 30, 2023 “How ChatGPT Works: The Model Behind The Bot” — Molly Ruby, blog.

▼ Holistic considerations; Ethics, Tactics, Strategy.

- ▷ (How) To accelerate or not to accelerate? e.g. [Open letter calling for 6 month moratorium](#)
- ▷ Higher-order consequences of LLM deployment (e.g. organizational shifts, changes in epistemic environments, [cognitive security](#))
- ▷ Personal (behavioral, psychological) implications: information overload, attention, trust, mental health, interpersonal relationships.

▼ Systems Science

- ▷ Area of exciting work — synthesizing LLM and Transformer-type foundation models, with extant work in Systems Science and Linguistics (e.g. by [George Mobus](#), [Janos Korn](#), [Jessie Henshaw](#), [Smekal & Friedman](#)).

▼ Tools

▼ Browser-based

- ▷ OpenAI ChatGPT: <https://chat.openai.com/>
- ▷ Coda OpenAI plugin: <https://coda.io/@coda/openai-for-coda> — [ISSS-LLM-GPT](#)
- ▷ Perplexity — <https://www.perplexity.ai/> — LLM with internet search access.
- ▷ <https://nat.dev/compare> — Compare many different LLM and play with their parameters.
- ▷ Writefull — <https://x.writefull.com/academizer>
- ▷ <https://open-assistant.io/>
- ▷ <https://huggingface.co/spaces/Vision-CAIR/minigpt4>
- ▷ <https://poe.com/Claude-instant-100k> — LLM with 100k context window.

- ▷ The above tools are all LLM, here is one nice image generator — [StableDiffusion_2.1](https://huggingface.co/spaces/stabilityai/stable-diffusion)
<https://huggingface.co/spaces/stabilityai/stable-diffusion>
- ▼ Code and beyond
 - ▷ GPT Agent Toolkit — <https://github.com/XpressAI/xai-gpt-agent-toolkit>
 - ▷ AgentGPT — <https://agentgpt.reworkd.ai/>
 - ▷ AutoGPT — <https://github.com/Significant-Gravitas/Auto-GPT>
 - ▷ BabyAGI — <https://github.com/yoheinakajima/babyagi>
 - ▷ <https://github.com/nickm980/smallville>
 - ▷ <https://github.com/101dotxyz/GPTeam>
 - ▷ <https://github.com/imartinez/privateGPT>
 - ▷ Personal offline GPT from Read Multiplex
<https://readmultiplex.com/2023/04/11/how-you-can-install-a-chatgpt-like-personal-ai-on-your-own-computer-and-run-it-with-no-internet/>
- ▼ Feeding 🗄️ [KM as a project](#) and [ISSS Archive Interface](#) details in.
 - ▷ Bringing in Article titles (voices from the past speaking out).
 - ▷ Bringing in some snippets from George's book
- ▼ Where now?
 - ▷ Type prompts or ideas in the chat that we can try.
 - ▷ Personal implications
 - ▷ Organizational implications
 - ▷ How can we carry this work forward in [Knowledge Engineering](#) and [Education](#) projects at ISSS.

Notes

- 🗄️ [KM as a project](#) — how to build value for ISSS members and Systems community, using the Archives?
 - How to match up excitement and possibility, with the goals/processes of ISSS? And how to engage in these activities?
 - How does ISSS create a SystemsAI?
- Tendency — *As tools unfold, look at what the tools do.* — This tendency advances as the tools become more advanced. There is also possibility of getting lost/dazzled in the technology.
 - ISSS producing value for larger sectors.
- Electronically illiterate — Intriguing that it is new forms of information.
 - Long history of Archival research. How to introduce this work into the system?
- Important experiences
 - Yiannis & Peter — discussing governance and cybernetics..... Asking the GPT..... disappointing, since the responses are professional, however with fabricated references. When told that the references don't exist, the system apologizes and gives other fake references.
 - Trust in these systems.
 - Discussion with Gary — structured democratic dialogue — couldn't we ask GPT? Asking about characteristics of an ideal future educational system.... coming up with 40-80 descriptors in human groups, LLM was able to come up with 120. Inclusive of the previous human answers.

- Work that we are doing for hours-years (e.g. writing a python project).
- Google's Bard what symptoms you'd expect from people being pushed to change how they live at Impossible rates:
- Are there copyright issues in using these tools on a knowledge base, like the ISSS archives or George's book?
- Human beings channel capacity — changing the way people live, accelerating change.
 - Politics, not just in terms of “political” also decision-making at individual and group levels.
 - Different ages & familiarities with technologies.
 - Channel capacity of humans is hugely important and seems to be overlooked as this topic. Humans have only five channels of communication of touch, tasted, smell, sound, and vision and each has limited capacity of bytes per second. This provided my basis for establishing the science of governance with Transaction Byte Analysis. As not coordinate action between any entities with transacting bytes and no change in information , knowledge or wisdom can occur without transacting bytes
- Dealing with — has the potential capacity to solve some of the biggest problems that are already happening.
 - Challenge — dealing with levels of language. Wider and Broader levels, always bringing in more, and more abstractions. The ultimate abstraction of oneness.
 - Issues of technical language.... Language of coherence — the part is in the whole, every part in the whole. Essential relationship to the whole in every part.
- The interesting thing about "separation" from nature is that these language tools will inevitably accelerate our separation from the experiential meanings of life in so far as the AI bots have none of that, and will be doing most of the talking...
 - and shifting us toward a cognitive world where most of the “activity” will be mental.
 - still. artificial intelligence, GPT. it relies on what is on the web. In my opinion, the task of our society is to upload as much information about the system approach to the network as possible. And GPT will allow generalizations to be carried out much faster and better
- With the knowledge and experience in the ISSS community we should be able to strengthen our connections to offer support and insight to and for each other as the accelerating consequences of this technology takes effect
 - It seems to me that you, and some others above, have already offered practical actions in response to the challenges in front of us. I think we have already some interesting thoughts to launch a serious structured dialogue on this.
- The experiential knowledge comment is a core one to address since most of our life decisions are based on this form of knowledge.
- It looks overwhelming. However if we approach this as tools, and understanding that knowledge is already beyond our capacities.
 - Layers of peace — Unity and Diversity, what makes us human. How can we match this with an approach so that it serves as a resource? And provide value for society? Bringing Love into Science, will offer many ways.
 - Thank you for a stimulating discussion. As Yiannis Laouris ? commented, would be good for ISSS to help curate community-based conversations which go beyond ISSS membership, into wider society about this very important topic of AI as tools vs AI creating the information and knowledge, I need to sign off now. Thank you . Pille - please stay hopeful!!Faith
- [Too Much to Know](#) Managing Scholarly Information before the Modern Age by Ann M. Blair
- <https://arxiv.org/abs/2212.01354> [Submitted on 2 Dec 2022] Designing Ecosystems of Intelligence from First Principles, Friston et al. 2022.
- <https://kindredmedia.org/glossary/indigenous-worldview/>
- Technology can always be used for good or bad. I am afraid that the negative possibilities of certain technologies (eg nuclear) threaten our very existence. Does this apply for AI?
 - I THINK THE IDEA THAT THE GOOD THINGS IT MIGHT DO COMPLETELY OVERLOOKS HOW THE ECONOMY WORKS. THE ECONOMY MULTIPLIES THE MOST PROFITABLE DIVERGENCES FORM THE PAST, WITH OUT ANY ATTENTION TO

THE EXTERNALITIES OF THOSE DECISIONS, HOW MANY STEPS BEYOND ANY ECONOMY COULD RECOVER FROM IF THERE WAS A COLLAPSE.

- THE PROBLEM WITH HUMANITY IS THAT THE TOOLS FOR USING POWER TO MULTIPLY POWER SEEMS SO VERY ATTRACTIVE IS THAT THOSE ATTRACTED TO THEM BECOME COMPLETELY BLIND TO THE CONSEQUENCES. ==== IT WOULD RAPIDLY MULTIPLY THE MADMEN IN OUR WORLD, AS IF WE DIDN'T HAVE ENOUGH.
- I do wish I didn't feel a need to be so negative, but here and elsewhere we've been sailing along on a definitely suicidal path, ever faster acceleration of our consumption, degradation and disruption of our world and measuring success with our momentary comfort.
- That's the danger we've been totally ignoring, well except for a very few finding it extremely hard to get the point across. WHAT WE NEED IS A RESTRICTION OF THE TOOL TO CAREFULLY COORDINATED USES.
- AS IT IS IT'S A SWIFT SWORD FOR FURTHER EMPOWERING THE POWERFUL BLIND TO THE DONSEQUENCES OF THEIR ACTIONS.
- Trim tabs are statistically too small to be recognised by statistical tools. So we will be drowned in drive.
- Most probably the main stream concept of power also is. At least there are other far more promising and joyful possibilities/options
- Imagination!
 - Algorithms have high speed.
 - Structuring the ideal state — may not know how to do that though, or not have confidence. Alternative, to look at it is (the Natural System). In the middle, is “how it is”, and “idea state”, what things are there that we can actually look at and move?
 - Ideal state — housing of imagination — to imagine an ideal.
 - Expressions, across all 5 dimensions — take a matrix slice — what would be accurate?
 - Viable concepts and ideals. — Can
- Constant production of noise — makes communication challenging.
 - Imagination and true human aspirations are key resources in combination with a disposition to learn, create, recreate in connection to promising scenarios: exciting life-sustaining realities that nowadays seem out of reach
- What information is fed into it? What is the process of training it?
 - Key step in steering —
 - Sensible economic model?
 - Who has the power to be a trainer of machines that belief in economic systems is counter productive to sustainability
- How would AI recognise concepts not described by English language like “owneeship”?
- Dangers in homogenization.
- Computing has the concepts of Computability; the Church-Turing thesis; Turing Complete etc, to indicate a level of computing development. Does AI have something similar ie. concepts about the capabilities/ limitations of what AI can do?
 - <https://arxiv.org/abs/2210.12761> Path integrals, particular kinds, and strange things

• <https://mygeekwisdom.com/2016/05/21/a-strange-game-the-only-winning-move-is-not-to-play/>

▼ Large Language Models // Chat interface (in Coda or otherwise)

▷ Custom corpus

▷ Formal knowledge model (SUMO, other approaches).

▷

• John Sowa talk on LLM/GPT

• Special Session of the Ontolog Forum on GPT

◦ https://ontologforum.com/index.php/ConferenceCall_2023_05_31

@ meeting_saved_chat.txt

ISSS-LLM-GPT

Summarize

When	Meeting	Notes	Summarize	GPT-3 Summary
2/23/23, 6:00 AM	#12 February 23, 2023		Generate	The primary direction is ISSS Collection, with Rob Young. Notes were taken on 2/23/2023 website in development which involves an underlying index to some materials and hosting by Organizations (divided into Collections of knowledge assets and Registers of lists), with the specific use case of someone interested in doing MS/PhD in the Systems field with a wider associated lists of events and conferences. Secondary directions involve collaboration with other non-archival/SCA efforts and the exploration of funding opportunities. Development interfaces involves a traditional database with search, interactive interfaces, custom corpus, and a formal knowledge model (SUMO, or other approaches). Writing includes a one-pager on the project scope and a position paper on the Systemic approach, corpus, theory, and practice.

Summarize and Translate

Paragraph	Query	AI
<p>This paper introduces a variational formulation of natural selection, paying special attention to the nature of 'things' and the way that different 'kinds' of 'things' are individuated from—and influence—each other. We use the Bayesian mechanics of particular partitions to understand how slow phylogenetic processes constrain—and are constrained by—fast, phenotypic processes. The main result is a formulation of adaptive fitness as a path integral of phenotypic fitness. Paths of least action, at the phenotypic and phylogenetic scales, can then be read as inference and learning processes, respectively. In this view, a phenotype actively infers the state of its niche under a generative model, whose parameters are learned via natural (Bayesian model) selection. The ensuing variational synthesis features some unexpected aspects. Perhaps the most notable is that it is not possible to describe or model a population of conspecifics per se. Rather, it is necessary to consider populations of distinct natural kinds that influence each other. This paper is limited to a description of the mathematical apparatus and accompanying ideas. Subsequent work will use these methods for simulations and numerical analyses—and identify points of contact with related mathematical formulations of evolution.</p>	<p>Summarize the follow text, giving 1 short sentence each of English, Chinese, Hindi, Russian, and Swahili:</p> <p>This paper introduces a variational formulation of natural selection, paying special attention to the nature of 'things' and the way that different 'kinds' of 'things' are individuated from—and influence—each other. We use the Bayesian mechanics of particular partitions to understand how slow phylogenetic processes constrain—and are constrained by—fast, phenotypic processes. The main result is a formulation of adaptive fitness as a path integral of phenotypic fitness. Paths of least action, at the phenotypic and phylogenetic scales, can then be read as inference and learning processes, respectively. In this view, a phenotype actively infers the state of its niche under a generative model, whose parameters are learned via natural (Bayesian model) selection. The ensuing variational synthesis features some unexpected aspects. Perhaps the most notable is that it is not possible to describe or model a population of conspecifics per se. Rather, it is necessary to consider populations of distinct natural kinds that influence each other. This paper is limited to a description of the mathematical apparatus and accompanying ideas. Subsequent work will use these methods for simulations and numerical analyses—and identify points of contact with related mathematical formulations of evolution.</p>	<p>This paper presents a natural selection through which authors focus on the different types of 'things' are considered. To do this, they use particular partitions to understand how slow phylogenetic processes constrain—and are constrained by—fast, phenotypic processes. The main result is a formulation of adaptive fitness as a path integral of phenotypic fitness. Paths of least action, at the phenotypic and phylogenetic scales, can then be read as inference and learning processes, respectively. In this view, a phenotype actively infers the state of its niche under a generative model, whose parameters are learned via natural (Bayesian model) selection. The ensuing variational synthesis features some unexpected aspects. Perhaps the most notable is that it is not possible to describe or model a population of conspecifics per se, but rather populations of distinct natural kinds interact with each other. This paper is limited to a description of the mathematical apparatus and accompanying ideas, and subsequent work will use these methods for simulations and numerical analyses—and identify points of contact with related mathematical formulations of evolution.</p>

The primary direction is ISSS Collection, with Rob Young. Notes were taken on the 2/23/2023 website in development which involves an underlying index to source materials and hosting by Organizations (divided into Collections of knowledge assets and Registers of lists), with the specific use case of someone interested in doing MS/PhD in the Systems field with a wider associated lists of events and conferences. Secondary directions involve collaboration with other non-archival/SCA efforts and the exploration of funding opportunities. Development of interfaces involves a traditional database with search, interactive interfaces, a custom corpus, and a formal knowledge model (SUMO, or other approaches). Writing includes a one-pager on the project scope and a position paper on the Systemic approach, corpus, theory, and practice.

Summarize the follow text, giving 1 short sentence each of English, Chinese, Hindi, Russian, and Swahili:

The primary direction is ISSS Collection, with Rob Young. Notes were taken on the 2/23/2023 website in development which involves an underlying index to source materials and hosting by Organizations (divided into Collections of knowledge assets and Registers of lists), with the specific use case of someone interested in doing MS/PhD in the Systems field with a wider associated lists of events and conferences. Secondary directions involve collaboration with other non-archival/SCA efforts and the exploration of funding opportunities. Development of interfaces involves a traditional database with search, interactive interfaces, a custom corpus, and a formal knowledge model (SUMO, or other approaches). Writing includes a one-pager on the project scope and a position paper on the Systemic approach, corpus, theory, and practice.

The paragraph provide the ISSS Collection, w main focus appears to which involves creatin materials and hosting divided into Collector of lists, with a specific interested in pursuing. Additionally, there will associated with this fi. There are also second collaboration with oth exploration of funding project is aiming to be of stakeholders. In terms of the develo traditional database w custom corpus, and a other approaches) will project is aiming to be positive sign. Finally, the paragraph important aspect of th one-pager on the proj the Systemic approac suggests that the proj deliberate approach to seems that the ISSS C planned and ambitiou: make a significant imp

LLM tools

- **Active Inference & Active Blockference**

- <https://github.com/ActiveInferenceInstitute/ActiveBlockference> Active Blockference implements Active Inference generative models with cadCAD.
- <https://github.com/cadCAD-org/cadcad-ri> Complex Adaptive Dynamics Computer Aided Design (cadCAD) is a language for encoding Generalized Dynamical Systems (GDS) as computer programs. This repository contains the reference implementation of the software, based on the formal specification. Python was chosen for the reference implementation for clarity and ease of use.

- **Multiagent LLM**

- <https://github.com/nickm980/smallville> Generative agents are virtual characters that can store memories and dynamically react to their environment. Using LLM models such as ChatGPT or StableLM, agents are able to observe their surroundings, store memories, and react to state changes in the world
- <https://github.com/chatarena/chatarena> ChatArena is a library that provides multi-agent language game environments and facilitates research about autonomous LLM agents and their social interactions. It provides the following features: Abstraction, Environments, User-friendly Interfaces.
- <https://github.com/OpenGVLab/GITM> **Ghost in the Minecraft (GITM)** is a novel framework integrates Large Language Models (LLMs) with text-based knowledge and memory, aiming to create Generally Capable Agents in Minecraft.
- <https://github.com/OpenBMB/AgentVerse> **AgentVerse** provides a flexible framework that simplifies the process of building custom multi-agent environments for large language models (LLMs). Our framework is designed to enable researchers to quickly build and customize their own environments with minimal effort, allowing them to focus on their research rather than implementation details.
- <https://github.com/BladeTransformerLLC/OvercookedGPT> An OpenAI gym environment to evaluate the ability of large language models (LLMs; eg. GPT-4, Claude) in long-horizon reasoning and task planning in dynamic multi-agent settings based on [gym-cooking](#).
- <https://github.com/101dotxyz/GPTeam> GPTeam uses GPT-4 to create multiple agents who collaborate to achieve predefined goals. The main objective of this project is to explore the potential of GPT models in enhancing multi-agent productivity and effective communication.
- **mkturkcan/generative-agents**: This repository includes a working version of the type of model described in Generative Agents: Interactive Simulacra of Human Behavior.

- **Task execution AI and AGI**

- <https://github.com/Significant-Gravitas/Auto-GPT> Auto-GPT is an experimental open-source application showcasing the capabilities of the GPT-4 language model. This program, driven by GPT-4, chains together LLM "thoughts", to autonomously achieve whatever goal you set. As one of the first examples of GPT-4 running fully autonomously, Auto-GPT pushes the boundaries of what is possible with AI.
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- <https://github.com/SamurAIGPT/Camel-AutoGPT> Camel AutoGPT allows you to configure and deploy communicating Autonomous AI agents. Name your own custom AI characters and have them embark on any goal imaginable .
- <https://github.com/Josh-XT/AGiXT> AGiXT is a dynamic Artificial Intelligence Automation Platform engineered to orchestrate efficient AI instruction management and task execution across a multitude of providers. Our solution infuses adaptive memory handling with a broad spectrum of commands to enhance AI's understanding and responsiveness, leading to improved task completion.

- <https://github.com/reworkd/AgentGPT> AgentGPT allows you to configure and deploy Autonomous AI agents. Name your own custom AI and have it embark on any goal imaginable. It will attempt to reach the goal by thinking of tasks to do, executing them, and learning from the results .
- <https://github.com/muellerberndt/mini-agi> MiniAGI is a simple autonomous agent compatible with GPT-3.5-Turbo and GPT-4. It combines a robust prompt with a minimal set of tools, chain-of-thoughts, and short-term memory with summarization. It is also capable of inner monologue and self-criticism.
- <https://github.com/enricoros/big-agi> Personal AGI App, powered by OpenAI GPT-4 and beyond. Designed for smart humans and super-heroes, this responsive web app comes with Personas, Drawing, Code Execution, PDF imports, Voice support, data Rendering, AGI functions, chats and more.
- <https://github.com/TransformerOptimus/SuperAGI> *Infrastructure to build, manage and run useful Autonomous AI Agents*
- **Multiagent AI**
 - https://github.com/deepmind/open_spjel OpenSpiel is a collection of environments and algorithms for research in general reinforcement learning and search/planning in games. OpenSpiel supports n-player (single- and multi- agent) zero-sum, cooperative and general-sum, one-shot and sequential, strictly turn-taking and simultaneous-move, perfect and imperfect information games, as well as traditional multiagent environments such as (partially- and fully- observable) grid worlds and social dilemmas. OpenSpiel also includes tools to analyze learning dynamics and other common evaluation metrics.
 - <https://github.com/NeuralMMO/environment> Neural MMO is a massively multiagent environment for artificial intelligence research inspired by Massively Multiplayer Online (MMO) role-playing games.
 - <https://github.com/datamllab/rlcard> RLCard is a toolkit for Reinforcement Learning (RL) in card games. It supports multiple card environments with easy-to-use interfaces for implementing various reinforcement learning and searching algorithms. The goal of RLCard is to bridge reinforcement learning and imperfect information games.
 - <https://github.com/Farama-Foundation/MAgent2> MAgent2 is a library for the creation of environments where large numbers of pixel agents in a gridworld interact in battles or other competitive scenarios.
 - <https://github.com/salesforce/ai-economist> This repo contains an implementation of Foundation, a framework for flexible, modular, and composable environments that **model socio-economic behaviors and dynamics in a society with both agents and governments.**
- **General LLM resources**
 - [filipecalegario/awesome-generative-ai](#): A curated list of Generative AI resources, which may include tools and models related to Generative Agents.
 - [EmbraceAGI/Awesome-AGI](#): A curated list of awesome AGI (Artificial General Intelligence) frameworks, software, and resources, including Generative Agents.
 - <https://github.com/tigerneil/awesome-deep-rl> Reinforcement learning is the fundamental framework for building AGI. Therefore we share important contributions within this awesome drl project.
 - [wel3kxial/AIGC_Resources](#): This repository gathers most useful tools, resources, and references in the field of Generative AI and Computational Creativity.
 - [imaurer/awesome-decentralized-llm](#): A collection of LLM (Large Language Models) resources that can be used to build products, including references to Generative Agents.
 - [gabriben/awesome-generative-information-retrieval](#): A curated list of resources on generative information retrieval, which may include tools and models related to Generative Agents.
 - <https://github.com/hwchase17/langchain> Building applications with LLMs through composability
 - <https://github.com/Mooler0410/LLMsPracticalGuide> A curated (still actively updated) list of practical guide resources of LLMs. It's based on our survey paper: [Harnessing the Power of LLMs in Practice: A Survey on ChatGPT and Beyond](#). We also build an evolutionary tree of modern Large Language Models (LLMs) to trace the development of language models in recent years and highlights some of the most well-known models.

- <https://github.com/microsoft/LMOps> LMOps is a research initiative on fundamental research and technology for building AI products w/ foundation models, especially on the general technology for enabling AI capabilities w/ LLMs and Generative AI models.

More AI

@Peter D Tuddenham @George Mobus @Rob Young @Dave Douglass I added this page tonight 6-5-2024

Context:

- DAF was an invited speaker on a panel on Large Language Models (LLM), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and synthetic intelligence more broadly.
- The conference was in-person in Berlin, Germany, in the first week of June 2024: [European Identity and Cloud Conference 2024](#).
- DAF joined remotely (session held at 2am PT) for a panel discussion with [Trent McConaghy](#) and [Mihaela Ulmer](#) (moderated by Scott David).
- In preparation/anticipation for the session, Scott sent around 11 questions about LLM and personal/organizational dimensions of AI.
- Below, for the interested, I present my bulletpoint responses to these questions. They were drafted as final statements or to be recited during the panel, rather to spark conversations & bring in more perspectives.

Relevance:

- You may be curious to learn more about what some people are asking & thinking about modern intelligence, from theory and practice perspectives.
- If you see anywhere you would like to comment, feel free to do so.
 - You can add another column entirely if you want to take a crack at all 11 questions, or add more questions as rows.
- I share it here because beyond the relevance of the topics, the question-catalyzed approach to inquiry across scales is a fundamental practice. As I look forward to June 2024 and beyond, I am thinking about: [learning more about the fractal questions & inquiries people are investigating](#) (the Epistemics of run-time Education systems) and [working to develop a science and art of knowledge systems](#) (the Pragmatics of design-time Engineering for aforementioned Education systems).
 - Any appropriate share, is better than unshared (with a broad semantic understanding of “appropriate” if & where syntactic and procedural customs are respected).
 - Sharing with context adds meaning. Describing the path of your inquiry, is like viewing the movie of it, and/or interviewing the director. However (little or much) you feel like you are honestly and authentically sharing, actually communicates across levels.

D

EIC 2024

Q Question

DAF Text

Q1	<p>In light of the advancements in AI, particularly with LLMs, does the concept of intelligence really change when applied to machines versus humans?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can one provide a satisfying finite response to this classic infinite question, about the semantics of “i change”? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Certainly unique contemporary factors must be taken into account: changes over the last decades in and prevalence of digital interactions (what Scott calls “the fifth-order consequences of Moore’s law”, terms of algorithm-driven centralized social media platforms, and the availability of multi-modal, or tra like ChatGPT. ◦ And I believe that framings and perspectives from across time can help us with sense-making and de Failure to integrate our learnings and anticipations across timescales, could result in loss of the forest wayfinding, or even loss of the forest entirely through ecosystem deterioration caused by failures of c • So, “does the concept of intelligence really change when applied to machines versus humans?”. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Short answer: Yes, the semantics, pragmatics, dynamics, and context of intelligence all are in change Interactivity, and Change are fundamental features of intelligence found across scales and systems. ◦ Another way to say this is: Yes, in practice, intelligence really does change in practice. And, in princip change in principle. • This is how we always already find ourselves, in what Bucky Fuller called “Critical Path”: steering an ongoi grappling with the specifics of pasts and futures, on the razor’s edge of survival across scales.
Q2	<p>In your opinion, How do we balance engineered intelligence systems in terms of innovation with responsibility?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The question is excellent and has been framed artfully. The question is not about some exclusive balance Innovation and Responsibility as if on a scales of justice or zero-sum allocation game. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Rather the questions asks how “we balance engineered intelligence systems”, in terms of Innovation \ considering each <i>with</i> (not opposed to) each other, and thinking about balancing the system so that t Perspectives, Innovation and Responsibilities are outcomes or Properties of certain engineered Proc more like the design-, build-, and run-time balancing of a ship or plane which needs to operate safely flung planet. • The proximate question to address organizationally becomes: How do we Design and Support our intellige ecosystem of shared intelligence processes, such that in Deployment they are able to steer and be steere • A broader question raised is: how can we come to understand the technical engineering of synthetic intell “innovation WITH responsibility”, implying our vision and capacity to communicate the total situation acros Operating Legal Technical Social)? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ In this area recently we have developed an open source Requirements Engineering inter-framework c core, as already utilized earlier in this response, P3IF consists of analyzing system requirements in ter Properties as viewed from defined Perspectives. The work was released as research article in Octob several organizational settings & being scoped for further technical development.
Q3	<p>What are some of the most promising areas of collaboration where the synthesis of AI and human intelligence can lead to breakthroughs?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only speaking here to the framing of “collaboration as interface” — two promising areas are related to eva modeling. • Development of capacities, norms, evaluations, and expectations for interfaces (ranging from the material arbitrary). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ AI benchmarking tests, which are really Phenotyping assays, span from the Syntactic on through now (Action models). Now, or perhaps plus or minus a few years depending on your threshold, these syntt reaching agentic status according to any reasonable application of the intentional stance. So it is a qu What could and should collaboration look like, within and across projects? • New approaches are facilitating design of custom compositional systems: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ For organizational design, modeling, and simulation, emerging approaches today include applied cate tokenomics, and systems engineering. I feel that in the coming years, these approaches and/or their f develop in applicability and enable new organizational phenotypes which will exist in new and differer multiscale thermo-evolutionary grounding connects the particulars of the collaboration to first princip ◦ Here there is an analogy to the Linnaean binomial nomenclature for genus and species. What is gener questions and learnings are transferable across BOLTS domains understood as Maps (of history)/pres towards a synthesis of science, engineering, and metagovernance in service of organizational ecolog incipiently forage towards.

Q4	In what ways are current forms of AI the same as or different than other "intelligent" systems?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • About the similarities and differences between "current forms of AI" and other "intelligent" systems... • Same: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Bound and enabled by materiality, like any body. And so subject to the same kinds of regularities of n perspectival limitations. • Different <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ "Current forms of AI" are Things that largely operate on digital chips as virtualized processes — this is environment and thermo-informational coupling than the autopoiesis associated with things that do h ants. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ However — Will this definition/distinction blur, or maybe it already has blurred in fractal way, in the human techno-cyber phenotype, as it gains operational enclosure over bodies and their computa ▪ What blurred or bright lines might exist, in the dynamic distributed physiology of information and synthetic intelligence, as the "edge" and how it maps itself comes to include itself in its mapping, On Exactitude in Science?"
Q5	What are the patterns of challenges when 2 different intelligent systems interact?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One way to approach this question, let's call it Scenario A, is getting one or each person's perspective on t having an auxiliary discussion about which responses should be paid attention to, converging down to a fi then used for recognition or used to guide decisions. A potential limitation here is that in the winnowing ar described patterns reflect only a sub-set of the group's total input, resulting in a sub-optimal artefact whic application relevance. • In Scenario B we hear "patterns of challenge" and contextualize this amidst other patterns, using a Pattern continuous reporting and provide continuing function, as new (types of) challenge patterns are asserted. . pattern languages and extensions in a calm and deliberate way, as interaction challenges keep rolling in (" something") and contextual remedies are applied in practice and perhaps only later understood. This rela ATLAS: A Question Oriented Approach to the Use of Pattern Languages in Knowledge Management".
Q6	Does the "order" created by the application of one form of intelligence necessarily create disorder in other neighboring forms?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Order is perspectival — it depends on the active interpretant. For example see Bongard & Levin 2022 "The Biological Systems as Evolved, Overloaded, Multi-scale Machines". In this Polycomputing view, the asse understood as agent-specific and only by subjective relationship. For example, a given input to a given ob noise on certain symbolic measures; in this situation the observer could not tell whether this is actually a r encrypted communication which only appears as noise to the unaware viewer. • Different concepts, mechanisms, and resulting patterns of Order and Randomness are in play with differer pseudorandom number, analog randomness, nuclear, quantum, biological). In a world of open-endedness in response to the original question, I do not believe that much more than "it depends" can be said.
Q7	What are helpful and practical framings for regular people to apply when dealing with AI and AGI systems?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ask, what/why/when does it matter or not, if I am interacting with a human? E.g. are we seeking from a pe Care, Knowledge, or Accountability, ...? Where and why do we seek, require, or disfavor (specific kinds of) intelligences? • Document your traces & trails — amidst awareness that our digital niche modifications will be used & leve in likely quite complex ways over the years to come. • Build up your practical and conceptual understanding of the kind of system you are working with. For exar nearby input points will have linearly-nearby outputs. AI systems, as all things do, have characteristic regu more nuanced (e.g. related to the neighborhood in semantic space). Hopefully better tools for understand outside of our evolutionary prior set, will develop • Where real consequences can occur from interacting with AI (including chains of thought stimulated by yc scaffold/setting and organizational processes are appropriate for what consequences may arise.
Q8	How do current forms of "intelligent" systems relate to historical forms? In what ways are they different?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Similar question to Q4.
Q9	What are the paradigms and framings of intelligent systems that you find helpful for your understanding when you read about new advancements in AI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active Inference meeting at the junction of the low road (bottom-up model construction) and high road (tc ecosystems). • Cognitive Security = Cognitive Science + Security Mindset-Posture • Embodied & Mortal Computing: Technological Approach to Mind Everywhere (TAME), Quantum Free Ener

Q10	What are 3 things that folks should remember when they are interacting with AI and other intelligent systems?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"><li data-bbox="462 115 1537 147">1. Focus on intention as coordinating an assemblage of diverse intelligences such as affective, temporal-spa<li data-bbox="462 147 1537 178">2. Digital and Cognitive systems are serious and also can be fun.<li data-bbox="462 178 1537 262">3. Just because there is rhetorical and symbolic relevance to lists with 3 members, doesn't mean that such li could be said
Q11	Can you share your positive imagery for the future state of human information systems in the year 2040 (15 years in the future)?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"><li data-bbox="462 294 1537 388">• I imagine ecosystems of positive affect distributions, like glimmering stars studded in tapestries of Bayesian internal states, doing as well as they expected or possibly even better, on most if not all of the critical func buffering, and message passing with each other.

What is the relevance of Gordon Pask's conversation theory today?

Gordon Pask's conversation theory was a pioneering contribution to the field of cybernetics, and it continues to be relevant today in a number of ways. Pask's work focused on the role of communication and interaction in complex systems, and he developed a framework for understanding how these systems evolve over time through a process of exchange and feedback.

One of the key insights of Pask's conversation theory is that **communication and interaction are essential for the emergence of intelligence and adaptability in complex systems**. This idea has been influential in fields such as artificial intelligence, where researchers are interested in building systems that can learn and adapt to changing environments. Pask's work has also inspired research on the role of communication and interaction in social and biological systems, and it continues to be an important influence in the study of complex systems.

Another aspect of Pask's conversation theory that remains relevant today is his **emphasis on the importance of context and perspective in communication**. Pask argued that the meaning of a message is determined not only by its content, but also by the context in which it is received and the perspective of the recipient. This idea has implications for fields such as communication studies and psychology, where researchers are interested in understanding how people interpret and respond to messages in different contexts.

Overall, Gordon Pask's conversation theory continues to be **relevant today as a framework for understanding the role of communication and interaction in complex systems**. Its insights and ideas continue to inspire research and advancements in a range of fields.

How would Gordon Pask implement a modern Knowledge Management System?

It is difficult to say exactly how Gordon Pask would implement a modern Knowledge Management System, as he is no longer alive and I am not able to access information about his specific views or plans. However, based on his work on conversation theory and his emphasis on the role of communication and interaction in complex systems, I can offer some possible insights into how Pask might approach the design and implementation of a Knowledge Management System.

1. **First, Pask would likely place a strong emphasis on the role of communication and interaction in a Knowledge Management System.** He would likely view the system as a network of conversations and exchanges, in which knowledge is shared, refined, and updated through a process of feedback and iteration. This would require the system to be designed in a way that supports and encourages communication and collaboration among its users.
2. **Second, Pask would likely focus on the context and perspective of the users of the Knowledge Management System.** He would recognize that the meaning and value of knowledge depends on the context in which it is used, and he would design the system to allow users to access and share knowledge in a way that is tailored to their specific needs and goals. This would require the system to be flexible and adaptable, and to provide tools and features that allow users to filter, organize, and present knowledge in a way that is meaningful to them.
3. **Third, Pask would likely be interested in the dynamics and evolution of the Knowledge Management System over time.** He would recognize that the system is not a static collection of knowledge, but rather a constantly changing network of conversations and interactions. He would design the system to support the growth and development of knowledge over time, and to provide mechanisms for tracking and analyzing the evolution of knowledge within the system. This would require the system to be able to capture and analyze data on the usage and impact of knowledge, and to provide tools and features that allow users to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of the system.

Overall, Gordon Pask's approach to the design and implementation of a Knowledge Management System would be based on his ideas about **communication, interaction, context, and evolution**. He would likely focus on building a system that is **dynamic, adaptable, and supportive of collaboration and communication** among its users.

Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository

Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository is an archiving effort led by Rob Young relating to ISSS and various other communities.

SCA Systems Community Repository v1p0-ISSS.pdf

- Systems Community Alliance (SCA)

What do I mean by 'Systems Community'?

*Systems Community in blue cloud, engaging with the (example) societal Covid activities

An eye on the future:

- Systems Community Alliance (SCA)
 - A collaborative network
 - A long term plan
 - (Neutral) Web domain eg.: SystemsCommunityAlliance.net (Systems Community Alliance, Network)
 - Alliance -33 at the level of infrastructure, not necessarily at level of leadership
 - A network of knowledge custodians in the community eg. ISSS, ISR, archives, individuals
 - Infrastructure (cf. roads, ports etc) eg:
 - Registers
 - Repository
 - Project support
 - News and events
 - Technical help
 - Coordination
 - Community building

ie. Any organisations/persons/etc who believes in 'The Systems Approach'

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- Repository

What do I mean by Repository?

- Exemplars

- Philosophers Index : <https://philindex.org/>
- Philosophy Documentation Centre : <https://www.pdcnet.org/>
- American Psychology Association PsycNet : <https://www.apa.org/pubs/databases/psycnet>
- JSTOR : <https://www.jstor.org/>
- Medline : https://www.nlm.nih.gov/medline/medline_overview.html
- Mendeley : <https://www.mendeley.com/>

Different taglines and ways that the current offerings listed here (Philosophers Index, PsycNet, JSTOR, Medline, Mendeley, etc.

What do I mean by Repository?

- Components

REGISTRIES (list of all...)

- Systems Organizations
- Systems Analysis
- Systems Events
- Systems Courses

BIBLIOGRAPHIC DATABASE

- Journals
- Books (summaries of articles)
- Books
- Websites

— Open, and/or access, where possible

— Links to access, from other stakeholders

— Capable to deliver full content on behalf of their partner

COLLECTIONS

- By subject matter
- For example, ISSS Collections:

Example: ISSS Collections:

- General Systems Yearbook (32 vols, 1956-1988)
- General Systems Bulletin (75, 1969-2013)
- Conference Proceedings (1963-1982)
- Conference Proceedings (1983-1992)
- Minor Symposia/ Workshops (2013)
- Ray B. Stammers Memorial Lectures (14, 1974-2019)
- Oranella Memorial Lectures
- ISSS Newsletter (1922-)
- ISSS Minutes
- ISSS Books
- ISSS Reports
- ISSS Projects (P-Index, Books, Lectures, SIGS, Systems Events, World of Systems)
- ISSS Journals (SR, BS, 1980)

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Different repository features

Ongoing steps (NOV #6 November 17, 2022)

Next steps: I will continue to...

- ... look for a suitable platform: Dspace; Dspace-CRIS, Digital Asset Management, Bibliographic software; Airtable; Plugin platforms (eg Wordpress)?
 - develop a Requirements Specification?
- ... catalogue content: See examples: (i) The Psyche Sciences (approximately 16 lists of Systems Resources, in spreadsheet format, prepared for Bibliographic insert); (ii) ISSS Yearbooks (32 yearbooks, 587 articles, in spreadsheet format).
 - Could increase the priority of cataloguing ISSS content/ working with ISSS? (would need to work with an ISSS-representative/s)
- ... saving legacy collections and work: For example: Books; UKSS Journal Systemist; Len Troncale work

Open for... partners/ collaborators/ enthusiasts/ lovers of history/ builders.

Contact: Rob Young: ryoung@wwwweb.org

Cambridge, England. LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/ryoung9/>

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SCA Systems Community Repository

6

Example of spreadsheets of historical materials

#	Year	Title	Presenter	Profession
1	1974	In memory of Ludwig von Bertalanffy's contribution to psychiatry	Ray R. Grinker Sr.	neurologist and psychiatrist
2	1975	Second annual Ludwig von Bertalanffy Memorial Lecture	James G. Miller	biologist
3	1976	General systems theory: A bridge between two cultures. Third annual Ludwig von Bertalanffy Memorial Lecture	Azotol Rapoport	mathematical psychologist
4	1977	The universe as a general system. Fourth annual Ludwig von Bertalanffy Memorial Lecture	Kenneth E. Boulding	economist
5	1978	Frontiers and Problems in the Evolution of Human Systems: An Anamorphic, Humanistic, Autopoietic Model	William Gray	
6	1979	Old Friends and New Trends in Systems Research. Sixth annual Ludwig von Bertalanffy Memorial Lecture	Robert Rosen	theoretical biologist
7	1980	The Structure Of Autonomy: Boundary in Living Groups	James E. Durkin	psychotherapist?

Discussion and notes.

- Contribution to the field and community.
- Structure, content, continuity, governance & metagovernance, continued management.
- How can the ISSS help / be involved?
- We can continue a dialogue, synchronizing/ coordinating/ allying with our group & others
- @Peter R recommends to start a ISSS. To coordinate, host, record, facilitate.
- Ongoing digital scholarship and Overview in different groups.
 - ISSS
 - Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository presented here
 - Cybernetics Society
 - Active Inference Institute
 - ...
 - Different organizational
 - “collections” (series of types of outcomes like symposium, papers).
- IFSR arising as a reaction.
- Coordination process, building networked, responsible and ethical directions.
- Building a professional approach, even if only to take on larger/faster/better projects
- Knowledge Management Archipelago

- <https://zenodo.org/record/5034809>
- Different aspects of 'knowledge management'
 - Technology (Computation)
 - Ontological
 - Cultural, Social, Narrative, etc.
- Network of custodians of systems information
 - In this meeting were exploring [FedWiki](#)
 - Multiple people and attempts.
 - Why failing? Can be compiled and analyzed.
 - Also can ask different people.
 - English, also there are other languages with relevant systems literature.
 - Unity and Unifying Science, and all bodies of knowledge about how things are around us, philosophy, science, theological, cultural. Different paradigms.
 - Michael and Janet Singers, involved in the Ontology meetings
 - [Active Inference Ontology](#)
 - Presidential theme — One Stop Shop.
- What is the Systems Community?

ISSS @ SCA

- Fundamentals of storage
 - Assessment & Documentation of the ISSS Catalog (@Rob)
 - ISSS internal repository and breadth of knowledge (and less tangible, general systems theory).
 - Accessibility and Humanness — Involves searching via Catalog/Index (library model).
 - Activities — Many possible projects.
 - Ingress and storage of materials
 - Annotation, Tagging, Marking, Linking
- Connect with Fundamentals of storage (interoperability)
- [Systems Community Alliance \(SCA\) Repository](#)
 - Previously a presentation was made at this meeting.
 - End of 2022 — @Rob provided a spreadsheet with list of assets.
 - Framing — seeing this as a year's trial.
 - Focus: Delivering content to who is responsive.
 - Partnership — Whatever the ISSS finds useful, as content. Then we can work together and plan it.
 - Soon — will be providing updated spreadsheet.
 - We can give feedback on staging of different works.
 - Collections are ongoing (as long as content production continues). There is just a large backlog.
 - Total storage
 - Currently the SCA is only reference/pointer to the organization's storage.
 - [Single unified ISSS storage](#)
 - Rob's SCA schema
 - **Organization** (unique entity, could be ISSS or another, or a person).
 - **Collections** (grouped under a theme, like Yearbooks, Proceedings, Bulletins, Mini-Symposium, Newsletter)
 - **Content itself** — identified by standard metadata by type.
 - Registers (simple lists — e.g. Systems Blogs, other archives)
 - Broad plans.
 - 1. Continuing content, along lines of ISSS Archive
 - Do we have all Collections at ISSS?
 - Within Collection — do we have all Content metadata?
 - Basic Document details — Collection, Title, Authors, Year.
 - Coverage of Entities: Collections, Authors
 - Collections: Proceedings and Conferences, Newsletters, General Systems Yearbooks.
 - Full text where possible (including information on e.g. IP / availability).
 - Understanding of where the coverage is total vs. incomplete.
 - Conversion to a format, and/or annotation, to allow syntactic or semantic search.
 - 2. Developing a website, to have go-to place for accessing what SCA is delivering.

Inventory across Collections (D221220A)

Metadata

Column 1	Column 2
Base file	SCA-ISSS-Collections-B221220.xlsx
Release Process	SCA-SP-RP-Subset-1
Distribution ID	SCA-ISSS-Collections-D221220A
Release Fil	SCA-ISSS-Collections-D221220A.xlsx
SCA Permalink Information Page	https://systemscommunityalliance.net/COL/SCA-ISSS-Collections

📎 SCA-ISSS-Collections-D221221A.xlsx

ISSS Collections

Collection	Description	Coda table
About, The ISSS	"The International Society for the Systems Sciences (ISSS) is among the first and oldest organizations devoted to interdisciplinary inquiry into the nature of complex systems"	
The ISSS Collections	The following ISSS Collections are indexed in this SCA Collections Spreadsheet:	
Conferences+ (CP)	Conferences + Proceedings: A list of the Annual conferences which have taken place since 1954, plus some additional Regional Conferences. Also, details on Proceedings, where available. (Conference Year; Theme; Venue; Dates; Proceedings). Selected proceedings available on the ISSS website, for members.	Confere
Gen Sys Yearbooks (GSY)	General System Yearbooks: Flagship publication of the ISSS, 32 Yearbooks from 1956-1989 (I-XXXII). Then a Special Issue in the Journal : 'Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue', published from 1998, to the present. Selected copies available on the ISSS website, for members.	General (Table)
Gen Sys Bulletins (GSB)	General System Bulletins: Bulletin newsletter, published from 1969 - 2013 (76 issues, usually 2 to 3 issues per year), with news, events and articles from the Systems Movement, and the Society. Available on the ISSS website, for members.	General (Table)
Newsletter 1981 (NL1981)	(Missing) SYSTEM TRENDS newsletter, from the Minnesota Chapter of the SGSR. Mentioned in: General Systems Bulletin	
Newsletter 2021 (NL2021)	2021+ Newsletters started by Editor: Roelien Goede (President ISSS, 2022-23)	
Reports (RPTS):	Various digitised Reports published by the ISSS, and it's members. Available on the ISSS website, for members.	

Books (BKS):	Various digitised Books published by the ISSS, and it's members. Available on the ISSS website, for members.
Videos - Mini-Symposiums (VIDMS):	A series of online mini-symposiums recordings/presentations, run yearly from 2018 onwards. Available on the ISSS website, for members.
Videos (VIDS)	Historic and current videos from the Systems Movement e.g. Dr James Miller interviewing Systems Luminaries; and on Living Systems Theory.
Presidents (PRES)	List of ISSS Presidents, from 1957, onwards.
Student Awards (SAWD)	Lists of Student award winners of: 1. Sir Geoffrey Vickers Award; 2. Anatol Rapoport Award; 3. Margaret Mead Award
LvB Memorial Lectures (MLMVB)	List of the Ludwig von Bertalanffy Memorial Lectures, with publication details.

Conferences+

Conferences+ (Table)

ISSS Meeting#	Year	Conference Title/Theme	Main Conf	Org - Society Name	SubOrg	ISSS Hist
-3	1954	(organizational meeting, in AAAS)	Annual	SAGST Society for the Advancement of General Systems Theory		1954 - meeting,
-2	1955	Entropy; (founding meetings and papers)	Annual	SAGST Society for the Advancement of General Systems Theory		1955 - and paper GA Entr
-1	1956	Systems under stress; (founding meeting as chapter in AAAS)	Annual	SAGST Society for the Advancement of General Systems Theory		1956 - meeting ; New York
1	1957	Organization for Humans, Cells, and Artifacts	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research		1957 1 AAAS(3rd Indianapolis Humans,
2	1958	Population Dynamics	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research		1958 2 AAAS(4th Populatic
3	1959	The Synthesis of Organization	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research		1959 3 AAAS(5th Synthesi:
4	1960	The Boundaries of Systems	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research		1960 4 AAAS(6th Boundari
5	1961	The Teaching of Systems Thinking	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research		1961 5 AAAS(7th Teaching
6	1962	Indicators of integration in a multi-state system	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research		1962 6 AAAS(8th
7	1963	General Systems and the Two Cultures	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research		1963 7 AAAS(9th General 9
8	1964	Positive Feedback in General Systems	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research		1964 8 AAAS(10 Quebec

9	1965	(various themes)	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research		1965 9 AAAS(11t various tl
10	1966	(various themes, particularly Symbolism)	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research		1966 1 AAAS(12 (various t Symbolis
11	1967	(various themes)	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research		1967 1 AAAS(13 themes)
12	1968	Man in Systems	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research		1968 1 AAAS (14 Systems
13	1969	(various themes)	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research		1969 1 AAAS(15 (various t
14	1970	World Cities of the Future	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research		1970 1 AAAS(16 Cities of
15	1971	The World System	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research		1971 1 AAAS U World Sy
16	1972		Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	Mid-Atlantic	1972 1 Washingt
17	1973		Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	Mid-Atlantic	1973 1 The Ame DC
NE?	1973	annual meeting at CUNY in New York City		SGSR Society for General Systems Research	REGION NorthEast Division	
18	1974		Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research		1974 1 AAAS U
	1974					Mentione (1976). In Bertalanf Behavior. https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-0374(76)90005-5

19	1975	Systems Thinking and the Quality of Life	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	North American	
SE01	1975	Man and his Artifacts: Quo Vadis?		SGSR Society for General Systems Research	REGION Southeastern	
MARD03	1975	Interdisciplinary Aspects of General Systems Theory		SGSR Society for General Systems Research	REGION Middle Atlantic Regional Division	1975 1 USA Bo Aspects
FW	1975			SGSR Society for General Systems Research	REGION Far West	
20	1976	General Systems Theorizing : An Assessment and Prospects for the Future	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	North American	1976 2 Systems and Pros
SE02	1976	GST Applications: A Genesis		SGSR Society for General Systems Research	REGION Southeastern	
21	1977	The General Systems Paradigm: Science of Change and Change of Science	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	North American	RY: ISSS: Denver, C USA De and Char

SE03	1977 (various)			SGSR Society for General Systems Research	REGION Southeastern	
22	1978	Avoiding Social Catastrophes and Maximizing Social Opportunities: The General Systems Challenge	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	North American	1978 2 Washingt Catastroj Opportur
SE04	1978	Systems in Sociocultural Development		SGSR Society for General Systems Research	REGION Southeastern	
23	1979	General Systems Research: A Science, A Methodology, A Technology	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	North American	1979 2 Houston, 25th Silv 1954 fou Internatic London
SE05	1979	Environmental Management: the systems perspective		SGSR Society for General Systems Research	REGION Southeastern	
INT01(London)	1979	Improving the Human Condition: Quality and Stability in Social Systems		SGSR Society for General Systems Research	INTERNATIONAL London	25th Silv 1954 fou Internatic London

24	1980	Systems Science and Science	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	North American	1980 2 Francisco Science
SE06	1980	(various): (1) The Computer, the Future, and Education (2) The Developing World and the New World Economic Order (3) Community, State, and Regional Planning: Current Status and Future Trends (4) Practical Applications of Forecasting in Planning		SGSR Society for General Systems Research	REGION Southeastern	
25	1981	General Systems Research and Design: Precursors and Futures	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	North American	1981 2 Canada
SE10?	1981	Paradigms in Changing Times		SGSR Society for General Systems Research	REGION Southeastern	
26	1982	A General Survey of Systems Methodology	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research		1982 2 Washingt Systems
SE?	1982	Understanding and Managing Mature Systems		SGSR Society for General Systems Research	REGION Southeastern	

27	1983	The Relationship Between Major World Problems and Systems Learning	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	1983 2 Relations Problems
28	1984	Systems Methodologies, Isomorphies and Applications	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	1984 2
29	1985	Systems inquiring	Annual	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	1985 2
30	1986	Mental Images, Values, & Reality	Annual	ISGSR International Society for General Systems Research	1986 3
31	1987	Problems of Constancy and Change, the Complementarity of Systems Approaches to Complexity	Annual	ISGSR International Society for General Systems Research	1987 3
32	1988	Systematic Redesign of 22 Systems	Annual	ISGSR International Society for General Systems Research	1988 3
33	1989	Systems Modelling As A Learning Tool : 33rd Annual Meeting, Edinburgh, Scotland, 2-7 July, 1989	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	1989 3 Scotland

34	1990	Towards a Just Society for Future Generations. Thirty-Fourth Annual Meeting, Portland, Oregon, July 8-13, 1990	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	1990 3
35	1991	Systems Science in the 21st Century: Integrating the New Science of Complexity in Service of Humans and their Environment	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	1991 3
36	1992	General Systems Approaches to Alternative Economics and Values	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	1992 3
37	1993	Ethical Management of Science as a System	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	1993 3 NSW
38	1994	New Systems Thinking and Action for a New Century	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	1994 3 Grove, C.
39	1995	Systems Thinking, Government Policy and Decision Making	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	1995 3

40	1996	Sustainable Peace in the World System, and the Next Evolution of Human Consciousness	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	1996 4 Louisville (Sept)
41	1997	Systems Thinking, Globalization of Knowledge, and Communitarian Ethics	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	1997 4
42	1998	Atlanta 1998: The 42nd Annual Meeting of the International Society for the Systems Sciences	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	1998 4
43	1999	Humanity, Science, Technology: The Systemic Foundations Of The Information Age : Asilomar 1999: The 43rd Annual Meeting of the International Society for the Systems Sciences	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	1999 4 Grove, C,
44	2000	A World Congress of the Systems Sciences for the Millennial Year : Understanding Complexity: The Systems Sciences in the New Millennium	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	2000 4
45	2001	Systems Science in the Service of Humanity : Asilomar 2001: The 45th Annual Meeting of the International Society for the Systems Sciences	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	2001 4 Grove, C, Service c
46	2002	Systems Thinking : Managing Complexity and Change : Shanghai 2002: The 46th Annual Meeting of the International Society for the Systems Sciences	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	2002 4
47	2003	Conscious Evolution Of Humanity: Using Systems Thinking To Construct Agoras Of The Global Village : Crete 2003: The 47th Annual Meeting of the International Society for the Systems Sciences	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	2003 4 (Hersonik
48	2004	Asilomar 2004: The 48th Annual Meeting of the International Society for the Systems Sciences	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	2004 4 Grove, C,

49	2005	The Potential Impacts of Systemics on Society. 49th Annual Meeting of the International Society for the Systems Sciences 2005 (ISSS 2005) : Proceedings of a meeting held 1-5 July 2005, Cancun, Mexico.	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	2005 4
50	2006	Complexity, Democracy, and Sustainability : Sonoma 2006: The 50th Annual Meeting of the International Society for the Systems Sciences	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	2006 5 Park, CA)
51	2007	Integrated Systems Sciences: Systems Thinking, Modelling and Practice : The 51st Annual Meeting of the ISSS was held August 5-10, 2007 in Tokyo	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	2007 5
52	2008	Systems that Make a Difference : 52nd Annual Conference of the International Society for the Systems Sciences 2008	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	2008 5
53	2009	Making Liveable, Sustainable Systems Unremarkable : 53rd Annual Conference of the International Society for the Systems Sciences 2009	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	2009 5

54	2010	Governance for a Resilient Planet : 54th Annual Conference of the International Society for the Systems Sciences 2010	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	2010 5
55	2011	All together now – working across disciplines: People, principles and practice : 55th Meeting of the International Society for the Systems Sciences, joining with KSS2011 International Symposium for Knowledge and Systems Sciences	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	2011 5
56	2012	Service Systems, Natural Systems : 56th Annual Meeting of the International Society for the Systems Sciences 2012 (ISSS 2012): Service Systems, Natural Systems	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	2012 5
57	2013	Curating the Conditions for a Thrivable Planet: Systemic Leverage Points for Emerging a Global Eco- Civilization : 57th Annual Meeting of the International Society for the Systems Sciences (ISSS 2013): Curating the Conditions for a Thrivable Planet	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	2013 5
58	2014	58th Annual Meeting of the International Society for the Systems Sciences (ISSS 2014)	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	2014 5

59	2015	Governing the Anthropocene: the greatest challenge for systems thinking in practice? : 59th Annual Meeting of the International Society for the Systems Sciences (ISSS 2015)	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	2015 5
60	2016	Realizing Sustainable Futures in Socio-Ecological Systems : 60th Annual Meeting of the International Society for the Systems Sciences (ISSS 2016)	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	2016 6
61	2017	From Science to Systemic Solutions - Systems Thinking for Everyone : 61st Annual Meeting of the International Society for the Systems Sciences (ISSS 2017)	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	2017 6
62	2018	Innovation and Optimization in Nature and Design : 62nd Annual Meeting of the International Society for the Systems Sciences (ISSS 2018)	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	2018 6
63	2019	Nature's Enduring Patterns: A Path to Systems Literacy : 63rd Annual Conference of the ISSS	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	2019 6
64	2020	ISSS2020 Stellenbosch (near Cape Town), South Africa - Cancelled due to COVID-19	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	2020 6
65	2021	The Art and Science of the Impossible: The Human Experience	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	

66	2022	Advances in Systems Sciences and Systems Practice	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	—
67	2023	Systems Practice for Professions	Annual	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	—

General Systems Yearbook (GSY)

General Systems Yearbook (GSY) (Table)

Seq#	Seq#R	Title	Title Year	Editors	Publisher	Rec Last Upc
1	I	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for the Advancement of General Systems Theory, Volume I, 1956	1956	Ludwig von Bertalanffy and Anatol Rapoport	SAGST Society for the Advancement of General Systems Theory	30-Nov-22
2	II	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume II, 1957	1957	Ludwig von Bertalanffy and Anatol Rapoport	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
3	III	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume III, 1958	1958	Ludwig von Bertalanffy and Anatol Rapoport	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
4	IV	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume IV, 1959	1959	Ludwig von Bertalanffy and Anatol Rapoport	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
5	V	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume V, 1960	1960	Ludwig von Bertalanffy and Anatol Rapoport	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
6	VI	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume VI, 1961	1961	Anatol Rapoport Ludwig von Bertalanffy and Richard L. Meier	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
7	VII	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume VII, 1962	1962	Ludwig von Bertalanffy and Anatol Rapoport	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
8	VIII	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume VIII, 1963	1963	Ludwig von Bertalanffy and Anatol Rapoport	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
9	IX	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume IX, 1964	1964	Ludwig von Bertalanffy and Anatol Rapoport	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
10	X	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume X, 1965	1965	Ludwig von Bertalanffy and Anatol Rapoport	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
11	XI	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume XI, 1966	1966	Ludwig von Bertalanffy and Anatol Rapoport	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
12	XII	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume XII, 1967	1967	Ludwig von Bertalanffy and Anatol Rapoport	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22

13	XIII	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume XIII, 1968	1968	Ludwig von Bertalanffy Anatol Rapoport and Richard L. Meier	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
14	XIV	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume XIV, 1969	1969	Ludwig von Bertalanffy Anatol Rapoport and Richard L. Meier	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
15	XV	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume XV, 1970	1970	Ludwig von Bertalanffy and Anatol Rapoport	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
16	XVI	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume XVI, 1971	1971	Ludwig von Bertalanffy and Anatol Rapoport	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
17	XVII	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume XVII, 1972	1972	Ludwig von Bertalanffy and Anatol Rapoport	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
18	XVIII	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume XVIII, 1973	1973	Anatol Rapoport	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
19	XIX	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume XIX, 1974	1974	Anatol Rapoport	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
20	XX	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume XX, 1975	1975	Anatol Rapoport	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
21	XXI	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume XXI, 1976	1976	Anatol Rapoport	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
22	XXII	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume XXII, 1977	1977	Anatol Rapoport	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
23	XXIII	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume XXIII, 1978	1978	Kenneth Boulding and H. R. Porter	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
24	XXIV	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume XXIV, 1979	1979	Brian Gaines and Larry W. Dybala	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
25	XXV	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume XXV, 1980	1980	Rammohan K. Ragade	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
26	XXVI	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume XXVI, 1981	1981	Rammohan K. Ragade	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
27	XXVII	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume XXVII, 1982	1982	Rammohan K. Ragade	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22

28	XXVIII	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume XXVIII, 1983-84	1983-84	Rammohan K. Ragade	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
29	XXIX	General Systems, Yearbook of the Society for General Systems Research, Volume XXIX, 1985-86	1985-86	Rammohan K. Ragade	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
30	XXX	General Systems, Yearbook of the International Society for General Systems Research, Volume XXX, 1987	1987	John A. Dillon Jr.	ISGSR International Society for General Systems Research	30-Nov-22
31	XXXI	General Systems, Yearbook of the International Society for the Systems Sciences, Volume XXXI, 1988	1988	William J. Reckmeyer	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	30-Nov-22
32	XXXII	General Systems, Yearbook of the International Society for the Systems Sciences, Volume XXXII, 1989	1989	Howard T. Odum	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	30-Nov-22
33	SRBS1997	Special Issue: "General Systems" Yearbook of the International Society for the Systems Sciences 1990-1997	1990-1997		Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22
34	SRBS1998	Special Issue: "General Systems" Yearbook of the International Society for the Systems Sciences 1998	1998		Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22
35	SRBS1999	Special Issue: "General Systems" Yearbook of the International Society for the Systems Sciences 1999	1999		Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22
36	SRBS2000	Special Issue: "General Systems" Yearbook of the International Society for the Systems Sciences 2000	2000		Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22
37	SRBS2001	Special Issue: "General Systems" Yearbook of the International Society for the Systems Sciences 2001	2001		Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22
38	SRBS2002		2002		Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22

39	SRBS2003		2003	Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22
40	SRBS2004		2004	Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22
41	SRBS2005	Special Issue: ISSS Yearbook: The Potential Impacts of Systemics on Society	2005	Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22
42	SRBS2006	Special Issue: Complexity, Democracy and Sustainability: The 50th Annual Meeting of the ISSS	2006	Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22
43	SRBS2007	Special Issue: ISSS Yearbook	2007	Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22
44	SRBS2008	Special Issue: ISSS Yearbook	2008	Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22
45	SRBS2009	Special Issue: Livable Sustainable Systems	2009	Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22
46	SRBS2010	Special Issue: Governance in the Relative When	2010	Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22
47	SRBS2011	Special Issue: ISSS Yearbook	2011	Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22
48	SRBS2012	Special Issue: Service Systems, Natural Systems - Science in Synthesis	2012	Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22
49	SRBS2013		2013	Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22

50	SRBS2014	Special Issue: ISSS Yearbook: Learning Across Boundaries	2014		Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22
51	SRBS2015	Special Issue: Governing in the Anthropocene: Contributions from Systems Thinking in Practice?	2015		Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22
52	SRBS2016	Special Issue: Realizing Sustainable Futures in Socio-Ecological Systems	2016		Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22
53	SRBS2017	Special Issue: ISSS Yearbook: Systems Thinking for Everyone: Theory and Practice	2017		Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22
54	SRBS2018	Special Issue: ISSS Yearbook: Innovation and Optimization in Nature and Design	2018		Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22
55	SRBS2019	Special Issue: ISSS Yearbook: Nature's Enduring Patterns: A Path to Systems Literacy	2019	Roelien Goede	Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22
56	SRBS2020	Special Issue: ISSS Yearbook: Systemic Change Towards Sustainable Development: Innovative and Integrative Approaches	2020		Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22
57	SRBS2021	Special Issue: ISSS Yearbook: The Art and Science of the Impossible: The Human Experience	2021	Delia Pembrey MacNamara	Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Issue 5, Special Issue	30-Nov-22

General Systems Bulletin (GSB)

General Systems Bulletin (GSB) (Table)

Seq#	Title	Title Year	Publisher	Volume
1	General Systems Bulletin, Vol. I, No. I, December 1969	1969	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	1
2	General Systems Bulletin, Vol. II, No. I, March 1970	1970	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	2
3	General Systems Bulletin, Vol. II, No. II, June 1970	1970	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	2
4	General Systems Bulletin, Vol. III, No. III, December 1970	1970	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	2
5	General Systems Bulletin, Vol. III, No. 1, May 1971	1971	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	3
6	General Systems Bulletin, Vol. III, No. 2, December 1971	1971	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	3
7	General Systems Bulletin, Vol. IV, No. 1, April 1973	1973	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	4
8	General Systems Bulletin, Vol. IV, No. 2, September 1973	1973	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	4
9	General Systems Bulletin, Autumn 1974, Vol. V, No. 1	1974	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	5
10	General Systems Bulletin, Winter 1975, Vol. V, No. 2	1975	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	5
11	General Systems Bulletin, Spring-Summer 1975, Vol. V, No. 3	1975	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	5
12	General Systems Bulletin, Autumn 1975, Vol. VI, No. 1	1975	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	6
13	General Systems Bulletin, Winter 1976, Vol. VI, No. 2	1976	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	6
14	General Systems Bulletin, Spring-Summer 1976, Vol. VI, No. 3	1976	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	6
15	General Systems Bulletin, Autumn 1976, Vol. VII, No. 1	1976	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	7
16	General Systems Bulletin, Winter 1977, Vol. VII, No. 2	1977	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	7
17	General Systems Bulletin, Spring-Summer 1977, Vol. VII, No. 3	1977	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	7
18	General Systems Bulletin, Autumn 1977, Vol. VIII, No. 1	1977	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	8
19	General Systems Bulletin, Winter 1978, Vol. VIII, No. 2	1978	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	8
20	General Systems Bulletin, Spring-Summer 1978, Vol. VIII, No. 3	1978	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	8
21	General Systems Bulletin, Autumn 1978, Vol. IX, No. 1	1978	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	9
22	General Systems Bulletin, Winter 1979, Vol. IX, No. 2	1979	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	9
23	SYSTEMS RESEARCH MOVEMENT: Characteristics, Accomplishments, and Current Developments. General Systems Bulletin Special Issue, Summer 1979, Vol. IX, No. 3	1979	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	9
24	General Systems Bulletin, Autumn, 1979, Vol. X, No. 1	1979	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	10

25	General Systems Bulletin, Winter, 1980, Vol. X, No. 2	1980	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	10
26	General Systems Bulletin, Summer, 1980, Vol. X, No. 3	1980	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	10
27	General Systems Bulletin, Fall, 1980, Vol. XI, No. 1	1980	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	11
28	General Systems Bulletin, Winter, 1981, Vol. XI, No. 2	1981	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	11
29	General Systems Bulletin, Spring-Summer, 1981, Vol. XI, No. 3	1981	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	11
30	General Systems Bulletin, Fall, 1981, Vol. 12, No. 1	1981	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	12
31	General Systems Bulletin, Spring, 1982, Vol. XIII, No. 1	1982	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	13
32	General Systems Bulletin, Fall 1982, Vol. XIII, No. 2	1982	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	13
33	General Systems Bulletin, Spring 1983, Vol. XIV, No. 1	1983	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	14
34	General Systems Bulletin, Fall 1983, Vol. XIV, No. 2	1983	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	14
35	General Systems Bulletin, Winter 1984, Vol. XIV, No. 3	1984	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	14
36	General Systems Bulletin, Fall 1984, Vol. XV, No. 1	1984	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	15
37	General Systems Bulletin, Winter 1985, Vol. XV, No. 2	1985	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	15
38	General Systems Bulletin, Fall 1985, Vol. XVI, No. 1	1985	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	16
39	General Systems Bulletin, Winter, 1986, Vol. XVI, No. 2	1986	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	16
40	General Systems Bulletin, Fall-Winter, 1987, Vol. XVII, No. 1	1987	SGSR Society for General Systems Research	17
41	Double Issue: General Systems Bulletin, Spring, 1987, Vol. XVII, No. 2	1987	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	17
42	Double Issue: General Systems Bulletin, Fall-Winter, 1988, Vol. XVIII, No. 1	1988	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	18
43	The General Systems Bulletin, Vol. XIX, No. 1, Fall, 1989	1989	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	19
44	The General Systems Bulletin, Vol. XIX, No. 2, Spring, 1990	1990	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	19
45	General Systems Bulletin, Vol. XX, No. 1, Fall, 1990	1990	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	20
46	General Systems Bulletin, Spring, 1991, Vol. XX, No. 2	1991	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	20
47	General Systems Bulletin, Autumn, 1991, Vol. XXI, No. 1	1991	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	21
48	General Systems Bulletin, Spring, 1992, Vol. XXI, No. 2	1992	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	21
49	General Systems Bulletin, Autumn, 1992, Vol. XXII, No. 1	1992	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	22
50	Missing: General Systems Bulletin, 1993, Vol. XXII, No. 2	1993	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	22
51	Missing: General Systems Bulletin, 1993, Vol. XXIII, No. 1	1993	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	23

52	General Systems Bulletin, Vol. XXIII, No. 2, Summer, 1994	1994	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	23
53	General Systems Bulletin, Vol. XXIII, No. 3/4, Fall/Winter, 1994	1994	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	23
54	Missing: General Systems Bulletin, 1995, Vol. XXIV, No. 1-?	1995	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	24
55	General Systems Bulletin, Vol. XXV, No. 1, Spring, 1996	1996	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	25
56	General Systems Bulletin, Vol. XXV, No. 2, Summer, 1996	1996	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	25
57	General Systems Bulletin, Vol. XXV, No. 3, Fall, 1996	1996	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	25
58	General Systems Bulletin, Vol. XXV, No. 4, Winter, 1996	1996	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	25
59	General Systems Bulletin, Vol. XXVI, No. 1, Spring 1997	1997	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	26
60	General Systems Bulletin, Vol. XXVI, No. 2, Summer 1997	1997	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	26
61	General Systems Bulletin, Vol. XXVII, No., 1998	1998	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	27
62	General Systems Bulletin, Vol. XXVIII, 1999	1999	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	28
63	General Systems Bulletin, Vol. XXIX, 2000	2000	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	29
64	General Systems Bulletin, Volume XXX, 2001	2001	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	30
65	General Systems Bulletin, Volume XXXI, 2002	2002	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	31
66	General Systems Bulletin, Volume XXXII, 2003	2003	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	32
67	General Systems Bulletin, Volume XXXIII, 2004	2004	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	33
68	General Systems Bulletin, Volume XXXIV, 2005	2005	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	34
69	General Systems Bulletin, Volume XXXV, 2006	2006	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	35
70	General Systems Bulletin, Volume XXXVI, 2007	2007	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	36
71	General Systems Bulletin, Volume XXXVII, 2008	2008	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	37
72	General Systems Bulletin, Volume XXXVIII, 2009	2009	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	38

73	General Systems Bulletin, Volume XXXIX, 2010	2010	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	39
74	General Systems Bulletin, Volume XXXX, 2011	2011	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	40
75	General Systems Bulletin, Vol. XXXXI, 2012	2012	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	41
76	General Systems Bulletin, Volume XXXXII, 2013	2013	ISSS International Society for the Systems Sciences	42

Yearbooks (SCA-ISSS-GSY-D230207A)

This is a followup to [Inventory across Collections \(D221220A\)](#)

📎 SCA-ISSS-GSY-D230207A.xlsx

Please find attached, the promised second ISSS spreadsheet from the SCA.

This second spreadsheet lists all of the articles in the **thirty-two General System Yearbooks**, giving:

- Yearbook, Volume, Year
- Article Title
- Author/s
- Pages: from-to (number of pages)
- Article permissions
- Errata

588 Articles, in 32 volumes.

File is in Read-only mode.

As per my first email (copied below), these SCA Collections are snapshots of living repositories, with a process for continuous improvement. I would welcome any feedback on this deliverable, and the ISSS and SCA working together.

I very much appreciate the discussions we have been having so far, and look forward to collaborating further in the forthcoming ISSS Knowledge Engineering Thursday meetings.

ISSS Resources

What @Rob has, is more updated than the below.

Tasks for ISSS Resources:

- Develop the ISSS Resources table and system, integrating the previous mapping & links.

- <https://web3.issss.org/km/> →

- .
- .
- .
- .
- .

ISSS Resources

Name	Column 2	Column 3	Notes

Metadata

The [table](#) Metadata for each resource is in the table below.

Metadata for each resource

Type	Name of Field	Example	Notes
▼ Full resource 1	Full data		
▼ Metadata 10	Link		
	Title		
	Type of resource		
	Metadata		
	Ownership		
	Rights		
	Access		
	Responsibilities		
	Ontology tags	Terms such as Systems	
	Identifiers	DOI, ISBN, etc	
▼ Template 1	Template type	Person, Resource, Software, Theory	
▼ Scholarship 1	Summaries		

Hardware

Software

MediaWiki

Tasks for MediaWiki

1. Map the relation with the [ISSS Resources](#) and outside
2. Developing Wiki Templates — People, Books, Software, Systems Theory
 - Taking templates from https://futureworlds.eu/wiki/R%26I_PEERS

Key links

- Administrators — <https://wiki.iss.org/index.php/Special:SpecialPages> — they see some more options here
- https://wiki.iss.org/index.php/Main_Page
 - <https://wiki.iss.org/index.php/User:Daniel>

Overview notes

- Wikipedia is an instance of MediaWiki.
 - There are embedding commands, for including one part of a MediaWiki into another.
 - If something cannot be done with MediaWiki itself — then there are hundreds of extensions <https://www.mediawiki.org/wiki/Manual:Extensions> — not all are well-maintained, however many are extremely useful (e.g. embedding PDF, video, media).
- Still we can have pages about the book in MediaWiki, even where there is no access for the full text.
- Various approaches to Systems Science — [Templates for Systems Theories](#)
 - Who started it? Who working on it? Key works & Players.
 - Longer article — developed over a few pages.
- Pages can be categorized into multiple types (e.g. it can be a Software, and a System Theory).
- Using Tags for search in MediaWiki?
- Begin with the articles where people have interest (e.g. themselves, key works).
- How to distribute responsibility and stewardship to the ISSS members.

Wiki Templates

- For 10/20/2022 — Review the [Wiki Templates](#) and:
 - suggest edits to [@Yiannis](#)
 - Plan to make 5-6 of each template type [@Resource](#) and [@Board Member \(Person\)](#)
 - Write documentation and onboarding so that ISSS members can get involved with improving the Wiki
- Interview someone to create a Wiki page.
 - Interests
 - History with ISSS
 - Education and Experience in Systems
 - Resources
- Conversations with ...Singers, Lynn, Jen, Peter, etc (...).
 - [Website](#) — World of Systems — different people's perspectives on Systems.
 - Collection of maps of systems, drawing forth previous work, views on people's systems in terms of maps.
 - Knowledge engineering project has an archival aspects, and conversational aspect.
 - Conversational records — Saturday sessions, etc, in recent years, as recorded presentations and conversations.
 - Series of conversations to be published, conversations with James Greer Miller, digitized, available on website. Multiple people working on this interview publication. Various interviews with relevant people.
 - Active Inference Institute, contributions to discourse analysis and conversation (Gordon Pask) theory by Dave Douglass. Modern developments in text processing e.g. GPT, Stable Diffusion.
 - Neo4j — Knowledge Graphs, Internet of things, supply chains.
 - Knowledge model of the ISSS resources. Cutting edge graph database approaches.
 - Next week — We could look at the Yearbook Index <https://www.iss.org/yearbooks/> , developing the criteria that could be entered in neo4j. Help find work that had been done previously, as reported in yearbooks.
 - Including Maps, published maps
 - Knowledge Engineering — Underlying engineering to support Education, etc.
 - Next week in Education 10/27/2022— [Yearbook](#) — scoping this as example of knowledge engineering tasks, full process from document discovery through publication, archiving, usage, etc.

Wiki Templates

Name	Template	Example	Notes
Resource			
Book			
Board Member (Person)			

MediaWiki Notes

Some preliminary thoughts on how to “design” a MediaWiki.

Basically, the first challenge is to decide on Templates and Categories.

Categories are “easier” in the sense that the task boils down to a schema or an ontology.

Templates are typically developed for different types of articles. So, we could have templates for:

- Terms
- Theories
- Books
- Conferences
- People

First Challenge: Come up with a complete list of all possible types of articles that we would like to host in our Mediawiki. Then develop a template for each. A template is composed of fields that can hold information. If a field is left empty, nothing is displayed. Templates are themselves “articles” that can be edited, modified, or created on the fly.

The next task is to develop a preliminary list of categories (i.e., schemas, ontologies). It is important to note that categories can be added and edited on the fly. At the same time, a good design at launch will save us time.

Here are some first thoughts about categories....

People: Under this category, we could have Past Presidents, Past all other roles, members, etc.. It is this “etc” that needs to be better defined.

Systems terms: This could be dedicated to definitions of all terms that are important for systems

Tools: We could have a few categories such as software, paper-based, etc.

Systems Theories:

Once I have a preliminary coordination meeting with Peter and Daniel, we might come up with a draft structure (for templates and categories) which can then be enriched by the group.

Website

webpage <https://www.isss.org/knowledge-engineering/> and a message board topic

- Possibly fitting in as a third technical project (overlapping though distinct from Education and Knowledge Engineering).
- Katrina has looked over the website, goal: Analyze the structure, content, etc. so that the presentation is accessible and useful.
- How to dive in?
- Where does the website project fit in?
 - How would this project be informing / getting information from the other projects.
- Thought about moving the site to self-hosted Wordpress?
 - Peter — no plans for change to the Membership site.
 - The site began with Peter working with the member management software, enabling people to have access to different portions of sites, keeping things updated in their areas (e.g. configuration of SIG by chairpeople).
 - Previously there was a Drupal website; then it was suggested that the Membership website become the main host, so things were copied over.
 - No anticipation in the hosting platform for [isss.org](https://www.isss.org) — We also do have an account on other (Drupal) hosting, which has some Wiki and Project sites.
 - [@Yiannis](#) and [Wiki Templates](#) — wiki.isss.org —
 - [KM as a project](#) is part of the discussion around making the information more accessible.... How best to present all the information we have?
 - Here first we are securing the ISSS assets.
 - In the Educational area, we're securing the responses to the survey.
 - Content management teams/coordination
 -
- What for proximate focus?
 - **Site map**
 - Also including external Social Media website.
 - Eventually Projects of ISSS Members, on many platforms (Coda, [FedWiki](#), etc)
 - Calendar coordination
 - What is out there, what are they
- Long-term plans for the ISSS site?
- How can the public be brought in?
- What can be an income stream via the site?
- Different social media platforms
- Are there 3 websites?
 - [isss.org](https://www.isss.org)
 - This is the gateway URL. Core website is robust, and no plans to change that.
 - journals.isss.org/
 - web3.isss.org/primer2/
 - wiki.isss.org

- web2.iss.org/ — not working.

Website Audiences

Name	Column 2	Column 3	Notes
ISSS Members			
Potential Members			
Public			

Website functions

Name	Audiences	Status	Notes
Register for an annual conference	Public Potential Members ISSS Members		
Register for one-off event			
Learn about a SIG			

Website Documentation

General ISSS Website Documentation and Notes

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1CqVX6POobXkaH1YdhJhQ9_-nW7ocKInleUfXDB-grJo/edit

Documentation folder

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1Aa28M40xSAXGa3_q3kgPNgXj98iPy4Q4

FedWiki

- David Ing and Ward Cunningham bringing [FedWiki](#) to [ISSS](#) in 2019 at Corvalis.
- Marc and Kerry
- <https://docxology.relocalizecreativity.net/view/welcome-visitors/view/about-daniel-friedman/david-ing.wiki.openlearning.cc/indexes-by-david-ing>

Tools for [FedWiki](#)

- <https://neo4j.com/labs/arrows/>

Blockchain

- Distributed authentication, cross-referencing.
- Modes of authenticating

Chat AI

Add tasks with start/end dates to the task tracker table. Tasks that begin before their pre-requisites end are shown in red. Tasks that are ongoing when their dependencies begin are shown in yellow. And any changes you make to the table will reflect in the timeline below. [+ Clear template](#)

Timeline

+ Add task

Task tracker

Name	Start date	End date	Prerequisite	Prerequisite end date	Dependent tasks	Dependent task start date
Jesus of Nazerath	1/1/2022	5/31/2023	Jesus of Nazerath	5/31/2023	Jesus of Nazerath First Gospel	1/1/2022, 8/18/2023
First Gospel	8/18/2023		Jesus of Nazerath	5/31/2023	[]	[]

2 Count

Education

Education Overview

From Chris & Discussion

- From Chris for [#25 September 21, 2023](#)
 - I saw last week's recording and it was a very interesting session. Thanks. Thinking about collaboration and relevance felt like a good grounding. I liked the point about people making collaboration work, not technology, but some basic tools are necessary.
 - I have started prepping to try some llm and non-llm explorations of the database. I found a few collections of tools and some discussions by searching Coda for the phrase LLM (some are below). Are there any other places I should be visiting to get grounded on getting started please?
 - In Coda: [LLM & ISSS](#), [ISSS-LLM-GPT](#) and also play around with Coda AI!
 - The most updated list for LLM tools I have is in the [Supplemental Information of the GRT paper](#)
 - I was not sure if there is good voice to text capability in the Coda list, but if not, I would appreciate any tips you might have. E.g., Otter.ai or something else?
 - We don't have speech to text going in Coda right now.
 - [LemuR](#), [otter.ai](#), [ActInf Journal Utilities use WhisperAI](#) — depends how much programming you want to do.
 - For standard use, word processor, google docs, they probably work fine.
- From Chris [#22 July 13, 2023](#)
 - I cannot make today's call but I wanted to give some feedback. I have two threads (but they are linked):
 - collaboration - especially group and
 - accessing the databases in a research / large language model way.
 - I also spoke to Peter Tuddenham as part of my inquiry about both. I have agreed to focus on finding things related / relevant to [Human Systems Inquiry](#) (Related to but not limited to the SIG).
 - I am thinking of the Knowledge engineering project as a place that provides tools and data, but maybe the tools can be appropriate for data outside the ISSS database.
 - **Yes, this makes sense for KE as developing enabling systems, and tools that apply to [ISSS Resources](#) and elsewhere.**
 - If we make it easy for people to learn from each other on clever ways to sift through systems research and also helped them share knowledge and work together generally, that could be self sustaining?
 - Are there off the shelf apps that could help with simple collaboration?
 - **In business world, people have made many attempts at building collaboration suites.**
 - **Substack chat, Discord, Discourse, other platforms for communication, Notion**
 - **It really depends on how people are to collaborate and why.**
 - Repository
 - Calendar
 - Video meetings
 - Documents
 - **The motivations of people in collaborations**
 - **Depends centrally on wanting to have community + wanting to accomplish something personal/group.**
 - How can we help curate walled gardens and prompt engineering that make llm's more accessible.
 - **Part of this is about whether we can train/use LLM on paywalled content (walled gardens).**
 - **Another aspect is about enabling people to generate**

- Even a marketplace of sharing tips and tricks, examples, etc?
 - Unique advantage / selling point for people to join their community. Standards, mentoring.
 - Systems science..... Having conceptual integration and synthesis work ABOUT Systems Science is a narrow adoption work — Tools, methods, etc. — Then the broader adoption can occur.
- Who are we looking to collaborate with?
 - Collaboration ON Systems Science
 - Collaboration explicitly WITH Systems Science about other domains
 - Collaboration that does not explicitly use/consider Systems Science
 - What about inter/transdisciplinary studies? E.g. someone who recognizes SS when they see it, sees their work and can connect it to the official literature (e.g. Cybernetics, Big History, [Gregg Henriques](#)) — When we see this, we can make contact with the people. You are doing great work and it is systems oriented.
 - Content → Semantic embedding and/or usage of Systems Ontology → Attention Ranking → Contact → Systems Adjacency Scores.
 - Bibliography → What are they reading or referencing?
 - Tom's System Types. And database with people, years, organizations, quotations. The version on the webpage now is ~1 year old, then a new version may be arising. Incremental feedback through taking in information. Getting to the ideas. Take in someone ideas, and connect them. Multiple definitions.
- Systems Science
 - Systemsness, rather than definition of System — allows us to specify what we mean by this. Pinning down what the characteristics are.
 - George's teachings, ranging from the non-science or in science undergraduates, to those in the computer science majors specifically (was more technical work to do, and application to computer systems).
- Chris S
 - I had somehow found myself on Jitsi, but I cannot find a record of my comments.
 - Basically I had a go with querying the [ISSS archives](#) to identify material related to human systems enquiry. This failed because I did not see a way to search the text. If the PDF's have not been scanned that greatly limits what is possible. **Correct, the full PDF are not available through that interface.**
 - What has been done, from Rob.
 - Peter T et al. have been digitizing the material (documents, reports). However this has not been OCR'ed and had the text curated.
 - The Indexing work of ISSS surveying at the Bibliographic level as of August 2023.
 - So, the question is how to integrate the full texts, with the bibliographic records, given e.g. different access/licencing to text
 - Human Systems Inquiry SIG — short of reading all, what can we do? How do we determine which even records are relevant?
 - Getting the full texts into the Systems Science work
 - Some sites have put in the abstracts and abstractions.
 - This also invokes e.g. Ontology discussions.
 - Moving towards open science/education/research with the materials that can.
 - Creating an Author Ontology. —
 - Janet & Michael Singer —

- ISSS Archives are a research resource. Then capture anything relating to HSI SIG ISSS and supply that to a meta-index that captures all of this tagging, upper ontology, etc. — Main idea is to put in the work to make the archive accessible so that SIG's and researchers can do the work (we're making the enabling system for these usages).
- I thought the only way to get some gains was to profile HIS generally on the web with author names and titles, then use that trained search against ISSS index info.
- Requesting that people can submit information for publication through

Language Models

Language Models general information

- Coding environment
 - <https://www.cursor.sh/>
- Text + Image local models & local API calling.
 - <https://jan.ai/>
 - <https://lmstudio.ai/>
- On research generally, I had a conversation with a friend (David Gurteen) about the idea of collaborative research using chat GPT. there seems to be a huge potential to create a research level playing field through translation and context adjusting capabilities. this could be a really interesting focus

📎 ISSS_2017.pdf

2017 and 2019 ISSS Conference

📎 ISSS 2019 Corvallis Program and Abstracts.pdf

Language Models and using on ISSS archive.

- Since the PDF have not all been brought into text, one idea is to bring in key texts.
- Where is it recorded with the OCR status? Is this recorded in the Systems Community Alliance (SCA) Repository fields somewhere?
 - See [HERE in Education](#) for last week's discussion on OCR and technical equations.
- → Some number of the documents have the OCR completed.
- Folders or repository of the OCR documents.
- API or interface connecting with Language Models
 - Simple and Lowest throughput → Uploading document to a language model (e.g. as per [Perplexity](#))
 - Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) —
 - Some may be tagged with SIG or other information.
 - Other relevant documents may not so much.
 - Training/Fine-tuning
 - .
- Human systems inquiry
 - [Ontology](#) and synonyms, see also, ...
 - Older approaches, e.g. expert system
- .

Ontology

- Controlled Vocabulary
- Taxonomy
- Classification
- Category/ Categorisation
- Glossary
- Ontology
- Meronomy
- Folk Taxonomies, Folksonomy
- Semantic Nets
- Knowledge Graphs
- Synonyms/ Hypernyms/ Hyponyms
- Knowledge Management
- Taxonomists
- Information Architects
- Controlled Vocabulary

Thomas Marzolf's Model

- ▷ database can be converted into different form.
- ▷ Enabling model-based collaboration.
- ▷ <https://web3.isss.org/marzolf-aug2023/index.html>
- ▷ more important longer term is to move forward in a “perfectable” idealistic design setting. Coherence.
- ▷ Information put in, understanding in a context. Improve it in loop with feedback. Needing to catch & register the kinds of (primary, annotation, etc) data.
- ▷ From capturing the information needed to develop a second model — the Systems Common model was constructed of notes.

- Tom's [Systems Science](#) database.

- RSAD source code (should be stored)
 - HTML export for web
 - UML export
 - August 24, 2023 — Tom has done this export. It is data-only, not with diagrams (they can be generated from the data — all the relational content is captured, however the Perspectives/View fine-tuning is not part of the export).
 - The Views show subsets of data with visual accessibility. This is a vital part, and part of keeping it adaptable / without redundancy. The relationality is defined once.
 - Can we store specifications for the view, using the system's base format itself?
 - Perhaps the Names of the view could be captured.
 - Consider the view about a Person. Information about person, link to page/Wikipedia, information on their bibliography, Quotations, and so on.
- Updated copy ([November 2021 version](#)).
 - This is stored in cloud format.
 - Directories
 - Views
 - One file for each view.
 - HTML packages directory

- This is from UML in the tool, converted to HTML
- If you have it all together, it is accessible.
- IBM software, Rational System Architect & Design (RSAD).

Semantic Model

- What is the [Semantic Model](#) of [Thomas Marzolf's Model](#)?
 - Nodes are entities
 - Core information is the Nodes and Edges
- Thinking about a “permanent model” — data only there one time. Easy to change and adapt.
- Then you can have 100 views. Each references a single place on the semantic model.
- Views with multiple levels of details. It is more than a sketch, because it is referencing the semantic model.
- BlockScience and technologies.
 - Reference Identifier (RID)
 - Content Addressable Transformers (CATs)
- Movement towards re-use in computer science and software engineering. System redundancy. Defining things only once
- Parts-Whole (merotopology) can be done in a more limited way than Categorization (might be many Categorizations/Views with different perspectives). We need this capability however most tools don't support this.
- Tom focused on Two models.
 - System-oriented view of the Cosmos. From an intrinsic perspective, this model has more in common with George's model.

Chapter 4 Analytical representation

Fig. 4.9 Interfaces are associated with the boundary of a system. Here they are shown as rounded rectangles that penetrate the boundary and act as pass-ways for inputs and outputs.

Fig. 4.2 Verbal descriptions have relations that map to the system language

- In [#26 October 5, 2023](#) we discussed how George expected to see Braces around the equation 4.1

Deriving a definition of system from the principles and the ontology, a system S is a 7-tuple:

$$S_{i,j} = C, N, G, B, T, H, M_{i,j} \quad (4.1)$$

where i and j are indexes. The index i is a subsystem index and the index j is the level of organization in the system-subsystem hierarchy.¹ Both are 0 for the initial system of interest. $S_{0,0}$ is the designated SOI. Recall from the previous chapter that the ontological framework specified that the SOI be designated as level 0. This will make sense in this definition as we show how the system definition leads to a natural way to deconstruct the component/interaction level (+1) in the framework. Several later chapters in the book will describe the application of these equations and the knowledgebase described in Chap. 8) to even more complex adaptive and evolvable systems (CAESs) described in Part III.

- This equation is the semantic core of the knowledge system.
- Chapter 8 “Knowledgebase”
 - C is the set of components.
 - In [Thomas Marzolf's Model](#) this could be e.g. Authors, books.
 - Sub-system underneath that could be e.g. all written books by them. All the references.

- [Wiki Templates](#) and [FedWiki](#) — expressing augmented

Chapter 8 Computational Architecture

Fig. 8.1 The knowledgebase architecture includes an RDBMS with a schema based on Eq. 4.1, multiple sets of wiki pages containing descriptive and relational texts (and graphics, etc.), and a search engine supplementing the wiki pages. The “core engine” ties everything together and produces the user views (DBMS tables, wiki pages that guide the analysis and control the retrieval of system knowledge. The KB core engine connects with the modeling core engine—see Chap. 10

Fig. 8.2 The RDBMS tables associated with the storage of system knowledge are shown with some of the relevant links. Black arrows show table links, green arrows show internal data links, and purple arrows show identification links (secondary indexes)

Fig. 8.3 The relation between a system and its component subsystems (Eq. 4.2) is captured in these two tables. See the text for details of the relations

Fig. 8.4 An example of the relation between the System table and Components shows how an SOI is represented along with a subset of its first level of component subsystems.

- Hierarchy, Parts and Wholes, Evolution and change, Boundaries — without details.
- What is useful to collect and integrate. Strategy. Information foraging.
 - Systems People/Organizations (Systems Common) — 12 or 15 factual classes. Not controversial in scope/topic.
- Understanding the whole. Through the synthesis and integration that we need. Studying the systems work that is already out in the literature. Resulting in preliminary information as basis for more comprehensive and ambitious model. That second model exists but cannot be easily converted into HTML, though parts of it are in a PowerPoint.
- Inclusion by reference — example is links from a Person page to Wikipedia. Then the information is added by reference. So there can be broken links.

information in a text and human-readable form.

Fig. 8.5 Every system has a boundary object that is comprised of a set of properties and a list of interfaces (Eq. 4.6). Every interface is also a component of the system. And since every component subsystem is also a system the linkage returns from the component back to the system

Coda Language models

What to do next?

1. Based on the content on the page "Semantic Model", it seems like the next steps could involve:
2. Defining the nodes and edges of the semantic model and identifying the core information.
3. Creating views that reference specific places on the semantic model to provide different perspectives and levels of detail.
4. Exploring the concepts of Reference Identifier (RID) and Content Addressable Transformers (CATs) in the context of BlockScience and technologies.
5. Considering the movement towards re-use in computer science and software engineering, and the importance of defining things only once.
6. Exploring the concepts of Parts-Whole (merotopology) and Categorization in relation to the semantic model.

7. Understanding the two models focused on by Tom: the system-oriented view of the Cosmos and the Systems People/Organizations model.
8. Synthesizing and integrating existing systems work from the literature to create a more comprehensive and ambitious model.
9. Exploring the analytical representation and the semantic core of the knowledge system.
10. Exploring the Knowledgebase in relation to the set of components and sub-systems.
11. Understanding how augmented information can be expressed in a text and human-readable form.

Where does UML fit into this?

UML (Unified Modeling Language) can fit into the context of the highlighted content in the following ways:

1. BlockScience and technologies: UML can be used to model and visualize the various blocks and components in a system. It provides a standardized notation for representing the structure, behavior, and relationships between different elements of a system.
2. Reference Identifier (RID): UML can be used to define and represent the relationships and dependencies between different reference identifiers in a system. It can help in visualizing how these identifiers interact and relate to each other.
3. Content Addressable Transformers (CATs): UML can be used to model the transformations and operations performed by CATs. It can help in capturing the inputs, outputs, and transformations involved in these processes.
4. Movement towards re-use in computer science and software engineering: UML can be used to design and document reusable components and modules. It provides a standardized way to represent the structure, interfaces, and behaviors of these components, making it easier to understand and reuse them in different contexts.
5. System redundancy and defining things only once: UML can help in identifying and eliminating redundant components and functionalities in a system. It allows for the definition of reusable and modular components, reducing duplication and improving system efficiency.

Overall, UML provides a visual and standardized language for modeling, documenting, and analyzing systems, which can be applied to various aspects mentioned in the highlighted content.

Can we use a Language Model to convert between structured text and an analytical representation of systems?

Yes, a Language Model can be used to convert between structured text and an analytical representation of systems. Language models, such as natural language processing (NLP) models, have the ability to understand and generate human-readable text. They can analyze the structure and content of the text and extract meaningful information.

In the context of systems analysis, a language model can be trained to interpret structured text describing a system's components, relationships, and behaviors. It can identify key concepts, entities, and their attributes from the text and convert them into an analytical representation, such as a semantic model or a diagram.

Conversely, a language model can also generate structured text from an analytical representation of systems. It can take inputs in the form of a semantic model or a diagram and generate human-readable text that describes the components, relationships, and behaviors of the system.

By using a language model, the conversion between structured text and an analytical representation becomes more flexible and efficient. It allows for easier communication and understanding of complex system models by converting them into a more accessible format.

Based upon the page, please write a comprehensive PhD dissertation outline.

Title: Understanding and Modeling Complex Systems: A Semantic Approach

1. Introduction

- Background and motivation
- Research objectives and scope
- Overview of the dissertation structure

2. Literature Review

- Overview of existing theories and models of complex systems
- Analysis of the limitations and gaps in current approaches
- Exploration of relevant research on semantic modeling

3. Theoretical Framework

- Introduction to the concept of a semantic model
- Definition of nodes and edges in the semantic model
- Identification of core information in the semantic model
- Discussion of the importance of defining things only once

4. Creating Views and Perspectives

- Explanation of how views can be created to provide different perspectives and levels of detail
- Case studies on creating views based on specific research questions or objectives
- Evaluation of the effectiveness of different views in understanding complex systems

5. BlockScience and Technologies

- Overview of BlockScience and its relevance to semantic modeling
- Analysis of Reference Identifier (RID) and its role in semantic modeling
- Exploration of Content Addressable Transformers (CATs) and their impact on semantic modeling

6. Parts-Whole and Categorization

- Discussion of the concepts of Parts-Whole (merotopology) and Categorization in the context of semantic modeling
- Evaluation of existing tools and methodologies for implementing Parts-Whole relationships
- Proposal of an enhanced approach for capturing Parts-Whole relationships in semantic models

7. Case Studies: Two Models by Tom

- In-depth analysis of the system-oriented view of the Cosmos model
- Examination of the Systems People/Organizations model
- Comparison and evaluation of the two models in terms of their scope, applicability, and integration with the semantic model

8. Synthesis and Integration

- Review of existing systems work from the literature

- Proposal of a comprehensive and ambitious semantic model
- Integration of different perspectives and concepts into the synthesized model

9. Analytical Representation and Knowledgebase

- Exploration of the analytical representation of the knowledge system
- Analysis of the semantic core of the knowledge system
- Discussion of the Knowledgebase in relation to the set of components and sub-systems

10. Augmented Information and Human-Readable Form

- Investigation of expressing augmented information in a text and human-readable form
- Evaluation of different approaches and techniques for conveying complex information in a clear and accessible manner

11. Conclusion and Future Directions

- Summary of the research findings and contributions
- Reflection on the strengths and limitations of the proposed semantic model
- Suggestions for future research directions and advancements in semantic modeling

12. References

- Comprehensive list of cited sources and relevant literature

Note: This outline provides a comprehensive structure for a PhD dissertation based on the content from the page "Semantic Model." It can serve as a starting point, and you can customize and further refine the outline based on your specific research goals and requirements.

Systems Commons Tours

Take a look at Systems Common: [Tour-2 views 10, 11A, 11B, and 12](#). All are mega-views where I experimented with large scope. They include text but much of the value is in the relationships and ability to grasp the large scope in a single view. Much text exists in the model associated with these instances not shown in such views. Of course, all of the UML elements are defined in the UML meta-model.

Another mega-view is System Age Begins under Events. Also see *Emergence and Convergence* (Bunge) under Document Views.

10

11A

11B

12

- Tom, about “How would you suggest I modify them?” — I have no specific modifications to suggest to either the Semantics or View of these examples. Here are some thoughts though:
 - The work that can go into making a view (such as these) can be variously a work of personal preference, conceptual expertise, pedagogical structuring, etc. So I could see the View as a standard “graphical abstract” for e.g. Courses, Dissertations, Histories, Arguments/Debates.
 - There could be a lot of ongoing/backend analytics on the relational database. Some of this could be summarized on the view (e.g. network statistics calculated for what is included in the view or adjacent to it), or used in interactive presentation with the user (e.g. prompting the entry of some kind of information, or highlighting the relevance of a possible modification to the View/Model).
 - For “grasp the large scope in a single view”, I think this is a hard challenge. Among other reasons why, as more cards are added to the view, the font gets smaller and this changes the Gestalt of the view. There might be different ways to help convey the relevance/meaning of single view, some ideas are:
 - Present manual summaries (or use LLM tools) of regions of the view, or the whole view.
 - Enable images or icons for different Types and Particular entities (to increase recognition/association and thus contribute to View Gestalt).
 - Enable some formatting or highlighting in the quotations so it is not just wall of text.
 - Integrate Questions in with the view, e.g. what questions is the view addressing and/or leaving open?
 - In the case of multi-author view, perhaps enable a lens on the view where you could see who asserted that relationship.
 - Ability to auto-order along an X or Y axis by Time (making it simpler to read the Timelines)
 - Provide direct space or link to where commentary/discussions can occur (like “in the margins” or among the index cards).
 - Provide a series of Views of building size/scope. For example in View 10, it could start with just Biosemiotics and a few key people/quotes. Then secondary people/associations/ideas can be brought in, and the viewer familiar with the antecedent visualization will then be able to take in that much more new information. That could be presented as a series, and give a dynamical-pedagogical element.

- Highlight where one can jump to another View (e.g. enable Views as entities that can be clicked on or linked? have hyperlinks for when a quote uses a term/entity that is in the Semantic Model even if unlinked?)
- Enable someone to modify the view, e.g. by altering the layout, adding or removing entities.
- I am very interested in all the topics of these maps (Biosemiotics, Gestalt, Pragmatism) and the history around them too. So thank for for sharing these cool and informative examples! Let me know if there are any other areas I could address, and/or we can discuss it at an upcoming meeting.

Paul Otlet was who I was thinking of regarding a 3x5 card knowledge repository. Note he referred to a "worldwide web" before the first computer. Note also quotation about substance.

Tom

The Ideal of Coherence Executive Report - Excerpt 2023

See [Notes on Thomas Marzolf ~ The Ideal of Coherence Executive Report - Excerpt 2023](#)

The Ideal of Coherence Executive Report - Excerpt 2023

Thomas Marzolf

Insights

Introduction

Much of my thinking about coherence has been sparked by insights gained years ago in the role of a modeler for software development projects. The modeler's job is to create a rigorous description of the pertinent business domain and requirements for an application. This necessarily involves delving into the minds of those who best know the business, commonly called **subject matter experts (SMEs)**, and creating a common representation from their combined expertise. Modeling opens a rare window into the inner minds of individuals and the challenges of collaboration.

Hidden Information and Dissonance

I soon discovered that SMEs' minds hold a great deal of valuable knowledge, some of which exists nowhere else, but also plenty of nonsense. Most surprising, I discovered that even experts understand the same concepts in significantly different – even totally conflicting – ways. In one eye-opening experience it was discovered after considerable painful discussion that two experienced and respected experts held diametrically opposed understanding of a fundamental business concept. I initially thought that such problems might be a quirk of the project or staff but with more experience realized that they are very much the rule, not an exception. Such differences are remarkably common; so common that I *now assume that many exist in every project unless I see convincing evidence to the contrary.*

Worse, I found that many apparent agreements were actually not agreements and in some cases were disagreements masquerading as agreements. The parties nodded in agreement even while their understanding was fuzzy or in conflict. A shared set of terms were in use, and agreements were stated using the terms. However, the terms were not well defined, i.e., they had no single generally accepted unambiguous meaning. In some cases, the meanings differed enough to allow nearly contradictory interpretations. So, while the words being spoken and heard were identical, the semantics being sent and received were different. Without explicit definitions to refer to, how would anyone know?

Magic Occurs

Another insight was sparked by the responses that the sight of a model reliably evokes. Most people unfamiliar with modeling are initially indifferent if not hostile to the prospect of creating a model but show revealing behavior as one develops. This common response has been captured in the often told tale of the person who asks the modeler: "why are you drawing those funny pictures?" followed soon after by "Hey, I didn't know that", and "can I get a copy of it". I have seen a similar scenario play out several times.

Why does non-interest quickly turn to interest and often fascination? How can this magic be explained?

One reason a model generates immediate interest is because it provides important new information. A model captures information existing only in one or a few peoples' heads and makes it available to all. Instead of their own individual subset of information, a member can suddenly see something approaching the community's superset, some of which the member previously had no inkling even existed.

Another reason for interest is that a model integrates information. That is, related parts are presented together and the relationships and interactions between them defined. The picture created after only a few modeling sessions is typically one

never seen because it integrates information never before integrated.

A third reason for the magic is something deeper: grasping of a system and its emergent properties. Those who study systems (system thinkers) are quite familiar with the phenomenon of emergence since it is the signature of a system. A system, by definition, is one in which the whole is greater than the sum of the parts. The difference between the whole and sum of the parts is accounted for by so-called *emergent properties*. Emergent properties are not present in any of the parts individually but appear when the parts operate together as a system. They are generated from the interactions among the parts of the system and the system with its context.

Life is perhaps the best example of an emergent property; certain chemicals when interacting as a living system have radically different properties than the same chemicals when not so interacting. The difference between life and its non-living constituents is so extraordinary that it was once thought that some “vital force” must be responsible for it. Emergent properties are not magical; they only seem so because they are so unlike any of the properties of the parts and so unexpected. Systems and their emergent properties can be understood only by seeing the structure and function of all the parts, the process of interaction, and the context of operation, i.e. only by grasping all of the elements together as a whole system.

Without bringing all the relevant elements together, we can easily miss the relationships and process of interactions among them. Without seeing the process of interactions, we can't see the system and its operation that is the source of emergent properties. We see random parts and functions but miss the system and its emergent properties. We see a few chemicals but miss life.

Understanding could be categorized from low to high as follows: (1) grasping parts separately, (2) grasping parts together, (3) grasping all of the parts along with their relationships and interactions as a system within its context(s). Unfortunately, we (who grew up in the West, at least) tend to give relationships and interactions short shrift compared to “things” and so put ourselves at a disadvantage in understanding systems. Without a model it is difficult to see how we can get past the first level. In fact, unless all the parts have been well defined, even getting to the first level is doubtful.

Recap

While communities develop and use a common vocabulary, individuals often hold and use different meanings for the words. Without an explicit set of well-defined terms, the meaning in use is not clear, enabling unnoticed misunderstandings and even complete disagreements.

When most knowledge is implicit, it becomes fragmented, with much of it residing only in one or a few minds, while others remain unaware. A cast of thousands is required in meetings to ensure coverage. Person-to-person working agreements are forged leaving others out of the loop and lacking the understanding to fully participate.

The interest generated by a model when it becomes available is indicative of how much of importance is routinely missed. We normally see only a fraction of the whole picture and often miss the most critical aspects. We must try to put a puzzle together without having all the pieces on the table, indeed without even knowing that some of them exist, and without being kept up to date when they change.

To put it in a nutshell: we communicate poorly and work half blind while accepting both conditions as normal.

A Great Opportunity Beckons

Comparisons to peers might not look too bad since, from my experience, these conditions are quite common. But such comparisons are much like the Big Three auto makers comparing quality with each other in the 1970s when they all delivered more than 30 defects with each vehicle. On any objective basis both situations are appalling.

We should instead compare against the ideal. Why should we not communicate perfectly with all terms well-defined, mutually coherent, and tailored to our needs? Why cannot all knowledge be made explicit, kept up-to-date, and always available to all? We must learn to view any lack of coherence as a defect and indictment of the process that produces it.

The bright spot here is the availability of a great opportunity since so much improvement is possible. (After grasping the prospect of Total Quality, all world auto makers now deliver far less than one, and still declining, defect per vehicle, while simultaneously delivering a better product more quickly and less expensively.)

Several points are clear if this opportunity is to be grasped.

We must have complete visibility. Whether we are trying to understand something that exists or design something new, we must make all of the relevant knowledge and ideas explicit. Everything must be always visible and accessible to everyone. All the pieces of the puzzle must be kept on the table.

We must know what we are talking about. Everything pertinent must be unambiguously defined and understandable to all in the same way.

We must put it all together. “Non-things”, i.e., relationships, interactions, and processes, must be addressed on an equal basis with “things”; that can only be done when all are brought together. **Systems can only be recognized and understood when all the parts, functions, process, and contexts are together and visible, i.e., when all is integrated.**

We must be able to change our representation and do so quickly and easily. Change is inevitable; we must embrace it. Learning depends on a succession of changes, both small and large, interspersed with reviews. Explicit representation is essential, but an approach based on representation cannot be fully viable unless it can keep up with changes in the world and with learning.

Finally, given these prerequisites, coherence becomes possible. Coherence must be achieved through the age-old iterative process of state, review, and update. That is, to make changes until all reviewers agree that flaws have been eliminated and everything now all “hangs together” and is “true as a whole”. This process could be called *jiggling*. Jiggling (incremental improvement) is a conceptually simple yet extremely powerful process; when properly applied jiggling can drive a representation to approach perfection and keep it there even under change.

Effective jiggling doesn't occur – and coherence is not achieved – because jiggling is difficult but because the prerequisites for effective jiggling are not met. That is, because all that is pertinent is not visible, well-defined, and integrated, and most of all because the representation mechanism is not sufficiently adaptable.

If coherence is our quest, then we must consider how to best achieve visibility, unambiguous definitions, integration, and adaptability, and how to make the jiggling process as effective as possible.

Notes on Thomas Marzolf ~ The Ideal of Coherence Executive Report - Excerpt 2023

- Boundaries // Interfaces .
 - Simon, Sciences of the Artificial
- This [Notes on Thomas Marzolf ~ The Ideal of Coherence Executive Report - Excerpt 2023](#)
 - This was from a group (described [#29 November 16, 2023](#)). Maybe 2005.
- Big idea: Things fitting together. Universe fits together. However our Views don't fit together (they do fit together the way they don't fit together).
 - Systems
 - Benefit of modeling: Make things coherent. Start from scratch. Doesn't mean tacking things on, it means evaluating the whole.
 - Hard to be coherent in e.g. systems with inertia. For Theoretical work, this first-principles / [Systems Science](#) approach is possible.
- In Enterprise Architecture —
 - Harmony/Interaction of multiple levels/scales of the organization. BOLTS.
 - Multiple timescales. Short and Long term.
- Same thing with Systems. The whole whole is Universe. Can't make the 1:1 map though can still map the spaces.
 - Chans. Coupled Human and Natural Systems. 1999-Onwards for several years, made a different approach. Different systems, coupling them together.
 - Operational coherence. Closed and Open systems. Operational enclosure.
 - Software/Ontology — overlaps/relationships of ontologies, and upper ontologies (e.g. [Suggested Upper Merged Ontology \(SUMO\)](#), [BFO Basic Formal Ontology](#), and others.
 - IT and Computer environment. VIE. AR/VR. → Spaces for truth and coherence.
 - Hence Systems/Systems Science ←- Computer/Information systems.
 - Ontology fusion in biomedical setting. Projects are working on this.
- Taxonomies and Classifications of Systems Science & Formal Sciences.
 - Modeling Ontologies as part of a larger whole.
 - Shifting ontologies/frames as kind of code/context switching.
 - Cognitive model ([attention as mental action](#)) descriptive model (not necessarily the way to implement) that AS IF shifts among different ontologies.
 - Epistemic qualitative paradigm → Ontology use/creation/modification.
 - The terms/relationships arise from discourses.
 - Software ontologies, does it have context?
 - UML ontology in [Thomas Marzolf's Model](#)
 - Can customize.
 - There is a meta-model for UML, and higher order for 4 such layers. This has been shown to be workable.
 - You can do Translation or Transformation. These define language mappings. A common model could transfer between disciplines/settings.
 - Can it be done / Is it being done?

- Develop things bottom-up. An earlier stage of software tried to work at a higher level, this failed. UML took alternative approach which seems to be better.
- Some work in Systems Science may be at too high a level; and with terms loosely defined.
- How are those UML meta-models related to Systems?
- Natural language — conveying information (language and visual foundation models).
 - Sets & Set Theory. Definitions with Natural language words (lol). Is that the “formal definition”? Just pointing at it?
 - Still the explanations are required.
- Qualitative — Statistical — Formal
- Web Ontology, enabling some kind of different communications. Google et al. are putting it together for their own purposes (?).
- Subjective & Objective
 - Coherent & Operational → Pragmatism
 - Going at the laws of reality? → Truth
 - Memory — representation hidden to observers.
 - Multi-agent system. What is preserved within/among scales?
 - Single And/Or Multiple Truths
 - Statistics.
- Some connections with Free Energy Principle:
 - <https://arxiv.org/abs/2212.01354> Designing Ecosystems of Intelligence from First Principles
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=N7QSuazEEhE> Realising Synthetic Active Inference Agents
- Synthesis
 - Heading towards modeling. Induction/Deduction & Abduction.
 - What does the brain do. What it is as-if the brain does.
 - Abstraction, Ab-Stract. That abstraction-map is of Epistemic and Pragmatic value. Can go on selecting different judgements/policies/etc in OODA.
 - Conjugated Relations.
 - Conjugated expression: math, language, etc.
 - The elements exist in relation to each other & other expressions.
 - Organic conjugation. That is natural. All part of the chain of being/causation/memory.
 - What does it mean to model this, the synthesized version? Representation & Reality.
 - Map-Territory
 - https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Simulacra_and_Simulation
 - <https://arxiv.org/abs/2208.06924> On the Map-Territory Fallacy Fallacy (2022)
- Software development
 - Reuse — Initially pieces of the system/business (People. Accounts.).
 - We only do things once.
 - Different positions/roles. Division of Labor // Task Allocation. Everything defined once and only one. No inconsistency. Minimum size. Single points of change → Easy to change and track.
 - Part of the way to get here, is to generalize.

- Sub-types of roles → hierarchy of sub-types. These Abstracts are important for managing knowledge & structurally handle it properly.
- There can be a large number of sub-types. Building these, are important for getting where we want to go.
 - ✦ [Systems Science](#) is very general. May not be many things to say about Systems themselves. In the Meso-space there is a lot.
- Re-Representation. This can be a useful and economical process. Properly represent things that only include new entities once. Most compact possible.

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The Ideal of Coherence - Executive Summary

📎 Coherence ExecSummary-P1.doc

The Ideal of Coherence - Executive Summary

Coherence is a highly desirable characteristic of every human enterprise. Everything should “hang together” and be “true as a whole” to quote common dictionary phrases. One of the most frustrating and disturbing aspects of working life is that everything doesn’t and isn’t. Most things fit only “sort of” if they fit at all. Gaps and inconsistencies abound. Assumptions must constantly be made. Confidence is hard to muster. True coherence is found rarely and then only within certain constrained domains.

Pertinent knowledge can be found many places in various shapes, forms, and vintages: planning documents, organization charters, announcements, reports, presentations, training material, web sites, emails, meeting videos, and lately even executive blogs. The most striking characteristic of such knowledge is its fragmentation, its many separate overlapping and inconsistent pieces. No single comprehensive picture exists. Assembly and fit is left to the user and must be done continuously. How can coherence be achieved or assessed without integrating all of the pieces to produce a single, comprehensive, up-to-date picture? How can a complex enterprise in a rapidly changing world be managed effectively without such a picture? There must be a better way.

At the most general level there appears to be only two approaches: (1) cope with lack of coherence, or (2) create *and maintain* coherence. Experience shows that the former approach has been the overwhelming choice, almost always by default rather than deliberate decision. Decision is seldom faced because no alternative is seen; global coherence is hardly conceivable.

This report considers the latter approach, the path not taken. Coping means to live with a problem without fixing it. This report considers how to *dissolve* the problem, i.e., eliminate it in a way that it will never return.

Why not coherence? Might it be possible? If so, how can it be achieved? The benefits of coherence are so great, and the cost of lack of coherence so high, that even at a considerable price, coherence would be a terrific bargain. It should at least be worth a look.

How would business change (whatever your business might be) if all pertinent knowledge could be integrated to produce a comprehensive picture that could be made and kept coherent?

This report contends that although incoherence may be quite common it is not normal. What we see is pathological, symptoms of a fundamental underlying sickness that must be understood and addressed.

Doing so is a challenge because it consists of a system of interrelated problems, what has been called a *mess*. A mess must be addressed holistically. We must untangle the interrelated problems and understand the systems of which they are a part. A non-systemic effort is ineffective for a mess and is as likely to make the problems worse as better. Such problems persist, not because they are insolvable, but because they are system problems and have not been addressed with a systems approach.

Idealized Design, an approach developed by Russell Ackoff and colleagues, provides guidance for dealing with a mess. We must grasp systemic nature of a mess and address it holistically, avoiding the application of predetermined solutions until we fully understand the problem. Imagining ideals, i.e., our true desires, is a signature activity of Idealized Design. The more common approach of eliminating problems is unlikely to reach the ideal. To do so you must focus on what you want rather than on what you don’t want, then work backwards to relax constraints.

Adopting coherence as an ideal signals a significantly different path. Doing so sets a goal, establishes a measure, makes a statement about the approach, and constitutes the first and perhaps most important step along the chosen path. Selecting Coherence as a goal declares a desire to go beyond just making a problem go away temporarily, exchanging it for others, or improving one part at the cost of the whole.

Two considerations of coherence must be paramount: coherence is a quality of the whole and coherence is dynamic in a dynamic world. The world and our understanding of it will continue to change. Coherence must be represented in a way that is highly adaptable even while addressing the large and complex. Partial coherence is an oxymoron. Representations that are

partial or transitory because they cannot be adapted are soon overlapped by other representations creating redundancy and fragmentation and rendering coherence impossible – much the situation today.

Coherent Modeling is conceived of as a way to provide such a representation. Its aim is to produce a Coherent Model that is highly adaptable – thus permanent, fully understandable, and can be perfected over time. Such a model can be made *and kept* coherent. Available tools provide sufficient support for a Coherent Model if the capability is understood and used properly. The heart of the support is the capability to decouple semantics, the meaning of elements, and presentation, how elements are depicted, and manage them as two relatively independent subsystems. Without such decoupling semantics and presentation become hopelessly entangled to the detriment of both and especially adaptability.

A Coherent Model provides a sharp contrast with traditional representations. Traditionally the whole is described, such as it is, by views developed piecemeal from many separate diverse representations. A Coherent Model can describe the whole using many diverse views from a single representation. The crucial difference is that a single model can be managed to achieve adaptability and coherence while many separate representations cannot.

Beyond easing the burden and limitation of coping with incoherence, coherence offers a vision of an exciting future that includes effective collaboration around an explicit, well-defined community mental model, rapid sharing of knowledge and ideas, a broad-based understanding of the whole including motivation, the recognition of relationships, generalizations, and patterns that often trigger creativity and innovation, and the ability to see the big picture and thus apply systems thinking to optimize the whole. Our view of a business, or the world, from a comprehensive, coherent, adaptable model would be profoundly different from the view we now can only draw from many, partial, incoherent fragments.

Business Motivation Model (BMM)

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📎 BMM-P4.pptx

From Tom on 1-19-2024.

The purpose of this presentation is to provide:

- Awareness of BMM and its potential value for systems
- An example of how BMM can be used to envision and define a customized modeling approach
- Awareness of a modeling approach customized for systems as partially described by a BMM plan
- Examples of the potential of modeling to manage complexity at several levels